

Economic analyses on the cost of Gender-Based
Violence in Namibia

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„Schrift ist sichtbare Sprache.“

Erik Spikermann

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\LaTeX code by [Elio A. Farina](#).

Foreword

I chose this topic because I have learned from my professional activity that the prevention of this social injustice is not receiving enough attention. The rather innovative approach of calculating costs is intended to give greater attention to the topic and its survivors.

Abstract

Violence against women is acknowledged globally as a fundamental human rights violation. Gender-Based Violence [GBV] is prevalent across high, middle, and low-income countries. It produces high economic costs in terms of expenditures on service provisions, lost income, and decreased productivity, including adverse consequences on future human capital formation for women and their families. This paper aims to make a significant contribution to the discussion through the conceptual mapping of the links between GBV and its economic impact. It reviews costing methods and identifies types of costs that potentially can be estimated given the different degrees of data availability. This study which is based on 2018 data, argues strongly for a focus on assessing the financial consequences of GBV, as it comprises a crucial element of economic growth. The empirical estimation suggests that this impact is significant, and in the case of Namibia, this cost is equivalent to 6.01 per cent of GDP in 2018.

Abstract JEL classifications – H53, I15, I31, I38, J12, J16, J17, J24, O57

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Abbreviations

AIDS	Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome
A\$	Australian dollar, AUD
৳	Bangladeshi taka, BDT
BMZ	Federal Ministry of Economic Cooperation and Development [Germany]
C\$	Canadian dollar, CAD
CAPS	Cape Area Panel Study
CHF	Swiss franc, CHF
CI	Confidence Interval
CJS	Criminal Justice System
CPI	Consumer Price Index
DALYs	Disability-Adjusted Life Years
DESA	United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, see UNDESA
DV	Domestic Violence
€	euro, EUR
EIGE	European Institute for Gender Equality
FDI	Foreign Direct Investment
£	GB sterling pound, GBP
GBV	Gender-Based Violence
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HALYs	Health-Adjusted Life Years
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
HOOR	Home Office Online Report
HRQL	Health-Related Quality of Life
ICRW	International Centre for Research on Women
IMF	International Monetary Fund
IPV	Intimate-Partner Violence/Interpersonal Violence
KPMG	Klynveld Peat Marwick Goerdeler
kr	Swedish krona, SEK
LCUs	Local Currency Units
MDGs	Millennium Development Goals
Mex\$	Mexican dollar, MXN
N\$	Namibia dollar, NAD
NAMPOL	Namibian Police
NBC	Namibia Broadcasting Corporation
NCCI	Namibian Chamber of Commerce and Industry
NCIP&C	National Centre for Injury Prevention and Control

NCRVAW&C	National Council to Reduce Violence Against Women and their Children
NDHS	Namibia Demographic and Health Survey
NIC	Namibian Investment Centre
NTA	Namibia Training Authority
OR	Odds Ratio
PAFs	Population Attributable Fractions
PPP	Purchasing Power Parity
PTSD	Post Traumatic Stress Disorder
QALYs	Quality-Adjusted Life Years
R	South African rand, ZAR
RR	Relative Risk
SADC	Southern African Development Community
SGBV	Sexual and Gender-Based Violence
STDs	Sexually Transmitted Diseases
₴	Ukrainian hryvnia, UAH
UCSR	Ukrainian Centre for Social Reforms
U.K.	United Kingdom
U.N.	United Nations
UNDESA	United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs
UNFPA	United Nations Population Fund
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
US\$	US dollar, USD
₫	Vietnamese dong, VND
WHO	World Health Organization
WTP	Willingness to pay
YLD	Years lived with disability
YLL	Years of life lost due to premature mortality

Executive Summary

Worldwide, an estimated one in three women will be physically or sexually abused in her lifetime, most commonly by a family member or partner (García-Moreno *et al.* 2013). Hence, such violence is a problem of significant magnitude.

GBV is not only a violation of human rights, but it also poses costs to society as a whole. In summary, this paper attempts to estimate the full range of its expenses at the individual, community, and macro-level by bringing together research from different sectors, including public health, sociology, psychology, and economics. This paper aims to identify the negative impacts of GBV holistically.

GBV has a tremendous consequence on the survivors¹ physical and mental health (Heise, Pitanguy, and Germain 1994; World Bank 2014; World Health Organization (WHO) 2009). Such violence does not only cause expenses to complainants in terms of lost economic output or personal losses, but the violence creates a cost to society as a whole too. GBV goes beyond today's time frame and triggers cost across generations (Dunkle *et al.* 2004; KPMG South Africa 2014). In brief, it restrains a whole society from unfolding its true potential because it hinders the economic growth and development of a nation across generations. This hindrance is even more harmful to developing and emerging countries. For instance, calculations of the cost of violence are 1.35 per cent of the gross domestic product [GDP] in Australia (KPMG Australia 2016), 3.19 per cent in Vietnam (Duvvury and Carney 2012), 3.93 per cent in Colombia (Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004), and up to 1.30 per cent in South Africa (KPMG South Africa 2014). GBV disproportionately affects low and middle-income countries, and it is likely to be more severe in developing and emerging nations (Duvvury and Carney 2012).

No such data is yet to exist for Namibia, despite the problem being a very pressing one, as GBV prevalence ratios are high. Overall, 20 per cent of ever-married Namibian women have experienced physical or sexual violence enacted by their current or most recent husband during the past 12 months (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 310). However, this study's definition goes beyond the mere spousal violence and includes GBV enacted by third individuals as well. Third parties can, for instance, include the stepfather, teacher, or the police.² In sum, this study's prevalence ratio comprises:

¹See the definition of the survivor-term in Section 2.1

²See Section 2.7 for the GBV definition.

17.50 per cent of women who experienced physical and sexual violence, which was enacted by all intimate partners, family members, or third parties, within the past 12 months³

Computing the cost of GBV provides a better basis for policy action and implementation. It provides data for policy-makers to carry out informed decision-making, including formulating targeted policy spending priorities. The information further assists in conducting a comparative evaluation of the impacts of preventive measures. In sum, international costing studies indicate the implications of non-intervention for today and future generations (García-Moreno *et al.* 2005 World Health Organization (WHO) 2013a World Health Organization (WHO) 2016b).

This study is based on a broader GBV definition. It draws on the advanced notion of the United Nations (UN) General Assembly 1993 and Council of Europe 2011. In detail, it includes violence between family members, such as father, stepmother, brother including other relatives, and intimates, as well as violence between acquaintances and strangers, such as rape through police officers, teachers, or friends. The employed GBV definition also covers sexual abuse by strangers, cultural practices, or structural violence in institutions like schools or public institutions.

A common way to organise the economic cost of GBV is to place them in categories based on their consequences and the services utilised as a result. In summary, this study computes the following cost classes:

1. lost economic output,
2. health service costs,
3. legal costs,
4. social welfare and special service costs,
5. personal costs,
6. intangibles, physical, and emotional impact,
7. second-generation costs.

These categories are derived from a holistic and extensive literature review. This included research in both developing and developed economies from 2000 onwards, narrowed down to a set of around 20 studies for further in-depth review. Based on this careful examination, the following became evident:

1. A lack of appropriate literature for developing and emerging countries: studies conducted for developing and emerging economies were often found to have different incompleteness. For instance, either not all categories are calculated, or the outcome is not projected to a national level.
2. Lack of available data: various data gaps within the current costing studies resulted in non-comprehensive calculations.

³In detail, 3.70 per cent of women have experienced sexual violence (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 300), and 13.80 per cent have suffered from physical violence (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 298).

-
3. Minor methodological variations have led to significant differences in cost outcomes. The higher GBV prevalence ratios found in developing nations did not automatically translate into increased GDP-cost shares as the calculations in developed countries often apply a more holistic approach.

There is a wide range of methodical differences in the current GBV costing literature. Based on the analysis of the feasibility of methods and the availability of data in Southern Africa, the following cost categories are identified to compute best the Namibian case⁴

1. Lost economic output: the health state model reflects all major and minor health consequences resulting from GBV.
2. Health service costs: the unit-cost approach derives from internationally accepted unit cost data for health services.
3. Legal costs and social welfare costs: the budget share approach offers the most holistic way to apply the Namibian datasets found in this category.
4. Personal costs: the unit-cost method delivers the best result to handle the mostly qualitative datasets available for this cost class.
5. Intangibles, physical, and emotional impact: the quality-adjusted life years [QALYs] approach based on the willingness to pay [WTP] model provides the most comprehensive results for calculating intangibles.
6. Second-generation costs: the Disability-adjusted life years [DALYs] approach best reflects Namibian children’s environmental situation and living conditions.

Table 1 shows the findings calculated based on the presented methods.

Table 1.: Total results.

Cost category	GDP share [%]
Economic output	1.64
Health services	0.26
Legal	0.50
Social welfare and special services	1.09
Personal	0.28
Intangibles	0.62
Second-generation	1.62
Total	6.01
Total [without second-generation costs]	4.39

Source: Own representation.

⁴The detailed derivations and reasonings for the Namibian context are presented in Chapters 3 and 5

Part I.

Economic analyses on the cost of
Gender-Based Violence in Namibia

1. Introduction

Namibia's economic wealth has grown steadily in recent years. According to the World Bank, the national GDP increased sixfold from US\$ 2.4 billion in 1980 to US\$ 11.6 billion in 2015. The gross national income per capita has more than doubled in the last 30 years and rose from US\$ 2,080 in 1982 to US\$ 5,210 in 2015. Through access to primary medical care, the average life expectancy rose from 47 years in 1960 to 65 years in 2014 (World Bank 2018e).

In contrast to the economic growth, Namibia has one of the highest GBV ratios worldwide (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). Statistics on violence show little differentiation and insights into society and changes within a nation. Hence, it might be tempting to regard high ratios of violence against women and gender inequalities as statistical artefacts. Patterns that will vanish eventually, if only the process of increased female human capital investment continues for long enough. One might suspect that older birth cohorts mainly drive high GBV prevalence proportions, specifically, generations, where the share of women with lower education and a different set of cultural values manifested through the Apartheid system in Namibia is relatively high (Dianne and Rimmer 2007).

Nevertheless, as noted above, although revenue growth occurred over the past 25 years, Namibian women did not benefit equally but even negatively. Despite increasing prosperity, violence against women rose simultaneously (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). From the perspective of economic theories, these figures are puzzling (Davis 2007). Following the new-Keynesian and neoclassical assumptions, the overall income growth is ultimately the most productive element to remove social inequalities (Jefferson 2012).

In the experimental economic literature, when aiming to uncover potential explanatory factors for unequal economic growth, the phenomena of GBV embedded in societies, especially in emerging markets, has received increased attention (Morazes and Pintak 2007; Western, Dwan, and Kebonang 2005). The argument is that certain socio-economic factors expressed through the high degree of GBV influence the economic inequalities of a nation. Systematic economic disequilibrium has indeed manifested itself in gender-specific disparities and has led to financial costs, as we observe them. However, these costs reflect the lack of appropriate interventions to tackle root causes. This view suggests that, although economic growth occurs, Namibian women are partly not only excluded from it but also burdened with the additional cost through the impacts of a violent culture (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). This research follows the assumption that socio-economic patterns are significant determinants for GBV outcomes (World Health Organization (WHO) 2013b).

The study aims to contribute to uncovering the costs associated with GBV in Namibia as an initiative to provide quantified incentives to address the high GBV prevalences.

1.1. Introduction to the chapter

Chapter 1 is structured in the following way: Section 1.2 presents the theoretical basics, and the GBV term and the individual cost categories are explained. Section 1.3 describes the impacts of GBV. The consequences of physical and mental health, the adverse effects that span generations, and the negative effects on a nation's economy are discussed, and the economic results are presented in more detail. The aspects of restricted economic growth, the reduced productivity, and the multiplier effect that reinforces these negative consequences are briefly outlined. Section 1.4 discusses the current GBV situation in Namibia in more detail. It deals with prevalence proportions in developing and emerging countries and specifies those in Namibia. The prevalences used in this study will also be briefly presented. Section 1.4 explicitly explains why it is essential from an economic perspective to measure the costs of GBV, and Section 1.6 narrates the paper's objective and structure in more detail. Section 1.7 discusses the current research status, and the literature dealing with the GBV topic, in general, is presented, and research in developing and emerging countries, particularly in the SADC region, is analysed. Section 1.8 explains the methods used in this study. For the sake of clarity, the specific cost classes and the methods applied in these categories are specifically analysed. Section 1.9 then summarises the key findings of this study, followed by a conclusion in Section 1.10.

In order to continue, Section 1.2 will introduce this paper's theoretical basics.

1.2. Theoretical basics

The paper's theoretical foundation uses a tailor-made GBV definition.

This paper's GBV definition

This paper's GBV definition originates from the findings advanced by the Declaration on the Elimination of Violence Against Women (United Nations (UN) General Assembly 1993) and the Council of Europe (Council of Europe 2011), respectively. This includes the following:

1. Types of violence: from an economic perspective, all forms of violence have a cost impact, including the physical and mental health status. Therefore, this study's GBV definition considers various kinds of abuse, including psychological, physical, and sexual.
2. Types of perpetrators: GBV generally includes violence between family members, such as father, stepfather, brother, other relatives. It further comprises violence between acquaintances or strangers, including rape through soldiers, police officers, teachers, or friends (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 299). Thereby, this definition covers GBV and physical and sexual violence enacted by third parties and structural violence in institutions, like schools or police.
3. Types of survivors: this definition encompasses all those affected and does not restrict the group to just a limited sub-sample. It also includes violence outside a domestic

setting or violence directed against single women. Furthermore, if the data permits, a distinction is made between violence committed by men and women¹

In order to continue, the following paragraph describes the computed cost classes.

Cost categories

This paper organises the cost by sector rather than according to direct and indirect categories. The calculation of expenses is based on the impact of violence and services utilised as a result. Therefore, this study computes the following categories:

1. lost economic output,
2. health service costs,
3. legal costs,
4. social welfare and special service costs,
5. personal costs,
6. intangibles, physical, and emotional impact,
7. second-generation costs.

The GBV terminology and the different cost categories have been briefly described, and Section 1.3 will summarise the negative impacts associated with GBV.

1.3. Impacts of GBV

Violence against women has several adverse effects on individuals and society as a whole. According to the WHO:

Domestic violence [DV] is abuse experienced within families or between intimate partners, and it is one of the most pervasive expressions of violence. Worldwide, an estimated one in three women will be physically or sexually abused in their lifetime, most commonly by a family member or partner (García-Moreno *et al.* 2013).

GBV is a problem of significant magnitude. Most women experience different kinds of abuse on more than one occasion. In other words, violence is a pattern of repeated behaviour rather than a single act that occurs once. GBV spans over all forms of abuse, including physical, sexual, or psychological (Walby and Olive 2014).

Impact on physical and mental health

The World Bank estimates that globally, nine million disability-adjusted life year [DALYs]² are lost each year due to GBV.

¹Since the information available on the violence committed by women against men is internationally very limited, most calculations only relate to the violence enacted by men.

²The approach was modelled in 1990 by scholars of the World Bank and Harvard University to quantify the weight of disease and disability in nations. The model computes the gap between the current health of

The figure is higher than all DALYs lost due to all forms of cancer and twice the losses of automobile accidents (Heise, Pitanguy, and Germain [1994](#)). Violence in women's lives ranks even higher as a contributor to death, disability, and illness, than, for instance, smoking, obesity, or high blood pressure (World Health Organization (WHO) [2009](#)).

There are links between GBV and a range of other reproductive and health problems, including sexually transmitted diseases [STDs], unwanted pregnancy, abortion, or maternal morbidity. There is a significant association between the actual HIV/AIDS risk [Human Immunodeficiency Virus/Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome] and the high levels of GBV. As a result, women living in violent relations have a higher risk of being HIV positive (Dixon, McDonald, and Roberts [2002](#); Jewkes *et al.* [2010](#); KPMG South Africa [2014](#); World Bank [2014](#)). Moreover, female survivors exhibit an increased probability of substance abuse, alcoholism, unhealthy feeding habits, or suicide, which have widespread adverse health effects (Duvvury *et al.* [2013](#); García-Moreno *et al.* [2013](#); World Health Organization (WHO) [2009](#)).

Impact across generations

GBV has a significant effect on children, whether they are directly affected by the abuse or only witnesses to it. The impact of such violence is staggering and extends far beyond the mere incident of victimisation. The most far-reaching impacts are those felt by the children, who also face a higher risk of continuing the cycle of violence themselves. Unlike with other forms of violence, the vast majority of affected experience repeated abuse. Besides, the severeness of GBV may increase over time. Violence is learned; therefore, childhood witnesses of family violence are associated with a higher likelihood that the affected minors will be later perpetrators or survivors of abuse themselves (Dunkle *et al.* [2004](#)). For instance, a woman who has experienced violence in her childhood is 3.11 times more likely to have experienced violence within the last 12 months. Moreover, a woman who has witnessed violence in her youth is 1.89 times more likely to experience violence during her lifetime (Stöckl *et al.* [2014](#)). This causes significant economic losses.

Financial impacts

The effect of GBV stretches through all financial spheres. The expenses include costs within the health system, justice, other service costs, lost earnings, revenues, taxes, or negative impacts on the Second-generation, including increased juvenile and adult crime. It is widely acknowledged within the economic GBV-literature that society pays for the losses of not addressing GBV since it restricts national economic growth and increases poverty within nations (Cuberes and Teignier-Baqué [2012](#); Duvvury *et al.* [2013](#); World Health Organization (WHO) [2016b](#)).

citizens and their ideal health state (Lajoie [2015](#)). In short, the disability-adjusted life year [DALY] method is used to calculate the burden of different diseases and consequences on Life-Years.

Economic impacts

GBV has enormous economic implications; it hampers growth, triggers a multiplier effect across generations, and impacts personal and national economic development as a whole. The following three subsections explain this economic perspective in more detail.

Restrained economic growth

Several studies on the economic impact over the last 20 years have demonstrated that GBV has a significant negative influence on GDP development (Dolan *et al.* 2005 Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010 KPMG South Africa 2014 Walby and Olive 2014). Violence distracts resources from their optimal use and reduces living standards. The consequences are vast government expenditures on services, including policing, the Criminal Justice System [CJS], or social and special services (Bohler-Muller 2001 Bolling, Mattinson, and Myhill 2002 Shapwa 2017).

This financial burden reduces the economic capacity for other policy areas and leads to suboptimal consumption while, at the same time, reducing household income. For instance, violent men often do not provide financial support to their families, even when they would be able to do so. As a result, women and their children have a significantly reduced income level, which is less than the reported median household income of society (Day, McKenna, and Bowlus 2005 Duvvury *et al.* 2013 Walby and Olive 2014 p. 10). Nevertheless, GBV decreases the overall household income level and restricts the household's productivity alike.

Reduced productivity

In sum, the household's overall productivity decreases, and thus, corresponding spending, savings, and investments. Women who suffer from GBV have a lower employment rate, reduced productivity or performance, and less employment. Further, there is an evident correlation between women experiencing violence and lower lifetime earnings. In addition, different expenses arise on the employer side, which results from the costs of replacing, searching, and hiring additional staff. In summary, costs are leveraged and multiplied throughout various areas (Dolan *et al.* 2005 Duvvury *et al.* 2009 Kötter, Obst, and Voltmer 2017 KPMG South Africa 2014 Reeves and O'Leary-Kelly 2007).

Multiplier effect

The reduced output is even more significant because of the economic multiplier effect, as private and public spending span across generations, which increases costs. It contributes to a lower amount of savings and investments passed onto the next generation, which restrains future economic well-being. Especially in Southern Africa, this multiplier effect has enormous leverage (KPMG South Africa 2014).

After having discussed the impacts of GBV, the following Section 1.4 briefly presents the reasons to measure its costs.

1.4. Reasons to measure the costs of GBV

Analysis of GBV's costs can reveal the extent and location of its impact on a range of social and economic institutions. The four significant benefits identified in estimating the GBV losses are the following:

1. Increased awareness by identifying its monetary value: the aim is to increase awareness and consequently possibilities for intervention by identifying its monetary value. Estimating the monetary value associated with GBV provides an understanding of its impact on a population. It also aims to raise the perpetrator's awareness of the costs they have to pay. For example, perpetrators have to pay for their crimes through imprisonment or any related financial shortfall during detention and after release.
2. Enhanced possibilities of comparison: the usefulness of the monetary value is that it enables comparison between [preventative] programmes or impacts onto different nations that previously were incomparable. The increased awareness, in return, strengthens arguments for the intervention of both public and private stakeholders (Council of Europe [2011](#) García-Moreno *et al.* [2005](#)).
3. Decreased social acceptance of violence: costing of violence removes the survivor from the centre of the debate. Thus, the discussion goes over to the correctness of cultural norms. Therefore, the analysis supports the process of understanding the broader consequences for society (Day, McKenna, and Bowlus [2005](#)). The costing informs the public about the lack of gender equality. It redirects the discussion on the implicit assumption that controlling women's behaviour through the threat and use of violence is unacceptable, and the private nature of acts of violence is questioned. In summary, measuring the cost of GBV aims to reduce its social acceptability (Dolan *et al.* [2005](#) Duvvury *et al.* [2013](#) KPMG South Africa [2014](#) Walby and Olive [2014](#)).
4. Increased quantity and quality of government programmes and policies: measuring the costs can be used by the government as an indicator that GBV is a social problem that falls beneath their scope. It provides evidence to justify policy intervention and to initiate changes in policy-making. Thus, it can promote social policy that is designed to decrease and tackle its prevalence (Walby and Olive [2013](#)).
5. Improved allocation of scarce resources: the economic analyses provide policymakers with information on spending priorities and presents the baseline for a more in-depth assessment. It delivers analytical data on how public resources can be spent more efficiently. Results can be used to argue for higher priority in the allocation of scarce resources among competing ends. The results-based analysis provides useful indications on required budgetary changes. Without adequate budgeting, programmes and services are jeopardised, as they will not be able to live up to the exact nature and volume of clients needs. This is particularly essential for developing and emerging nations, as resources are limited, and social service provision is already relatively restricted (Day, McKenna, and Bowlus [2005](#) Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) [2003](#) Walby [2004](#)).
6. The establishment of budget lines that reflect GBV impacts: further, understanding the costs of service delivery is necessary to ensure sufficient budgets. As the literature indicates, early prevention and action will cost less than later crisis intervention. Also, such information is essential to evaluate the economic impact and effectiveness of interventions (Day, McKenna, and Bowlus [2005](#); Walby [2004](#)).

In summary, measuring the cost showcases how GBV drains resources from a vast majority of stakeholders, including the private sector, government, civil society, and individuals. It further stresses the need for early investments, as in prevention and treatment programmes, which result in potential future savings (Day, McKenna, and Bowlus 2005). Generally, the objective of estimating the cost of GBV is two-fold, and in brief, it includes the:

1. Estimation of current expenses: to evaluate GBV losses that will artificially increase over time if no action is taken.
2. Calculation of the cost of inaction: to calculate the cost reductions or the potential gains achieved due to preventative programmes.

To conclude, the critical functions of the analysis of the economic costs of GBV are to:

1. evaluate the cost to society and specific sectors of a nation,
2. inform policymakers about spending priorities,
3. offer an economic basis for GBV policies,
4. enable monitoring and comparative evaluation of prevention programmes,
5. identify areas wherein better data is needed to measure and monitor relevant actions,
6. indicate potential economic savings from a reduction of GBV,
7. provide an assessment of the cost of non-intervention.

After having discussed the rationale to calculate the costs of GBV, Section 1.5 briefly will summarise the situation in Namibia.

1.5. GBV in Namibia

Prevalence of GBV in emerging countries

As with other types of violence, the true extent of GBV is unknown. Different studies suggest that prevalences are high, but cost figures are difficult to compare, given the cultural differences and the silence surrounding violence (Heise, Ellsberg, and Gottemoeller 1999; Walby and Olive 2014). However, GBV disproportionately affects low- and middle-income countries. The World Health Organization [WHO] estimated that more than 90 per cent of all violence-related deaths occurred in developing and emerging nations. Furthermore, the estimated homicide figures in low-income countries are 32.1 per 100 000 people; and thereby higher, as compared to 14.4 per 100 000 in high-income countries (Waters *et al.* 2004), with Namibia being no exception.

Prevalence of GBV in Namibia

The only GBV costing study within the Southern African Development Community [SADC] was the 2014 Klynveld Peat Marwick Goerdeler [KPMG] study (KPMG South Africa 2014) carried out for South Africa. The prevalence ratio³ of women experiencing GBV was between 20 and

³Please note that the term prevalence ratio or prevalence proportion is always chosen. Specific literature erroneously calls it the prevalence rate ratio or the prevalence rate. However, the recorded GBV prevalence

30 per cent, and the estimated cost was at least 0.9 to 1.3 of the 2012 GDP. Nevertheless, the figures should be considered the smallest estimate because the paper does not include all necessary data needed for comprehensive cost analysis, as certain information was unavailable at the point of research, among others (KPMG South Africa [2014](#) p. 11). In the SADC region and especially in Namibia, GBV is an endemic problem. As a result of the escalating cases, the Namibian government has enacted several laws to protect survivors and punish perpetrators (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) p. 295).⁴ However, despite enormous efforts to curb the crisis, prevalence ratios remain high (Bott, Morrison, and Ellsberg [2005](#)). In detail:

- Over one third [36 per cent] of ever-partnered women reported having ever experienced physical or sexual violence enacted by an intimate partner (García-Moreno *et al.* [2006](#)).
- About ten per cent of the Namibian women reported that an intimate partner had either tried to kill them or threatened to kill them (García-Moreno *et al.* [2005](#)).
- Overall, 20 per cent of ever-married Namibian women have experienced physical or sexual violence enacted by their current or most recent husband during the past 12 months (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) p. 310).⁵

In order to narrow this proportion down for this case study, the used prevalence proportions are presented in the next paragraph.

Prevalence ratio of this study

The study's definition goes beyond mere spousal violence and includes GBV enacted by third persons, including family friends, teachers, police, or soldiers too (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) p. 299). Thus, this paper's ratio is based on the following data:

17.50 per cent of Namibian women have experienced physical and sexual violence enacted by all types of intimate partners, family members, or third parties during the past 12 months. In detail, this figure includes 3.70 per cent of women who have experienced sexual violence (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) p. 300) and 13.80 per cent who have suffered from physical violence (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) p. 298).

In brief, GBV is acknowledged as a significant concern within the country, and several strategies were explored to address it (Hubbard *et al.* [2006](#)).

After the situation in Namibia was presented, Section [1.6](#) will outline the objectives and structure of this study.

is not a rate, as it depicts how significant the phenomenon's impact is in one group of people with specific characteristics or attributes to another group, which does not have such features (Martinez *et al.* [2017](#)).

⁴These laws include, among other things, the Married Persons Equality Act [No.1 of 1996], the Combating of Rape Act [No.8 of 2000], the Combating of DV Act [No.4 of 2003], the Maintenance Act [No.9 of 2003], and the Children Status Act [No.6 of 2006] (Coomer [2019](#); Dianne and Rimmer [2007](#); Gender Research and Advocacy Project [2012](#); Hubbard *et al.* [2006](#); Legal Assistance Centre (LAC) [2005a](#); Legal Assistance Centre (LAC) [2005b](#); Ministry of Justice, Namibia [2000](#)).

⁵The time frame refers to the 12 months preceding the interview.

1.6. Objectives and structure of this study

Objectives

In summary, this paper's two main objectives are to provide:

1. An overview of literature: the objective is to analyse and assess the available methodical options of GBV costing. The study offers a desk review of the available methods and literature for developed and developing countries, including an analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of such. Its further aim is to map existing knowledge on the links to economic growth, focusing on developing and emerging nations.
2. The GBV costs for Namibia: this paper will elaborate and apply a conceptual model to calculate the cost of GBV in Namibia. It asks what kind of costs occur in Namibia and how high these costs are in proportion to the national GDP.

Structure

The study's structure subdivides into the following four steps:

1. A literature review of all available methods and all relevant research that meets the defined set of eligibility criteria.
2. A review of the strengths and weaknesses of the respective approaches.
3. The application of chosen methods and the computing of associated costs categories.
4. The conclusion, including recommendations.

The first step is a desk review of all available methods. The text identifies and discusses the differences in applied methods among existing studies for both developed and developing countries, focusing on similar economic development levels and GBV prevalence, as in Namibia. This paper presents in detail the different approaches employed to determine the losses. It reviews its strengths and weaknesses and gives recommendations for future research. The reviewing and computing divide into the seven cost classes of:

1. lost economic output,
2. health service costs,
3. legal costs,
4. social welfare and special service costs,
5. personal costs,
6. intangibles, physical, and emotional impact,
7. second-generation costs.

After the overarching goals and structure of this study were presented, Section [1.7](#) provides an overview of the current research status on GBV costing.

1.7. Present state of literature

Section [1.7](#) summarises the current state of the literature in general, in emerging countries and the SADC region, including Namibia.

Literature on the economic implications of GBV

The research on costs linked to GBV gained momentum through the Millennium Development Goals [MDGs] (UN Women 2018a), upon which a literature review is conducted on the different methods of evaluating the direct and indirect costs of GBV (Day, McKenna, and Bowlus 2005). A growing body of research aims to estimate the cost of the negative impacts in monetary terms (Duvvury *et al.* 2013 García-Moreno *et al.* 2013). These studies have been critical in framing the context for policymakers. They have supported placing the issue within the broader social welfare agenda of public budgeting priorities (Morrison and Orlando 2004). A separate body of literature has focused on the impacts of abuse on survivors' employment, productivity, and income. The European Institute for Gender Equality [EIGE] updated the findings in its latest report on "Estimating the cost of Gender-Based Violence in the European Union" and explores specific patterns for calculating all costs associated with GBV (Walby and Olive 2014). However, there is little systematic knowledge in research about the impact of GBV on economic costs and their links to economic growth, especially in developing and emerging countries (Day, McKenna, and Bowlus 2005; Duvvury *et al.* 2013).

Literature on the economic implications of GBV in developing and emerging countries

The majority of the cost studies are primarily confined to high-income industrialised countries, where the data availability across the various cost categories is more extensive and robust. Nevertheless, the calculation of economic costs in developing and emerging countries are becoming increasingly important. However, the effects on economic growth have not yet been systematically analysed and not extensively tested (Duvvury *et al.* 2013). It is particularly challenging to disentangle losses linked to GBV for the scope of the developing nations since the quality and quantity of data is often restricted. In several case studies, the framework conditions developed in the industrialised countries are applied to developing and emerging countries (Williams 2014). A limited number of analyses concentrate on countries that are comparable with the Namibian situation in terms of data availability or GBV culture (Morrison and Orlando 2004).

Literature on the economic implications of GBV within the Southern African Development Community [SADC] region

Nevertheless, so far, only one single study estimates the costs for the SADC region. The African KPMG study estimated the economic impact of GBV for South Africa in 2014. The research seeks to identify costs associated with individual survivors, governments, civil society, and businesses. Nevertheless, due to the lack of comprehensive data, the report uses a considerable number of assumptions. Therefore, the overall outcome must be considered indicative, and in some cases, even speculative. However, despite the high prevalence ratios, there is no case study calculating the cost of GBV for Namibia yet (Tibinyane 2018). This paper would be the first calculation and careful examination of the overall economic losses conducted for this region.

After the current research status has been briefly presented, Section 1.8 will show the applied underlying methods.

1.8. Methods

Based on the literature review, the analysis on the feasibility of methods and concerning the availability of data in Namibia, the approaches presented in Table 1.1 were identified to best compute the Namibian scenario.

Table 1.1.: Different methods of GBV costing.

Cost category	Approach
Economic output	Health state
Health services	Unit-cost
Legal and social welfare	Budget share
Personal	Unit-cost
Intangibles	QALY-loss-based WTP
Second-generation	DALY

Source: Own representation.

The categories and methods shown in Table 1.1 include the following elements:

1. Lost economic output: the category estimates the lost earnings due to physical and sexual violence. Costing is conducted on survey-based data found in the Namibia Demographic and Health Survey [NDHS] (MoHSS and ICF International 2014), utilising the purpose-built model of Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005. The essential elements within the approach of Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 are adverse health state outcomes derived from survivors' statements of injury, researched by Walby and Allen 2004. An average value of the lost economic output for each violent crime category is formulated from simulated statistical probability modelling the prevalence of psychological and physical health injuries and the corresponding work-time loss. A statistical probability is assigned to each adverse health state. For instance, due to rape, 2.50 per cent of women endure an abortion, or in the case of common assault, 13.75 per cent suffer from an acute stress disorder (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 34). Based on this, Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 updated the findings of the 2004 Home Office Online Report [HOOR] by Walby and Allen 2004, concerning the frequency of different PTSDs and added them to the crime categories of sexual assault or wounding.
2. Health service costs: this class estimates the cost of utilising mental and physical health services from police data and survivors' self-reporting of injuries sustained in representative Namibian surveys (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). Findings reporting the prevalence and nature of GBV injuries from accident and emergency department cohorts have been employed (Walby and Olive 2014).
3. Legal costs: the Criminal Justice System [CJS] approach includes police service costs, legal aid, prosecution fees, forensic services, prison expenses, conditional sentencing, and expenses for probation and offender programmes (Legal Assistance Centre (LAC) 2017).
4. Social welfare and special service costs: the approach covers gender equality and community empowerment activities. Further, it includes general social welfare services and relevant national and international donor activities (Bell 2003; Ministry of Gender Equality and Child Welfare 2012).
5. Personal costs: this category reflects the variety of other expenses borne by the individual survivor, and estimates include the cost of damage to property, relocation expenses,

home repossession, and personal legal expenses, for instance (Cohen *et al.* 2000 Crowne *et al.* 2010 Gass *et al.* 2011).

6. Intangibles, physical, and emotional impact: the applied model estimates the monetary value of avoiding the physical and psychological harm of GBV. It is based on the QALY-WTP model (Bala and Zarkin 2000 Gold, Stevenson, and Fryback 2002 Hirskyj 2007 Malek 2000 Sassi 2006 ⁶).
7. Second-generation costs: the used model computes the impacts on children’s health due to malnutrition and morbidity. The cost estimates include expenditures on psychological counselling, children’s support, or protection (Caspi *et al.* 2002 Cohen *et al.* 2000 Covell 2005 Dube *et al.* 2002 Fang *et al.* 2017 World Health Organization (WHO) 2016a).

However, the problem of underestimation within GBV cost estimations infuses all listed categories. The estimates tend to be conservative because there is yet insufficient evidence and research to thoroughly analyse all relationships between GBV and its associated impact in all forms. Thus, the development of methods, including the production of necessary data to document it, is essential to improving outcomes.

Section 1.9 summarises the overall key findings of this paper.

1.9. Key findings

Table 1.2 summarises the computed costs.

Table 1.2.: Total results of all categories.

Cost category	GDP share [%]
Economic output	1.64
Health services	0.26
Legal	0.50
Social welfare and special services	1.09
Personal	0.28
Intangibles	0.62
Second-generation	1.62
Total	6.01
Total [without second-generation costs]	4.39

Source: Own representation.

When comparing the outcome with the results of the other studies, the following conclusions can be drawn:

⁶The QALY health losses, combined with the WTP-model employed by Dolan *et al.* 2005 Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 Walby 2004, is identified as the most appropriate to compute the losses through intangibles, physical, and emotional impact.

-
1. Lost economic output: the calculated costs are in the upper range compared to other studies and nations.
 2. Health service costs: the methods used in developing and emerging countries are not always holistic, making it difficult to compare this category. The approach used in this study is comparable to that applied in developed countries. Overall, the results in this Section 1.9 are in the upper range.
 3. Legal costs: the calculated costs are very high. It should be noted that the studies carried out for developing and emerging countries are often methodologically incomplete.
 4. Social welfare and special service costs: the applied method goes beyond the standard approaches, which usually are used to calculate social benefits, and as a result, the costs estimated in this category are higher.
 5. Personal costs: the results of the international literature exceed the results of this study because the calculated cost-share is relatively low. This is mainly due to the legal and cultural hurdles that make divorce difficult. In consequence, the personal costs incurred in this segment are lower compared to other research.
 6. Intangibles, physical, and emotional impact: international literature calculates a relatively higher GDP cost-share in this cost class. The assumptions made in this category are rather conservative, which reflects in the lower overall results.
 7. Second-generation costs: this category, in turn, has a very high share of costs compared to other results. It is mainly because the method used is extensive in its level of detail and scope.

Based on these results, the hypothesis created could be confirmed. Costs are around six per cent of gross domestic product. It should be noted that the calculated cost-share is very extensive, as it covers all areas of life and also includes cross-generational costs.

Another finding is that studies that calculate the cost of GBV as a share of gross domestic product in developing and emerging countries show certain shortcomings. Difficulties include, for example, problems with gross domestic product surveys, which are often based on outdated data. In addition, numerous studies are characterised by methodological issues. A weak methodological basis is used for many cost categories, which led to distortions. In addition, cultural norms create further challenges. For instance, certain public officials in Namibia have internalised the culture of GBV, making it difficult for survivors of violence to access critical services even though these services are earmarked.

To continue, Section 1.10 will provide a final overview of the content covered in Chapter 1.

1.10. Conclusion

This introductory Chapter 1 presented the various challenges involved in calculating the cost of GBV. The analysis begins with the definition of GBV. Various terminologies make it challenging to compare studies consistently. GBV has different consequences on physical and mental health. The impact continues to span over generations. These conditions provide challenges to comprehensive cost calculations. It should also be noted that violence has different effects on a nation's economic growth. It determines its productivity and multiplies the negative consequences on the economic sectors.

Furthermore, there is a different strand of research with various methods and definitions of violence. Hence, output and results differ widely. A detailed examination of the selected methods is therefore essential to achieve valid results. The analysis of violence costs is vital to clarify the economic consequences today and in the following years. In order to accomplish this, this study examines the seven cost categories presented in this introductory Chapter **1**

In order to continue, the following Chapter **2** deals with the theoretical basics essential to conducting the calculations in this study.

2. Theoretical foundations

2.1. Introduction

Chapter 2 on the theoretical foundations is structured as follows: first, the different types of violence are described. The explanations span the terms of physical, sexual, psychological, and economic violence. Section 2.3 deals with the impact of GBV. The consequences on the physical and mental conditions are explained. Section 2.4 describes the terminology of domestic violence [DV], interpersonal violence [IPV], and the considered Gender-Based Violence [GBV] term. Section 2.5 deals extensively with the concept of Gender-Based Violence. In detail, the concept of the perpetrator, the survivor, and the definitions of the frequency are explained, and the different theoretical strands within the GBV research are presented. In doing so, a distinction is made between the academic views, which place their research focus on, first, the women, or second on the different power relations within a relationship and third on the various norms and cultures. The GBV definition used in this study is then derived. Section 2.8 explains the different types of costs and their broader categorisation. A distinction is made between direct and indirect and tangible and intangible costs. Then the several cost classes are explained in detail. The seven categories used are the following:

1. lost economic output,
2. health service costs,
3. legal costs,
4. social welfare costs,
5. personal costs,
6. physical and emotional impact,
7. second-generation costs.

The following outline describes the specific categories of violence and their application within mainstream literature.

There are many alternative terms used in the literature when talking about GBV, including:

- family violence,
- interpersonal violence [IPV],
- domestic violence [DV],
- battered wives and women, and
- gender-based Violence [GBV] (Duvvury *et al.* 2013 García-Moreno *et al.* 2005).

It has become common in many guidelines and circles of practitioners to refer to GBV; however, several definitions are actively used (Walby 2004 p. 39). However, they vary depending on the type of abuse and the relationship to the perpetrator (Walby 2004 p. 1).

It should be noted that the relevant data basis was not available for a large part of the cost categories to calculate the costs for men. The reason is that the violence perpetrated by women against men is still little noticed in the literature. Therefore, many of the results only include the violence committed by men against women and, if possible, against minors. Concerning the survivor term, the following must be mentioned in this introductory part.

The survivor term

The term survivor underlines that those affected have overcome or will overcome their trauma and eventually evolve to become survivors of the abuse (Forde 2018). However, specific references indicate that the term may provide a misleading conclusion. This means that not everyone affected will overcome their trauma and the adverse effects of GBV (Danielle, C. 2018).

Nevertheless, the term is chosen because it reflects the strengths of the abused. It does not force the abused into a victim role, which is a negative term in most cultures. Therefore, the term “survivor” is mainly used in this work instead of the terminology “victim.”

There are several contexts in which individuals can experience violence. Therefore, the various sub-groups of abuse are presented in Section 2.2 to develop the GBV definition of this study.

The following subsection will elaborate on the definition of violence used in this study, starting with a documentation of the different types of abuse.

2.2. Particular types of violence

The following four paragraphs will discuss the notions of physical, sexual, psychological, and economic abuse, on which the literature agrees.

Physical violence

Physical abuse is generally considered to include the use of a:

- weapon, or
- physical force.

Literature commonly defines physical abuse as being:

- slapped or having something thrown at,
- pushed or shoved,
- hit with a fist or something else,
- kicked, dragged or beaten up,
- choked,
- burnt, or
- being threatened or harmed with a gun, knife, or another weapon (Duvvury *et al.* 2013 Walby 2004; World Health Organization (WHO) 2013b).

Another significant subset of GBV is that of sexual abuse.

Sexual violence

In the public health and psychological literature, *sexual violence* is generally defined as a harmful, violent sexual act committed against the survivor's consent (Christofides *et al.* 2006 United Nations (UN), Secretary-General 2016). This includes all actions taken under the pressure or influence of drugs or alcohol. In general, the literature agrees with the WHO concept that sexual violence is:

“Any sexual act or attempt to obtain a sexual act, unwanted sexual comments or advances or acts to traffic that is directed against a person's sexuality, using coercion by anyone, regardless of their relationship to the survivor, in any setting, including at home and at work” (World Health Organization (WHO) 2016a).

In general, the literature distinguishes the following three types of sexual violence:

1. sexual violence and sexual abuse involving sexual intercourse [e.g. rape];
2. sexual violence and sexual abuse without sexual intercourse [e.g. undesirable touches, but without sexual intercourse]; and
3. non-contact sexual violence [for example, the threat of sexual violence, exhibitionism, and verbal sexual harassment] (Butchart *et al.* 2015).

According to Walby and Olive 2014, the term includes:

The unwanted or attempted penetration of the body, such as vagina or anus, by other body parts or objects without consent (Walby and Olive 2014 p. 35).

In addition, sexual and physical abuse is often associated with psychological harm. This term is briefly explained in the next paragraph.

Psychological violence

There is less agreement about which behaviours constitute psychological violence and which frequencies have to occur in practice. The term generally refers to any action that has the purpose of:

Enacting control or isolation by threatening, degrading, insulting, stalking, or humiliating the survivor (Duvvury *et al.* 2013; García-Moreno *et al.* 2013; World Health Organization (WHO) 2009).¹

An important subcategory of psychological abuse is stalking. International literature generally defines it as:

“Repeated visual or physical proximity, nonconsensual communication, and or verbal, written, or implied threats directed at a specific individual that would

¹Although the literature accepts these behaviours as part of GBV patterns, they are rarely considered in international cost calculations (Duvvury *et al.* 2013; Duvvury and Carney 2012; Siddique 2011).

arouse fear in a reasonable person” (Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003).

There is general agreement that psychological abuse is a critical part of the economic impact of GBV. So far, studies have not fully calculated the costs of this type of violence yet. However, among those who have done, there is little agreement on the methods to be used (Walby and Olive 2014).

However, generally, the outlined WHO definition of psychological violence is widely accepted in the broad literature.

Another internationally recognised type of violence is that of economic abuse.

Economic violence

Economic violence is a new type of violence that is increasingly applied in recent literature. In general, research agrees that monetary or financial abuse involves the widespread denial of the survivor’s access to material goods, essential resources, and assets. It is a relatively new addition to the GBV term. Currently, only a few studies have included this aspect in their cost estimates, as most research only calculates the consequences of sexual, physical and psychological violence (Duvvury *et al.* 2013; Walby and Olive 2014; World Health Organization (WHO) 2013b; World Health Organization (WHO) 2016b).

The consequences of such in the form of physical and mental damage are examined in more detail in Section 2.3.

2.3. Consequences of violence

The effects of violence are complex and include damage to physical and mental health (García-Moreno *et al.* 2013). To further build on the concept of health, the World Health Organization [WHO] definition is outlined. The WHO defines health as:

“A state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being² and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity” (World Health Organization (WHO) 1948).

This definition is an essential element in structuring the effects of GBV on health and well-being. The WHO has identified the following three main aspects of physical and mental disabilities related to GBV, namely:

1. physical injury,
2. mental trauma and stress,

²The Cambridge Dictionary describes well-being as the state of feeling healthy and happy (Cambridge Dictionary 2019).

3. anxiety, and control (García-Moreno *et al.* 2013).

Physical injury is one of these elements long structured and explained. However, other affiliations between violence and its effects on well-being and health are less understood (Abramsky *et al.* 2011, Arias 2004, Bleakley 2010). These include weight problems, substance abuse, or coronary infarctions. Nevertheless, the literature, among others Walby and Olive 2014, broadly agree on calculating the effects of the following two aspects:

- physical damage resulting from violent events that lead to serious health problems; and
- psychological damage resulting from long-term harmful physical restrictions and mental stress (Walby and Olive 2014, p. 37).

The following paragraph explains the two terms in more detail.

Physical harm

Direct consequences for physical health generally include those that lead to various illnesses such as injuries, disabilities, chronic pain, or cardiovascular diseases. This also consists of an increased risk of premature birth, miscarriage, morbidity, and mortality (Duvvury *et al.* 2013, p. 7). In addition, violence, trauma, and stress during pregnancy have severe consequences for the mother's health and unborn/child alike (Altarac and Strobino 2002). A growing body of literature shows that GBV significantly increases women's vulnerability to HIV/AIDS and other sexually transmitted diseases [STDs]. However, research is just beginning to uncover the relationship between GBV and STDs (García-Moreno and Watts 2000). Studies conducted in sub-Saharan Africa, including South Africa, Tanzania, or Kenya, showed that HIV-positive women had more GBV experience than HIV-negative women (Campbell *et al.* 2008). For the South African context, Jewkes (Jewkes 2018, Jewkes *et al.* 2010) estimates that 25.80 per cent of women have tested HIV-positive because of some form of GBV. If gender equality and the low power balance of women in heterosexual relationships were improved, 13.90 per cent of HIV infections could be prevented. Jewkes further states that 11.90 per cent of HIV infections would have been prevented if women had no more than one physical or sexual partner violence experience in South Africa (Jewkes *et al.* 2010, p. 6). Nevertheless, the relationship is complex and causalities challenging to establish. The same complexity applies to the psychological consequences of GBV.

Psychological harm

GBV is generally associated with psychological damage such as anxiety or depression, among others (Swanberg, Macke, and Logan 2006). For example, women exposed to violence are more than twice as likely to suffer from depression. As the WHO review shows, exposure to GBV is also associated with a higher prevalence of suicide attempts (García-Moreno *et al.* 2013). In general, psychological or emotional harm can include:

- acute stress disorders,
- severe and moderate post-traumatic stress disorder [PTSD],
- short and long-term [moderate to severe] depression,
- suicide,
- obesity, eating disorders, or
- anxiety.

The probability of physical and mental damage also differs depending on the type of abuse that has occurred (Dolan *et al.* [2005](#); Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#)). In order to describe this topic in more detail, the various forms of violence are briefly defined in Section [2.4](#).

2.4. Terminologies of violence

In the literature, the terms DV, IPV, and GBV are often used interchangeably. However, there are significant operational differences. The terms differ, among others, in their specification by the type of relationship between the perpetrator and the abused. However, the definition of this relationship is of central importance for calculating the economic consequences since it determines the size of the population under consideration. The subsequent paragraphs will present an overview of the different terms used in the literature (The UN Refugee Agency (UNHCR) [2019](#); World Health Organization (WHO) [2018a](#)).

Domestic Violence

DV is also often defined as spouse or family violence. It is characterised as a pattern of abusive behaviour by one or both partners in a [intimate] relationship. There are many forms, including physical harm, sexual and emotional abuse, behaviour control, intimidation, stalking, and passive abuse as neglect or economic expropriation; these include:

- members of the same household, who can be spouses and other intimate partners;
- other family members, such as parents, children, or siblings.

The term often includes violence between individuals who previously shared a household as former partners or spouses (Duvvury *et al.* [2013](#); Walby and Allen [2004](#); Walby and Olive [2014](#); World Health Organization (WHO) [2018b](#)).

In summary, DV refers only to any act of violence committed by a family member against another [former] family member. Hence, this definition is minimal and reduces the circle to a small subset of survivors (Duvvury *et al.* [2013](#)). As a result, the broader concept of IPV is discussed in more detail next.

Interpersonal Violence

The term IPV goes beyond the domestic environment and is broader. It involves violence between:

- people who have had or still have an intimate relationship. They may or may not share the same household (Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) [2003](#); VicHealth [2004](#)).

The Council of Europe defines IPV as:

“All acts of physical, sexual, psychological or economic violence between former or current spouses or partners, whether or not the perpetrator shares or has shared the same residence with the survivor” (Council of Europe [2011](#), p. 19).

In summary, it can be said that IPV is not tied to a domestic environment but focuses on a former or current intimate partner. As a result, other offender profiles fall through the grid, profiles that are critical to determining the economic cost of violence. For example, the term does not include physical and sexual violence by police officers, soldiers, or institutional settings such as schools (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) p. 299). For these reasons, the following paragraph will analyse the term GBV more closely (Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) [2003](#) Krug *et al.* [2002](#) Waters *et al.* [2004](#) World Health Organization (WHO) [2018a](#)).

2.5. Important GBV terms

The GBV term goes beyond this framework. The difference between GBV and the terms DV and IPV results from the following three categories:

1. the perpetrator,
2. a group of survivors, and
3. the frequency of abuse (Mogotsi *et al.* [2015](#) The UN Refugee Agency (UNHCR) [2019](#)).

A peculiarity of the GBV term, which has a significant influence on the cost calculation, is its used definition of the perpetrator.

Perpetrator-term

The GBV definition, in broad terms, includes the following group of offenders:

1. families and relatives, including all types of family members;
2. partners, covering friends and former [intimate] partners;
3. acquaintances, friends, and co-workers;
4. unknown persons who exercise so-called external violence; or
5. institutional actors that trigger so-called state violence, as in schools, at the workplace, or in nursing homes (Dolan *et al.* [2005](#) Duvvury *et al.* [2013](#) García-Moreno *et al.* [2013](#) Waters *et al.* [2004](#) World Health Organization (WHO) [2013b](#) World Health Organization (WHO) [2018b](#)).

Another category that strongly influences the outcome of GBV's economic costs is the definition of the group of survivors affected, which is presented in the next paragraph.

Survivor-term

The GBV term usually includes the following group of survivors:

- intimate partners, both current and former spouses, and partners,
- sexual partners and acquaintances,
- friends and family members,
- employers and employees, or
- unknown persons.

The GBV term covers typically all age groups concerned and includes the abuse of older people, as well as minors, and specific violence, which is committed by or against people between 10

and 29 years of age. Most studies only include survivors over the age of 15 (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#)). However, it is rare, at least within the current economic surveys, that the effects on children or the elderly are calculated. It should be noted that according to research, including the impact of GBV on children dramatically increases the economic costs (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#) Duvvury *et al.* [2013](#) Walby and Olive [2014](#)).

Another category that has a considerable impact on cost estimates is the definition of the frequency term within the applied GBV definition.

Frequency-term

In general, the literature does not agree on the frequency criterion within the GBV definition. In short, the arguments circulate the following topic:

“Whether women should be included who have only experienced one form [of violence] or whether there must be a minimum criterion for x-forms and/or y-times”
(Duvvury *et al.* [2013](#)).

Research generally uses the following approach:

1. Data from last year: the current literature mainly uses data on acts of violence that have taken place in the past 12 months since the answers of the respondents may be impaired by memory loss. However, *last year* is only a small subset of *always*. Still, last year’s data is less likely to be distorted by memory loss (Walby and Olive [2014](#) p. 15).
2. Worst-incident data: often, the calculations are based only on injuries sustained in the worst abuse cases. See, for instance, Walby and Olive [2014](#), p. 34 and Dolan *et al.* [2005](#) p. 310. This approach follows the same reasoning used in the *data from last year* argument since memory loss could lead to distortions in the data. Nevertheless, the probability that other incidents occurred that are not taken into account by this methodical procedure is high. One person may have had more than one, sometimes many, incident (Walby and Olive [2014](#), p. 38). Therefore, this approach is likely to result in an underestimation of the cost.
3. Disregarded facts: there is a smaller subset of survivors who are very heavily abused. As a result, additional cumulative violations are likely not recorded (Walby and Olive [2014](#), p. 25). In addition, an action may have caused several incidents that are later summarised in a single act. This leads to underestimating the number of actual incidents and underestimating the costs (Walby and Olive [2014](#), p. 21).

However, most studies use the *past year* and *worst incident* terminology in their GBV definition to avoid bias due to memory loss.

Having discussed the critical aspects of the GBV term, a brief overview of the various definitions in the mainstream literature is now given.

2.6. Theoretical views on GBV

There are three main interpretations of the GBV term in the current debate, each of which results from different theoretical roots. All three are briefly explained in the following paragraphs.

Focus on women

The most common understanding of GBV is that it is primarily male violence against women and girls. As set out in the 1993 U.N. Declaration on the Elimination of Violence Against Women, which defines GBV as:

“Any act of Gender-Based Violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring in public or in private life” (United Nations (UN) General Assembly [1993](#) Article 1).

The definition emphasises the structural nature of male violence against women in every area of behaviour throughout the life cycle. It highlights the gender balance of power that causes and maintains this social imbalance. These definitions are derived from a feminist theory that emphasises the gender aspect of violence against women explicitly (Read-Hamilton [2014](#)).

The second approach defines GBV mainly in the context of maintaining power.

Focus on unequal power relations

A second interpretation of the term is derived from the literature on masculinity and sexuality and reflects particularly unequal power relationships. It understands GBV mainly as violence directed by men against women. According to this interpretation, GBV is used to suppress a defined group of citizens and to enforce through a power mechanism, certain gender hierarchies, or state power. This understanding of the GBV term also includes homophobic violence and sexual exploitation of minorities (Read-Hamilton [2014](#)). An example of this interpretation is the definition by the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees [UNHCR]:

“Sexual and gender-based violence [SGBV] refers to any act that is perpetrated against a person’s will and is based on gender norms and unequal power relationships. It includes physical, emotional or psychological and sexual violence, and denial of resources or access to services. Violence includes threats of violence and coercion. SGBV inflicts harm on women, girls, men and boys and is a severe violation of several human rights” (The UN Refugee Agency (UNHCR) [2019](#)).

In addition, the third theoretical point of view defines GBV more in the context of gender roles and norms and fully includes men as victims too.

Focus on cultural norms

Researchers from the third ideological stream interpret GBV as violence against everyone, and because of its specific social role, it all together includes men and women as survivors. Violence is generally construed as a means of maintaining and strengthening gender roles and norms. In this view, all people can be affected equally. For example, this stream defines the

recruitment of boys as combatants in armed groups as a form of GBV as well (Read-Hamilton 2014). A definition derived from this view is that of the EIGE, which is as follows:

“Gender-Based Violence is a phenomenon deeply rooted in gender inequality and continues to be one of the most notable human rights violations within all societies. Gender-Based Violence is abuse directed against a person’s gender. Both women and men experience Gender-Based Violence, but the majority of survivors are women and girls” (EIGE 2019).

Namibian legislation, including the Namibian Combating of Rape Act 8 of 2000, is in line with this theory because it emphasises both the unequal balance of power and the maintenance of power. It is implicitly recognised that sexual abuse is not just a sexual crime but a crime of violence and power, using sex as a weapon of control (Ministry of Justice, Namibia 2000). It removes the emphasis on the survivor’s lack of consent and replaces it with the argument that the perpetrator used coercion. Most importantly, however, sexual violence also occurs in marriages and is recognised as such for the first time in this legislation. A relationship or marriage is no longer a justification or a safe zone to commit abuse (Hubbard *et al.* 2006 p. 5 ff.). It further redefines rape in gender-neutral terms to consider that men and boys can also be affected by such violence (Ministry of Justice, Namibia 2000).

After a brief reflection on the various theoretical aspects of GBV terminology, the definition used in this study will be presented in Section 2.7.

2.7. This paper’s GBV definition

Following the advanced Namibian legislation, this study defines GBV according to the last interpretation – focus on cultural norms – and considers it a more comprehensive instrument used to maintain and strengthen gender hierarchies. The GBV term of this study contains the following four aspects, based on the contents of the previous argumentation:

Forms of violence: from an economic perspective, all forms of violence have cost implications. The physical and mental damage are those that are mainly included in financial estimates. However, this study aims to calculate, wherever possible, all costs holistically. Thus, the used definition takes into account the following categories of violence, namely the:

1. physical,
2. sexual,
3. psychological/emotional, and
4. economic violence.

Group of offenders: this study defines GBV as violence between family members such as fathers, stepmothers, brothers, other relatives, and confidants. Violence exercised by known persons and unknown persons, such as police officers, teachers, friends, or strangers, is included. Consequently, this definition should not only cover forms of DV or IPV but also:

1. child sexual abuse,
2. sexual violence by strangers,

-
3. structural violence by public institutions, or
 4. workplace violence.

Types of survivors: the cost estimates must include all those affected and not restrict the group to a limited sub-sample. However, based on data availability and in order to avoid bias, an [natural] age cohort will be introduced. For example, according to national research, Namibian women usually only enter into sexual partnerships after 15 (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). Abuse enacted against children is calculated separately. If the data allows it, violence against men is also included wherever possible.

The frequency parameter: the frequency parameter is the most controversial and most important one for calculating the costs. Babcock *et al.* 1993, p. 42, for instance, include the following frequencies:

1. six or more minor acts [pushing or hitting],
2. two or more moderate acts of violence [slapping], or
3. at least one life-threatening act of violence [including beating or threatening with a knife or weapon].

However, other international research defines the presence of at least two cases of violence or stalking behaviour as a sufficient requirement for a GBV classification, such as the paper “Cost of Violence in Partnership Against Women in the United States,” by the Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003. In summary, however, the researchers did not agree on any frequency parameters and did not identify a constant factor, making the comparison of international cost surveys even more complicated. To avoid memory loss bias and to remove the most abused cohort, the past 12 months and worst-case incident data is used for this analysis. A subsequent underestimation of the costs is acknowledged.

Based on the four parameters mentioned, the GBV definition of this study is as follows:

“Gender-based violence is a phenomenon that results from inequalities in societies. It includes all violence against individuals based on their gender. Both women and men of all ages can be affected. Still, most of the survivors are women and girls. GBV encompasses physical, sexual, mental, emotional, and economic abuse. The violence extends to all areas of society and covers the private/domestic sphere and public. It includes violence used in [public] institutions like schools, through the police and soldiers, or in the workplace too.”

After this study’s definition has been elaborated, Section 2.8 lists the theoretical foundations of the various types of costs associated with GBV.

2.8. Types of costs

2.8.1. General overview

The cost categories vary depending on the literature. In general, they can include the following:

-
1. expenses in the judicial system, including civil, police, and administrative facilities;
 2. public and private healthcare costs;
 3. social benefits, including special services such as shelter, preventive, and supportive activities for the abused and their children;
 4. private expenses, including for health care, translocation, property damage, accommodation, or attorney fees;
 5. intangible losses, such as lower household income or productivity;
 6. second-generation costs, including any impact on children;
 7. reduce public tax revenue (Walby and Olive [2014](#) World Health Organization (WHO) [2013b](#)).

When categorising losses, most of the GBV literature divides costs into the two categories of direct and indirect costs. Those that are easier to measure are the direct expenses.

Direct costs

There are direct costs for capital or material use. In most cases, the expenditure is directly related to preventing or responding to GBV. The direct costs refer to expenses through:

- health and psychiatric care such as medication and emergency rooms;
- police, law enforcement and detention;
- legal, judicial services or civil justice;
- social services such as accommodation and counselling;
- property damage or moving costs (García-Moreno *et al.* [2013](#); UN Women [2010](#); Walby and Allen [2004](#); Walby and Olive [2014](#); World Health Organization (WHO) [2019](#)).

Direct costs are relatively easy to calculate, while indirect damages are more challenging to identify in most cases.

Indirect costs

Indirect costs include all expenses that are associated with GBV cases but are not directly related to them. They have an assumed financial value, although they do not always present a monetary transfer per se (Walby and Olive [2014](#)). The economic consequences that result from the physical and psychological trauma or the lifelong effects of GBV include, among others:

- Indirect costs by reducing the Quality of Life due to pain and suffering, including the indirect effects on other family members and children.
- Indirect costs due to loss of income, loss of employment, or loss of time, such as household chores.
- Indirect, non-monetary costs such as lost investment in human capital or the decreased value of housing in neighbourhoods with a high GBV prevalence.³

³Some studies aim to calculate the adverse effects of GBV on property values, for example. The Mexican Inter-American Development Bank, Research Department [2013](#) study found that a one per cent rise in homicide rates reduced house values by 1.80 per cent. The literature has also found a correlation between high GBV prevalence proportions and reduced investment rates, or high GBV prevalence and higher insurance rates for all members of society (Agüero [2013](#); Brand and Price [2000](#); Institute of Medicine and National Research Council [2012](#); Waters *et al.* [2004](#)).

Indirect expenses are often not delineated from the category of Tangible and Intangible costs. The following paragraph, therefore, describes such shortly.

Tangible and Intangible costs

When estimating the cost of GBV, it is equally important to distinguish between the following expenses:

1. tangibles costs – expenses that can generally be monetised, and
2. intangibles costs – expenses that cannot easily be monetised (Agüero [2013](#); Dolan *et al.* [2005](#) Post *et al.* [2002](#)).

Table [2.1](#) summarises the information on direct and indirect costs in greater detail.

Table 2.1.: Overview of direct, indirect, tangible and intangible costs.

Cost category	Explanation	Example
Tangibles		
Tangible and direct	Tangible – they represent actual money spent. Direct – the expenses are directly related to a GBV case.	Taxi fare to a women’s shelter. Salaries for staff in an emergency unit.
Tangible and indirect	Tangible – they have a designated monetary value. Indirect – the expenses are measured in terms of loss of potential. They represent opportunity cost rather than actual spending.	The lost personal income or lower earnings and profits derived from reduced productivity or absenteeism at work or school.
Intangibles		
Intangible and direct	Intangibles – they have no direct monetary value, and they are often approximated by the Quality or Value of Life approach. Direct – they are expenses that directly derive from a GBV case.	They include emotional suffering or reduced QALYs.
Intangible and indirect	Intangible – they have no assigned monetary value. Indirect – the expenses only indirectly derive from a GBV case.	Adverse psychological effects or psychosomatic symptoms of children who witness[ed] GBV.

Source: Own representation based on Day, McKenna, and Bowlus [2005](#)

This classification serves to create a comprehensive and holistic understanding of cost occurring in the area of GBV. Splitting expenditure into more detailed categories helps to understand the effects of GBV better and makes it easier to find the correct data to carry out the actual cost estimation (Day, McKenna, and Bowlus [2005](#)). Based on the theoretical basis provided in the previous section, Section [2.8.2](#) presents the types of costs to be calculated in this study.

2.8.2. This dissertation

The literature usually classifies the economic costs of GBV according to the consequences of violence. Section [2.8.2](#) lists the categories that are best suited for the purpose of this study. It

provides an overview of the most common types of expenses within current research, starting with the category of lost economic output.

Lost economic output

Violence affects the individual, the company, or the state, and a nation's general economic performance. GBV prevents a society from realising its full economic potential. Violence redirects aggregate demand and expenditure on goods and services to cost, such as preventing GBV. As a result, monetary resources are averted from their optimal use, which leads to lower economic growth and a lower standard of living. As a result, productivity, production, tax revenue, exports, savings, or investments within a society decrease. Consequently, the next generation will experience a lack of economic well-being. Thus, GBV has enormous adverse financial effects for future generations (Agénor and Canuto 2015; Brauer and Dunne 2010; Chan and Cho 2010; Institute of Medicine and National Research Council 2012). In detail, they include, for example, the following components:

- Direct costs: every state of physical injury and mental damage is associated with an average value of lost economic output, measured in days. Losses spread, from housework to self-employment to paid employment. The costs result from different categories of violent crime such as rape, sexual, or general assault (Cuberes and Teignier-Baqué 2012; Dalal and Dawad 2011; Duvvury *et al.* 2013; Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010).
- Indirect costs: they represent costs that result from economic losses due to physical and mental illnesses such as burnout or anxiety. The rape crime category, for example, includes additional costs associated with psychological harm caused by substance abuse, depression, or anxiety (Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005).

Health service costs

Health care costs are high for both the state and individuals and vary depending on the extent to which health care is publicly or privately funded. According to Gallant, Gwendolyn, and Royak-Shaler 1997, women exposed to GBV report more health problems and a higher frequency of using such facilities than those who are not suffering from violence. However, health management is structured differently around the world (Walby and Olive 2014, p. 37), and therefore, the different publications employ various methods (Abramsky *et al.* 2011; Ackerson *et al.* 2008; Bleakley 2010; Brown 2008; Day, McKenna, and Bowlus 2005; Drummond *et al.* 2015; Enlow *et al.* 2012; García-Moreno *et al.* 2013; Morrison and Orlando 2004). Current cost studies typically include the following healthcare costs:

- Direct costs:
 - Salaries of staff: in emergency rooms, hospitals, outpatient clinics, medical practices by paramedics, physiotherapists, or other specialists such as psychiatrists or psychologists.
 - Infrastructure costs: including all laboratories, equipment, machines, or vehicles.
 - Material costs: such as medication, hospital food, technical material, costs for electricity, and heat supply.
 - Personal expenses: including additional health services, preventive medical checkups, medication, surgeries, or alternative health services and psychological and dental treatments that are not covered by public medical care (Arias 2004; VicHealth 2004; World Health Organization (WHO) 2018c).

-
- Indirect costs:
 - In healthcare: this includes the increased medical costs due to the higher susceptibility to an illness of those affected.
 - Restricted mobility: including the impairment to participate in social life.
 - Reduced happiness and well-being: this results from a reduced quality of life or a reduced physical and mental health.

In addition, sexually transmitted diseases [STDs] such as HIV/AIDS significantly impact healthcare's direct and indirect costs, especially for women affected by GBV (Jewkes *et al.* 2010).

Legal costs

Legal costs include expenses for police, court proceedings, and punitive costs such as compensation, community penalties, or imprisonment (Immigration and Refugee Board of Canada 2012, Legal Assistance Centre (LAC) 2017, Namibia Superior Courts 2019). Direct costs generally include:

- Direct costs:
 - Capital costs: for example, expenditure on buildings and vehicles for the police, courts, or prisons, the payment of survivors' benefits, or legal aid in the area of civil justice and security.
 - Labor costs: expenses related to all salaries of employees who work in the civil justice field in probation, offender therapy, law enforcement, or forensic services.
 - Use of materials: general consumption costs, such as gasoline costs for police vehicles or supplies for the detained perpetrators (Gender Research and Advocacy Project 2012, Hubbard *et al.* 2006).

Although it does not cover many other expenses, the public sector pays most of these costs, including personal costs such as volunteering, perpetrator counselling, or private attorney fees⁴

- Indirect costs:
 - Losses: for example, loss of earnings of detainees or travel times to court appointments.
 - Time lost: to prepare, comply with, and commute to court proceedings; this also includes third parties who serve as witnesses in court (Day, McKenna, and Bowlus 2005).

In general, it can be said that legal costs are closely linked to public social expenditure. The following paragraph deals with the potential cost of the social system.

Social welfare and special service costs

Social welfare costs stem from providing public support to all parties, survivors, perpetrators, and relatives. They can be privately funded, or in most cases, publicly funded. Every time a person gains access to public services, there occur costs in the welfare structure. Community centres, social workers, or private institutions such as social institutions support complainants and their children as well as the perpetrators themselves. The list of services that can be

⁴This is covered under the corresponding category of personal costs.

accessed is extensive (Bell [2003](#); Day, McKenna, and Bowlus [2005](#); Ministry of Gender Equality and Child Welfare [2012](#); Rank, Hong-Sik, and Hirschl [2003](#)). In detail, the costs can include:

- Direct costs:
 - Public core programmes: publicly funded measures such as women’s shelters, support hotlines, preventive measures, benefits for social workers, counselling, therapy, or emergency concepts.
 - Other public programmes: these programmes include, for example, research grants, expenses for consultants, special educational services for minors, awareness-raising campaigns, or individual school activities to reduce the GBV.
 - Privately funded programmes: the concepts include the operation of counselling hotlines, general community activities, therapeutic support [for perpetrators], or therapy groups.
- Indirect costs:
 - Opportunity costs, including the alternative use of tax revenues.
 - Costs that result from a lower level of education among women and their children or from the reduced ability to work, especially for survivors who have reached a lower level of education due to GBV.
 - Costs like volunteer hours.⁵

Personal costs

GBV significantly influences the income and consumption of an individual household, as it distracts income and expenditure, among others. Individual costs may include:

- Direct costs:
 - General personal disbursements: these include transportation, additional childcare, alternative therapies, personal security measures, or mortgage and rental expenses in the event of separation or property damage (Day, McKenna, and Bowlus [2005](#)).
- Indirect costs:
 - Reduction of household income: due to [potentially] missed opportunities or decreased unpaid household chores (UNFPA Ukraine [2017](#) p. 15).
 - Intangible damages: such as the loss and reduction of one’s Quality of Life.

It should be noted that this non-material damage is not always consistently categorised in the literature. Such Intangible losses are often calculated in a separate category, called the Physical and Emotional impact.

Physical and Emotional impact

This category calculates reduced health expenditure based on a standard metric that indicates the expected Years of Life lost. This metric includes adverse health states, such as wounding or rape related to GBV (Walby and Allen [2004](#)). In detail, the computed losses may integrate the following aspects:

⁵However, it has to be noted that generally, these are listed in the literature as a separate category, namely under personal costs.

-
- Direct costs:
 - Limitations in physical and mental health: such as the duration and intensity of injuries and traumas due to violence (Walby and Olive 2014).
 - Indirect costs:
 - Consequences for municipalities: including, justified, or unfounded fears of citizens living in societies with high GBV prevalences.
 - Consequences for entire societies: like the loss of social values.
 - Consequences for third parties: for example, the shame and guilt non-violent households feel because of the GBV acts of other people in their families or communities (Day, McKenna, and Bowlus 2005).

Second-generation costs

This category includes expenses and services for children who are witnesses to GBV or directly affected by it. They represent costs that occur, such as the impact on children's health due to malnutrition and injuries. They also include expenditure on psychological counselling, support, or protective measures (Caspi *et al.* 2002; Cohen *et al.* 2000; Covell 2005; Dube *et al.* 2002; Fang *et al.* 2017; World Health Organization (WHO) 2016a). The costs extend further to the consequences of behavioural problems, impacts on education level, and even the adverse effect on future labour force participation and employment stability. In particular, they can contain the following components:

- Direct costs:
 - Health care costs: these include expenses to reverse the health problems of children and unborn babies during pregnancy, including all associated physical and mental consequences.
 - Special social services: they include the cost of childcare, child protection or emergency accommodation, among others (Enlow *et al.* 2012; Fang *et al.* 2017; Howell *et al.* 2010).
- Indirect costs:
 - Short to long-term damage: indirect costs in the short and medium period include loss of Quality of Life or the cost of additional education and support programmes that result from cognitive deficits and behavioural problems. Such damage usually results from trauma and can still occur after decades.
 - Other social effects: for example, a later higher probability of increased crime in adolescence due to personality disorders and disorders of social behaviour, which causes additional costs to the entire Civil Justice System.
 - Economic consequences: the loss of income and reduced economic productivity due to trauma and assault (Habetha *et al.* 2012, p. 68 f.).

The vicious cycle of abuse is particularly evident within this cost category: problems at school lead to lower professional qualifications, less well-qualified employment, and lower salaries. Later life is adversely affected by disadvantageous mental and physical health or increased crime rates (Habetha *et al.* 2012, p. 71).

2.9. Conclusion

Section 2.9 explained the different definitions of violence against women and determined the concept of the survivor used in this study. Victims are not described as victims but as survivors who have successfully mastered a violent situation. Different types of violence were also explained. They extend to physical, sexual, psychological, and economic violence. The effects of violence on physical and mental health have also been described. The various definitions of violence that are mainly used in the current research were also presented. Different terminologies extend to DV, IPV, and GBV; they deviate according to the terms of the perpetrator, the victim, and the frequency. Different views of GBV within the research were also considered. The opposing theoretical currents focus on the one hand on women, on the other hand on unequal power relationships within a partnership, and the other hand on norms and cultural aspects of a nation. The GBV definition used in this study is derived based on this latest view. The holistic definition includes all types of perpetrators. This also integrates perpetrators outside the domestic context and acts enacted by third parties who work in an institutional setting, such as police officers or teacher. The scope of the survivors has also been expanded. It also includes children and men and does not focus on just one gender. In order to avoid distortion, the period of the last twelve months is selected within the GBV frequency parameter. This is currently the most chosen model in research. In addition, the used cost types were defined too.

Based on current research, this case study calculates the following seven types of costs:

1. lost economic output,
2. health service costs,
3. legal costs,
4. social welfare and special service costs,
5. personal costs,
6. intangibles, physical, and emotional impact, and
7. second-generation costs.

In order to continue, the results of the literature research will be presented in Chapter 3

3. Literature review

3.1. Introduction

Chapter 3 is structured as follows: Section 3.2 describes the progression of the current literature. The development steps are divided into three phases, and the literature in industrialised, developing and emerging countries is briefly examined. For a detailed analysis, Section 3.3 explains the exclusion criteria that are used during the literature search. Overall, Section 3.3 first presents the studies excluded from further research and later describes the papers suitable for further investigation. The outline also showcases all studies that did not meet the inclusion criteria. Table 3.1 summarises all publications that have been excluded and gives the exact reasons in a summary overview. The exclusion criteria are defined based on the theories, methods, and hypotheses used in this study. The detailed information is presented at the beginning of Section 3.3. Studies that meet the search criteria are examined further in Section 3.4 and are summarised in Table 3.2. Table 3.2 also shows which criteria the reviewed studies fulfil, which costs they calculate in the respective subcategories, and which overall result they have evaluated. Section 3.4.1 provides an overview of the research that has determined all costs. Not all studies have always calculated the overall impact on the gross domestic product. Therefore, these calculations are prepared separately for this case study and are explained in more detail in the respective footnotes. The search in Section 3.4.1 is divided into developing and developed countries. This division is made to better compare the methods and theories used in the respective geographical regions, thus drawing more detailed and systematic conclusions on the studies' results and sub estimates. The division into developing, emerging, and industrialised countries is based on the classifications of the World Bank. Section 3.4.2 provides a more detailed overview of the included studies that have calculated specific cost categories. This includes papers that have not calculated all costs but have contributed to a single class only. All the seven cost types processed in detail are: 1. lost economic output, 2. health service costs, 3. legal costs, 4. social welfare and special service costs, 5. personal costs, 6. intangibles, physical, and emotional impact, and 7. second-generation costs. In the paragraph Lost economic output, particularly the studies of Duvvury *et al.* 2013, KPMG Australia 2016, Walby 2009 are examined in greater detail. The following outline displays the research that specifically analysed the category of health service costs. In particular, the 2005 Home Office Online Report [HOOR] by Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 is analysed. The next segment deals in-depth with legal cost estimates. In particular, the UNFPA Ukraine 2017, Walby 2004 studies are evaluated. The following paragraph will assess the cost categories of social welfare and special service costs. Studies that provide detailed work and research in this area include the 2004 Australian study by Access Economics (Access Economics 2004a), the Colombian study by Ribero and Sánchez Torres from 2004 (Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004) and the Swedish study by Envall and Eriksson from 2006 (Envall and Eriksson 2006). The subsequent paragraph analyses publications that have dealt explicitly with personal cost estimates, including the 2017

Ukrainian study from UNFPA (UNFPA Ukraine [2017](#)). The next segment goes into more detail about the intangibles, physical, and emotional impact costs, and reviews explicitly Walby's 2009 study on Great Britain, for instances (Walby [2009](#)). The last paragraph deals with the second-generation cost calculations. This section particularly highlights the challenges for such estimates, and a further literature analysis is carried out in this cost class. All research dealing with the costs for children are analysed across all areas of research. This step was necessary because the literature analysis from Sections [3.3](#) and [3.4](#) did not produce enough valid data and results that could have been used. As a separate investigation is created for this sub-cost category, the paragraph on second-generation costs lists the studies which are excluded and included for further analysis. Based on this more in-depth analysis, the 2017 study by Fang *et al.* [2017](#) on South Africa is identified for closer evaluation. Finally, Section [3.5](#) provides an overall conclusion.

Moving forward, Section [3.2](#) shortly presents the development of GBV literature.

3.2. Stages of literature development

The following paragraph provides a review of the processing of research in the area of GBV costing.

Three phases of development

The literature calculating the cost of GBV had three particular stages. In the first phase, experts constructed their data on small sample groups or case studies. Prevalence ratios of violence depended mainly on proxy measures (Edleson [1991](#), Mansingh and Ramphal [1993](#), Petrou and Renton [1993](#)). During this phase, the significance of good data-keeping became evident. Thus, more pressure was put on institutions to provide higher quality data.

In the second phase, scholars had access to a higher quality of representative statistics. Thus, national cost estimates could be better computed. A limited number of papers were published based on restricted datasets for specific cost categories. High-quality data sources became more available in this process since GBV attracted more awareness as a cross-national issue.

In the third and current phase, studies have used better datasets, and scholars could conduct more representative research. [See the work of Bolling, Mattinson, and Myhill [2002](#), Ellsberg *et al.* [1999](#), Godenzi and Yodanis [1999](#), Golding [1999](#), Heiskanen and Piispa [2001](#), Walker *et al.* [1999](#), for example]. Nonetheless, research still faces limitations regarding suitably qualified data to estimate the Intangible costs better, for instance (Walby and Allen [2004](#), Walby and Olive [2014](#)). However, the more data institutions provide, the better the accuracy of final estimates will become in the near future (Day, McKenna, and Bowlus [2005](#)), and better and more comprehensive costing studies can be conducted (Ackerson *et al.* [2008](#), Bloom, Canning, and Sevilla [2004](#), Christofides *et al.* [2006](#), Coker *et al.* [2002](#)).

Developed countries

The first studies on the economic impact of GBV in industrialised countries were carried out in the late 1990s [See, for example, the work of Brand and Price [2000](#), Godenzi and

Yodanis [1999] Greaves *et al.* [1995] Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996] Morrison and Orlando [1999] Stanko, Crisp, and Hale [1998] Walker *et al.* [1999]. However, most studies continue to focus on raising awareness of the enormous costs associated with GBV rather than developing methodological approaches to estimate the actual costs. There are currently only a limited number of studies that holistically calculate GBV losses, as only a restricted set of research measures the cost categories extensively and in detail. These studies are primarily based on national datasets in the United States, Australia, Canada, Great Britain, Finland, Denmark, Germany, Switzerland, France, or Spain (Access Economics [2004a] Australian Bureau of Statistics [2012] Day [1995] Habetha *et al.* [2012] Henderson [2000] Jäger, Sobocki, and Rössler [2008] VicHealth [2004] Villagómez [2010] Vos *et al.* [2006] Walby [2009] Zhang *et al.* [2012]). These studies mainly represent countries with the world's highest GDP per capita share. Increased tax revenues allow national governments and institutions to keep good data records and to collect high-quality data.

Developing and emerging countries

Few studies are currently available in developing and emerging countries. They were mainly conducted in Latin America, the Caribbean, Southeast Asia, Uganda, or South Africa (Agüero [2013] Åsling-Monemi *et al.* [2003] KPMG South Africa [2014] Mansingh and Ramphal [1993] Morrison and Orlando [1999]). GBV prevalences tend to be much higher in these geographic areas than in the United States or the European Union, for example. Nevertheless, the number of representative qualitative studies is rather limited.

Section 3.3 provides an overview of the research related to the total and specific cost estimates discussed.

3.3. Overview of excluded studies

3.3.1. Search strategy and exclusion criteria

The primary search criteria for this formal literature review incorporated peer-reviewed and non-peer-reviewed studies in English, French, Spanish and German on the topic of GBV costing at any level and geographical area, which was mainly listed in the three international databases; including Scopus, EBSCO Education Source, and Web of Science. The research was conducted from 2018 to 2020, with an opening of 150 papers classified. Studies are narrowed to those published during or after 2000, as from this year, new methodologies were introduced into the GBV-costing literature. Whilst this review is conducted as rigorously as possible, its search methodology restricts each paper. Although three institutional research databases are chosen that are comprehensive in their extent, by employing the foundations of research published only in the chosen languages, analysis written on the topic in other languages is not covered in this study. This also refers to research in conference settings, book chapters, or studies not distributed in journals listed in the three databases examined. Research with more project resources could examine a more extensive quantity of data to broaden the analysis.

In detail, the literature search excludes studies if:

1. They are out of date, and the same author has published an update. For example, see Walby [2004] Walby [2009]

2. They were published before 2000 because new methodological developments took place after 2000.¹
3. They represent studies that have not added new or additional methodological knowledge based on the current theoretical understanding.
4. They have restrictions regarding the following aspects:
 - a) The studies use limited content data, such as in the paper of Walker *et al.* 1999, which only collects health care costs for women who have suffered child abuse in the past.
 - b) The studies are based on a restricted sample group and do not use representative and valid datasets. See the survey by Bowlus *et al.* 2003 for instance, which bases its cost calculations on interviews with a cohort of 19 individuals only (Bowlus *et al.* 2003).
 - c) The studies have a limited [forensic] scope. For example, Varcoe *et al.* 2011 only calculate the cost of leaving violent relationships, or Post *et al.*, who only determine the cost of rape (Post *et al.* 2002).

Based on these underlying research criteria, Table 3.1 presents the studies that have been excluded.

3.3.2. Excluded studies

This review splits into literature from developed, developing and emerging countries. The subsequent research has been excluded based on the indicated reasons in Section 3.3.1

Table 3.1.: Overview of excluded studies.

Region ²	Country	Author	Year	Reason
Worldwide	General Review	Institute of Medicine and National Research Council	2012	No additional knowledge of methodical approaches.
	General Review	Skaperdas	2011	Scope too broad: general violence.
	General Review	Chan and Cho	2010	No additional knowledge of methodical approaches.
	General Review	Brauer and Dunne	2010	Scope too broad: conflict and peace.
	General Review	Willman	2009	No additional knowledge of methodical approaches: review.

Continue on next page

¹It should be noted, however, that the Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996 study is nevertheless included because of its extensive methodology.

²Publications are clustered according to geographical region.

Continue Table 3.1

Region	Country	Author	Year	Reason
		Day, McKenna, and Bowlus 2005	2005	No additional knowledge of methodical approaches: overview.
		Godenzi and Yodanis 1999	1999	Outdated: more recent and updated methods are available. Scope too broad: male violence.
		Greaves <i>et al.</i> 1995	1995	Outdated: more recent and updated methods are available.
		Yodanis, Godenzi, and Stanko 2000	2000	No additional knowledge about methodological approaches: overview.
Developed countries				
North America	U.S.	Logan, Walker, and Hoyt 2012	2012	Scope too restricted: injunctions and protective orders only.
	U.S.	Reeves and O'Leary-Kelly 2007	2007	Scope too restricted: impacts on workplaces only.
	U.S.	Post <i>et al.</i> 2002	2002	Scope too restricted: rape tax for the state of Michigan only.
	U.S.	Miller, Fisher, and Cohen 2001	2001	Scope too restricted: juvenile crime only.
	U.S.	Walker <i>et al.</i> 1999	1999	Scope too restricted: calculation of government costs only for health care of women who have suffered child abuse and neglect in the past.
	U.S.	Revicki 1995	1995	Outdated: more recent and updated methods are available. Scope too limited: health costs, and QALYs only.
Canada	Canada	Varcoe <i>et al.</i> 2011	2011	Data gaps and limitations: sample group of women, who have left abusive relationships only.
	Canada	Bowlus <i>et al.</i> 2003	2003	Scope too restricted: child abuse only.
	Canada	Day 1995	1995	Outdated: more recent and updated methods are available.
Australia	Australia	VicHealth 2004	2004	Scope too restricted: health costs only.

Continue on next page

Continue Table 3.1

Region	Country	Author	Year	Reason
	Australia	Henderson 2000	2000	Scope too restricted: calculates the impacts on Australian businesses only.
Europe	Europe	Andlin-Sobocki <i>et al.</i> 2005	2005	Scope too restricted: brain damages only.
	U.K.	Walby 2004	2004	Outdated: more recent and updated methods are available, a more updated study has been published, and Walby 2009 is included in the literature review in Section 3.4
	U.K.	Brand and Price 2000	2000	Scope too broad: costs of crime in general.
	U.K.	Walker <i>et al.</i> 1999	1999	Outdated: more recent and updated methods are available; Scope too limited: health care costs are calculated for women with a history of childhood abuse and neglect only.
	U.K.	Stanko, Crisp, and Hale 1998	1998	Outdated: more recent and updated methods are available.
	Denmark	Kruse <i>et al.</i> 2011	2011	Scope too restricted: health care costs only.
	Switzerland	Jäger, Sobocki, and Rössler 2008	2008	Scope too restricted: bain disorders only.
	Italy	WeWorld Intervita 2013	2013	Data gaps and limitations: costing is based on impacts identified through qualitative research with nine respondents only.
	Spain	Institute for Women of Andalusia 2003	2003	Outdated: more recent and updated methods are available – See Villagómez 2010

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Continue Table 3.1

Region	Country	Author	Year	Reason
Developing and emerging countries				
General	Developing and emerging countries	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2013 ³	2013	Scope too restricted: lost productivity and income only.
	Developing and emerging countries	Duvvury, Grown, and Redner 2004	2004	Scope too broad: provides an operational framework for developing countries only.
	Developing and emerging countries ⁴	Morrison and Orlando 2004	2004	No additional knowledge about methodological approaches: overview.
	Bangladesh	Wu and Ahmed 2012	2012	No additional knowledge of methodological approaches: only summarises the current methods for cost analysis.
Oceania	Papua New Guinea	Williams 2014	2014	Scope too restricted: estimates cost to businesses only.
South America	Latin America, The Caribbean	Agüero 2013	2013	Scope too restricted: estimates Intangible costs only.
	Chile and Nicaragua	Morrison and Orlando 1999	1999	Scope too limited: only calculates the effects on employment and the reduced ability to work ⁵
	Jamaica	Mansingh and Ramphal 1993	1993	Outdated: more recent and updated methods are available.
Africa	South Africa	Dalal and Dawad 2011	2011	Data gaps and limitations: a community study based on a non-representative sample group.
	South Africa	Christofides <i>et al.</i> 2006	2006	Scope too restricted: focuses primarily on HIV/AIDS.
Europe	Macedonia [FYRM]	Gancheva <i>et al.</i> 2010	2010	Data gaps and limitations: the sample group is not representative.

Source: Own representation.

³The study is not included because not all relevant cost categories are estimated. However, the study is analysed in Section 3.4.2 since it calculates certain specific categories.

⁴The study includes the countries of Peru, Haiti and Zambia.

⁵ Morrison and Orlando 1999 base their calculations on random samples in Chile and Nicaragua. The scope of the analysis is limited to employment calculations. The calculated cost-share is 1.60 per cent [of GDP] for Nicaragua and two per cent [of GDP] for Chile.

After having presented both the excluded and included literature, Section 3.4 will depict the included studies.

3.4. Overview of included studies

Section 3.4 summarises the research that is selected based on the presented selection criteria. It covers studies from developed, developing, and emerging countries. They are organised according to their geographical location. Research from the western hemisphere, including the USA, Canada, Australia, and in Europe, the countries of Great Britain, Denmark, Sweden, Germany, and France receive special attention, as they represent a large cohort of the research examined. Literature from developing and emerging countries are underrepresented in this review. This is also because there are few high-quality studies for these geographic areas. Section 3.4.1 will present all selected comprehensive GBV studies in greater detail.

3.4.1. Comprehensive studies

The calculations vary considerably depending on the type of costs calculated, the methods used, or the data available (Walby and Olive 2014). There are complex methodological challenges in measuring the economic cost of GBV. These begin with the availability of relevant data since, for example, several crime cases can occur within one incident, among others. In addition, indirect costs such as lost investment in human capital or reduced productivity are complex in their calculations. However, due to the increasing need to contain the social phenomenon of GBV, there is a wide range of relevant international literature that uses suitable methods extensively (García-Moreno *et al.* 2013; Walby and Olive 2014; World Health Organization (WHO) 2013b; World Health Organization (WHO) 2016b).

Table 3.2 provides a summary overview and shows which of the cost categories were collected and which cost results were calculated based on what prevalence. It should be noted that most studies did not provide total cost estimates, nor did they state their costs in relation to GDP or gave uniform prevalence proportions. These calculations are all made for this overview. The exact data and calculation methods are shown in Part II

Overview

Table 3.2.: Overview of selected GBV cost studies.

Country ⁶	Year ⁷	Author	Cost category								Prevalence [%] ⁸	GDP share [%] ⁹	
			Economic output	Health service	Legal	Social welfare	Personal	Special services ¹⁰	Intangibles ¹¹	Second-generation			Others
Developed countries													
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.79	0.05
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996 12	✓	✓	✓ ¹³	✓ ¹⁴	✓	✓	✓	✓ ¹⁵	-	1.95	0.98

Continue on next page

⁶The studies are organised according to their geographic area. If multiple studies were published in one geographic area, they were ranked by year of publication.

⁷Only the literature published after 2000 was examined. See the exclusion criteria in Chapter [3](#)

⁸The prevalence refers to the data given in the study. Whenever this prevalence or the primary source from which it originated was not included in the original research, these calculations use other international preliminary data. For comparison purposes, this review mainly uses data published in the U.N. Women global database. In a second step, the proportion of women over the age of 15 who have been subjected to physical or sexual violence in the past 12 months is selected in the U.N. Women data (UN Women [2018a](#)).

⁹Whenever the study examined did not include the share of GDP, these figures were calculated for the purpose of this study. The per capita GDP data from the period that corresponds to the year of publication of the original research are used in the calculations. If the year of publication and the year of research differ, the GDP figures from the survey year were applied. World Bank GPD per capita data (World Bank [2018a](#)) and nominal per capita GDP in the current local currency unit [LCU] was used for this calculation. This is because, first, the current LCU data recognises the fact that the various cost categories, such as healthcare costs, are usually subject to inflation. Secondly, researchers typically use the CPI, which also reflects inflation when the expenses from previous publications are translated into a different national context. Third, nominal GDP based on the current LCU is used to avoid bias because real GDP is typically lower without adjustments for inflation. Applying such a lower GDP figure to the total cost calculation would lead to an artificially higher figure and distortion in the data.

¹⁰This study summarises the surveys for social welfare costs under special service costs.

¹¹In this study, they are referred to as intangibles, physical, and emotional impact.

¹²Although this overview and study only included publications after 2000, the Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#) study was still included due to its methodology.

¹³The study included only legal costs absorbed to cover medical expenses (Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#) p. 10).

¹⁴However, the paper is mainly restricted to police and fire services (Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#) p. 12).

¹⁵Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#) p. 11 state that the surveys are not very extensive and that further investigation is required.

Continue Table 3.2

Country	Year	Author	Cost category										Prevalence [%]	GDP share [%]
			Economic output	Health service	Legal	Social welfare	Personal	Special services	Intangibles	Second-generation	Others			
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ ¹⁶	1.00	0.47	
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia 2016	✓	✓	✓	✓ ¹⁷	✓	✓ ¹⁸	✓	✓	✓ ¹⁹	[11.13] ²⁰	1.35	
Australia ²¹	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	✓	✓	✓	✓ ²²	✓ ²³	✓ ²⁴	✓	✓ ²⁵	✓ ²⁶	7.10	0.76	
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ ²⁷	✓	✓	✓	✓ ²⁸	5.00 (Access Economics 2004a p. 15)	1.07	

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¹⁶Zhang *et al.* 2012 also calculate the costs of third parties, including funeral expenses (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 61), the costs of loss of affection (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 61), but also the costs of other people who harmed during incidents (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 62), and other damage to the employer (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 65).

¹⁷The costs are listed under transfer costs (KPMG Australia 2016 p. 6).

¹⁸Ibid (KPMG Australia 2016 p. 6).

¹⁹The report includes the cost to the business sector (KPMG Australia 2016 p. 5), consumption-related activities (KPMG Australia 2016 p. 5), funeral-related expenses (KPMG Australia 2016 p. 6), lost tax revenues (KPMG Australia 2016 p.6), and costs to friends and family (KPMG Australia 2016 Foreword).

²⁰For the 11.13 per cent in KPMG Australia 2016 the primary data refers to *since the age of 15, not to within the past 12 months* (Australian Bureau of Statistics 2012). For detailed information, see Chapter 15.

²¹The study is an update from the 2004 publication. Both studies illustrate the problem that solid GDP growth hides social issues. Detailed information can be found under further explanations in the section on: "Australia 2004."

²²The author lists the cost under the category: Administration (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009 p. 53).

²³Consumption costs include replacing damaged property and bad debts (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009 p. 49).

²⁴The author lists the cost under the category: Administration (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009 p. 53).

²⁵The study includes costs for children who have witnessed and live with violence, including expenditure on child protection services and increased youth and adult crime (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009).

²⁶The analysis covers the loss of economies of scale in consumption (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009 p. 49) and the loss of taxes – as transfer costs (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009 p. 61).

²⁷The author lists these costs as consumption costs in the form of destroyed property (Access Economics 2004a p. 45).

²⁸The paper includes lost taxes (Access Economics 2004a p. 60), loss of economies of scale in consumption (Access Economics 2004a p. 45), and transfer costs, including deadweight loss of taxation (Access Economics 2004a p. 60), and a sensitivity analysis (Access Economics 2004a p. 61).

Continue Table 3.2

Country	Year	Author	Cost category								Prevalence [%]	GDP share [%]	
			Economic output	Health service	Legal	Social welfare	Personal	Special services	Intangibles	Second-generation			Others
U.K.	2009 ²⁹	Walby 2009	✓	✓	✓	✓ ³⁰	–	✓	✓	– ³¹	–	0.60 (Walby 2009 p. 6)	1.00
Denmark	2010	Helweg-Larsen <i>et al.</i> 2010	✓	✓	✓	✓ ³²	✓	✓	✓	✓ ³³	–	2.01	0.004
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson 2006	✓	✓	✓	✓	–	✓	– ³⁴	–	– ³⁵	2.60	0.10
Finland	2001	Heiskanen and Piispa 2001	✓	✓	✓	✓	–	✓	– ³⁶	–	–	5.00	0.08
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017	✓	✓	✓	✓	– ³⁷	✓	–	– ³⁸	– ³⁹	3.00	0.12
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	✓ ⁴⁰	✓	✓	✓	–	✓	– ⁴¹	–	–	1.26	0.03
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	✓	✓	✓	✓	– ⁴²	✓	–	– ⁴³	– ⁴⁴	5.00	0.17
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	✓	✓	✓	✓	–	✓	– ⁴⁵	–	–	2.00	0.22

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²⁹The Walby 2009 study is an update of the Walby 2004 publication.

³⁰The cost calculation of social services only includes costs associated with children (Walby 2009 p. 5).

³¹The publication does not calculate the long-term effects on children (Walby 2009 p. 4).

³²The total cost of the paper does not include expenses incurred to research violence or public expenditures for emergency shelters and other relevant areas. Due to an access barrier, the study of Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010 was removed from the comparisons in Chapters 7 to 13.

³³The study estimates the lost QALYs under intangibles.

³⁴The paper does not calculate intangibles such as any Physical and Emotional impact (Envall and Eriksson 2006).

³⁵The calculations only include expenses for volunteering.

³⁶The study uses the human capital approach to estimate the cost related to morbidity and mortality (Heiskanen and Piispa 2001). Due to an access barrier, the study of Heiskanen and Piispa 2001 was removed from the comparisons in Chapters 7 to 13.

³⁷Expenses are listed mainly in the form of intangibles, such as the loss of employment (Sacco 2017 p. 104) or loss of productivity (Sacco 2017 p. 109 ff.).

³⁸The study only calculates trauma costs incurred by children (Sacco 2017 p. 114).

³⁹The study includes, among other costs of unemployment, the hiring of external staff during illness and the loss of productivity due to death and suicide.

⁴⁰Further information can be found in the overview by Stern *et al.* 2013 p. 7.

⁴¹The report calculates the lost QALYs under the category of intangibles (Stern *et al.* 2013).

⁴²Personal expenses are not stated directly (Nectoux *et al.* 2010 p. 394).

⁴³The study computes the mortality of children as well (Nectoux *et al.* 2010 p. 394).

⁴⁴The costing was done for both men and women (Nectoux *et al.* 2010 p. 394).

⁴⁵Villagómez 2010 p. 5 has calculated the costs of specialised services within the social cost category.

Continue Table 3.2

Country	Year	Author	Cost category								Prevalence [%]	GDP share [%]	
			Economic output	Health service	Legal	Social welfare	Personal	Special services	Intangibles	Second-generation			Others
Developing and emerging countries													
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012	46	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	47	25.40	3.19
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011	48	✓	✓	✓	49	50	✓	51	52	24.00	2.10
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004		✓	✓	54	✓	✓	✓	55	53	18.00	3.93
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	–	–	27.70	–
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	–	–	30.00	–
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	56	57	20.00–30.00	0.90–1.30
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine 2017		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	58	–	10.00	0.23

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors. The numbers are rounded to two digits after the comma.

Source: Own representation.

Table 3.2 presents the literature included in this study and is divided into industrialised countries, developing and emerging countries. The following cost categories were examined for each study: lost economic output, health service costs, legal costs, social welfare costs, personal costs, special service costs, intangibles, second-generation costs, and others.

⁴⁶For more information, see Duvvury and Carney 2012 p. 81.

⁴⁷The study included children's health and academic performance, including missed days or poor grades (Duvvury and Carney 2012 p. 2).

⁴⁸Duvvury *et al.* 2009 also calculate the costs for Bangladesh. However, Siddique's work is more methodologically sophisticated. See the explanations for the Duvvury 2009 study of Morocco and Uganda.

⁴⁹The study also included costs related to non-governmental organisations (Siddique 2011 p. 45 ff.).

⁵⁰The paper also calculates the costs of displacement and relocation (Siddique 2011 p. 40).

⁵¹The study estimates the Intangible costs for mental and physical health, mainly for stress-related illnesses in families. This also increases the likelihood that a family member will be injured while trying to stand up for another (Siddique 2011 p. 22).

⁵²The report calculates the costs for children only as part of preventive and supportive programmes to end violence against women and children (Siddique 2011 p. 46). Nevertheless, such are usually already included in the costs for social welfare or specialised services.

⁵³The other costs include loss of income for both survivors and their families (Siddique 2011 p. 39). Siddique also calculates the lost income for perpetrators and their families (Siddique 2011 p. 41).

⁵⁴The costs only cover legal costs for medical purposes and are listed under "Medicina legal" (Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 p. 32).

⁵⁵The costs for children also include, for example, health consequences for minors or restricted income prospects of affected children (Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 p. 27).

⁵⁶The study uses the DALY concept (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 30).

⁵⁷The paper also calculates the costs for companies (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 35).

⁵⁸UNFPA Ukraine 2017 only reflects the cost of psychological counselling for children.

Within the industrialised nations, the results of countries from Australia, the USA, Canada but also numerous European countries such as Germany, Spain, Switzerland, or Sweden are examined. There was less choice of relevant publications in developing and emerging countries. Particular attention is paid to include studies from the African region. Ukraine is listed within the developing and emerging countries. This division is based on the classifications of the World Bank [2018a](#). The prevalence proportions and the shares of the gross domestic product are shown in the last columns. The prevalence proportion shown is the prevalence displayed in the study, or if the prevalence was not specified in the publication, it was calculated for this comparison. The sub-calculations used are shown systematically in the footnotes or Part [II](#). If it was not possible to calculate the prevalence proportions because essential data was not shown in the respective paper, global comparative data from the U.N., such as UN Women [2018a](#) was used. In order to conduct this review, this data is compared with the cost result and is measured in relation to the gross domestic product. If the costs were not calculated in the respective study, they are explicitly computed for this overview. The calculations and data used are explained in the footnotes and in Part [II](#) too. Not all studies have calculated the cost of men and women equally. In fact, a large part of the studies omitted the costs for men. If a study also estimated the costs for the male part of the population, this was explicitly noted in the review. The proper calculation of these values is fundamental in order to be able to objectively compare the results of this study with the values from other research and provide answers to questions such as the following:

How is it possible that a relatively low prevalence proportion of 1.95 per cent in the American Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#) study, for example, leads to a relatively high GDP cost-share of 0.98 per cent, whereby mainly the costs of marriage violence are calculated?

Whereas a relatively high prevalence proportion of 7.10 per cent, as in the Australian National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) [2009](#) report, leads to a much lower GDP share of 0.76 per cent, although the study uses a detailed model and calculates each cost category.

These two studies are selected for comparison because both were conducted in developed countries; nevertheless, despite significant differences in the respective prevalence, a similar cost-share of less than one per cent of GDP is calculated. However, the significant difference in prevalence is not reflected in the GDP cost-share.

The next paragraph is intended to answer this question and contains a more comprehensive analysis of publications in industrialised countries, and highlights of the respective studies are presented. These include improvements in the area of methods and data. The weaknesses of the studies in terms of methodology or data are also briefly addressed. If the publication stands out in a methodological area for a specific cost category, it will be discussed in more detail in Section [3.4.2](#). The review begins to discuss research published in developed countries.

Developed countries

The studies from the USA, Canada, Australia, Great Britain, Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Germany, Switzerland, France, and Spain are presented in the next paragraphs. The evaluations start with the American Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease

Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) [2003](#) study.

U.S. – 2003 – Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC): The Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) [2003](#) calculated the “Cost of Violence in Partnership Against Women in the United States.” The report focuses in particular on estimating economic losses and health care costs. Thereby, most of the costs resulting from personal injury cases. Individuals indicated whether the recent act of violence caused time loss in routine activities such as housework, childcare, or nursing. According to the survey, female survivors in the United States lost nearly US\$ 8.0 million in paid work annually, which equates to 32,114 full-time jobs a year. The study reported a relatively low share of GDP at 0.05 per cent, compared to a relatively high prevalence proportion of 4.79 per cent. The reason is that the report did not calculate cost categories such as legal advice, social care, personal costs, intangibles, or second-generation costs. Another publication within the United States is the Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#) study which will be presented in the next paragraph.

U.S. – 1996 – Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema: In their 1996 study “Victim costs and consequences – A new look,” Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#) calculated the total annual cost of personal crime in the United States, including the cost of DV, sexual assault, rape, and child abuse. Based on a prevalence of 1.95 per cent, the study estimates a relatively high share of GDP at 0.98 per cent. The paper calculates medical costs, lost profits, and specific program costs. The analysis also estimates the Intangible costs such as pain, suffering, and the Quality of Life [in years] lost. Intangible assets increased the total costs by over 400 per cent. The study calculates US\$ 105 billion a year for direct costs, including medical expenses, lost income, and public program expenses. The authors compute an additional US\$ 450 billion a year for indirect losses from pain, suffering, and reduced quality of life. Although the study was published before 2000, it was included in this review because it was among the first to calculate such Intangible losses. To answer the above question, the work serves as an example of how cost estimates increase when Intangible assets are fully included. Two recent reports that also calculate Intangible losses are the 2012 Canadian study and the 2016 Australian KPMG study, which are summarised in the following paragraphs.

Canada – 2012 – Zhang *et al.*: Zhang *et al.* [2012](#) calculate a relatively high share of GDP [0.47], which results from a relatively low prevalence [one per cent], as the paper covers all categories in detail. In addition, the authors use an approach that integrates and calculates both diagnosed and undiagnosed mental health problems, which significantly increases expenses. The study also estimates both material and immaterial losses. Zhang *et al.* [2012](#), p. 81 state that Intangible losses account for over 74 per cent of the overall economic impact of spouse violence in Canada. The calculations were based on detailed surveys that asked participants about their experiences with mental health problems within one year of a GBV incident. However, in some countries, especially in developing and emerging countries, such detailed information is often unavailable, which means that the data and method used are probably not transferable. Zhang *et al.* further do not include the treatment costs that go beyond the one-year period after the injury phase, which leads to a likely underestimation of costs.

Australia – 2016 – KPMG Australia: The Australian government published its latest report on the economic costs of GBV in 2016. KPMG Australia [2016](#) evaluates “The Cost of Violence against Women and their Children in Australia.” The authors cover all categories and even the costs of the second-generation. The calculations also include the losses of emotional abuse and stalking (KPMG Australia [2016](#) p. 2). For example, the paper contains detailed estimates of indirect costs such as pain, suffering, and premature mortality, which sum up to around 50 per cent of all expenses. In detail, the total cost was US\$ 22 billion per annum, while the indirect expenses were US\$ 10.4 billion per annum (KPMG Australia [2016](#) p. 5). Concerning the economic losses, the report calculates the costs for both the survivors and the perpetrators alike. It covers both the production-related losses and such due to absenteeism or job-related administrative costs. The study calculates:

1. personal expenses, including lost wages and profits;
2. costs for the employer include search and recruitment costs, loss of work capacity of existing employees, or expenses for retraining new employees.

This two-sided approach is crucial as research shows that the employer and the survivor each pay half of the economic loss. The report also calculates losses due to the absenteeism of the survivor and the perpetrator from paid and unpaid employment alike. The study also calculates additional administrative costs, including the process of searching, hiring, and further training in the workplace. The paper bases its results on the unit cost value approach, which derives from average weekly salary data. However, there is no reflection on different health conditions, which leads to a possible underestimation. Other studies choose an even more detailed approach that tends to increase estimates. Dolan *et al.* [2005](#) Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#) estimate the loss of economic output due to any harmful damage, for instances. The authors calculated the likelihood of specific health outcomes as a result of GBV. For example, severe bruising occurred in around 15 per cent of all cases of physical violence, which resulted in an average stoppage of ten days (KPMG Australia [2016](#) p. 14).⁵⁹ Hence, although all categories were comprehensively surveyed and Australia has with 11.13 per cent⁶⁰ one of the highest prevalence proportions for the context of the industrialised countries, the GDP share of the study is relatively low at 1.35 per cent.

Another study on Australia that met the eligibility criteria is the National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) [2009](#) report, titled “Reduce Violence against Women and their Children,” which is discussed in the next paragraph.

Australia – 2009 – National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C): “The Cost of Violence against Women and their Children” study by the National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) [2009](#).

⁵⁹For instance, the calculated economic loss is very detailed in Dolan *et al.* [2005](#) Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#) since the approach covers the costs incurred for both the perpetrator and the employer. The approach will be discussed in more detail in Section [3.4.2](#). This explains the relatively low cost-share of the Australian publication.

⁶⁰Regarding the 11.13 per cent in KPMG Australia [2016](#) the primary data refers to *since the age of 15, not to within the past 12 months* (Australian Bureau of Statistics [2012](#)). See Part [II](#)

analyses all categories, including the cost of children who have witnessed and are living with violence. The calculated cost includes expenditure on child protection services and increased youth and adult crime. The study comprises explicitly costs for perpetrators, minors, as well as for state and local government. The methodological structure of the study is very progressive and extensive. However, a relatively high prevalence of 7.10 per cent results in low overall costs relative to GDP. One drawback is that the study does not show whether the prevalence covers the period from the age of 15, as in the KPMG Australia [2016](#) study mentioned before, or only includes the period of the past 12 months (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) [2009](#) p. 72). It should also be noted that the publication predicts losses for 2021. This forecast is based on the analysis of Access Economics [2004a](#), which is described in the next paragraph.

Australia – 2004 – Access Economics: “The Cost of Domestic Violence to the Australian Economy” by Access Economics [2004a](#) is based on data from 2002. The aim of the paper is to calculate the costs of DV. Therefore, the study is limited to violence between partners within a domestic setting. However, abuse between family members and other third parties and violence against children outside this environment are excluded, which significantly reduces the total cost-share. In addition, the productivity loss of survivors, perpetrators, and employees is not quantified (Access Economics [2004a](#), p. 37). There are also no estimates on the loss of future life income resulting from lower productivity or the possibility of being less likely to be in employment (Access Economics [2004a](#), p. 12). On the other hand, the study carries out a thorough cost calculation and collects all seven cost categories. In particular, it includes costs due to pain, suffering, or premature mortality, as well as health care costs, production, and consumption-related expenses, such as for the replacement of property or losses of the second-generation, as well as transfer costs including reduced taxes. This very detailed and far-reaching approach consequently results in a relatively high cost-share of 1.07 per cent of GDP with a prevalence of five per cent. In summary, the analysis uses a very extensive and representative dataset. However, the results must be read with care, as some values are based on small case numbers or on parameters that utilise simplified assumptions (Access Economics [2004a](#) p. 2, 8, 66, 72). For example, the calculations of suffering are based on the net lifetime pain approach. Today, more holistic methods are available, such as the QALY model, by Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#)⁶¹

Another study that uses a holistic approach based on robust primary data is the 2009 British study by Walby, which will be explained in the next paragraph.

U.K. – 2009 – Walby: The Walby [2009](#) report on “The Cost of Domestic Violence: Up-date 2009” builds on her 2004 findings. Walby calculates the direct and indirect costs of violence against women in England and Wales. The author derives her calculations from the U.K. Department of Transportation, which calculates the cost of health care and the cost of reduced productivity due to injuries from car accidents (Walby [2004](#) p. 45). Walby bases her results on the work of the Brand and Price [2000](#) Home Office report and on data from the 2001 British

⁶¹The model will be examined in more detail in Section [3.4.2](#)

Crime Survey self-completion module on Interpersonal Violence, presented in Walby [2004](#), p. 24, which got updated in Walby [2009](#). In general, Walby calculates costs in the categories of justice, healthcare, social services, housing, legal aid, lost production, and Intangible losses such as pain and suffering. Walby covers all categories except for personal costs and costs for the second-generation (Walby [2004](#), p. 12). The total GDP cost-share is at one per cent relatively high compared to prevalence proportions in other studies, as Walby's research reflects a prevalence ratio of 0.60 per cent. However, a recent analysis, with data from 2014, carried out by the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights [2014](#); UN Women [2018a](#) states that the prevalence of physical and sexual IPV has been five per cent for the U.K., including Northern Ireland, in the past 12 months. According to the global database, the prevalence proportion includes women aged 18 to 74 and covers cases within the past 12 months. Although the data was surveyed in varying time periods, this difference should be noted. In order to compute the intangibles, Walby's approach adds the willingness to pay [WTP] to the QALY method. The technique uses a cost-benefit analysis approach and reflects the amount of money a society or a survivor is willing to spend to avoid a particularly harmful outcome. Walby [2004](#), p. 14 uses data from a WTP survey on road traffic injuries. In summary, the paper transfers the WTP values to the scope of GBV. In doing so, Walby wants to analyse how much an entity is willing to pay to avoid GBV and its associated negative factors. The basic structure of the method has a high potential to be used in Namibia. In line with other studies, Walby's Intangible costs account for over 70 per cent of all total losses, as human and emotional costs sum up to £ 17.1 billion out of a total £ 22.9 billion (Walby [2004](#), p. 12), which is a considerably high proportion.

Further, it shall be stressed that Walby's legal cost surveys, in particular, are very substantial because they use well-grounded data to calculate the total expenses of the Criminal Justice System [CJS], and which is also supported by the British government (Walby and Olive [2014](#), p. 63). Thus this part will be analysed in more detail in Section [3.4.2](#) and Chapter [5](#).

In order to continue with the studies published in Northern Europe, the 2010 Danish study by Helweg-Larsen *et al.* will be described next.

Denmark – 2010 – Helweg-Larsen *et al.*: Helweg-Larsen *et al.* [2010](#) calculate “The costs of violence: Economic and personal dimensions of violence against women in Denmark” for 2010. The team encompasses all seven cost categories and further uses the QALY method for Intangible costs. However, the total costs do not include funding for GBV research, public funds for emergency shelters, or second-generation costs. The calculated prevalence of 2.01 per cent results in a relatively low GDP cost-share of 0.004. The authors calculated the prevalence proportion based on 35,500 cases for women aged 16 to 64 years (Helweg-Larsen *et al.* [2010](#), p. 11). However, the study only states the number of reported cases and no uniform prevalence proportions. Therefore, they were calculated for this overview, and the number of cases was related to the total number of 1,762,355 women aged 16 to 64 who lived in Denmark in 2010.⁶² For comparison, the prevalence data of the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights [2014](#), p. 34 shows a different development for women aged 18 to 74.

⁶²Further information can be found in Part [II](#)

According to the source, four per cent of the population experienced violence by a current partner within the past 12 months, almost twice as much as in Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010. The European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights 2014 data could be more realistic, as the case numbers in the Danish study only reflect people who have either received medical help, reported their cases to the police, or have used police protection services. The authors also state that the actual number of incidents that have not been registered may even be ten times higher (Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010, p. 17). Therefore the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights 2014 p. 34 ratio of four per cent might be a more realistic indicator. In general, the Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010 study calculates one of the lowest GDP shares within this literature review. It is even smaller than in other studies with lower prevalences, such as in Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996, Stern *et al.* 2013 as displayed in Table 3.3.

Table 3.3.: Comparison of the Danish 2010 study.

GDP share [%] ⁶³	Prevalence [%]	Country	Year	Author
1.00	0.60	U.K.	2009	Walby 2009
0.98	1.95	U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996
0.22	2.00	ESP	2010	Villagómez 2010
0.03	1.26	[0.91] ⁶⁴ CH	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013
0.004	2.01	DNK	2010	Helweg-Larsen <i>et al.</i> 2010

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

One might argue that the reason for this low cost-share is that the analysis neglected the evaluations of the costs of the second-generation (Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010, p. 14), but so do Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996, Stern *et al.* 2013. Furthermore, the study does not calculate a variety of social costs. However, the proportion of this type of cost is usually too small to explain the significant differences in the total output. Other studies such as those by Villagómez 2010 and Stern *et al.* 2013 based their evaluations on a lower prevalence but; however, calculated a higher total cost-share. Since Helweg-Larsen *et al.* in fact, did compute all seven cost categories, the reason can only be found in the depth of their approach. Another problem is the reported prevalence since losses are mainly calculated based on the registered number of cases. As previously mentioned, the team even emphasises that the actual number that is not reported can be up to ten times higher (Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010, p. 17). This fact underscores the need for suitable multiplier arithmetic in order to ascertain a realistic prevalence based on the reported cases (Walby and Olive 2014).

In order to continue, the two other included studies for the Northern European context are the Swedish 2006 study by Envall and Eriksson and the Finish report by Heiskanen and Piispa from 2001, both of which are discussed in the following paragraphs.

⁶³The table sorts the figures according to a descending share.

⁶⁴The prevalence data includes individuals from 16 to 36 years and uses the past 12 months time frame (Stern *et al.* 2013, p. 8). The primary data is from Killias *et al.* 2012. According to Killias, during the last 12 months, overall, 1.26 per cent, thereof, around 0.90 per cent of women and 0.35 per cent of men have experienced physical or sexual abuse by their current partner or ex-partner in heterosexual or gay and lesbian relationships.

Sweden – 2006 – Envall and Eriksson: In their study on the “Costs Of Violence Against Women,” Envall and Eriksson estimate Sweden’s costs for 2006 (Envall and Eriksson 2006). However, the study omits categories such as personal, immaterial, and second-generation costs. As a result, the GDP cost-share is in the lower range at 0.10 per cent but is higher than the Danish study discussed above [0.004]. This difference occurs even though the two countries have similar prevalence proportions – the Danish study has a prevalence of 2.01 per cent and the Swedish 2.60 per cent. However, the approach of the Swedish study to calculate expenditures, especially such of special services, is more holistic.

Finland – 2001 – Heiskanen and Piispa: Heiskanen, Piispa, and Aromaa 1998 conducted a national survey with 7,000 Finnish women who were randomly selected in 1997 and asked about their consequences of violence. The team used this previous work to estimate “The price of violence,” in: The cost of men’s violence against women in Finland, published in Heiskanen and Piispa 2001. The report uses several different qualitative and quantitative datasets. Heiskanen and Piispa use national victimisation surveys, data from service providers, and interview data with experts and survivors. The study holistically covers the cost of special services. For example, the paper includes support groups for perpetrator intervention or costs of detention. Nevertheless, the study lacks personal cost surveys or neglects the costs of the second-generation. This omission may explain why the GDP cost-share is with 0.08 per cent relatively low.

Germany – 2017 – Sacco: Sacco 2017 conducted the first nationwide DV study in Germany based on data from 2016. She calculated a 0.12 per cent share of GDP based on a prevalence of three per cent.⁶⁵ The calculated share of costs is higher than that for most Northern and Western European countries such as Denmark [0.004 per cent], Sweden [0.10 per cent], Switzerland [0.03 per cent], or Finland [0.08 per cent]. European countries with a higher GDP share are currently only France [0.17 per cent], Spain [0.22 per cent] and Great Britain [1.00 per cent] (Nectoux *et al.* 2010, Stern *et al.* 2013, Villagómez 2010, Walby 2009). In summary, the German study calculates the direct costs from police operations, court hearings, support programmes, or health services. Sacco calculated the intangibles, including losses in Quality of Life such as illness, costs due to unemployment, or injuries to children. However, what distinguishes the paper but also contributes to a higher loss ratio is the integration of trauma costs for children who experience(d) violence.⁶⁶

Switzerland – 2013 – Stern *et al.*: Stern *et al.* 2013 use in “Costs of Intimate Partner Violence: Summary” a wide range of quantitative and qualitative data from the interview- or insurance records. The team assesses Intangible losses using the advanced QALY approach. However, personal expenses and costs for the second-generation are not included. Both the prevalence of 1.26 [0.91 per cent of which are only for women] and the share of GDP in 0.03 per cent are among the lowest in the European Union. In general, the study aims to calculate a holistic review of health care costs and economic losses. The calculations of

⁶⁵Details on the calculation of the prevalence proportion can be found in Part II

⁶⁶Section 3.4.2 explains whether this approach can be applied to the existing Namibian datasets.

the losses are based on data from national central insurance data. Follow-up care for the duration of a one-year cycle was also included in the calculation. However, only the costs of psychiatric care were taken into account, and only the economic damage caused by depression was calculated. The reason for this restriction was the lack of suitable datasets, for instance (Stern *et al.* 2013 p. 22).

In the further course, the French study of 2012 by Nectoux *et al.* is summarised.

France – 2010 – Nectoux *et al.*: Nectoux *et al.* 2010 assess in their report “Évaluation économique des violences conjugales en France” the economic costs of France. Nectoux *et al.* computed almost all categories, including second-generation losses. Direct cost analysis spans three levels. The micro-level analysis comes from expert interviews that are responsible for childcare, accommodation, or telephone helplines. The mesolevel uses data from national medical facilities, social, administrative, and legal records, including institutional reports and national registries. At the macro-level, national and international economic data such as public expenditure, national economic indicators, and EUROSTAT data are used. In the area of indirect costs, Nectoux *et al.* calculate a reduction in productivity and loss of production caused by illness, premature mortality, absenteeism, or imprisonment. The authors use the unit-cost approach to calculate average gross hourly wages to compute individual wage losses. Cost estimates for loss of life mainly result from the value assigned to the Quality-of-Life approach. Based on multiplier calculations, Nectoux *et al.* compute the number of working women exposed to GBV and estimate the number of cases of murder and other deaths, such as the suicide of the perpetrator or domestic murders that can be related to GBV. The total cost of the study is 0.17 per cent of GDP. This GDP share is relatively high compared to other European countries. However, the analysis does not contain information on different categories that can contribute to a further increase in costs though. For example, when calculating the cost of bodily harm, no data on ambulance costs or expenses for providing primary care is considered. Furthermore, personal losses include only legal fees but no property damage or moving expenses. In addition, legal costs do not cover expenses for private and public legal aid. As a result, the GDP share of 0.17 per cent should be seen as a rather conservative estimate. In contrast, the Spanish Villagómez 2010 study calculates a relatively high share of costs based on a relatively low prevalence.

Spain – 2010 – Villagómez: The Spanish Villagómez 2010 study calculates a cost-share of 0.22 per cent of GDP with a prevalence of two per cent. For comparison purposes, other findings with a prevalence of around two per cent are listed in Table 3.4

Table 3.4.: Comparison of the Spanish 2010 study.

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence GDP share		Not included
			[%]	[%]	
Denmark	2010	Helweg-Larsen <i>et al.</i> 2010	2.01	0.004	Second-generation, others
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson 2006	2.60	0.10	Personal, intangibles, second-generation, others
Spain	2003	Villagómez 2010	2.00	0.22	others

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.
Source: Own representation.

The other European studies with a prevalence proportion of around two per cent have a lower share of GDP than the Spanish Villagómez study. The study is more extensive and calculates more cost categories than, for example, the Swedish or Danish paper. Further, the Spanish research is also more holistic within its individual cost categories. For example, the special costs of the government were calculated in more detail. The selected datasets are also very extensive. Over 100 indicators have been examined on the effects of violence on women and their children. Villagómez [2010](#) calculates unit costs based on state and provincial budgets and relates them to a sophisticated set of multipliers.

Summary Within this paragraph, studies in the United States, Canada, Australia, the United Kingdom [U.K.], Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Germany, Switzerland, France, and Spain were evaluated. In summary, the prevalence of industrialised countries was between 0.60 and 7.10 [11.13], and the share of GDP was between 0.004 and 1.07 per cent [1.35 per cent], see Table [3.5](#)

Table 3.5.: Overview of GBV prevalence and GDP share: industrialised countries.

	Prevalence [%]	GDP share [%]
Developed countries	0.60–7.10 ⁶⁷	0.004–1.07 ⁶⁸

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

It can be said that there are extensive and numerous studies within the industrialised countries. Good governance structure and a large and valid data availability support this development. However, publications depict significant methodological differences, and not all studies have calculated all cost categories extensively, for instance.

This paragraph deals in more detail with research published within developing and emerging countries. As in the paragraph on industrialised countries, the special features of the studies will be presented in more detail. This includes, for example, innovations in the area of methods and data applications. The research's weaknesses regarding the applied methodology or invalid datasets are also briefly summarised, and the preliminary question from Section [3.4.1](#) will be further discussed. If the publication is particularly suitable in a methodological area of a cost category, this will be explained in more detail in Section [3.4.2](#).

Developing and emerging countries

The following paragraph discusses the studies from Vietnam, Bangladesh, Colombia, Morocco, Uganda, South Africa, and Ukraine. The detailed analysis begins with the two Asian studies from Vietnam by Duvvury and Carney and Bangladesh by Siddique (Duvvury and Carney [2012](#) Siddique [2011](#)).

⁶⁷For the 11.13 per cent in KPMG Australia [2016](#) the primary data refers to *since the age of 15*, not to *within the past 12 months* (Australian Bureau of Statistics [2012](#)); for more information, see Part [II](#)

⁶⁸Ibid. As 1.35 per cent refers to KPMG Australia [2016](#).

Vietnam – 2012 – Duvvury and Carney: Based on a 2012 household survey in Vietnam, Duvvury and Carney [2012] calculated out-of-pocket costs resulting from missed paid and unpaid working hours, the cost of services used, or expenses related to damaged property. The data was generated from qualitative interviews, including surveys with households and service providers. As already mentioned, GBV proportions are disproportionately high compared to the industrialised countries. For instance, in Vietnam, 25.40 per cent of women have experienced violence in the past 12 months (Duvvury and Carney [2012] p. 13). However, the high prevalence does not automatically lead to an increased GDP cost-share. In Vietnam, the 3.19 per cent GDP cost-share based on a high prevalence of over 25 per cent seems to be relatively low compared to surveys outcomes of the European Union or the United States. One reason for this could be that the Intangible costs based on the QALY method are not included in the cost calculation, among others. Based on the evaluations of other studies, see, for example Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996] this cost class often significantly increases cost estimates.

Bangladesh – 2011 – Siddique: The total cost calculated is 2.10 per cent of GDP. The calculations are based on primary and secondary survey and interview data. The sample size of the qualitative interviews was 500 families. However, it should be noted that the respondents were only in 40 per cent of the cases the survivors themselves. In the other cases, it was, for example, the mother [22 per cent] or the father [17 per cent] of the individual concerned who answered. In addition, the study has other data restrictions. For example, no data was examined at the community level. Another challenge for Siddique was “to place a price tag on” Intangible costs (Siddique [2011] p. 30). Today, however, there are more detailed and up-to-date methods for such scenarios, as the QALY approach, for instance (Walby and Olive [2014]).

The following paragraph contains the literature selected for the South American context.

Colombia – 2004 – Ribero and Sánchez Torres: Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004] calculated the highest cost-share in terms of GDP of around four per cent, based on a relatively low prevalence of 18 per cent compared to the other developing and emerging countries included in this overview [except for Ukraine with a prevalence proportion of ten per cent] (UNFPA Ukraine [2017]). This is remarkable because the study does not calculate Intangible losses, which tend to increase the total costs enormously. [See, for example, Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996]. For the other categories, however, the method of Ribero and Sánchez Torres is very detailed. The authors also include the costs of complications in childbirth, miscarriage, minor abuse, severe abuse of minors, or children’s health problems. In summary, it can be said that the research takes extensive account of the losses that occur for the second-generation. A high GDP cost-share also results from the loss of income. According to Ribero and Sánchez, these represent around 1.90 per cent of the total calculated GDP cost-share of 3.93 per cent (Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004] p. 28). In order to calculate the lost economic output, Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004] p. 26 base their calculations on the formula:

$$\text{Economic costs} = \text{effect} \cdot \text{unit cost} \cdot \text{incidence} \cdot \text{affected population} \quad (3.1)$$

The idea on which this formula is based is in line with other international research results. [See, for example, Dolan *et al.* [2005] Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005]. The forecast for losses incurred by government or Civil Society Organisations [CSOs] is also differentiated. The underlying method to calculate unit costs is based on qualitative and quantitative datasets.

If unit costs were not available or were not valid, the study uses a budget-share approach. Overall, it can be said that the methods used in this study, especially for the category of the social welfare costs, are detailed⁶⁹

To continue, the two studies selected for the African context are the Duvvury *et al.* 2009 report on Morocco and Uganda and the KPMG South Africa 2014 study. Both studies are discussed in the subsequent paragraphs.

Morocco and Uganda – 2009 – Duvvury *et al.*: The Duvvury *et al.* 2009 publication is a multi-country research for Morocco, Bangladesh, and Uganda. Its primary aim is to estimate the out-of-pocket expenditures for accessing services and missed days of work. Calculated costs mainly derive from random sample surveys with individuals.⁷⁰ However, the study has several limitations, as intangibles and second-generational costs are omitted, among others.

Further, it neither considers government and donor budgets on GBV nor sets lost economic output into relation to GDP per capita data. Moreover, it does not link lost workdays to women's average market wage ratio with similar education (Duvvury *et al.* 2009 p. 11). Consequently, this leads to the discrimination of poorer cohorts and difficulties to estimate values for women that perform household chores only. Thus, the use of GDP per capita data may be a more objective and better approach.

South Africa – 2014 – KPMG South Africa: Until now, projections of the economic losses for the SADC region have only been carried out in one study, namely in the KPMG South Africa 2014 study. The study “Too costly to ignore. The economic impact of gender-based violence in South Africa” aims to determine the costs for survivors, government, civil society, and businesses. Income lost through GBV was calculated based on monthly and daily payment and employment data. The analysis shows that according to a conservative estimate, the country of South Africa incurs costs due to GBV of between R 28.4 and 42.4 billion per year – or between 0.90 and 1.30 per cent of GDP. However, the calculations should be viewed as a partial and minimum estimate of the actual costs since not all expenses could be calculated due to insufficient data. For example, the exact prevalence proportion is not known. However, estimates assume a relatively high proportion of 20 to 30 per cent. The calculations must, therefore, be read as an assumption only. Furthermore, the cost categories for government expenditure are only presumptions because the figures could not be identified in the national expenditure report. Moreover, there is no holistic calculation of the Intangible costs caused by pain and suffering (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 2). This category typically significantly increases the total losses (Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996). Further, the costs of the second-generation are not included, either (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 25). The overall results are therefore not comprehensive.

⁶⁹A more detailed explanation will be conducted in Section 3.4.2

⁷⁰The sample size was 2,003 women in Bangladesh; 2,122 in Morocco, and 1,272 in Uganda (Duvvury *et al.* 2009 p. 6).

The next paragraph describes the 2017 UNFPA study from Ukraine, which was chosen based on this paper’s selection criteria and is summarised in the following.

Ukraine – 2017 – UNFPA Ukraine: The UNFPA Ukraine 2017 study on the “Economic costs of violence against women in Ukraine” calculated costs of around 0.23 per cent of GDP, based on a prevalence of ten per cent. According to the World Bank 2018a, Ukraine is a country of transition; hence it was included in this paragraph. As mentioned earlier, GDP estimates appear to be very low compared to other findings. Table 3.6 shows a comparison of the current publications, which have a lower prevalence but a higher GDP cost-share than the Ukrainian publication.

Table 3.6.: Comparison of the Ukrainian 2017 study.

Prevalence [%]	GDP share [%]	Country	Author	Excluded
10	0.23	Ukraine	UNFPA Ukraine 2017	Second-generation costs, others
Studies with a lower prevalence, but higher GDP cost-share ⁷¹				
1.95	0.98	U.S.	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996	Others
2.00	0.22 ⁷²	Spain	Villagómez 2010	Others
5.00	1.07	Australia	Access Economics 2004a	–
7.10	0.76	Australia	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	–
[11.13] ⁷³	1.35	Australia	KPMG Australia 2016	–

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.
Source: Own representation.

The total cost-share of other research is significantly higher despite their lower prevalence. The calculation methodology of the lost economic output category in this study can serve as a potential explanation. The UNFPA Ukraine 2017 paper distinguishes between minor and severe injuries. Nevertheless, it calculates the financial loss, not based on the individual’s adverse physical health state, such as a broken arm or broken teeth. Therefore, the cost result in this category should be seen as an approximate estimate only. Regarding the application of the unit cost methodology, it can be said that the health expenditure is calculated on the basis of unit cost in Ukrainian hryvnia ₴. The unit-cost approach of the paper appears to be robust in general, especially for the personal cost category. However, it has to be added that it remains unclear from which source the unit cost data derives. In addition, the calculated losses do not take into account long-term post-traumatic behaviour disorders, which leads

⁷¹The studies are arranged in ascending order according to their prevalence.

⁷²The share of GDP is lower, but the prevalence is, however, significantly lower in value. The Spanish study was therefore included in this summary.

⁷³The prevalence is higher, but the GDP share is, however, significantly higher in value. The KPMG Australia 2016 study was therefore included in this summary. For details on the prevalence composition, see Chapter 16.

to an artificial cost-reduction in consequence. This fact has to be taken into account when investigating a possible methodological application further.

In order to calculate the legal costs, the research applies the unit-cost approach as well. It calculates the cost of the CJS based on worked hourly rates. The time the police spend talking to the perpetrator or for administrative work, for instance. The consumed hours are set in relation to the official national salary index; for example, a district inspector earns €7,000, a police officer €6,600, or an investigator €10,000, among others. The study reports the costs in either € or US\$. In addition, the average hourly unit cost for each employee was collected, is multiplied by the average workload per activity, and then was set into relation to the registered cases (UNFPA Ukraine 2017 p. 43) [see Table 3.7].

Table 3.7.: UNFPA’s unit cost calculations.

Activity	Average salary [per month]	Registered criminal cases
Registration of a GBV case <i>etc.</i>	District inspector [€7,000] <i>etc.</i>	116,548 <i>etc.</i>

Source: Own representation based on UNFPA Ukraine 2017 p. 44.

UNFPA Ukraine 2017 uses the average time units consumed in the judicial system to persecute a perpetrator, participate in a police patrol, or prepare court hearings. Nevertheless, the study contains numerous uncertain variables since specific results are based on qualitative surveys with restricted sample sizes (UNFPA Ukraine 2017 p. 44 ff.). The study is limited to Domestic Violence [DV] cases; hence, incidents involving violence by strangers, teachers, or police officers are omitted. In addition, there is no international research with appropriate data on how much time units, police, or legal staff consume on average to manage and to investigate GBV incidents. As a result, [international] data comparison becomes challenging.

The UNFPA Ukraine 2017 study was the last publication to be examined within this paragraph; in order to continue, the following paragraph provides a summary of Section 3.4.1.

Summary

To answer the question asked at the beginning of Section 3.4.1

How is it possible that a relatively low prevalence proportion of 1.95 per cent in the American Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996 study, for example, leads to a relatively high GDP cost-share of 0.98 per cent, whereby mainly the costs of marriage violence are calculated?

Whereas a relatively high prevalence proportion of 7.10 per cent, as in the Australian National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009 report, leads to a much lower GDP share of 0.76 per cent, although the study uses a detailed model and calculates each cost category.

Section 3.4.1 conducted a brief evaluation of the current literature. It became clear that only slight differences within the methods for the three cost categories: lost economic output, intangibles, physical, and emotional impact and second-generation costs led to considerable differences in the total costs. They even outweigh the omission of specific cost categories such as personal or legal costs. In addition, the high prevalence in developing and emerging

countries does not automatically lead to high cost-shares, as it is the case with analyses for the USA or the EU, for instance. For example, in the case of Vietnam, the GDP cost result of 3.19 per cent appears to be very low compared to the high prevalence ratio of over 25 per cent in rural areas (Duvvury and Carney 2012). In general, it can be said that the cost results in relation to GDP in developing and emerging countries are significantly lower compared to the industrialised countries, although they tend to have a higher prevalence. The reason for this lies partly in the more conservative or outdated methods applied and secondly in more significant data gaps than in the industrialised countries. One could further argue that developing and emerging countries have a smaller budget to carry out prevention and support activities. This reasoning is often applicable; nevertheless, this does not explain the mostly low cost-results in the area of Intangible costs. It is also not always the case that the developing and emerging countries have lower budget expenditures for prevention and GBV measures in terms of their GDP share (Ministry of Finance 2018). The cause must, therefore, be partially found in the methods used. Section 3.4.2 intends to analyse this matter further. After the current literature has been examined regarding its scope, methodological peculiarities, and weaknesses, the appropriate publications will be discussed in more detail. Table 3.8 shows a summary of studies that were identified to be suitable.

Table 3.8.: Overview of methodically suitable literature.

Category	Country	Year	Author
Economic output			No study identified.
Health services			No study identified.
Legal	U.K.	2009 [2004]	Walby 2009
Social welfare and special services	Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a
	Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004
Personal			Various studies.
Intangibles	U.K.	2009 [2004]	[partially] ⁷⁴ Walby 2009
Second-generation			No study could be identified.

Source: Own representation.

A suitable study and methodology could be found within the literature search for the following categories: legal costs, social welfare costs, special service costs, personal costs, and intangibles. However, the methods presented in the literature overview were not suitable for the following categories: lost economic output, health service costs, and second-generation costs. Either the method cannot be transferred to the Namibian context, for example, due to the restricted data situation, or the study had significant methodological weaknesses. For these cost classes, Section 3.4.2 will look for other suitable publications that, for example, only calculate a

⁷⁴The word “partially” is added because Walby uses the method but the primary data derives from other publications. The primary data stems from the research of Bolling, Mattinson, and Myhill 2002 Budd *et al.* 2000 Dolan *et al.* 2005 Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005

distinctive cost class and therefore were not included in Section 3.4.1, which examined only the publications that estimate all major cost categories. Hence, this additional part was added, among other things, because there are excellent works that only estimate individual cost types. The review begins by examining the cost category of the lost economic output in greater detail.

3.4.2. Specific studies

Section 3.4.2 takes a closer look at studies that have stood out for a particular category, starting with the lost economic output.

Lost economic output

For this category, no suitable study could be identified based on the literature review. Therefore, a brief introduction to the various assumptions on which the calculation of economic losses is based is given. The first aspect is that the methods must include:

- The impact on human capital: personal health determines how much time a person can spend on producing goods and income. Overall, health, in general, is a critical aspect of human capital and economic prosperity (Abramsky *et al.* 2011).
- Effects on employment: the literature is ambivalent about the relationship between GBV and its impact on employment. On the one hand, studies indicate that employment is a protective factor against violence. For example, working women and men report illness less frequently, according to Bhattacharyya, Bedi, and Chhachhi 2011; Crowne *et al.* 2010. On the other hand, research on women who live in abusive partnerships report that such are more likely to lose their jobs, see for instance Meisel, Chandler, and Rienzi 2003, or have a higher job turnover, according to Reeves and O'Leary-Kelly 2007; Rothman and Corso 2008. However, some studies show that women who suffer from GBV are more often in paid employment. Some of which is the work of Agüero 2013; Farmer and Tiefenthaler 2004a; Farmer and Tiefenthaler 2004b.
- Impact on productivity: in addition, violence not only affects employment but also explicitly affects the productivity of an economy (Duvvury *et al.* 2013). Healthier workers can be more productive for various reasons, as they tend to have more stamina, general health, focus, or attention (Dolan *et al.* 2005). According to Reeves and O'Leary-Kelly 2007 survivors show a significantly higher level of distraction at work, or, as stated by Kötter, Obst, and Voltmer 2017, also display higher rates of absenteeism in their workplace.

In short, GBV affects the quality of human capital, employment, and overall economic productivity across an entire nation (Duvvury *et al.* 2013; Walby and Olive 2014). A comprehensive cost survey in this category must take these aspects into account.

Publications suitable for this category

As no suitable paper was found in Section 3.4.1, a more extensive literature search was carried out in Section 3.4.2. Based on this, the following two studies, displayed in Table 3.9, were determined, explicitly calculating the cost category of the lost economic output.

The following two paragraphs present the two publications in greater detail.

Table 3.9.: Overview of appropriate studies: lost economic output.

Country	Year	Author
U.K.	2005	Dolan <i>et al.</i> 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005
Global	2013	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2013

Source: Own representation.

U.K. – 2005 – Dolan *et al.*; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns: Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Walby and Allen 2004 created a fundamental methodology to measure the loss of production. Essential elements that Dolan and Dubourg use in their papers are the results from different health conditions, which derive from relevant injury report data. Every state of physical injury is associated with an inevitable loss of economic performance. These values are calculated for different categories of violent crime, such as rape, sexual assault, or robbery. A statistical probability of their occurrence is assigned to each negative physical health state. This method and data are very robust and can be used internationally. To implement this method, data on the current number of cases, broken down by type of violence and a suitable multiplier, are required to adjust the crime statistics recorded by the police since GBV is one of the least reported crimes (Duvvury *et al.* 2013). In summary, a significant advantage of this method is that:

1. The approach focuses on the actual time lost.
2. Losses from housework, self-employment, and paid employment are calculated and interpreted equally. It does not matter whether this time is a loss of paid time only, as it includes the loss of time from unpaid housework/chores as well, for instance. Based on the per capita income data baseline, unemployed or surviving dependents with lower wages or people who are not employed for cash are not discriminated.
3. The method considers losses for various categories of crime such as wounding, sexual assault, or rape due to mental illnesses, including burnout or anxiety. The additional psychological damage caused by drug abuse, depression, or anxiety was calculated in the rape category too (Walby 2009).

In summary, it can be said that the fundamental values of lost economic performances per violent crime are transferable, the approach requires little data, and is very holistic in its extend. The data basis seems to be internationally transferable and would, therefore, be suitable for the scope of this study to calculate the category of lost economic output for Namibia.

In addition, another analysis was found that provides an overview of the calculation of the lost economic output for emerging countries. This is the World Bank study by Duvvury *et al.* 2013, which is presented in the next paragraph.

Vietnam/Global – 2013 – Duvvury *et al.*: In her study for the World Bank, Duvvury *et al.* apply this method to Vietnam, Bangladesh, and Uganda. In “Intimate partner violence: Economic costs and implications for growth and development,” Duvvury *et al.* focus on the category of the economic impact of violence. The team calculates the loss of productivity and production based on the production data of the most important economic sectors within the Vietnamese market. Their approach is based on the sectoral distribution of female labour force participation. Duvvury *et al.* argue that the empirically-based multi-sector model is

suitable for analysing the economic contribution of women in different sectors of an economy. Analysis of these employment patterns shows the impact of violence on the economy and the female workforce in general. The approach aims to highlight the mutually reinforcing dynamics between GBV and a country's economic development.

Duvvury *et al.* use the following equation to calculate the economic losses: the number of people at risk of violence in the sector i is given by

$$DV_i = (LFP_i^w \cdot PR) + (LFP_i^m \cdot PR) \quad (3.2)$$

LFP_i^w is the number of women and LFP_i^m is the number of men employed in sector i . PR reflects the GBV prevalence. The total cases of violence in a sector i are calculated as:

$$TIV_i = DV_i \cdot IR \quad (3.3)$$

DV_i represents the DV cohort in sector i and IR shows the incidence rate of violence which is defined as the average number of incidents. The total lost working days are determined using Equations (3.2) and (3.3):

$$TD_i = (TIV_i \cdot a_i^w \cdot LDVW) + (TIV_i \cdot a_i^m \cdot LDVM) \quad (3.4)$$

TIV_i is the total value from Equation (3.3), which provides the total number of cases in sector i . Furthermore, a_i^w is the proportion of absolute events that lead to absenteeism in women, and a_i^m is the number of events that lead to absenteeism in men. $LDVW$ is the average number of days women miss per incident. In addition, $LDVM$ is the average number of days that men miss per incident.

$$ILDV = \sum (TIV_i \cdot LDVW) + (TIV_i \cdot LDVM) \quad (3.5)$$

To note, Duvvury *et al.* base their equations partially on the results of the Duvvury and Carney (2012) survey in Vietnam. The paper studied a total of 1,053 women for GBV-related losses at the household level.

In summary, the Duvvury *et al.* method seems feasible, primarily due to its minimal data requirements. The approach is therefore tested and applied to the Namibian context. In summary, the methods of Dolan *et al.* (2005), Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns (2005), Duvvury *et al.* (2013) were identified to be best suitable. In order to continue, the next paragraph provides an overview of the literature and the various methods that can primarily be used to calculate the GBV health service costs.

Health service costs

The problem with health costs is that expenses go beyond immediate health expenditure and benefits. GBV can exacerbate costs because losses span a lifetime as they are related to HIV/AIDS infections or triggered alcohol or drug abuse, for instance (Abramsky *et al.* (2011), Ackerson *et al.* (2008), Bleakley (2010), Brown (2008), Day, McKenna, and Bowlus (2005), Drummond *et al.* (2015), Enlow *et al.* (2012), García-Moreno *et al.* (2013)). In developing and emerging countries, poor data management and record-keeping often pose obstacles to realistic calculations (García-Moreno *et al.* (2013)). Hence, it is difficult to quantify the health burden from GBV fully, and therefore a holistic estimation remains a challenge. An entirely suitable approach could not have been

identified in Section 3.4.1. As a result, the primary literature used was analysed from the literature examined in Section 3.4.1. The studies of Walby 2004 and Walby 2009 presented use elements of the British 2004 Home Office Online Report [HOOR] of Walby and Allen 2004, for instance. The findings of Walby 2009 are partially derived from the results of Dolan *et al.* 2005. Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005. Both scholars devote their research to quantifying GBV health losses.

Table 3.10.: Overview of appropriate studies: health service costs.

Country	Year	Author
U.K.	2005	Dolan <i>et al.</i> 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005

Source: Own representation.

The method is to be discussed in more detail in the following paragraph.

U.K. – 2005 – Dolan *et al.*; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns: The approach was developed in response to the limitations of existing methods and is supported by the British government (Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Walby and Allen 2004). The model associates the possibility of certain health conditions arising from different types of crime. In detail, the authors calculate the cost of health care [in euros] – per murder case, [serious] wounding, sexual assault, and rape (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 43). Overall, the concept is based on the different degrees of health-damaging consequences that are determined within the method. In addition to the probabilities of reduced physical health states reported in the British Crime Survey by Walby and Allen 2004, the technique adds consequences of psychological trauma to the calculations (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 41 ff.). The probability of various post-traumatic stress disorders [PTSDs] was calculated for the criminal categories of sexual assault and wounding. In particular, the possibility of psychological harm within the category rape was considered in more detail. For example, according to Dolan *et al.*, in cases of sexual abuse, 14.70 per cent of women experience severe PTSDs. For the crime category of sexual abuse, potential mental health loss due to drug and alcohol abuse, suicide, anxiety, or eating disorders have been estimated in addition (Dolan *et al.* 2005, p. 974). Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 base their calculations on data from various surveys with GBV survivors. In general, their approach is robust and available for both men and women and can also be applied to other geographical areas. It should be noted that this method may underestimate the costs because it only takes one treatment cycle into account. On the other hand, the cost of treating minor injuries, such as bruises, could be overestimated because affected survivors may manage such themselves.

However, after reviewing all available literature and considering the exclusion criteria presented in Section 3.3.1, this approach currently appears to be the most appropriate to be applied. In order to continue, the following paragraph will present the chosen literature on legal costs.

Legal costs

The costs that the legal and judicial system incurs due to GBV vary and depend on the definition of the national legal framework. In general, expenditures extend to responding, enforcing, and protecting those affected. These include, in particular, the issuing of protective orders, specific administration and support in court proceedings, compensation for survivors, or the persecution and detention of perpetrators. Few studies attempted to calculate all

associated losses. The one that was found most suitable in Section 3.4.1 is Walby's 2009 [2004] study.

Table 3.11.: Overview of appropriate studies: legal costs.

Country	Year	Author
U.K.	2009 [2004] ⁷⁵	Walby [2009]

Source: Own representation based on Walby [2004] Walby [2009].

U.K. – 2009 – Walby: On the one hand, Walby [2009] determines the losses based on the CJS unit costs, and on the other hand, based on the proportion of time spent on a specific activity. The unit-cost approach is derived from the work of Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] in which relevant unit costs were computed in British pounds. [See Table 3.12].

Table 3.12.: 2004 Walby example of policing.

Police activity	Share of police time [h]	Police budget [£]	Number of offences [in thousands]
Violence against the person <i>etc.</i>	14 <i>etc.</i>	1,135,842 <i>etc.</i>	2,908 <i>etc.</i>
Overall policing activity	100	8,309,984 [100%]	–

Source: Own representation based on Walby [2004] p. 40.

In addition, Walby [2009] integrates police costs of various crime types into the total CJS costing by using research from Brand and Price [2000]. Table 3.13 displays an example pattern of Walby [2009].

Table 3.13.: 2004 Walby example of total CJS costs.

CJS activity	Crime categories		
	Homicide [£]	Sexual offences [£]	<i>etc.</i>
Police activity	107,299	1,900	<i>etc.</i>
Prosecution <i>etc.</i>	410	60	<i>etc.</i>
Overall CJS cost per incident	118,299	3,837	<i>etc.</i>

Source: Own representation based on Walby [2004] p. 42.

However, the study also displays some weaknesses. For example, Walby calculates the time units spent on policing activities based on the “Email Communication from Jamie Thorns, Assistant Economist, Department of Economics and Resource Analysis, Home Office” (Walby [2004] p. 116), which is an unpublished reference. Therefore, it is not clear on what data basis the costs of £107,299 for the police per murder case were surveyed, for instance.

Nevertheless, in summary, Walby builds her research on a solid set of quantitative and qualitative data, and the approach used is generally transferable.

⁷⁵The 2004 Walby study was updated in 2009 (Walby [2004] Walby [2009]).

The next paragraph discusses further research on social welfare and special service spending.

Social welfare and special service costs

During the review, a distinction was made between certain costs of social benefits such as expenses for illness, disability, or support for single parents. special services include interpersonal interventions such as telephone helplines, GBV support centres, or therapies. Although general information is available, the unbundling of expenditure for specific services is complex and often requires direct primary data from specific service providers (Bell 2003 Ministry of Gender Equality and Child Welfare 2012 Mogotsi *et al.* 2015).

Table 3.14 provides an overview of studies that use best-case approaches to estimate the cost of social welfare and special services⁷⁶

Table 3.14.: Overview of appropriate studies: social welfare costs.

Country	Year	Author
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004

Source: Own representation.

In order to continue, the Australian and Colombian studies will be discussed next.

Australia – 2004 – Access Economics: The Australian Access Economics 2004a study has applied a suitable approach for calculating social benefits expenditure. The costs include, for example, financial support, expenses for sickness or mobility grants, disability payments, or services for single parents. Access Economics 2004a calculates the financial income support granted based on the estimated use of social benefits for GBV survivors. The research uses a four-step approach to calculate public sector costs. The multi-stage model provides well-founded estimates (Walby and Olive 2014, p. 73) because it is, among others, based on holistic primary data of the Australian McLennan 1996 survey. In short, the paper applies the following steps:

1. Firstly, the calculation and application of the recipient ratio and the proportional distribution of social security expenditure between the general population in relation to sickness and mobility allowances, renting allowances, disability allowances, or other emergency payments.
2. Secondly, the calculation of the recipient groups for the specific types of payouts.
3. Thirdly, the adjustment of the number of recipient groups. In the case of Access Economics 2004a they were scaled to 35.50 per cent based on the GBV cohort within the group of beneficiaries. The increase was made to take into account the higher likelihood of GBV survivors seeking social assistance.

⁷⁶The Swedish Envall and Eriksson 2006 and the Spanish Villagómez 2010 studies have a suitable methodology and were identified as suitable in Section 3.4.1. However, the applied method is comparable to that used in the Australian Access Economics 2004a and Colombian Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 study, which is why they are not described again in detail in this section.

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4. Fourth, the calculation of the cumulative payments for the GBV-affected cohort within the total group of social assistance recipients (Access Economics [2004b](#), p. 61).

However, there are different concerns about the application of the third step. The analysis found that a survivor who has had a GBV incident within the past three years is 35.5 per cent more likely to receive some form of government support. In contrast, the Access Economics [2004a](#) scholars have not found this increase when evaluating only the time frame of the past 12 months within the dataset. This lack of statistical evidence in the past 12 months data partly undermines the outcome of the paper.

In addition, the budget-share approach, by Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004](#), is examined in the following.

Colombia – 2004 – Ribero and Sánchez Torres: Overall, the report assesses the impact of GBV on households in Colombia. The authors base their cost estimates on a detailed dataset including demographics, human capital, labour market shares, or household income surveys. Table [3.15](#) summarises how Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004](#) calculate their social spending based on the budget-share approach.

Table 3.15.: Approach of Ribero and Sánchez.

Overall expenses	Region [numbers]	Nation [numbers]
PROY – Assistance to children and support to the family	44,934	46,531
SUBP – Promotion of restitution culture regarding the rights of children and their families	1,429	1,429
<i>etc.</i>	<i>etc.</i>	<i>etc.</i>

Note: Figures are in millions of pesos, in 2003.

Source: Own representation based on Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004](#) p. 31.

The used budget-share approach encompasses all resources allocated by the government under its institutions in relation to GBV. The data is mainly derived from the budget information of the public bodies involved. However, Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004](#), p. 31 do not comprehensively include all social spending, as payments such as unemployment benefits or single parent payments are omitted. Therefore, if applied to the Namibian context, the approach shall be extended to such additional elements.

In order to continue, the following paragraph describes selected studies in the area of personal cost estimations.

Personal costs

Numerous studies calculate personal costs based on the unit-cost approach. For example, the UNFPA Ukraine [2017](#) report estimates that the individual must bear a high proportion of the expenses due to the systematic lack of accommodation and services. In summary, the paper expands the individual cost segment, as the investigations include material costs such as loss of property and income, expenses for personal security measures, translocation costs, mortgages, or rent for separate accommodations. In addition, Intangible losses such as a deteriorated Quality of Life are recorded, including potentially lost income opportunities or lost QALYs (UNFPA Ukraine [2017](#), p. 5). In order to make the situation more authentic for the reader, the study works with many direct quotes from survivors, as in “I lost everything, as I had to go

and leave it all to my former husband” (UNFPA Ukraine [2017](#), p. 62). The authors conducted interviews with those affected looking for support at various institutions, and a total of 707 women were interviewed to quantify direct material expenditure (UNFPA Ukraine [2017](#), p. 61). Numerous studies follow this method. Table [3.16](#) summarises the available literature, which computes the unit costs within the category of personal expenses. Table [3.16](#) also shows which data sources are used in the selected literature presented in Section [3.4.1](#) to estimate the unit costs and their respective multipliers best.

Table 3.16.: Overview of unit costs: legal costs.

Unit Cost	Data sources	Multiplier	Data sources
Per divorce [average]			
Per divorce [high]	Administrative data, interviews, national surveys	Ratio of divorce, injunction, property damage, or relocation per annum	Public and legal data
Per court order and injunctions			
Per property damage			Representative national surveys
Per relocation			
Per repossession			

Source: Own representation based on Walby and Olive [2014](#)

Survivors have to pay various expenses, such as the cost of personal security, property repairs, travel expenses, additional accommodation, or losses associated with being a single parent. Due to the lack of availability of data, evaluations are often complex. However, there are several techniques for calculating personal payments. Unit costs can be computed using various sources such as administrative data, interviews, or national surveys. A suitable multiplier has to be determined for each payment category, which can be derived from regulatory, legal data, or representative surveys (Gass *et al.* [2011](#); Helweg-Larsen *et al.* [2010](#); Logan, Walker, and Hoyt [2012](#); Reeves and O’Leary-Kelly [2007](#); Wright, Fagan, and Crittenden [2011](#)).

After appropriate parameters in personal cost calculations have been presented briefly, the following paragraph summarises the identified relevant literature, which calculates the Intangible losses.

Intangibles, physical, and emotional impact

As indicated, none of the studies reviewed was found to be entirely appropriate to measure the Intangible cost for this study’s setting. Hence, the analysed range of literature was expanded further. Intangibles are often calculated based on a similar method as used for the discussed lost economic output calculation. The Home Office Online Report [HOOR] by Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#), for instance, assesses the expenses based on the loss of health state outcomes. The British research was among the first to use QALYs to calculate the Intangible harm of crime in general for this context.

Table 3.17.: Overview of appropriate studies: intangibles.

Country	Year	Author
U.K.	2009 [2004]	[partially] Walby 2009

Source: Own representation.

U.K. – 2009 – Walby; Walby and Allen; – 2005 – Dolan *et al.*; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns:

The publications of Walby [2004] Walby [2009] Walby and Allen [2004] are only partially suitable to calculate this category. However, they were listed because through the work of Dolan *et al.* [2005] p. 964, or Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] p. 36, they have undergone further progression. Dolan *et al.* [2005] Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] deal more specifically with calculating the Intangible losses. Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] p. 34 measure the expected QALY losses [measured in terms of lost years of total health] based on various adverse health conditions such as wounding, rape, or frequent bodily harm. The QALY losses in years per crime are set to the QALY costs per unit multiplied by the respective number of cases. Table 3.18 summarises the procedure used by Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] in the HOOR 2005.

Table 3.18.: Calculation of QALY data according to Dubourg 2005.

Category	QALY loss [years of total health]	Unit cost QALY [£]	Crime cases [numbers]	Lost QALYs [£]
Rape	0.561 (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] p. 34)	80,620 (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] p. 34)	100 ⁷⁸	4,522,782

Source: Own representation based on Dolan *et al.* [2005]

Walby [2004] p. 92 and Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] p. 29 add the willingness-to-pay approach to the QALY data. The technique is based on a cost-benefit analysis and aims to represent the amount of money that a society is willing to pay to reduce or avoid a specific harmful result, such as GBV. The method allows the entire cost spectrum of GBV cases, including sexual violence, to be estimated. The approach also includes the cost of physical injury and psychological harm, and therefore, provides a holistic picture of encountered losses. In general, it can be said that the method is replicable, and its obtained results are comparable.

After summarising the appropriate literature for the category of intangibles, the following paragraph looks at suitable research that analyses the second-generation costs.

Second-generation costs

It is more difficult to calculate the extent of GBV that affects children. On the one hand, because most abuse is not reported, on the other hand, because the consequences of violence experienced in childhood and early adolescence are the most difficult to assess. The 2002 World Report on Violence and Health by Krug *et al.* [2002] concluded that the murder rate of children under the age of five, for boys in developed high-income countries, is 2.20 cases

⁷⁷The word “partially” is added because Walby applies the method; however, the used primary data derives from other publications. The primary data stems from the research of Bolling, Mattinson, and Myhill [2002] Budd *et al.* [2000] Dolan *et al.* [2005] Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005]

⁷⁸Assumption.

per 100,000 inhabitants, and for girls, it is 1.80 cases per 100,000 inhabitants. In contrast, the number of cases in low and middle-income countries was 6.10 cases for boys and 5.10 cases for girls per 100,000 citizens. However, in Africa, the cases were among the highest at 17.90 cases for boys and 12.70 cases for girls per 100,000 inhabitants.

Regarding calculation methods, the GBV costs for children have already been partially included in the previous categories. For example, in the cost classes:

1. Health service costs: surveys in this category also estimate the deteriorated health of girls from the age of 15. However, the calculations do not include other costs, such as violence during pregnancy and its consequences for the unborn child or general physical and mental consequences for children living in violent families.
2. Social welfare and special service costs: this category also partly includes the services offered to minors, for example, in the form of protection and accommodation.
3. Intangibles: the research primarily includes girls and sometimes boys from the age of 15 who suffer physically and mentally from violence. Children in younger age cohorts are usually not taken into account. For example, the KPMG Australia [2016](#) only calculates the costs for children who are over 15 years, based on the Australian Bureau of Statistics [2012](#) data, among others.

When comparing the literature, it quickly becomes apparent that it is an essential matter, which costs to include in this category (Habetha *et al.* [2012](#) p. 62). Most studies centre exclusively on direct-related costs for minors and only partially consider Intangible losses due to their associated obstacles. The following summary lists the most significant challenges when it comes to computing losses for children.

1. Data availability: the availability of cost data is a key criterion. A one-time summation of the costs incurred after traumatisation is not adequate. Further, there is usually no specific data to differentiate between trauma-related and non-trauma-related factors. The question also arises [if it was collected] how reliable and up-to-date the data is. Due to the lack of clarity and potential biases in correlations, the results in current studies, therefore, mainly present estimations only (Habetha *et al.* [2012](#) p. 62).
2. Individual health conditions: some children may be resilient towards its psychological impacts. Resilience is attributed to endogenous and exogenous protective determinants that give an individual the ability to overcome traumatic events. However, trauma can (re)occur with a delay, or re-traumatisation can occur in adulthood again (Caspi *et al.* [2002](#) Wetzels [1997](#)). Such different unfoldings further complicate the GBV costing for children.
3. Consequences of non-treatment: missing or inappropriate treatment and care deficits can lead to a domino effect, where children experience multiple trauma, which again has a negative impact on their later adulthood, and increases cost artificially (Kraft *et al.* [2006](#) Schmid, Fegert, and Petermann [2010](#)).

These particular determinants are taken into account, and a further, more tailored literature analysis is carried out for this cost category based on the eligibility criteria presented in Section [3.3.1](#). In this course, the Fang *et al.* [2017](#) study from South Africa was selected. The 13 studies that were examined additionally for this category, but were excluded, are summarised in the Appendix.

Table 3.19.: Overview of appropriate studies: second-generation costs.

Region	Country	Year	Author
Africa	South Africa	2017	Fang <i>et al.</i> 2017

Source: Own representation.

South Africa – 2017 – Fang *et al.*: The South African Fang *et al.* 2017 study estimates “The economic burden of violence against children in South Africa” by using the disability-adjusted life year [DALY]-concept. DALYs take the actual local life expectancy of society into account. They were initially developed to document data on relative health in communities. The aim was to create a database that provides reliable information on fatal and nonfatal health outcomes. In short, DALY researcher assign health-adjusted life years [HALYs] measurements to diseases, primarily for practical reasons since the collection of comparable primary data from the large number of countries for which a global disease burden is estimated is complex (Gold, Stevenson, and Fryback 2002). The Fang *et al.* 2017 paper uses the following three-point strategy to calculate DALY-losses:

1. Calculation of population-based proportions [PAFs]: PAFs combine the occurrence of risk factors such as violence against children and the probability of certain diseases. The study computes the likelihood of alcohol and drug abuse, sexually transmitted diseases [STDs], self-harm, and mental disorders, including depression and anxiety. The team calculated PAF data for each form of violence against children for each of these harmful outcomes.
2. Cape Area Panel Study [CAPS]: in addition, data from the Cape Area Panel Study [CAPS] were used in the analysis. CAPS involves a representative sample of South African minors residing in Cape Town who have been accompanied from puberty to adulthood for seven years. The research includes a variety of time series measurements within the sample and additional population surveys. One advantage of this approach is that the study also utilises representative data from extensive demographic surveys. The data was collected in five successive periods. Based on the information, correlations between the different types of violence against children, including emotional, sexual and physical violence, and the associated risk behaviour, such as violence, wage levels, drug and alcohol abuse or mental health, were collected⁷⁹
3. Calculation of DALYs: based on this data, the lost DALYs were calculated. This includes losses due to lethal violence, adverse physical and mental health, and consequences of Physical and Emotional violence against children. DALY losses estimate the monetary value based on data from the World Health Organization (WHO) 2001 and Brown 2008. Both reports assume that one DALY per year corresponds to the annual national GDP

⁷⁹The Heckman two-step approach was later used to correct for selection bias. Heckman’s correction is a statistical method for correcting distortions from randomly selected samples or other variables. This is achieved by modelling the individual sample probability of each observation [the so-called selection equation], together with the conditional expectation of the dependent variables [the so-called outcome equation]. See, for example, Kim and Jang 2010, or Moon, Balasubramanian, and Rimal 2005, for more information on the approach.

per capita. Due to the possibility of comorbidity due to child abuse and other unrelated adverse health conditions that preceded the occurrence of violence in childhood, the DALY data was only calculated for children over 15 years of age.

Table 3.20 provides a data overview of the information that the study uses in its calculation.

Table 3.20.: Overview of a possible DALY loss calculation: children.

Health Outcomes	Sexual violence DALY Loss	Economic Value in million Rand, R	Neglect DALY Loss	Economic Value in million Rand, R
Depression	14,127	1,032	48,008	3,507
Alcohol abuse	70,520	5,152	29,717	2,171
Self-harm	44,677	3,264	–	–
Overall	375,097	27,405	93,804	6,853

Source: Own representation based on Fang *et al.* 2017

The study calculates a significant number of lost DALYs due to sexual, physical, emotional violence, and neglect; as for children, an additional separation between abuse and neglect is conducted. According to Fang's calculations, 2.3 million and 84,287 DALYs lost in South Africa in 2015 are attributed to nonfatal and fatal violence against children. The estimated economic value of DALYs lost to violence against children [including both fatal and nonfatal violence] in South Africa was R 173 billion [US\$ 13.5 billion] or 4.30 per cent of South Africa's gross domestic product in 2015 (Fang *et al.* 2017 p. 1). This is the highest estimated GDP loss calculated compared to all other studies examined.

Table 3.21.: Comparison of studies: second-generation costs.

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%]	Cost of women	Cost of children	GDP share [%]
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012	25.40	✓	✓ ⁸⁰	3.19 ⁸¹
Bangladesh ⁸²	2011	Siddique 2011 ⁸³	24.00	✓	✓	2.10 (Siddique 2011 p. 50)
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	18.00	✓	✓	3.93 (Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 p. 36)
South Africa	2017	Fang <i>et al.</i> 2017	– ⁸⁴	–	✓	4.30

Source: Own representation.

⁸⁰Children's health and school performance, including missed days, failing, poor marks (Duvvury and Carney 2012 p. 2).

⁸¹In relation to the 2010 GDP (Duvvury and Carney 2012 p. 78).

⁸²Duvvury *et al.* 2009 also report on Bangladesh. However, the Siddique study is methodically more elaborate. See explanations from the Duvvury 2009 study under Morocco and Uganda.

⁸³Duvvury *et al.* 2009 also examine the region of Bangladesh. Nonetheless, the study depicts certain lacks. See Section 3.4 and the columns on Morocco and Uganda.

⁸⁴Children only.

The South African Fang *et al.* 2017 study only calculates the costs for children and still estimates the highest share of GDP costs. This shows how comprehensive the DALY method is to economically measure the loss of health in life, as these Intangible losses are actual and very significant for those affected.

3.5. Conclusion

At the beginning of Chapter 3 the different stages of literacy development were presented. The process was briefly divided into developing and industrialised countries. There is a significant gap in the applied methods and results of both. The used methods and the outcome in the developing and emerging countries are nowhere near as detailed and mature as the data in the published literature in the industrialised countries. At the beginning of Section 3.2 an overview of all literature development was given, which was summarised into three stages. At the same time, in Section 3.3 the exclusion criteria were determined based on which publications were excluded or included in the literature comparison. Based on this, a number of 19 studies have been included in the shortlist. The studies were broken down into geographical areas; first industrialised countries, and second developing and emerging countries. Table 3.22 presents the integrated studies.

Table 3.22.: Overview of selected GBV cost studies.

Country	Year	Author
Developed countries		
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia 2016
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a
U.K.	2009	Walby 2009
Denmark	2010	Helweg-Larsen <i>et al.</i> 2010
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson 2006
Finland	2001	Heiskanen and Piispa 2001
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010
Developing and emerging countries		
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine 2017

Source: Own representation.

In order to carry out a comprehensive comparison, the results of the individual studies were compared to the respective national gross domestic product. If the paper did not state the gross domestic product outcome, the data was calculated for this comparison. If the study also did not summarise the overall result, the subtotals in the individual categories were summed up to produce this number. Further, the prevalence proportion used in the publication was also discussed. If no cross-sectoral prevalence proportion was given, for example, if a different prevalence proportion or number of cases was provided for each category, statistical datasets from the U.N. were used to enable a cross-sectoral comparison. The division was again made between industrialised and developing countries to compare the later results stringently since different methods, and theoretical foundations were used within the geographical areas.

Higher case numbers do not lead automatically to increased costs and expenses in terms of gross domestic product for developing and emerging countries. Although the prevalences in developing and emerging countries are significantly higher than those in industrialised countries, the total costs calculated to GDP are considerably lower. On the one hand, this is due to inaccuracies in the methodology. The methods of data collection, data analysis, and data evaluation used in industrialised countries are often more comprehensively. The theoretical foundations on which the studies are based are also much broader in industrialised countries. Numerous papers published in industrialised countries have expanded the GBV term, for instance. A large part of the studies not only refers to violence against women but also include violence against children and men. In addition, not only cases in the domestic environment are considered but also acts of violence that are carried out based on gender by institutional officials.

Section 3.4.2 presented studies that perform particularly methodical work in the area of specific cost categories. Studies were also integrated, which do not calculate all-important cost categories but only focus on particular parts and bring high methodological and theoretical added value. All the following cost categories were systematically processed:

1. lost economic output,
2. health service costs,
3. legal costs,
4. social welfare and special service costs,
5. personal costs,
6. intangibles, physical, and emotional impact,
7. second-generation costs.

Based on this analysis, the studies depicted in Table 3.23 present a particular added value for the respective cost category displayed.

Regarding the category of the second-generation costs, the estimation of the cost for children is a crucial area in itself. Numerous GBV studies do not include this cost class, as the determination of this category is associated with several challenges. However, its evaluation is of great importance since DV primarily affects children and has physical and mental

⁸⁵The Walby 2004 study was updated in Walby 2009

Table 3.23.: Overview of appropriate studies: summary.

Category	Country	Year	Author
Lost economic output	U.K.	2005	Dolan <i>et al.</i> 2005, Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005
Lost economic output	Global	2013	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2013
Health services	U.K.	2005	Dolan <i>et al.</i> 2005, Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005
Legal	U.K.	2009 [2004] ⁸⁵	Walby 2009
Social welfare and special services	Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a
Social welfare and special services	Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004
Personal	Numerous studies		
Intangibles	U.K.	2009 [2004]	Dolan <i>et al.</i> 2005, Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, Walby 2004, Walby 2009
Second-generation	South Africa	2017	Fang <i>et al.</i> 2017

Source: Own representation.

consequences, which impact generations. Its inclusion is therefore imperative to create a holistic cost calculation.

In sum, the following challenges regarding the evaluation of the economic costs of GBV, in general, were identified during the review process within Chapter 3:

1. Lack of available data: there are various gaps in cost studies, such as a limited geographical scope. Although numerous new initiatives have been planned to undertake international research on a large scale, tight national budgets, poor data collection practices, and restricted data reliability, especially in emerging countries, prevented such plans (World Health Organization (WHO) 2013b, World Health Organization (WHO) 2016b, World Health Organization (WHO) 2018c). However, international organisations such as the United Nations (UN Women 2018a) have made collecting evidence of violence against especially women and children a high priority. Therefore, the careful combination of data from such international sources offers the opportunity to collect more relevant information and demonstrate a higher level of detail within the analysis.
2. The impact of critical methodological differences on the results: it becomes clear that minor methodological differences lead to a significant difference in the overall GDP result. Therefore, developing and emerging countries with high GBV prevalence ratios do not automatically have a higher GDP cost-share compared to countries in the European Union or the USA, for instance. In general, the cost-outcome in developing and emerging countries tends to be lower than in developed countries due to more conservative or outdated methodology or more significant data gaps.
3. Lack of appropriate literature within developing and emerging countries: studies carried out in developing and emerging countries often showed different incompleteness in methodology, the validity of data, or overall stringency.
4. Challenges in calculating the costs for children: the availability of valid data remains crucial for calculating the costs of GBV for minors. Furthermore, a simple summation of the incurred and additional costs that occur after traumatising is hardly possible since there is often no precise information about the difference between trauma-related and non-trauma-related costs. Instead, the question arises as to what proportion of the total expenditure, for example, on education, can be attributed to GBV traumatising

and how accurate and up-to-date this corresponding data is. The data used requires considerable completeness and a high level of detail. Due to the many uncertain or unknown variables in this equation, all the cost studies cited show that the total cost figures presented are more likely estimates than secured values. Furthermore, all calculations must consider that various forms of trauma or re-traumatisation are possible after the initial traumatisation, which is displayed even more often in children (Habetha *et al.* 2012, p. 62–65). Moreover, trauma disorders can occur with a delay, and re-traumatisation can happen in adulthood, and its impact is difficult to measure [also economically] (Caspi *et al.* 2002; Wetzels 1997). This makes it even more challenging to calculate a realistic picture of the costs that have arisen and are occurring for children.

To advance further, Chapter 4 will discuss the hypothesis to be tested.

4. Hypothesis

4.1. Introduction

Chapter 4 will explain the derivation of the hypothesis. In Section 4.2.1, the results of all studies classified as suitable based on the literature search criteria are analysed. The purpose of this summary is to provide an overview of the relevant literature outcome regarding their prevalence and their total costs measured in terms of gross domestic product. This is intended to provide a more comprehensive overview of the current study situation to draw better conclusions for constructing the hypothesis. From this, further derivation steps are carried out. In Section 4.2.2, the studies are examined for their overall results, which have dealt extensively and in high quality with the three cost categories of lost economic output, intangibles, physical, and emotional impact, and second-generation costs. These three categories represent the sections with the highest cost-share, measured in terms of gross domestic product. This closer examination is of great relevance to the hypothesis since the method chosen in these categories significantly alters the total result of each study. In Section 4.2.3, the KPMG South Africa 2014 study is being analysed in detail. This in-depth analysis is necessary to compare the outcome of the KPMG study with the results of the studies for both, industrialised countries and for developing and emerging countries to generate more profound knowledge for the better construction of the hypothesis. In Section 4.3, the hypothesis is derived based on the previous analysis, and Section 4.4 provides a summary of all findings.

4.2. Construction of the hypothesis

Results from other research regarding their GDP proportion of cost are reviewed to develop the hypothesis. The literature review in Chapter 3 already gave a detailed summary of the currently available research. For reasons of practicability, the identified and eligible studies with their respective outcomes are summarised in Table 4.1

Table 4.1.: Overview of the GBV prevalence and GDP share worldwide.

	Prevalence [%]	GDP share [%]
Developed countries	0.60–7.10 ¹	0.004–1.07 ²
Developing and emerging countries	10.00–30.00	0.23–3.93

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

The prevalence ratios for developed countries range between 0.60 and 7.10 per cent. In contrast, ratios for developing and emerging countries span between 10 and 30 per cent, with African and Southern Asian countries depicting the highest shares. Cost in terms of GDP share differs between 0.004 and 1.35 per cent for developed countries and between 0.23 and around four per cent for developing and emerging countries.

The following subsection examines the GDP cost ratio of the literature, which has carried out a holistic calculation for all relevant cost categories to narrow down further the possible share of GDP cost outcome for this study.

4.2.1. Holistic publications

Section 4.2.1 only analyses the studies that have included all of the following cost categories:

1. lost economic output,
2. health service costs,
3. legal costs,
4. social welfare and special service costs,
5. personal costs,
6. intangibles, physical, and emotional impact, and
7. second-generation costs.

Table 4.2 will present a more detailed overview of the included research.

In summary, the prevalence ratios and GDP shares, presented in Table 4.3, were found in the selected research displayed.

Comparing Tables 4.2 and 4.3 shows:

- For industrialised countries: the lower-bound share of GDP costs rose from 0.004 to 0.12 per cent.
- For developing and emerging countries: the old GDP share ranged between 0.23 to 3.93 per cent, and the new share of GDP in the remaining research is 2.10 per cent.

This shift concludes that the more a study covers cost categories, the higher the share of GDP converts. However, this does not apply to the context of developing and emerging countries. This phenomenon has already been identified in Chapter 3. In these nations, a higher prevalence usually leads to smaller country spending relative to GDP. The reasons for such lower-cost calculations could be more conservative or outdated methods, higher data gaps, or limited national budgets compared to industrialised countries.

¹For the 11.30 per cent in KPMG Australia 2016 the primary data refers to *since the age of 15*, not to *within the past 12 months* (Australian Bureau of Statistics 2012). See Appendix.

²Ibid.

Table 4.2.: Overview of GBV studies: all seven categories.

Country	Year	Author	Category of cost	Prevalence [%]	GDP share [%]
			Economic output Health service Legal Social welfare Personal Special services Intangibles Second-generation		
Developed countries ³					
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	1.00	0.47
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia 2016	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	[11.13]	1.35
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	7.10	0.76
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	5.00	1.07
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	3.00	0.12
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	5.00	0.17
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	2.00	0.22
Developing and emerging countries					
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	24.00	2.10

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Table 4.3.: GBV prevalence and GDP share: holistic GBV studies.

	Prevalence [%]	GDP share [%]
Developed countries	1.00–7.10 ⁴	0.12–1.07 ⁵
Developing and emerging countries	24.00	2.10

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

It also becomes clear that slight differences in the used method to determine the three cost categories of lost economic output, intangibles, physical, and emotional impact and second-generation costs lead to considerable deviations in the total outcome. These deviations even outweigh the omission of certain cost classes, such as personal or legal costs.

In order to further narrow the hypothesis, Section 4.2.2 will only discuss those studies that were selected in Section 3.4.2 to be best suitable for calculating those three specific categories.

³The 1996 Miller study has been removed because the paper was published before 2000, and Section 4.2.2 is not concerned with analysing the methodology per se.

⁴For the 11.13 per cent in KPMG Australia 2016 the primary data refers to *since the age of 15*, not to *within the past 12 months* (Australian Bureau of Statistics 2012). See Part II

⁵Ibid.

4.2.2. Tailored studies

In order to continue, Table 4.4 provides an overview of the identified literature.

Table 4.4.: Overview of selected studies.

Category	Country	Year	Author
Lost economic output	U.K.	2005	Dolan <i>et al.</i> 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005
	Global	2013	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2013
Intangibles, physical, and emotional impact	U.K.	2009 [2004]	Dolan <i>et al.</i> 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Walby 2004; Walby 2009
Second-generation costs	South Africa	2017	Fang <i>et al.</i> 2017

Source: Own representation.

However, it should be noted that the listed studies may only display good results for these specific cost classes and may have weaknesses for others. For example, the Home Office Online Report [HOOR] by Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 which uses the findings of Dolan *et al.* 2005. Walby and Allen 2004 was considered most suitable for calculating the cost category of the intangibles but may be unsuitable for other cost classes. Nevertheless, this more detailed step should lead to a deeper understanding of these three critical category cost-shares to further narrow down the hypothesis.

Table 4.5 presents the detailed sub-results of the selected studies on the lost economic output, intangibles, physical, and emotional impact, and second-generation costs.

Table 4.5.: Overview of the KPMG study results: details.

Country	Year	Author	Category of cost	Prevalence [%]	GDP share [%]
			Lost output		
			Health		
			Legal		
			Social welfare		
			Personal		
			Special services		
			Intangibles		
			Second-generation		
			Other		
U.K.	2009	Walby 2009	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ - ✓ ✓ - -	0.60	1.00
Vietnam	2013	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2013	✓ - - - - - - -	27.00	1.60 ^a
				(Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2013, p. 39)	
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ - ✓ -	18.00	3.93
South Africa	2017	Fang <i>et al.</i> 2017	- - - - - - ✓ -	7	4.30

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Reflecting only on these four studies, it becomes evident how significant any comprehensive methodology increases the overall GDP result.

1. The Walby 2009 study does not compute around 33 per cent of all cost categories, has a relatively low prevalence ratio of 0.60 per cent, but still computes a relatively high GDP proportion of one per cent (Walby 2009).
2. The Duvvury *et al.* 2013 study on Vietnam solely reflects the lost economic output category. Still, the study's 1.60 per cent GDP ratio already amounts to nearly 80 per cent of Siddique's result, which computes all categories. Duvvury *et al.* 2013 exhibit an analytical approach to estimate losses in productivity based on national economic sector data.
3. Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 compute the highest GDP cost-share of around four per cent, however, grounded in one of the lowest prevalence ratios [18 per cent] for the context of developing and emerging countries. This is startling since the paper does not reflect on intangibles, which tend to significantly increase the cost.⁸ However, Ribero and Sánchez's method for the other categories is comprehensive. For instance, the paper integrates second-generation data extensively, and the scholars include cost deriving from problems with childbirth, miscarriages, severe abuse of minors, or children's health problems. Further, Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 utilise a holistic and precise method to measure the lost economic output. The cost-share derived from such losses is around 1.90 per cent of the total 3.93 per cent GDP cost-share (Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 p. 28).
4. The South African Fang *et al.* 2017 study only calculates the costs for children but estimates the highest GDP proportion at 4.30 per cent of GDP. Further, Fang's results are more than four times higher than those of the Walby 2009 paper. This indicates how holistic the used DALY method is and shows again how much the comprehensiveness of an approach alters the final output.

The KPMG South Africa 2014 study will be analysed in more detail to narrow down the possible cost range further. In Chapter 3, the study was briefly discussed already, but for the sake of the hypothesis construction, a more comprehensive examination is carried out in Section 4.2.3

4.2.3. 2014 KPMG study

In order to introduce this chapter, Table 4.6 presents a review of the main aspects and results of the 2014 KPMG study's findings.

⁶The study estimates the lost economic output in Vietnam for 2011. The total production loss represents 1.60 per cent of the 2011 GDP in Vietnam (Duvvury *et al.* 2013, p. 36).

⁷The Fang *et al.* 2017 study calculates the costs for children only. It estimates the economic burden of violence against children in South Africa in general and is not limited to GBV cases only.

⁸See, for instance, Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996

Table 4.6.: Overview of the KPMG study results: summary.

Country	Year	Author	Category	Prevalence [%]	GDP share [%]
			Economic output		
			Health		
			Legal		
			Social welfare		
			Personal		
			Special services		
			Intangibles		
			Second-generation		
			Other		
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa	2014	20.00–30.00 ⁹	0.90–1.30 ¹⁰

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

The KPMG South Africa 2014 study “Too costly to ignore – the economic impact of Gender-Based Violence in South Africa” computes based on a high prevalence ratio of 20 to 30 per cent a relatively low GDP cost-share of 0.90–1.30 per cent. The prevalence is based on GBV incidences within the last 12 months and includes women aged 15 years and older (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 25). Due to a lack of comprehensive data, the paper uses a considerable number of assumptions to estimate losses. All findings must, therefore, be considered conditional and sometimes even speculative. Further, the report does not include the second-generation costs, which are usually cost-intensive. Consequently, this study’s estimates may be higher due to such methodical differences than those of the KPMG report.

Additionally, each cost class has certain inconsistencies and lacks, and a review of such for each cost category is given in the next paragraphs, starting with the lost economic output.

Lost economic output

The KPMG South Africa 2014 report bases its lost economic output calculation on, among other things, the following data surveyed in the U.K. In detail, the paper states: “It is assumed that there are 20 working days per month and that women who experience GBV are absent from their work for an average of five days per year.” However, firstly, the primary literature cannot be found within the paper’s index (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 29); hence, no deeper assessment was possible¹¹. Secondly, there is no argumentation on how the U.K. data fit into

⁹The costing is based on a prevalence ratio of 20.00 to 30.00 per cent (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 39 f.) within a given year (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 2). The official U.N. GBV prevalence data was not available at the point of research. Thus, the KPMG results were used.

¹⁰The economic loss was between R 28.4 billion and R 42.4 billion from 2012 to 2013 (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 2). The South African GDP, in the current LCU, in 2012 was R 3.254 trillion [in detail, R 3,254,000,000,000], according to World Bank 2018a data. The paper computes an overall GDP cost-share of 0.90 to 1.30 per cent (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 28 f.).

¹¹The source indicated: <http://caadv.org.uk/> leads to the following content: Web Hosting Unlimited web hosting packed full of great hosting features, from only £ 2.49 per month. Find out more about our unlimited web hosting.

the South African cultural context and how they were/can be possibly transferred. Thirdly, there is no analysis regarding the specific types of injuries resulting from GBV. The author's team states, "It is likely that survivors are absent from work on average for more than five days per year in South Africa, but we do not have data to support this" (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 38). Dolan *et al.* 2005, Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 provide detailed probabilities of particular adverse states associated with GBV and their recovery time. Consequently, the KPMG South Africa 2014 study is likely to underestimate the lost economic output for South Africa.

Health service costs

The Health costs derive from the Dalal and Dawad 2011¹² study that found the average price per incident of violence in their sample to be R 7,435.¹³ However, the Medical Research Council in South Africa found that medical costs for rape amounted to R 6,320 per case in 2006 already (Christofides *et al.* 2006,¹⁴ which are R 13,033 in 2018 figures. That is nearly double the estimated cost of the Dalal and Dawad 2011 study. Consequently, the primary data chosen display a significant underestimation of actual expenses. Further, a distinction between different types of offences, such as homicide, sexual violence, or common assault, was not conducted in the KPMG South Africa 2014 paper. This is an issue, as health treatments for sexual abuse are higher than for common assaults. See, for example, the research of Dolan *et al.* 2005, Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, or Walby 2004. Thus, KPMG's health service cost calculations may estimate only a fraction of the actual costs that occurred.

Legal costs

The KPMG South Africa 2014 study does not calculate the legal spending of individuals (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 29), and further legal aid spending is not computed under government expenses either (KPMG South Africa 2014, p. 33).¹⁵

Social welfare expenses

The paper's estimations do not include transfer costs, such as social welfare payments among others, (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 37) and thus only computes a part of the actual GDP cost-share. Further, the report leaves out expenses for activities carried out under, for instance, the Ministries of Gender and Health or the respective Social Security, Power Eradication and Social Welfare departments.

¹²Dalal and Dawad 2011 have studied 261 women who have sought help from a community health centre in Chatsworth in South Africa. They found that survivors' average monthly income was R 3,400, and the average price per incident was R 4,875.

¹³The Dalal and Dawad 2011 study calculates R 4,875 per individual survivor in 2011, which is R 7,435 in 2018 figures (World Bank 2016).

¹⁴The Christofides *et al.* 2006 study lists costs of R 6,320 per individual for 2006, which was R 13,033 in 2018 (World Bank 2016).

¹⁵The Justice and Constitutional Development category includes only the cost of employing staff, funding research, targeted programmes, the establishment of 42 sexual offences courts, and the maintenance of the National Register of Sexual Offenders (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 33).

In detail, the KPMG South Africa [2014](#) paper did not fully consider the other social welfare payments provided under various associated national bodies. Such as the Ministry of Gender, including their community empowerment activities or childcare protection services; the Ministry of Health, with their Emergency relief support or specific disease programmes; the Social Security Commission that provides sick leave and death benefits; or the Poverty Eradication and Social Welfare department that delivers social assistance or food provisions to vulnerable individuals. Consequently, this paper's estimated GDP cost-proportion for Namibia is envisaged to be higher.

Personal costs

The KPMG study includes in its calculations the consumption costs of the following three aspects:

1. logistical cost related to seeking help, such as transport or phone calls;
2. cost of services, including medical expenses or counselling expenses;
3. losses due to relocation.

Nonetheless, personal cost estimations usually include private legal fees, property damages, or repossession losses as well [16](#) which the KPMG South Africa [2014](#) research does not integrate. Especially the personal legal expenses tend to increase the total cost-share (Walby and Olive [2014](#)).

This research aims to integrate such costs; thus, again, the estimated losses are envisaged to be higher than the KPMG study's findings.

Special service costs [17](#)

The special services split into the costs that occurred to government and civil society. KPMG South Africa [2014](#) includes government expenses, such as costs for providing GBV related services. Data from the KPMG study stems from surveys sent to the relevant government departments (KPMG South Africa [2014](#) p. 32). The KPMG South Africa [2014](#) p. 38 report states that "Budgets to implement GBV programmes are not ring-fenced and as such are unidentifiable in national expenditure estimates." However, as a measure of reproducibility and control mechanism, the usage of public government spending data for the relevant fiscal year may be more appropriate. It would serve as an additional controlling indicator next to the utilisation of qualitative interviews. Further, the report does not cover a comprehensive estimate of provincial and local GBV expenditures. The cost of correctional services and expenses of the Department of Basic Education is not included either.

KPMG South Africa [2014](#) states that civil society provides around 60 per cent of all social services to women and children in South Africa. The paper includes expenses for shelters and support services, like counselling programmes. The estimates are derived from cost-per-client data, which was multiplied by the number of customers. In detail, the applied unit value

¹⁶See Chapter [3](#)

¹⁷In this study, the calculations for special service costs are integrated under social welfare costs.

is R1,200, which derives from a per client figures provided by the NGO Rape Crisis. The KPMG paper assumes that around 19 per cent of survivors sought services from a Civil Society Organization [CSO]. This premise is derived from the study of Jewkes *et al.*, 2010, who estimated this ratio for the Gauteng region in South Africa. Nonetheless, the study's final bibliography does not list the reference of Jewkes *et al.*, 2010, however. Hence, it cannot be determined which exact publication of Jewkes was used (KPMG South Africa 2014, p. 34). Further, KPMG South Africa 2014 states that data is obtained from the Gauteng region only. However, an examination of relevant NGO's national budgets on their GBV activities for the applicable fiscal year may provide more accurate and holistic findings.

Moreover, according to the South African Medical Research Council, the treatment costs of a single rape case, including medical therapy provided only on that particular day, without trauma or HIV follow-up support, accounted for R6,320 in 2006 already (Christofides *et al.* 2006). Consequently, the applied unit cost figure of R1,200 in 2014 states a significant underestimation of expenses for this context and should have been set into comparison with other findings. Further, the report does not consider the spending of international NGOs and development aid agencies (KPMG South Africa 2014, p. 38), as from the U.N. or European aid agencies, which usually contribute significant financial aid (Council of Europe 2011).

The next paragraph outlines the paper's estimates on the physical and emotional impact.

intangibles, physical, and emotional impact

The KPMG paper states that the standard practice in estimating the economic costs of morbidity and mortality resulting from disease is to use of the QALY or DALY approach. However, due to a lack of data, the KPMG model does not consider the Intangible losses resulting from Years Lived With disability [YLD] (KPMG South Africa 2014, p. 30, 37). However, the YLD, as a measure of indirect costs from suffering and pain, resemble a significant portion of the DALY measure. The KPMG study thereby omits a high proportion of expenses.

Summary

The KPMG assessments should be considered only a partial or minimum estimate of the actual costs, as it first does not reflect all relevant cost categories. Secondly, according to the report, there is no national prevalence ratio available for South Africa. Third, GBV government spending calculations are mainly based on qualitative interview data only. Fourth, there are no holistic estimates of Intangible losses derived from pain and suffering, which tend to increase the total expenses significantly. Fifth, second-generational costs are not included too (KPMG South Africa 2014, p. 2-25). In summary, Table 4.7 reflects the cost classes for which a likely underestimation of expenses has occurred.

Due to these methodological shortcomings, it is assumed that the cost-share of this study is higher than that of the KPMG South Africa 2014 report with a GDP share of 0.90 to 1.30 per cent.

In summary, the level of detail of the method showed the most significant impact on the results, according to research, and hence, tends to be more important than the holistic calculation of all cost categories. Based on these findings, Section 4.3 presents the hypothesis established.

Table 4.7.: Overview of the KPMG study results: shortcomings.

Category	KPMG Study
Lost economic output, for men and women	Underestimation.
Health service costs [Homicide, Wounding, Sexual offences, Common Assault]	Underestimation.
Legal costs [government, NGOs]	Underestimation.
Social welfare costs [government, NGOs]	Underestimation.
Personal costs	Underestimation.
Special service cost [government, NGOs]	Underestimation.
Intangibles, physical, and emotional impact [QALYs for Wounding, Sexual offences, Common Assault]	Underestimation.
Second-generation costs	Not included (KPMG South Africa 2014, p. 25).

Source: Own representation.

4.3. This dissertation's hypothesis

The following four points present the construction of the hypothesis grounded in the findings of the previous subsections.

1. Numerous international studies on the economic impact of GBV over the past 20 years have shown that violence against women has a significant negative impact on the economy's well-being of a country. [See, for instance, Agüero 2013; Brand and Price 2000; Dalal and Dawad 2011; Day, McKenna, and Bowlus 2005; Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005]. Some of the most significant studies in the developing and emerging countries estimate a GDP cost-share of between 0.23–3.93 per cent [See Table 4.8].

Table 4.8.: Overview of GBV prevalence and GDP share: developing countries.

	Prevalence [%]	GDP share [%]
Developing and emerging economies	10.00–30.00	0.23–3.93

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Nonetheless, the outcomes are likely to represent an underestimation of costs, as most literature applies a conservative method and as there is a considerable under-reporting of violence in general (Jewkes and Abrahams 2002).

2. When examining research on the SADC region specifically, it is found that the South African culture of violence is similar to the Namibian one (Abrahams *et al.* 2008; Bradshaw *et al.* 2003; Christofides *et al.* 2006; Dalal and Dawad 2011; Dunkle *et al.* 2004). The KPMG's GDP cost-share for South Africa is at 0.90–1.30 per cent (KPMG South Africa 2014, p. 2) [see Table 4.9].

Table 4.9.: Overview of GBV prevalence and GDP share: KPMG study.

	Prevalence [%]	GDP share [%]
South Africa (KPMG South Africa 2014)	20.00–30.00 ¹⁸	0.90–1.30 ¹⁹

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

However, KPMG South Africa 2014 lacks in its methodical stringency and quality of primary data. In contrast, this study intends to use a different methodical set-up²⁰ and database. Hence, this paper is likely to exceed the GDP share of KPMG South Africa 2014.

3. When only looking into research that fulfilled the eligibility criteria that was methodically considered to be appropriate, and that has computed all seven categories²¹ it becomes evident that minor methodical differences in how to determine the three cost categories of lost economic output, intangibles, and second-generation have led to significant deviations in the overall cost output. These variations even outweigh the difference in leaving out other cost classes. For instance, although the displayed Siddique 2011 study on Bangladesh [see Table 4.10] computes all cost groups, its applied method for those three cost classes is rather imprecise. Hence, its GDP cost-share is even smaller compared to such papers that do not cover all cost categories.

Table 4.10.: Overview of GBV prevalence and GDP share: Siddique 2011 study.

	Prevalence [%]	GDP share [%]
Developing economies ²²	24.00	2.10

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

4. When examining the four studies that best compute the lost economic output, intangibles, and second-generation costs, namely Walby 2009, Duvvury *et al.* 2013, Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004, and Fang *et al.* 2017, the following becomes evident:
 - a) Walby 2009 computations are based on a prevalence ratio of 0.60 per cent and a GDP share of one per cent. If the prevalence were the same as in Namibia with 17.50 per cent, the new GDP share would increase to hypothetically 27 per cent.

¹⁸The estimates are grounded in a prevalence ratio of 20 to 30 per cent (KPMG South Africa 2014, p. 39 f.) within a given year (KPMG South Africa 2014, p. 2). The official U.N. GBV prevalence data was not available at the point of research (UN Women 2019e). Thus, the KPMG figures are used, although they only reflect a broad scope.

¹⁹The economic loss of GBV is between R 28.4 billion and R 42.4 billion for the year 2012 to 2013 (KPMG South Africa 2014, p. 2). According to the World Bank 2018a, the South African GDP, in current Local Currency Units [LCU], in 2012 was R 3.254 trillion [in detail, R 3,254,000,000,000]. The paper states the overall computed GDP share with 0.90 to 1.30 per cent (KPMG South Africa 2014, p. 28 f.).

²⁰See Chapter 5.

²¹See Section 3.4.

²²Table 4.10 reflects the outcome of the Siddique 2011 paper on Bangladesh, as it was the only one that fulfilled the narrowed criteria.

-
- b) Duvvury *et al.* [2013] compute a 1.60 per cent GDP ratio solely on the lost economic output category. While theoretically assuming that each of the other seven categories would have half the share each, namely costs of 0.80 per cent, the new GDP share would be 7.20 per cent.
 - c) Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004] calculate a 3.93 per cent ratio. Still, the authors leave out the intangibles. Such have contributed to a significant cost rise and have, in certain studies, increased the overall cost by over 400 per cent. See Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996]. A new GDP share that theoretically includes the intangibles would amount moderately to approximately five to six per cent.
 - d) Fang *et al.* [2017] compute only one category, namely the second-generation cost, in very much detail and nevertheless estimates a GDP share of 4.30 per cent. While theoretically assuming that the remainder of the seven categories has only ten per cent of this share, namely 0.43 each, the new GDP share would likely be 7.31 per cent.

Hence, based on the previous findings and by applying a formal, conservative cost-estimation model appropriate for the Namibian context that will yield relevant theoretical predictions, the following hypothesis shall be tested:

The cost of Gender-Based Violence [GBV], including second-generation losses, is projected to be around six per cent, and excluding second-generation costs; it is likely to be approximately four per cent of Namibia's 2018 national GDP.

4.4. Conclusion

First, all the studies included in this literature review were examined for their results. To narrow the hypothesis in more detail, Section [4.2.1] only examined literature covering all cost categories. This created an improved understanding of the actual outcome. In order to further narrow the hypothesis, only the studies that calculate the classes of lost economic output, intangibles, physical, and emotional impact and second-generation costs were analysed. Since these categories make up a significant part of the overall result, the step of evaluating this individual data was of enormous importance. In a third step, the KPMG South Africa [2014] study was analysed in more detail. It was at the point of research the only available publication in the regional scope of Southern Africa. The final hypothesis was created from these evaluations that the cost of Gender-Based Violence [GBV], including second-generation losses, is envisaged to be around six per cent, and excluding second-generation costs; it is likely to be about four per cent of Namibia's 2018 national GDP.

5. Methods

5.1. Introduction

Chapter 5 describes the methods used in this study. The applied methods differentiate for the various cost classes. In summary, these are:

1. lost economic output and health service costs: the health-state outcome model,
2. legal costs, social welfare, and special service costs: the budget-share approach,
3. personal costs: the unit-cost approach,
4. intangibles, physical, and emotional impact: the QALY-loss-based WTP approach,
5. second-generation costs: the disability-adjusted life years [DALYs] approach.

Chapter 5 describes the different methods used for the cost classes in detail. Each subchapter summarises the method, with its advantages and disadvantages as well as its applicability for this case study. Section 5.2 describes the method used for the lost economic output and health service costs. The health-state outcome approach is based on the 2005 British Home Office Online Report [HOOR] by Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005. The method is very robust, is used in various renowned studies, and has little data requirement. Section 5.3 analyses the budget-share approach used for the cost categories legal costs, social welfare costs, and special service costs. Top-down analysis is carried out in this approach, and the total budget for a specific cost type is analysed. The unit cost method is applied in the cost category of personal costs.

In contrast to the budget-share model, it uses a bottom-up approach. The method is briefly outlined, its advantages and disadvantages are analysed, and the area of application for this case study is discussed. Section 5.5 describes the applied method for the cost category of the intangibles, physical, and emotional impact. The technique used for this category is the QALY-loss-based WTP approach. This approach has been used in renowned studies for this cost class. The description of the method is divided into two parts; first, the QALY model, and in a second step, the WTP model with its advantages and disadvantages are described. The estimated GBV-QALY values are also presented. Section 5.6 introduces the selected model for the second-generation costs. The disability-adjusted life year, called DALYs, are discussed for this category, and the structure of the model is summarised. Health-adjusted life years, the HALY indicators that serve as the basis for the method are presented in more detail. The principle is also analysed based on which criteria the individual health status is rated zero or one. This is followed by a summary of the advantages and disadvantages of the model and its application to the scope of this study.

5.2. Lost economic output and health service costs: health-state approach

Section 5.2 reflects on the health-state approach developed by Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 which was identified as best to calculate both the lost economic output and the health service costs.

Table 5.1.: Best approach to calculate the lost economic output and health service costs.

Country	Year	Author	Reason	Scope
U.K.	2005	Dolan <i>et al.</i> 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Walby and Allen 2004	Is transferable, and has despite minor data requirements and high accuracy	Lost economic output, health service costs

Source: Own representation.

As already discussed, the British Home Office Online Report [HOOR] by Walby and Allen 2004 computes its lost economic output based on this approach. The underpinning research is grounded in longitudinal surveys on the actual time loss or utilisation of health facilities, spanning over four years after the initial injury has occurred.

Approach

Essential elements are health state outcomes derived from survivors' statements of injuries (Walby and Allen 2004). An average value of the lost economic output for each violent crime category is formulated from simulated statistical probability, modelling the prevalence of psychological and physical health injuries and their corresponding work-time loss. As displayed in Table 5.2 a statistical prevalence probability is assigned to each physical state. According to Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 34, for instance, due to rape, 2.50 per cent of women endure an abortion, or in the case of common assault, 13.75 per cent suffer from an acute stress disorder. Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 updated the Home Office Online Report [HOOR] by Walby and Allen 2004, concerning the frequency of different PTSDs, which were added to the crime categories of sexual assault or wounding, respectively. Probabilities of psychological harm were added due to its significant losses in more detail in the crime class of rape too¹.

As demonstrated in Table 5.3, each physical injury element is associated with an average value of lost economic output, defined in days related to the different types of violent crimes, such as wounding, rape, or sexual assault (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 p. 38).

As indicated in Table 5.3, the presumable health losses constitute the basis for the computation of the average health care treatment expenses for various kinds of offences. Later, they are set to the national GDP per capita data for the respective time frame. In sum, the approach shows the following advantages and disadvantages:

¹For the transferability of the approach to Namibia, see Chapter 6

Table 5.2.: Prevalences of adverse health states.

Health states	Prevalence of health state by type of crime			
	Wounding	Common assault	Rape	Sexual assault
Physical health				
Broken bones	0.0801	0.0025	0.0370	0.0070
Minor bruises or a black eye	0.2754	0.3400	0.1920	0.0360
Chipped teeth	0.0276	–	–	–
Abortion	–	–	0.025	–
<i>etc.</i>				
Psychological health				
Acute stress disorder	0.5500	0.1375	1.0000	1.0000
Suicide	–	–	0.0010	–
Anxiety	–	–	0.0500	–
<i>etc.</i>				

Source: Own representation based on Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#) p. 34.

Table 5.3.: Number of working days lost as a result of decreased health status.

Health states	Working days lost as a result		
	Total discounted duration [days]	Prevalence [%]	Time off work [days]
Physical health			
Broken bones	42	75	31
Minor bruises or black eye	10	25	3
Chipped teeth	7	25	2
Abortion	7	100	7
<i>etc.</i>	<i>etc.</i>	<i>etc.</i>	<i>etc.</i>
Psychological health			
Acute stress disorder	28	75	21
Suicide	6.421	100	6.421
Anxiety	1.037	100	1.037
<i>etc.</i>	<i>etc.</i>	<i>etc.</i>	<i>etc.</i>

Source: Own representation based on Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#) p. 38.

Advantages

The significant benefits are:

1. The method is robust, and besides, it is internationally applicable. The only information required is incident-level data, such as police or crime statistics that are broken down by type of violence, and an appropriate set of multipliers to adjust police records, as GBV is one of the most underreported crimes (Duvvury *et al.* [2013](#)).
2. The focus lies in the period of lost productivity. It does not matter whether this time is actual time-off-work. Hence, it treats paid and unpaid productivity losses equally and avoids discrimination against more vulnerable social groups.
3. It manages losses from unpaid employment, self-employment, and paid employment equally, as it uses the average GDP per capita income as a multiplier. Hence, it does

-
- not discriminate against the unemployed or survivors working for none or low salary, as those, for instance, who are stay-at-homes or who are performing household chores only.
4. Probabilities are obtained from actual GBV survivors' reporting and can be calculated for both men and women.
 5. The approach also accounts for losses due to mental illness, such as burnout or anxiety, for various crime categories, including wounding, sexual assault, or rape. For the crime type of rape, additional psychological losses resulting from drug abuse, depression, or anxiety are calculated.
 6. Another problem that is solved is the calculation of multipliers based on police records to produce realistic cost estimates. As already stressed in the introduction, GBV, including rape, is globally one of the most underreported crimes (Duvvury *et al.* 2013). Consequently, to base calculations on police statistics only would lead to a significant underestimation. For instance, according to Rennison 2002, p. 2, 63 per cent of sexual assault cases were not reported to the U.S. police in the period of 1992–2000. The same applies to the Namibian scenario, as women often withdraw their GBV cases or do not report them at all. [See, for instance, the article “Police urge women not to withdraw violence cases” (The Namibian 2017)]. In this regard, an appropriate approach to compute multipliers has been developed by Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005. Based on police records and comparable subsets, see, for instance, Mirrlees-Black *et al.* 1998, Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 23 calculate a more realistic volume of offences to offset underreporting and case withdrawing.

In summary, the approach is one of the most holistic currently available; its unit values are transferable, it requires little data, and still displays high elaborateness (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 39). Nonetheless, the following disadvantages have to be mentioned.

Disadvantages

The disadvantages are that:

1. On the one hand, the approach may underestimate the costs as it considers one treatment cycle only (Walby and Olive 2014). On the other hand, there may be an overestimation of expenses for the treatment of minor injuries, as individual survivors may self-manage them alone, return more quickly to work, or do not show absence at all (Dolan *et al.* 2005).
2. The approach does not account for the different probabilities of victimisation. It assumes that all members of society are at equal risk of being subjected to GBV related crimes. However, international research (Access Economics 2004a; Council of Europe 2011; Day, McKenna, and Bowlus 2005; Duvvury *et al.* 2013) suggests that the risk varies significantly by location, age, or gender.²
3. The lost workdays and absenteeism are set in relation to the national GDP per capita. However, there are regional differences in the per capita data. For instance, the British Statistical Bureau states that the national U.K. GDP per capita differs from the local

²For instance, the Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 39 paper found that an adult in the area of London has a probability of 7.70 per cent of being a survivor of specific crimes. However, an adult from the Yorkshire or the Humber region has only a 5.60 per cent possibility.

levels. In consequence, depending on the scale of regional economic differences, it may introduce bias into the assessment (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 39). Further, GDP per capita data vary among gender. For instance, the British New Earnings Survey finds that full-time male workers earned, on average, almost a third more than full-time female workers in the U.K. in 2002 (Office For National Statistics 2003). Cross-national research depicts the same tendency and states that male workers' earnings tend to be higher than those of their female counterparts (Bott, Morrison, and Ellsberg 2005; Day 1995; Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2013; Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016). Hence, the average or national GDP per capita may not be the best indicator to compute the lost economic output. Nonetheless, the alternative would be to tailor costing to specific characteristics such as the survivor's residence or sex. Although that may be justified theoretically from an economic point of view, the outcome may be that crime prevention is focused on regions with higher per capita income levels or urban areas with different ethnic groups that depict higher income levels. It would value least the prevention of crimes against those already the most disadvantaged, such as the unemployed, the disabled, or minors. It would have a politically unacceptable impact and discourage socially fair policy-making (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 39).

In brief, the limitations presented in the papers of Dolan *et al.* 2005, Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 are acknowledged. However, irrespective of its flaws, the approach is internationally-backed, and after having examined all available literature, the approach seems to be currently the most appropriate for this paper's context.

Scope of this study

In summary, the health-state approach is:

1. A robust method that is recommended in different distinct papers (Walby and Olive 2014) and can be used to calculate the lost economic output and health service costs, respectively (Dolan *et al.* 2005).
2. A procedure with little data requirement and is transferable to other regional scopes, especially to developing and emerging countries, which are usually characterised by a scarcity of high-quality datasets (Duvvury *et al.* 2013; KPMG South Africa 2014).

5.3. Legal, social welfare, and special service costs: budget-share approach

Section 5.3 exhibits the budget-share approach, or also called proportional expenditure, which was recognised as one of the best methods currently available to calculate legal, social welfare, including special service costs.

Approach

The method is utilised within various international literature to compute services or social spending associated with GBV (Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010; Institute for Women of Andalusia 2003; Walby 2004; Walby 2009). In summary, the approach applies the following steps:

1. The definition of an overall budget for social welfare and special services offered to GBV complainants disaggregated by their age and respective reference year(s).
2. The calculation of the total number of GBV beneficiaries is conducted based on the utilisation ratios of GBV survivors.
3. The computation of the total social welfare payments for the population of GBV survivors [per year grounded in a standard distribution across age groups] through the multiplication of this ratio to the overall budget (Walby and Olive 2014).

In this regard, Table 5.4 provides an overview of possible appropriate data sources.

Table 5.4.: Budget-share approach to calculate the civil justice costs.

Budget area	Data source	Share
Civil representation	Administrative data, annual financial statements or budgets	Administrative and government records and NGO data on the proportion of GBV survivors to estimate the utilised share of services.
Legal support		
Public proceedings		
<i>etc.</i>	<i>etc.</i>	<i>etc.</i>

Source: Own representation based on Walby and Olive 2014

Based on Table 5.4 Walby describes in her research, the calculation of the overall budget costs of, for instance, child protection services in the following manner:

1. Firstly, the calculation of the sum of the costs of, e.g. children's social care, family support services, or foster care.
2. Secondly, the multiplication of this sum with the proportion of children referred because of abuse or neglect.
3. Thirdly, the multiplication of this figure by the proportion of GBV overlap (Envall and Eriksson 2006 Heiskanen and Piispa 2001 Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010).

In conclusion, the legal and social welfare costs dedicated to GBV are computed (Walby and Olive 2014 p. 77). The following paragraph presents the associated advantages and disadvantages.

Advantages

The comparative budget-share approach has the following benefits:

1. Robustness: government and service provider budgets usually reflect the reality of spending. In combination with national estimates or service data on the proportion of individuals that have utilised such assistance, the assessments are conducted on a robust foundation.
2. Simplicity: information is very likely to be available and easy to access.
3. Replicability and feasibility of data: however, in some instances, it is difficult to define specific cohorts, for example, if abused children simultaneously suffer from a DV/GBV

background (Envall and Eriksson 2006; Heiskanen and Piispa 2001; Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010³). DV technically refers to any violent act perpetrated by a family member against another one. Nonetheless, this definition is minimal and reduces the circle only to a small sub-group of survivors (Duvvury *et al.* 2013). However, if children suffer from abuse in homes where GBV occurs, then they are subjected to violence in a domestic setting, from which they cannot merely escape. Thus, the notion of DV is added when discussing and computing the costs of children. Nevertheless, in most situations, it is feasible to determine the proportions of the overall budget dedicated to DV and GBV (Walby and Olive 2014, p. 76).

Disadvantages

The approach is associated with the shortcoming of subjectivity, as identifying suitable activities within national budgets is, to a certain degree, a subjective matter of the respective scholar. Further, costing is not obtained from total incidents, and proxy multipliers are applied if the exact number of adult survivors or children who have a DV/GBV background is not available (Envall and Eriksson 2006).

Scope of this study

In a nutshell, due to its robustness, simplicity, and feasibility, the method fits the scope of this study and the Namibian context.

Section 5.4 will present the unit-cost approach used to estimate the personal costs (Access Economics 2004a; Henderson 2000; Walby and Olive 2014; Zhang *et al.* 2012).

5.4. Personal costs: unit-cost approach

The unit-cost approach usually breaks the overall expenditure incurred by a single entity into one unit of spending. Unit costs include all fixed costs, mainly investments to run infrastructure and all variable costs, such as attorney per hour fees, among others (Investopedia 2018).

Approach

In summary, there are two sets of information required to apply the model, first unit costs and second multiplier data (Walby and Olive 2014, p. 76). Based on the literature review, the following three-step strategy is applied in the literature to calculate such (Day, McKenna, and Bowlus 2005). For instance, to compute the overall cost of relocation:

1. The first step is to calculate the standard expenses for an average relocation, for example, of a three-bedroom apartment for three household members. National statistics or surveys usually contain such data. The other option is qualitative surveys with specific service providers, such as relocation companies.

³When examining the costs for children, the term DV is utilised as well, as explained in Chapter 2

2. The second step is the estimation of relevant case numbers. In this example, the number of overall relocations per year is multiplied by the national GBV prevalence.
3. The third step is to multiply all relevant case numbers by their unit cost per year (UNFPA Ukraine 2017).

Table 5.5 provides an overview of such unit cost and multiplier data sources.

Table 5.5.: Overview of unit costs and multiplier data sources for the estimation of personal costs.

Unit cost	Data source	Multiplier	Data sources
Per divorce	Government budgets, spendings on legal and civil proceedings, financial statements of social welfare and special service provider, annual reports of CSOs and NGOs.	The first option is the number of citizens exposed to GBV reporting cases of divorce, injunction, or property damage per annum. The second option is the multiplication of the listed case numbers set in relation to the respective GBV prevalence.	Census data in national population surveys or proportions in large-scale GBV studies.
Per repossession			
Per property damage			
<i>etc.</i>	<i>etc.</i>	<i>etc.</i>	<i>etc.</i>

Source: Own representation.

In brief, the advantages and disadvantages relevant to this study can be summarised as the following:

Advantages

1. Unit costs and their respective multiplier data contribute to higher comparability of findings (Walby and Olive 2014 p. 82).
2. The model has the potential to deliver a highly accurate outcome (UNFPA Ukraine 2017), as weighted low-level unit cost data produce a more precise estimate than high-level spending data (Walby and Olive 2014 p. 57).

Disadvantages

1. In the case of the unavailability of detailed and robust administrative data, unit costs cannot be calculated. In such a situation, the budget-share approach serves to be a better option (Walby and Olive 2014 p. 57). Even in some European research, unit costs and their respective multiplier data were not always available or straightforward to compute (UNFPA Ukraine 2017).
2. Unit costs may isolate expenditures from the remainder of the budget and thus can contribute to an underestimation. For instance, legal aid spending on divorces resulting from GBV is listed in different budgets, such as public legal assistance records or other sources, like in-kind contributions from NGOs who then generate funding from national institutions, local authorities, or the international community (Walby and Olive 2014 p. 76), and it is important to take all such income and budget streams fully into consideration.

Further, identifying suitable activities within the budget is a subjective matter of the respective scholar and may lead to falsification.

Scope of this study

In general, the unit cost model was found to generate estimations that are both simplistic and replicable. Nonetheless, the model's feasibility depends upon the availability and quality of public and special service provider data.

In order to continue, Section 5.5 outlines the QALY-WTP approach used to compute the intangibles.

5.5. Intangibles: QALY-loss-based WTP approach

The QALY health losses, combined with the WTP model employed by Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Walby 2004 was identified as the most appropriate to compute the intangibles losses.⁴

Both the QALY and WTP methods are assessed in the next paragraph.

QALY approach

The QALY approach is a novel method to conduct GBV costing. It is utilised to compute the Physical and Emotional impact of GBV. The British researcher Dolan *et al.*; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns modelled it based on violent crimes reported in the Crime Survey for England and Wales. Since the Crime Survey did not reflect on psychological harm, Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 added psychological trauma outcomes to such particular crime types.

QALYs were developed in the late 1960s to analyse the cost-effectiveness of clinical interventions. So far, the approach has been utilised to calculate the direct Intangible costs of long-term pain and disease. It has been applied to both developed and developing countries (Duvvury *et al.* 2013).

The approach computes the number of years lived and the Quality of Life achieved through a specific set of interventions (Gold, Stevenson, and Fryback 2002). In the context of restricted resources, QALYs give insights on cost-utilities of treatment and explicitly state its potential outcome on the Quality of Life concerning the particular investments that have been made. In summary, QALYs generate an outlook on how the quality of an individual's life is enhanced through specific treatment or interventions (Lajoie 2015).

As said, QALYs usually are utilised to analyse the effectiveness of clinical interventions, such as the usefulness of cancer treatments. For the area of GBV, Quality of Life-enhancement

⁴For more information, read Section 3.4.2

arises from programmes, such as support or prevention measures, or the absence of GBV in total. QALYs use the utility weights zero and one. Zero represents death, and one reflects a year of perfect health without injury, disease, or violence. Such utility values are derived from two sources. First, the individual patient’s opinion on his or her respective health state, which is defined as patient weights. Secondly, from third-party judgments, including health professionals and qualified researchers, which are also described as community weights (Gold, Stevenson, and Fryback 2002). The actual unit value originates from time trade-off or standard gambling techniques. The standard gamble approach, for instance, asks a sample group to generate health state values by specifying how much they are willing to sacrifice to shift a poor into a perfect health state. If the life year is not spent in an ideal health condition, for instance, through chronic pain, a value between zero and one will be assigned. In general, the scoring acknowledges both the physical and psychosocial aspects of a disease. In sum, it accounts for the following five dimensions: first mobility, second pain or discomfort, third self-care, fourth anxiety or depression, and fifth general liveliness (Lajoie 2015).

Bolling, Mattinson, and Myhill 2002; Budd *et al.* 2000; Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 have collected relevant primary data. The research uses quality adjustment weights correlated to adverse physical health states derived from the disability measurements of the Global Burden of Disease survey (Murray and Lopez 1996 Tab. 4.4). The study displays the data of 32 injuries, including their disability weights and duration, based on the findings from the International Classification of Disease analysis. To be specific, disability weights for psychological harm are obtained partly from computations of the Global Burden of Disease study and partly from the Dutch National Burden of Disease report (Stouthard *et al.* 1997). Where no disability weights were available, among other things, for miscarriage and abortion, scholars made assumptions (Dolan 1997). Further, particular QALY data, like the one for rape and sexual assault, have been altered to fit the Namibian context, such as the HIV ratio, which was adjusted to the local prevalence, for instance.

Specific GBV patterns are observed worldwide to be similar, as prevalence spans across all socioeconomic groups. International literature agrees that violence mainly originates from men and that abuse usually intensifies over time. Moreover, emotional abuse is as harmful as physical abuse, and alcohol abuse further increases the intensity of violence (Heise, Pitanguy, and Germain 1994). The García and Moreno report on “Global and regional estimates of violence against women: prevalence and health effects of intimate partner violence and non-partner sexual violence,” published in co-work with the WHO, the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, and the South African Medical Research Council display the first global systematic analysis on the prevalence of two kinds of violence against women, namely IPV⁵ and sexual abuse by third persons [non-partner sexual violence]. The survey also describes the global impact of violence on physical, reproductive, and mental health (García-Moreno *et al.* 2013). The Garcia review incorporates all published and unpublished research worldwide and showcases, for the first time, aggregated global and local prevalence estimations. The authors did not place any restrictions on language or time frame, and the report stresses the impact of violence against women and selected health outcomes worldwide. It reflects

⁵Literature uses the terms DV, IPV, and GBV often interchangeably. For more information, see Chapter 2.

on AIDS/HIV, reduced birth weight, STIs, premature birth, [induced] abortion, or related mental consequences such as alcohol abuse, suicide, and depression, as well as mortality (García-Moreno *et al.* 2013 p. 21). For instance, in certain regions, the likelihood of acquiring HIV is 1.5 times higher than compared to women who have not suffered from GBV, or worldwide, the prevalence of abortion or depression is almost twice as likely (García-Moreno *et al.* 2013, p. 22, 31). In detail, the findings from the 31 studies provide strong evidence that women with a history of IPV are more likely to report an induced abortion [pooled odds ratio [OR] = 2.16; 95 per cent, Confidence Interval [CI] = 1.88 to 2.49]. Regarding homicides, based on an overall of 226 different papers, capturing 1,121 evaluations across 65 nations from 1982 to 2011, the median prevalence of intimate partner homicide of approximately 13 per cent was computed (García-Moreno *et al.* 2013 p. 23 ff.)⁶ Hence, GBV has globally similar consequences on individuals' physical and mental health states, and therefore a transferability of QALY-data is assumed.⁷

In this study, the QALY model will be interlinked with the WTP approach, and citizens indicate how much they are willing to pay to live in a society free of violence (Dolan *et al.* 2005 Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 Walby 2004), in order to provide a more holistic picture of costs.

WTP approach

Various literature stated that the application of the WTP approach has increased as research advocates for higher use (Hanley, Ryan, and Wright 2003). In sum, the WTP defines how much a consumer is willing to spend on one unit of a good or service.⁸ The used method computed an individual's WTP to avoid physical and emotional harm of GBV. Primary data derives from survivor's statements on the amount they would be prepared to spend in order to reduce the probability of suffering from injuries and fatalities.⁹ That approach is then transferred

⁶The study's limitations are that estimates of prevalence ratio and health impacts were restricted to physical and sexual IPV and did not cover psychological abuse (García-Moreno *et al.* 2013 p. 32). Further, the review only includes evaluations of sexual violence among women over 15 years. Because if sexual abuse committed by all perpetrators [intimate partners and non-partners], during childhood and adolescence were combined, the prevalence ratio would increase significantly. Besides, the number of adverse health states that were covered is rather limited. For instance, the literature indicates a correlation between IPV and chronic diseases, as cardiovascular disorders. Nevertheless, research is only at the beginning to understand such patterns. The survey did not consider the literature on the consequences of violence on children's health and development (García-Moreno *et al.* 2013 p. 33).

⁷For more details, see Chapter 6.

⁸There is debate on the proper application of certain aspects. First, the choice of the interview partner, as current, prior, or potential users of treatment. Secondly, the chosen sets of questionnaires, third, the interview techniques, as single open-ended questions or multiple close-ended questions, among others (O'Brien and Viramontes 1994). For more information, see Hole, Um, or Loureiro, for instance (Hole 2007 Loureiro and Umberger 2003 Um, Kwak, and Kim 2002). However, this discussion shall not be so much about the different methodical concerns and shall rather elaborate on the suitability and applicability of the approach to GBV (Gafni 1998).

⁹A possible example presents the topic of seatbelts. The study summed up the amount that citizens are willing to spend on belts across the U.K. population. The figure was then utilised as a proxy for the value of the life saved by a seatbelt. For instance, one may cost US\$ 30, and it lowers the chance of dying by a probability of 1/100,000 per person down to zero. Before seatbelts were developed or available on the market, one person in 100,000 would die from road accidents due to a missing seatbelt. After seat belts have been known, for instance, 100,000 citizens purchased them, each of them spending US\$ 30 per belt. The cost of society is US\$ three million in total, and one person's life has been saved. Hence, the computed

to crime and violence. Brand and Price [2000](#) use the WTP approach to investigate the cost of avoiding certain types of violent crime. For instance, the scholars assigned to a homicide case the same value as to the reported fatality from accidents. Further, common assaults attributed to the same cost as light injuries sustained from other types of accidents. Walby [2004](#) later transferred this concept to the spectrum of GBV. She matched different types of injuries resulting from GBV to similar damages from violent crimes (Brand and Price [2000](#)). For instance, the pain and suffering determined from stalking are assumed to be identical to the one of an assault case (Walby [2004](#)). As with all methods, also the QALY-loss-based WTP model has a specific set of advantages and disadvantages. The ones that hold particularly true when it comes to GBV costing are summarised in the following.

Advantages

Since the approach combines both the QALY and the WTP approach, this paragraph addresses both separately.

- QALYs:
 1. Combine the calculation of both the increased length of life and the new quality gained from a particular set of interventions, and they thus calculate a holistic picture of costs (Malek [2000](#)).
 2. Provide an average unit cost [per QALY], which allows for comparison between the different activities for both, the same area of treatment, and across medical fields (Gold, Stevenson, and Fryback [2002](#)).
 3. Unite the outcomes of a variety of interventions on mortality and morbidity into one single index. Consequently, they provide a common currency by which comparison across different fields becomes possible (Whitehead and Ali [2010](#)).

However, QALYs alone cannot constitute a sole reference for decision-making. Other factors, as population, health needs, and local priorities, or the WTP of survivors, and population to stop violence, must be considered as well.

- The willingness-to-pay approach [WTP]:
 1. Provides higher accuracy calculations, as it derives its values from information on primary data on society's behaviour.
 2. Requires only a minimum of data and is thus easily replicable and feasible to apply.
 3. Relies on different international datasets that are usually updated regularly.
 4. Serves as a helpful advocacy tool to support policymakers in choosing the appropriate interventions on violence prevention since it produces estimates on what citizens are willing to pay to avoid crime or adverse health outcomes.
 5. Is more reliable and holistically than previous approaches utilised in literature, as it derives from individuals' reporting of injuries and includes mental health impacts as a result of GBV as well (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#) Walby and Olive [2014](#)). In total, the overall advantage of the recommended QALY-loss-based WTP model

value of life is estimated to be US\$ three million since this is the amount that citizens are willing to pay to prevent such death. The figure is called the value of a statistical life (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#) Walby [2004](#) Walby and Allen [2004](#)).

is its robustness and minimised data needs make it applicable to GBV costing in general (Walby and Olive 2014 p. 15). Nevertheless, caution should be applied when utilising the unit cost per QALY estimates, as there are several methodical challenges.

Disadvantages

- QALYs:
 1. Receive their primary data from various types of research conducted in different locations, employing other techniques of estimating utilities. Thus, the data has to be applied with care to their respective content (Malek 2000).
 2. Maybe challenging to compare, as their comparison is often conducted through the means of league tables. These tables compare QALYs for different interventions. This approach faces several challenges, as calculations are, in general, dependent on both the population and the period surveyed. Furthermore, different periods and societies have varying preferences. Consequently, a direct comparison can only be conducted when such factors are taken into account (Bala and Zarkin 2000).
 3. Measurement techniques may be weak. Several papers have stated that QALYs sometimes derive from invalid sources, including small, non-representative sample sizes (Hirskyj 2007).
 4. Have been criticised for lacking to include non-health benefits as social life, faster return to employment, or better school performance since they are of significance. Hence, policy decision-making should not be carried out in isolation, as QALYs do not contain all aspects of healthcare, social, and ethical factors (Malek 2000).
 5. Unit values may be erroneous, as the unit costs of QALYs have been a centre of critique. A QALY is the outcome of utility and time. Nonetheless, in QALY models, value is designated to an arbitrary scale from zero [death] to one [perfect health]. However, the application of zero prevents arithmetic procedures as division and multiplication, and hence, specific values are omitted. A possible solution would be to estimate time and utility by employing alternative units of measurement (Pettitt *et al.* 2016).
 6. Display difficulties with attempted trade-offs between Quality and Quantity of Life. If Quantity of Life is used to evaluate Quality of Life, the outcome is influenced by an individual's judgment of their current health state. Since for certain diseases, as mental health disorders or GBV, which is embedded into a cultural context, these measurements are incredibly subjective (Malek 2000).
 7. Are not ideal to compute the losses for children. Several authors have focused on paediatric sample groups and the limited capability of children to accurately assess their Quality of Life. Concerns have been raised whether it is sufficient to rely on proxy report measures [such as parents], and critics have called for innovative strategies to overcome such limitations (Pettitt *et al.* 2016).
- WLP approach:
 1. May underestimate the cost, as it accounts for one treatment cycle and specific injuries only. Thus, it is likely to decrease the greater extent of psychological harm and other non-health-related consequences resulting from GBV (Golding 1999).

-
2. Artificially increases certain costs because medical treatment for certain injuries, such as broken teeth, is budgeted, but which are sometimes treated alone (Golding 1999).
 3. Makes certain assumptions regarding the duration and intensity of injuries and trauma. Tailored data is necessary to compute public WTP for interventions correctly (Walby and Olive 2014).
 4. Often relies on data from third sources, as surveys on GBV are often not conducted as frequently (Walby and Olive 2014).
 5. Maybe restricted in its scope and reach. Violence against women is normalised and socially accepted in many developing and emerging countries. The approach only unfolds its full potential if society achieves a minimal consensus on GBV being a harmful behaviour linked with the necessity to reduce its impact (Duvvury *et al.* 2009). Thus, the approach may be less effective in cultures and societies where GBV is an accepted norm.
 6. Derives in some instances from assumptions. In line with the bullet point above, the level of per capita income and product prices differ significantly among nations. Consumer goods that save lives, such as a seat belt, may be willingly purchased in North America, but maybe rarely in other countries, such as South Africa, since there is less disposable income available to spend on such items. WTP data is, therefore, very culture-dependent (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005).

Although the approach depicts some methodical problems, it is one of the few tools currently available that allows for comparisons across areas. Thus, the QALY model is vital for this study's scope, especially when combined with the WTP approach.

Scope of this study

In summary, both methods may prove to be appropriate and applicable to the Namibian scope. QALYs merge the effects of health measures on mortality and morbidity into a single index; thus, comparison among different fields becomes possible (Whitehead and Ali 2010). Further, it covers health service costs and the Physical and Emotional impact holistically and thoroughly evaluates the losses of rape and sexual violence in general, as it incorporates mental and physical harm as well. The approach is likely to be replicable and feasible due to its relative minimum data requirements. According to research, GBV has globally similar consequences on individuals' physical and mental health state, and therefore a transferability of certain QALY-data sets is assumed¹⁰

In order to continue, the DALY method was another approach identified in Chapter 3 to compute costs for children best witnessing or being subjected to GBV and will be explained in Section 5.6

¹⁰For more information, see Chapter 6.

5.6. Second-generation costs: DALY approach

DALYs enjoy popularity among the current health economics literature and are equally applied in both developed and developing nations.¹¹ The approach was modelled in 1990 by scholars at the World Bank and Harvard University to quantify the weight of disease and disability in societies. It computes the gap between the current health of citizens and their ideal health state (Lajoie 2015). In short, the disability-adjusted life year [DALY] method is used to calculate the burden of different diseases or the consequences of other forms of violence, for instance.

Approach

Health-adjusted life years [HALYs] are population-based health models allowing the impact of morbidity and mortality to be expressed within a single figure. They are beneficial for overall assessments of the burden of disease, measurements of the corresponding influence of particular illnesses and ailments on both societies, and economic assessments. QALYs and DALYs are forms of health-adjusted life years [HALYs]. Although both QALYs and DALYs conduct calculations of morbidity and mortality, their initial purpose differed, and their process of computation varies (Gold, Stevenson, and Fryback 2002).

QALYs focused on the development of medical interventions. Developers of health-related Quality of Life [HRQL] models put a greater emphasis on subjects as to estimate responsiveness, sensitivity, and reliability, spending less consideration to producing overall paradigms of disease occurrence, severity, and mortality (Patrick and Erickson 1993). Because of their validity, QALYs are generally chosen to compute adverse health states in adults. In contrast, DALYs have initially been designed to document data about the relative health of communities. Precision and responsiveness to more nuanced shifts in well-being status at the individual level were less critical than compiling a database that could produce reliable data concerning the epidemiology of fatal and nonfatal health consequences.

Table 5.6 offers an overview of the DALY approach. DALY designers assign measures of HRQLs to distinct diseases rather than to health states. Primarily, this was done for practical purposes, given the complexities of accumulating comparable primary data from the large numbers of nations for which a global burden of disease is estimated. Based on the extensive work of Fang *et al.* 2017, for instance, who calculated DALYs as a consequence of violence directed against children in South Africa, they are used in this study to assess adverse health impact on children as a consequence of GBV too.

Although not without critics, DALYs and QALYs have proved beneficial for their originally denoted applications. Each model spreads across the chasm that divides society's health and medical care (Gold, Stevenson, and Fryback 2002).

¹¹DALY calculations enjoy long popularity in research. Heise, Pitanguy, and Germain 1994 calculated that globally, 9.5 million [based on 1994 figures] DALYs are lost due to rape and DV. Lozano 1999 states that in Mexico City, rape and IPV was the third most relevant cause of DALYs lost, after diabetes and child-birth related complications, and they were even higher than those lost due to road accidents.

Table 5.6.: Overview of the DALY approach.

Abbreviation	Explanation	Calculation	Explanation
YLL	Years of life lost due to premature mortality [YLL]	$n \cdot L$	N . Number of death; L . Standard of life expectancy at the age of death in years
YLD	Years lived with disability [YLD]	$n \cdot L$	P . Number of prevalent cases; DW . Disability weight ¹²

Source: Own representation based on Lajoie [2015](#)

In contrast to many other methods, the DALY approach estimates the burden of violence or disease based on lives lost and quantifies the loss in Quality of Life. The DALY approach derives from the hypothesis that lifetime, measured in years, is the most appropriate indicator to compute the burden of disease and includes the time linked to the disability or the time lost due to premature mortality, respectively (Young [2004](#)). In summary, DALYs are calculated in the following way:

Years of life lost due to premature mortality [YLL] + Years lived with disability [YLD]

Health status, disability or illnesses receive assigned values according to a scale from zero to one [opposite to the QALY approach] and:

- zero defines a perfect health state and
- one represents death¹³

The health-related Quality of Life [HRQL] weights indicate the preferences that citizens carry for each health state. HRQL weights are elaborated by asking a sample group to assign disability weights to a specific disease or health state. Thereby different trade-offs and questioning techniques are employed (Gold, Stevenson, and Fryback [2002](#))¹⁴

The advantages and disadvantages are similar to those for the QALY context. The most relevant when it comes to evaluating the method regarding the phenomena of GBV are summarised in the next paragraphs.

Advantages

1. The HRQLs, in the DALY approach, describe a specific disease rather than a particular health state. The underlying reason is to avoid self-assessment of a specific health state since that may potentially bias outcome, particularly when it comes to cross-cultural

¹²Another possibility of estimation would be $YLD = I \cdot DW \cdot L$. I = the number of incident cases, DW = disability weight, and L = average duration until the cessation of the problem or death (World Health Organization (WHO) [2013a](#)).

¹³It is the opposite then used for QALYs.

¹⁴For more information on measurement techniques, see, for instance, Gold, Stevenson, and Fryback [2002](#)

comparison. That procedure assists in achieving better data in a society that may suffer from a high mortality ratio due to GBV but tends not to report adverse health states because of cultural misperception (Gold, Stevenson, and Fryback 2002).

2. DALYs estimate the burden of adverse health conditions based on a standard metric of life years lost (Hong 2011). Thus, the consequences of GBV and any benefits of intervention can be set directly into relation.
3. The metric is easily accessible to the global public, health system, or policymakers (Gold, Stevenson, and Fryback 2002).
4. Other approaches indicate a one-time snapshot of a disability or mortality linked to, for example, GBV only. In contrast, the DALY metric accounts for the burden of living with a disability for the remaining lifetime (Hong 2011). Thus, they reflect the GBV consequences for children in the most holistic way available.

Disadvantages

1. Since the method does not focus on health states but instead on diseases, DALY assessments do not cover other aspects, such as the psychological impact on other family members, for instance (Thacker *et al.* 2006).
2. There is an obstacle to age weights within DALYs. The DALY method will, in this study, be utilised to evaluate the impact on minors. In this regard, the approach's age weighting is probably the most controversial societal value formulated within the underlying matrix. The age weight for a year of healthy life of younger or older citizens is quantified with less weight than a year of health lived in adulthood. A year of life during childhood or at an older age cohort is valued less than one in adulthood (Murray *et al.* 1996). The purpose is to display the generation with its associated economic productivity. Therefore, the primary concern of the approach is that it is mainly an economic measurement of productivity. However, several scholars do not support this principle and have decided to omit age weighting (Young 2004).
3. Calculations are data-intensive, and relevant information must be available, which may be problematic, especially for developing and emerging countries. The biggest issue is to ensure that different sources from different countries have equivalent data quality. In order to face this hurdle, Lozano *et al.* 2012 configured a six-step model to assess and enhance data quality and to manage missing datasets or stochastic variations, for instance.
4. Another problem that arises when comparing the value of one healthy-lived year in the past compared to a healthy-lived year in the future, is that the value of the present years of health may be different to the one in the future. Various studies use the approach of reduction to solve this challenge. The Global Burden of Disease study, by Lim *et al.* 2012, computes a decrease at three per cent for future life years. This approach translates into; one year saved next year is worth 97 per cent of a year of life held this year (World Health Organization (WHO) 2013a). Hence, it is essential to acknowledge such underlying social values and weights when comparing DALY data.

For the scope of this study, this translates into the following:

Scope of this study

The variability of the techniques employed to derive DALY weights is a concern. Nonetheless, the increasing level of methodical guidance supports a better stringency. DALY data has been applied worldwide due to its standard, robust metric, and holistic estimates (Parks 2014). DALYs have been developed for and by the World Health Organization (World Health Organization (WHO) 2013a) to gear funding better and to account for disease burden, especially in developing and emerging countries, as conducted by Fang *et al.* 2017 for South Africa. Hence, their utilisation for the Namibian context is feasible.

Based on this methodical outline, Section 5.7 summarised this section's findings.

5.7. Conclusion

Chapter 5 presented the methods that will be used in this study. In summary, these are:

1. lost economic output and health service costs: the health-state outcome model,
2. legal, social welfare, and special service costs: the budget-share approach,
3. personal costs: the unit-cost approach,
4. intangibles, physical, and emotional impact: the QALY-loss-based WTP approach, and
5. second-generation costs: the disability-adjusted life years [DALYs] approach.

Section 5.2 described the method used for the lost economic output and the health service costs. The health-state outcome approach is based on the British Home Office Online Report [HOOR] by Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005. The method is very robust, is used in various renowned studies, and has little data requirement. Section 5.3 analysed the budget-share approach used for the cost categories legal, social welfare, and special service costs. Top-down analysis is carried out in this method. The total budget for a particular cost type is analysed to the GBV share. This approach is particularly suitable for these three cost classes. Its robustness and ease of use characterise the method. On the other hand, the unit-cost approach was chosen for the cost category of personal cost. In contrast to the budget-share model, it uses a bottom-up approach. First, the various cost units, such as the average cost of a divorce, or the average cost of property damage per case, are determined. In a second step, these are set to the average number of cases of the respective cost units. The model has the advantage to collect precise data for this cost type. Section 5.5 describes the method for the cost category of the intangibles, physical, and emotional impact. The methodology applied for this class is the QALY-loss-based WTP approach. This model has been used in renowned studies for this cost type. The QALYs were developed in the 1960s and have been used in developing, emerging, and industrialised countries alike. They describe how the Quality of Life of an individual change through specific treatment, such as the elimination of violence. The method originates from clinical research such as cancer therapy research and is applied to the phenomenon of GBV in this case study. The application has already been carried out in renowned studies worldwide, which means a high volume of valid QALY data and indicators are available. In order to achieve even more targeted results, the QALY method will be used in conjunction with the WTP model. The WTP model describes how much a society is willing to pay to reduce or completely prevent certain phenomena such as GBV. This creates a link between the QALY data, the statements on how the Quality of Life changes, and the WTP

data, which provide an economic reference for efforts to reduce GBV (Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Duvvury *et al.* 2013; Gold, Stevenson, and Fryback 2002; Hanley, Ryan, and Wright 2003; Hole 2007; Lajoie 2015; Loureiro and Umberger 2003; O'Brien and Viramontes 1994; Stouthard *et al.* 1997; Um, Kwak, and Kim 2002; Walby 2004). Section 5.6 presented the chosen method for the second-generation costs. The model of the disability-adjusted life years [DALYs] was explained in more detail. The approach is based on HALY indicators. These indicators depict the value that describes how an individual's health status changes as a result of an illness such as cancer or criminal offences, like GBV, that results in an adverse health profile and disease. In contrast to the QALY data, which measures the general loss of quality of an individual's health, the DALY data focuses on measuring the particular clinical profile. This approach is more suitable to carry out the costing for minors especially. The method is characterised by a high level of validity and objectivity, and based on the current state of research; it is one of the most suitable for measuring the costs for children caused by GBV (Gold, Stevenson, and Fryback 2002).

Table 5.7 summarises this chapter's findings and presents the selected methods that were identified best appropriate for computing the different cost categories.

Table 5.7.: Overview of the chosen method.

Category	Approaches and literature	Methods
Lost economic output	Health state outcomes, as in Dolan <i>et al.</i> 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Walby and Allen 2004	Health state outcome approach
Health service costs	Health state outcomes, as in Dolan <i>et al.</i> 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Walby and Allen 2004	Health state outcome approach
Legal costs	Proportional expenditure/budget-share approach, as in Walby 2004	Proportional expenditure/budget-share approach
Social welfare and special services	Proportional expenditure/budget-share approach for social welfare spending, as in Access Economics 2004a and for special services, as in Envall and Eriksson 2006; Heiskanen and Piispa 2001; Helweg-Larsen <i>et al.</i> 2010	Proportional expenditure/budget-share approach
Personal costs	Unit-cost approach as presented in Walby and Olive 2014	Unit cost
Intangibles, physical, and emotional impact	QALY-approach, as in Dolan <i>et al.</i> 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Walby and Allen 2004	QALY
Second-generation costs	DALYs approach based on the data of Fang <i>et al.</i> 2017 for South Africa.	DALY

Source: Own representation.

6. Data

6.1. Introduction

The most critical factor in calculating the cost of GBV is an appropriate set of data. For this research, the primary data derives from national household surveys and secondary data from international sources, among others. In addition, particular assumptions are applied to transfer global results. The following explanation describes the used primary data and the employed premises.

Each chapter defines the used datasets and their original sources in detail, as they differ for each category. This chapter shall only serve as a review of significant data sources utilised in every cost category.

The consideration of the likely availability of relevant data to support analysis in Namibia was undertaken within each cost class. This includes the dimensions to which there are sufficient findings from the NDHS on violence against women (MoHSS and ICF International 2014) or from other national studies on survivor services (Breuer 2015, Hubbard *et al.* 2006, Jewkes *et al.* 2010), or administrative data sources on GBV (The Namibian Police 2018).

Chapter 6 evaluates the primary data used in this research. Section 6.2 presents the Namibian Demographic Health Survey [NDHS]. This survey serves as the basis for numerous calculations, be it for determining prevalence ratios or percentages of the severity and frequency of injuries that result from GBV. Section 6.2 describes the British crime study of 2004 and analyses the transferability of specific British data to Namibia. The section analyses categories such as gender, socio-economic criteria, household income, active social network, age, the number of underage children living in the household, health status, or ethnic background. This detailed analysis is essential to evaluate whether the transferability of the U.K. data is given. Then, Section 6.3 analyses the data on which the Purchase Power Parities [PPPs] are based. The categories of data used to transfer health costs are presented. The health care shopping basket includes expenses for pharmaceutical products, therapeutic aids, medical offers, hospital fees, or other charges for doctors, nurses, or medical personnel. Section 6.4 describes the data underlying the prevalence ratios and multipliers. It explains what data is used to calculate the GBV prevalence ratio for Namibia. The HIV factor is also discussed, which is adjusted for this research, and Section 6.4 describes how the HIV factor for Namibia was calculated. Section 6.5 describes problems related to gross domestic product data in emerging and developing nations. Obstacles due to large informal markets or actual data tracking are discussed. These factors may make it difficult to measure the cost in relation to the gross domestic product for developing and emerging countries.

As the major primary sources, this study applies findings from the Namibian Demographic and Health Survey (MoHSS and ICF International 2014) and the British 2004 Crime Survey (Walby and Allen 2004), both of which are discussed in the following 1

6.2. Primary data

The following outline presents the primary data utilised in this paper.

2013 Namibian Demographic and Health Survey [NDHS]

The 2013 Namibian Demographic and Health Survey (MoHSS and ICF International 2014) depicts a repeated update on the Namibian demographic and health status. The release, published in September 2014, is the fourth national-level study conducted so far. It is a component of the global Demographic and Health Survey's plan to monitor national progress. The program is set to examine updated and appropriate data on fertility, family planning, maternal health, and children's health. This includes the prevalence ratio and data on HIV/AIDS and GBV. For the first time, the DV module was included in the 2013 report. However, the review of reliable data on GBV is associated with a particular set of difficulties, as there is a culture of silence, which consequently influences the reporting of GBV cases. The 2013 GBV module surveys data on all relationship states, including never-married, ever-married, divorced, separated, or widowed women, in the age range of 15 to 49, against whom violence was enacted by their current or former intimate partner or by third parties. The DV module reflects a sample of households; however, only one woman per household has participated. The report justifies this setting with ethical requirements 2 The sample includes a total of 2,226 women. Furthermore, specially designed weights were applied to ensure that the DV cohort is nationally representative and to adjust for selection bias (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 297).

The second study, whose primary data was mainly employed, is the British Crime Survey presented in the next paragraph.

2004 British crime survey and its transferability to Namibia

The economic model in Walby 2004 was determined to be used to estimate the lost economic output and the health service cost category best. Section 6.2 shall not determine whether the approach is appropriate 3 but instead, whether specific data and findings are transferable to the Namibian context.

¹This paper computes the cost of 2018. However, the findings of the NDHS (MoHSS and ICF International 2014) and Dolan *et al.* 2005 Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 are based on research before 2018. However, their outcome still applies because the results state the proportion, not a total number, tight to any given year.

²For more information related to the ethical elements, read MoHSS and ICF International 2014

³As this has already been carried out in Chapters 3 and 5

The following outline compares the outcome of the British findings and the Namibian 2014 NDHS. The objective is to investigate whether their findings on GBV depict similar patterns and to explore whether the British study's results can be utilised for this study's context. The explanations in the next paragraph present the main findings of this analysis. In summary, both papers report the following similar results on GBV:

1. Gender: in both papers, gender is a significant risk factor. Women are more likely than men to be subjected to GBV, especially to sexual violence.⁴
2. Socio-economic criteria: reduced access to economic resources, and limited financial independence, increase the vulnerability to be subjected to GBV in the U.K. (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 74). The Namibian situation reflects the same pattern. The percentage of women who have experienced physical violence since the age of 15 drops with an increasing wealth status (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 299).⁵
3. Household income: in the U.K., women in poorer household cohorts were subjected to higher frequencies of DV than those in wealthier homes.⁶ For British men, while there was found some association, however, the finding was less evident than for women (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 75). The Namibian situation is similar. Women who are employed not for cash are more likely [34 per cent] to have experienced physical violence since the age of 15 (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 297).
4. Active social network: an active social network benefits support for the British and European context. However, such a network, on the one hand, may in itself constitute a risk, as it exposes a survivor to a broader range of potential insecurities. On the other hand, it serves as a relevant security mechanism (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 82). For the Namibian setting, such relationships are more relevant, and the most common source of help is the woman's family. Forty-eight per cent of abused women who sought help did so from their own families, 15 per cent did so from the police, eight per cent sought help from their friends, and only seven per cent from a doctor or medical professional (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 316).
5. Age: Walby has found for the British setting that the younger an individual is, the more prone she or he is to be subjected to GBV. In general, those under the age of 25 are the most likely to suffer from violence (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 84).⁷ Also, in Namibia, such a relationship is discovered, and women aged 20 to 24 are more likely than women of older age cohorts to experience physical violence (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 297).

⁴See Walby and Allen 2004 p. 74, and MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 313.

⁵Regarding the social class factor, unlike the variations in risk associated with household income or the ability to find money at short notice, the link between GBV prevalence and social class was not significant in the U.K. (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 78). In Namibia, such social interlinkages were not explicitly surveyed. Still, Namibian women with no education were found to be more likely, than such with at least some form of education, to have experienced physical violence since the age of 15 [43 per cent] and to have experienced physical violence in the 12 months preceding the survey [25 per cent] (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 298).

⁶Specifically, women in households with an income of less than £10,000 per annum were three and a half times more at risk than those in households with earnings of over £20,000 per annum, which was just beneath the national average wage line during the study's period (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 75).

⁷Literature, for instance, the Farrington 1992 study states that such age-related findings occur as young men are physically much more likely to commit numerous forms of violence and crime than are older men.

-
6. Marital status: according to Walby, the risk of being exposed to GBV varies by marital status. Women who are either single or separated⁸ showcase the highest risk of having experienced sexual assault (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 85). The same pattern is found for the Namibian context. Fifty per cent of divorced, separated or widowed women, compared to *just* 37 per cent of women currently married or living together with a partner, have experienced physical violence since the age of 15 (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 297).
 7. Dependent children in the household: the U.K. study reveals that the presence of children in a household doubles the risk of GBV. That is consistent with other findings saying that women are unwilling to protect themselves by breaking up a relationship or home if there are children involved. Furthermore, women encounter more [economic] challenges moving out and establishing a home of their own when being a single parent with dependent children to support (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 87). The Namibian survey reveals a similar pattern. Physical violence among women increases with the number of dependent children to support. Thirty-seven per cent of women with five or more children have experienced violence. In contrast, based on the sample cohort in the NDHS, *just* 29 per cent of women with no children to support suffered from GBV. The occurrence of physical violence for the time frame of the past 12 months displays a comparable pattern too. For instance, 19 per cent of women with five or more children, whereas only 13 per cent of women with no children have experienced physical abuse (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 297 f.).
 8. City and urban areas: variations of violence across different regions, including metropolitan or rural regions, exist but are relatively insignificant for the U.K. However, the probability of experiencing GBV and living in an inner-city is equally high as the proportion of being exposed to GBV and lacking economic resources (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 82). In Namibia, the extent of regional distribution is even more evident. For instance, the Kavango area has the highest percentage of women who have ever experienced physical violence [49 per cent], followed by the Omaheke region [42 per cent]. The reported prevalence of violence is also relatively high in Karas and Kunene [41 per cent and 36 per cent, respectively] and is lowest in Omusati [19 per cent] (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 298)⁹
 9. Health status: women who self-reported poor health status have suffered more than twice the prevalence of violence than those who stated a self-assessed good health situation (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 87). Also, the Namibian research indicates several correlations between the occurrence of violent acts and specific adverse health states (MoHSS and ICF International 2014).
 10. Ethnic background: the British data depict little contrast in the appearance of interpersonal violence linked to ethnicity (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 74), as Table 6.1 displays. The Namibian NDHS does not reflect expressly on ethnic belonging (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). The U.K. data indicates that women, apart from their ethnic background, are equally affected by GBV. It implies that the British and other global data

⁸In such cases, GBV could be a continuous act from a former intimate partner, or either it may be violence that occurred before the time of separation or interview.

⁹These variations may be grounded in the diverse cultural pattern of the different Namibian ethnic groups (Reddy 1991).

Table 6.1.: Overview of GBV prevalence ratio by ethnicity of respondents in the U.K.

Women's ethnic background	White [%]	Black [%]	Asian [%]
GBV survivor	4.20	4.30	4.10

Source: Own representation based on the findings of Walby [2004](#) p. 79.

on GBV are applicable across ethnic groups, which is an essential finding. Based on this conclusion, data of Dolan *et al.* [2005](#); Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#); Walby [2004](#); Walby and Allen [2004](#) will be employed for the cost classes of lost economic output, health service costs, and intangibles in this report, but will be tailored to the Namibian context, for instance, to the higher HIV/AIDS ratios, if necessary.

In order to continue, Section [6.3](#) presents the underlying foundations relevant to the transfer and utilisation of global results.

6.3. Purchasing Power Parity [PPP] data

Global data is mainly transferred by using Purchasing Power Parities [PPPs]. Specifically, the PPP approach is used for calculations in the categories of the lost economic output, social welfare costs, personal costs and intangibles ¹⁰. The following paragraph provides a review of why and how this paper applies them. PPPs depict the overall amount of goods and services that a single currency unit of country A can purchase in another country B. PPPs can hence be utilised to convert the price of a basket of goods and services into a common currency while abolishing the price level differences across nations. In summary, PPPs are conversion ratios that show the value of the prices in national currencies of the same basket of goods and services in different countries (International Comparision Program (ICP) [2017](#)). PPPs have several advantages. Due to notable cost differences across international markets, the market exchange rate does not adequately measure the relative dimension of a national economy and its levels of material wealth. PPPs provide a solution to this obstacle. They make it feasible to compare national economies' output and the inhabitant's prosperity in real terms to control price level differences across nations (International Comparision Program (ICP) [2017](#)). GDP PPPs have usually been applied as the most appropriate and reliable conversion ratio for health care expenditures. They derive from a broad basket of goods and services, chosen to represent all economic activity. Their usage implies that the resulting variations, for instance, in health care costs, state differences in the volume of the respective goods and services and changes in the price levels to GDP prices across economies (Lorenzoni and Koechlin [2017](#)). The basket of goods and services used to derive PPPs includes all goods and services covered by GDP estimations (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) [2018](#)). In detail, the entire product list includes 2,500 consumer goods and services (Organisation for Economic

¹⁰For more information, see Section [7.5.2](#) or Section [21.3](#) for instance.

Co-operation and Development (OECD) [2012](#)). This paper focuses on health care expenditure. The Eurostat-OECD expenditure basket on health includes the three institutional sectors, namely:

- households,
- non-profit institutions serving households [NPISHs], and
- government.

The basket on health includes the following products and services:

1. “Pharmaceutical products,
2. therapeutic appliances and equipment,
3. out-patient medical services,
4. out-patient paramedical services,
5. hospital services fees,
6. other medical products, and
7. compensation of employees such as physicians, nurses, and other medical staff” (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) [2012](#)).

The PPPs are applied to compute the health care expenditure data that was not available in Namibia. PPPs were used to calculate unit values for treatment costs. For instance, the calculations will use a 2018 PPP conversion factor to transfer the British findings for certain cost classes. Section [6.4](#) presents the underlying information on the applied prevalence and multiplier data.

6.4. Prevalence and multiplier data

Significant attention needs to be laid onto the utilised data basis (Habetha *et al.* [2012](#), p. 62). The multipliers were used in each cost type to bring the police-based case numbers to a realistic level. It has been recalculated and adjusted for each category.

Criminal statistics, including the Namibian Police [NAMPOL] data, only contain recognised and documented incidents but do not reflect the reality of claims, as GBV is one of the most underreported crimes (Rennison [2002](#)). Consequently, to base estimates on police records would lead to a significant underestimation of damages. In Namibia, women mainly withdraw their GBV cases or do not report them at all. [See, for instance, the article “Police urge women not to withdraw violence cases” (The Namibian [2017](#))]. Therefore, the number of recorded NAMPOL cases do not resemble reality, and for all cost categories, the number of cases had to be recalculated based on multiplier data. Population surveys are often utilised to shed light on the hidden extent of incidents that have remained concealed to official institutions. Therefore, the findings of the Namibian NDHS are used as baseline information in each chapter too.

Multiplier data

There is a set of factors influencing the calculation of the multiplier data. The most important are briefly outlined in the next enumeration:

1. Sexual violence is one of the most underreported crimes worldwide (Forde [2018](#)); thus, NAMPOL data does not reflect the reality of cases.

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- a) International data: the Bureau of Justice Statistics [2017](#) from the U.S. Department of Justice, for instance, reported in its National Crime Victimization Survey from 2010 to 2016 that overall, three out of four cases occur unregistered [11](#). These findings are in line with surveys from the Brennan Center for Justice [2018](#), among others.
 - b) Southern Africa: the data indicate that only one out of 13 [7.69 per cent] of non-intimate partner rape cases, and overall only one out of 25 [four per cent] of intimate partner rape cases were reported (Machisa *et al.* [2011](#)). The same situation applies to Namibia, as it shares, according to research, similarities to gender norms occurring in South Africa. [12](#)

In consequence:

2. Large panel qualitative surveys in Namibia provide more appropriate data: the comparison of NAMPOL with the NDHS sexual offence datasets reveals that only one out of around 27 cases [3.71 per cent] is reported [13](#). Consequently, the ratio between the NAMPOL and NDHS case numbers, depicted in Table [8.5](#), is similar to other research conducted in Southern Africa. [14](#)

In conclusion:

3. Trends in sexual assaults cannot be drawn based on crime reports [only]: due to the circumstances listed, institutions refuse to analyse patterns in sexual assault cases based on criminal records (Brennan Center for Justice [2018](#)). Hence, the estimation of multipliers becomes complex.

The next paragraph describes the employed GBV factor in more detail.

Applied Namibian GBV prevalence factor

The factor presented in this chapter is used in all cost categories. This data is essential, as the calculated costs are compared with the prevalence and cost-shares in the other studies. The paper applies a prevalence factor of 17.50 per cent. However, there are different data stated within the NDHS. The 17.50 per cent was chosen over a 20 per cent prevalence because:

- The 20 per cent ratio symbolises the offset of spousal violence only. Twenty per cent of ever-married women in Namibia have experienced physical or sexual violence. Their current or most recent husband enacted the abuse during the past 12 months before the survey (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) p. 310). However, this study's definition goes beyond spousal violence and includes GBV enacted by third persons, including teachers or the police. Thus, another factor was chosen, namely, the 17.50 per cent.

¹¹The high underreporting derives from the reality that sexual assault survivors struggle with a wide range of emotions. According to psychotherapist Beverly Engel, "individuals are often too ashamed to come forward. Sexual assault is a very humiliating and dehumanizing act," and "attached to that shame is a lot of self-blame, as we have a culture, where we tend to blame individuals in general" (Forde [2018](#)).

¹²For instance, Namibian men, especially those in rural areas, believe that women should not refuse sexual intercourse and be disciplined whenever they *misbehave* (Gender Research and Advocacy Project [2012](#)).

¹³The figure derives from a quotient of 946 reported NAMPOL cases and 25,501 NDHS cases per year. For detailed information, see Table [8.5](#)

¹⁴See, for instance, the research of Machisa *et al.* [2011](#) on South Africa.

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- The 17.50 per cent states the sum of Namibian women, in the cohort of 15- to 49-year-olds, who have often, or sometimes experienced physical violence [13.80 per cent], (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 298) or have experienced sexual abuse [3.70 per cent] in the past 12 months before the survey. It includes perpetrator such as a [former] partner, husband as well as other siblings [(step)father, (step)brother], family friend, teacher, or stranger (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 300 f.)¹⁵

The next subparagraph discusses the applied HIV factor.

Applied HIV factor

The factor is used, for example, for specific partial calculations in the cost categories of lost economic output [Chapter 7] or social welfare costs [Chapter 10]. In summary, the HIV estimates from Europe cannot be transferred to the Southern African context because of the higher African prevalence ratios. Due to an increased HIV ratio, the figure calculated by Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Walby and Allen 2004 of 0.000001 cannot be applied. Instead, Jewkes *et al.* 2010 estimates for the South Africa context are used and transferred, as, according to Jewkes 2018 Namibia depicts similar patterns. The 25.80 per cent presents the sum of, firstly, the 13.90 per cent of HIV infections that would have been prevented if gender equity and the low power ratio of women in a heterosexual relationship had been enhanced. Secondly, the 11.90 per cent of HIV infections that could have been avoided if women had not experienced more than one episode of physical or sexual partner violence. The ratio includes only individuals who suffered from more than one incident of GBV during the survey period (Jewkes *et al.* 2010, p. 6).

In order to continue, Section 6.5 presents the problems associated with GDP data, particularly in emerging markets.

6.5. Gross Domestic Product [GDP] data

There are several obstacles regarding the exact measurement of GDP data in developing and emerging countries, especially in Africa and Southern Africa. Section 6.5 describes the issues regarding national GDP per capita data, informal markets, or selection bias in GDP data that primarily occur in emerging market environments (The Economist 2014b).

Informal markets

The International Monetary Fund [IMF] results suggest that the informal economy in Sub-Saharan Africa remains among the largest in the world, although its share has been gradually declining (Medina, Jonelis, and Cangul 2017). The GDP measurement, for instance, does not take

¹⁵The assumption is made that the ratio is still appropriate, although research was conducted in 2013 and published in 2014. Anti-violence work and public awareness campaigns have not produced a significant difference yet, as police still record very high caseloads (Namibia Press Agency 2019).

into account the earnings generated through black markets, parallel economies, or in sum, by any economic activity that has led to growth but is not officially recorded (Doepke 2020). That points to a probable underestimation of GDP in Africa as a whole.

Problems in reporting

The GDP estimate is facing delays in reporting. Since first, the compilation of data on transactions included in evaluating the GDP data in any country is a time-consuming process. Secondly, the data is surveyed only on an irregular basis. This fact becomes, for instance, evident in The Economist 2014b article on “How Nigeria’s economy grew by 89 per cent overnight.” An economy’s actual growth degree is typically measured by reference to prices in a given base year. In Nigeria, for example, the reference year for the old GDP estimates was 1990. The IMF recommends that such baseline years be updated at least every five years. Nigeria has not done such an update for over 20 years. As a consequence, the old GDP figures were all inaccurate (The Economist 2014a). Consequently, the description and calculation of the cost to GDP in this Namibian scenario might suffer specific inadequacies too.

Selection bias in GDP data

The GDP data differs depending on the nature of the crime, where it is committed, and upon whom. With an estimated per capita income of N\$ 72,726 [in the current LCU] in 2018 (World Bank 2018e), Namibia was classified as an upper-middle-income country. Nonetheless, it masks extreme poverty, as well as inequalities in income distribution and standard of living (World Bank 2020b).¹⁶ With a poverty rate of 18.30 per cent in 2018, an unemployment ratio of 33.40 per cent in 2018 (Economics 2018), and an HIV prevalence of 12.10 per cent among adults aged 15 to 49 in 2017 (UNAIDS 2019), large parts of the Namibian nation remain vulnerable (National Planning Commission 2015). Besides, Namibia has extreme inequalities in income distribution and standards of living among ethnic groups. For instance, the average per capita consumption of a Khoisan-speaking citizen was N\$ 7,088¹⁷ per annum, the one of an Oshiwambo citizen was N\$ 23,626¹⁸ per annum, and the per capita income of a German-speaking Namibian citizen was around N\$ 199,330 per annum (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016 p. 97).¹⁹ Citizens with more substantial per capita incomes primarily run private businesses such as tourist lodges with business revenues that are significantly higher than the average Namibian salaries and wages. Further, the unemployment ratio²⁰ is higher for women than for men, and the gap is continuously widening. The Namibian Labour Force Survey stated that women generally earned less with an average of N\$ 6,642 per month than men with an average of N\$ 6,850 per month in 2016 (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2017 p. 14). Further, domestic workers, who are predominately women, earned substantially less than other employees (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2017 p. 15). This finding and other data suggest that Namibian men are more

¹⁶For more information, see White 2017.

¹⁷This was around € 420 in 2015.

¹⁸€ 1,400 in 2015.

¹⁹In Euro-terms, this was € 12,000 in 2015.

²⁰The unemployment rate reflects the individuals of a working-age group who were not in self-employment or paid employment despite being available on the labour market (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2017 p. 14).

often employed and receive higher wages compared to female employees. This implies that the average GDP per capita data may not be an appropriate indicator to estimate the lost economic output. However, the alternative would be to tailor lost production and productivity estimates to the specific survivor's characteristics like age, gender, ethnic group, or residence. Although this may be justified theoretically from an economic point of view, the consequence would be a higher valuation of the prevention of crimes against those at higher income levels. It would value least the prevention of crimes against those already the most disadvantaged and vulnerable in society, such as children, the unemployed, and the disabled. Again, it would have socially unacceptable consequences and would be counter to the practice of good policy-making (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 39).

In order to continue, Section 6.6 will present a summary of this chapter's findings.

6.6. Conclusion

Chapter 6 described the primary data used in this study. The NDHS was first presented (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). The paper applies a multitude of factors for many sub-areas related to GBV in Namibia. The British Walby and Allen 2004 study was briefly presented in the further course, and its transferability to Namibia was analysed. Various categories were examined, such as the socio-economic situation, household income, age, number of children living in the household, or ethnicity. The brief analysis concludes that the data is transferable to Namibia, as the 2004 British study found no differences in the ethnic background in terms of GBV. Furthermore, the Power Purchase Parities [PPPs] were presented. The concept and the underlying data were found to be applicable for transferring international cost data to the Namibian context. Further, the chosen Namibian prevalence factor was described. The proportion of 17.50 per cent was determined. This is the closest to the theoretical views on which this study is based. Because this factor encompasses all groups of survivors and involves third party perpetrators such as family, friends or teachers. The used HIV factor was described in Section 6.4. According to the team of authors, the HIV factor is based on South African research data (Jewkes *et al.* 2010) that, can be applied to Namibia too. Finally, the issues with the gross domestic product data in developing and emerging countries were presented. Certain countries have some problems with the topicality and size of their database, which can sometimes be delayed. For example, the gross domestic product in Nigeria grew by 89 per cent overnight (The Economist 2014a). For the sole reason that the data was updated the day before, which was not done for a period of over twenty years. These factors pose specific difficulties and must be considered when presenting the costs in relation to the gross domestic product in Namibia.

In the subsequent chapters, all cost categories will be calculated to test the hypothesis:

The cost of Gender-Based Violence [GBV], including second-generation losses, is projected to be around six per cent, and excluding second-generation costs; it is likely to be around four per cent of Namibia's 2018 national GDP.

In order to continue, Chapter 7 will estimate the first cost category, the lost economic output.

7. Lost economic output

7.1. Introduction

GBV impacts people's capacities in many ways, and one of these is productivity and employment. Time off work can lead to lost earnings, reduced performance, limited probability of promotion, or the loss of employment (Abramsky *et al.* 2011; Barker, Ricardo, and Nascimento 2007; Crowne *et al.* 2010; Duvvury *et al.* 2013; Grossman 2000; Meisel, Chandler, and Rienzi 2003; Reeves and O'Leary-Kelly 2007). This can contribute to the low household income, which is found to be associated with GBV (Day, McKenna, and Bowlus 2005; Duvvury *et al.* 2013; KPMG South Africa 2014; Walby and Olive 2014, p. 10). In a nutshell, the productivity of an economy as a whole diminishes (Dolan *et al.* 2005; Duvvury *et al.* 2013; Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010; KPMG South Africa 2014; Walby and Olive 2014, p. 10). Chapter 7 estimates the economic losses as a consequence of individuals' adverse physical and mental health state in Namibia. In Section 7.2, the applied methods based on Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 are discussed. In Section 7.3 the primary data used in this Chapter 7 is presented. The primary data, the therapy data, and the data of the case numbers and their sources are showcased. The overall results will be presented in Section 7.4. A calculation is made for both men and women. In Section 7.5 the conclusions are drawn, the results are summarised, and are compared with the outcome from other countries. In order to work out the best possible comparison, the prevalence ratios of the other studies are hypothetically raised to the Namibian level. This is to enable a deeper comparison. The evaluation again differentiates between developing, emerging, and industrialised countries. In Section 7.5, there will be conducted a further discussion, and the sub-areas and aspects that occurred during the calculation of the results are dealt with.

7.2. Approach

The approach of Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 was identified as the most suitable to estimate the lost economic output.

Health-state approach

The health-state approach used in Dolan *et al.* [2005], Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] has been identified as best applicable.¹ In short, the method is robustly underpinned and has a high degree of replicability and feasibility, as the requirement for data is moderate, and the information needed is generally accessible. Further, the model is government-backed and appropriate for calculating the economic and health losses (Walby and Olive [2014]). In order to continue, Section [7.3] will present the applied data sources.

7.3. Data

Basic data

In addition to the 2013 Namibian Demographic and Health Survey [NDHS] data (MoHSS and ICF International [2014] p. 313), the following primary data is employed:

- Dolan *et al.* [2005], Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005], Walby [2004], Walby [2009], Walby and Allen [2004] the prevalence ratio and the duration of adverse states, like drug abuse, depression, or eating disorders, for instance, resulting from violence are utilised to determine the lost economic output.²

Treatment cost data

- GDP data of the World Bank [2018e] the World Bank's national GDP per capita data is used.

Case number data

- United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) [2018b] 2018 data on the current female population is used for the cohort of 15- to 49-year-olds.
- Jewkes *et al.* [2010] findings on the local HIV/AIDS ratios are utilised.³

Table [7.1] depicts the UNDESA's 2018 census data utilised for the calculations.

¹Chapter [3] classified the most relevant literature, and Chapter [5] reviewed the methodical approach to best compute the lost economic output (Dolan *et al.* [2005], Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005], Duvvury *et al.* [2013]). Chapter [16] showcases the findings of the Duvvury *et al.* [2013] approach in more detail.

²Please read Section [6.2] for a detailed explanation of why the British findings are transferable to the Namibian context.

³For instance, due to a higher HIV prevalence, the Dolan *et al.* [2005], Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] figure of 0.000001 is not used. Instead, the 25.80 per cent ratio from the South African research of Jewkes *et al.* [2010] p. 6 is applied.

⁴For more information on the composition of the 17.50 per cent, see Section [6.4].

⁵13.80 per cent of 689,222 Namibian women aged 15 to 49 often have or sometimes have experienced physical violence (MoHSS and ICF International [2014] p. 298) in the past 12 months before the survey.

⁶It was calculated with the data of 13.80 per cent for physical and 3.70 per cent for sexual violence. These are given on pages 298 and 300 in MoHSS and ICF International [2014], respectively. If the median value

Table 7.1.: Current Namibian female population in 2018.

Category	Women [numbers]	
The current female population in, 2018	1,328,333	(United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b)
The current female population aged 15 to 49 years, in 2018	689,222	(United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b)
Suffering from physical and sexual violence [17.50 per cent], in 2018 ⁴	120,614	
Suffering from physical violence only [13.80 per cent], in 2018 ⁵	95,113	
In employment, suffering from physical violence [74.10 per cent]	70,478	
In employment, suffering from sexual violence [74.10 per cent]	18,896	

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation based on UNDESA data⁶
(United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b)

In the age range of 15 to 49 years, the current female population was 689,222 women in 2018 (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b).

Table 7.2 depicts the estimated case numbers for men.

The in-employment factor was applied because only 74.10 per cent of citizens receive a GDP per capita income from some form of employment¹⁰ as 25.90 per cent of the population lives

from the individual data within the table is calculated, the result is a factor of 13.76 per cent for physical violence and a factor of 3.66 per cent for sexual violence. [See the report on pages 298 and 300]. That gives a new total factor of 17.42 per cent. There is a deviation of 0.08 per cent from the information in the two MoHSS and ICF International 2014 tables. This deviation should be pointed out. The factors of 17.50 per cent and 3.70 per cent were used for this study, however.

⁷This age cohort is chosen as the U.N. development goals on GBV, mainly includes the cohort of 15- to 49-year-olds (UN Women 2018a).

⁸In detail, 4.60 per cent of Namibian women aged 15–49 have committed physical violence against their partners during the past 12 months (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 313).

⁹Data on men is only available for physical, not for sexual violence (MoHSS and ICF International 2014).

¹⁰Since, according to the Namibia Household Income and Expenditure Survey (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016, p. 98), 25.90 per cent of the population does not belong to any specific economic sector and lives from remittances and grants [9.60 per cent], drought, and in-kind receipts [2.70 per cent], subsistence farming [10.60 per cent], or others [three per cent].

Table 7.2.: Current Namibian male population in 2018.

Category	Men [numbers]	
The current male population, in 2018	1,259,465	(United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b)
Thereof, aged 15 to 49 years, in 2018 ⁷	660,080	(United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b)
Thereof, subjected to GBV physical violence in the past 12 months [4.60 per cent], in 2018 ⁸	30,364	
Thereof, subjected to GBV sexual violence in the past 12 months, in 2018 ⁹	–	
In employment, suffering from physical violence [74.10 per cent]	22,499	
In employment, suffering from sexual violence [74.10 per cent]	–	

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation based on UNDESA data (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b).

from in-kind donations or grants, among others¹¹. A figure which is more closely in line with the national GDP per capita database and output loss¹².

The calculations are based on a Namibian GDP per capita in 2018 [current LCU] of N\$ 72,725,957 (World Bank 2018e). It was divided by 365.25 days and resulted in a Namibian GDP per capita of around N\$ 199 per day. The individual daily rates were multiplied by this value.

On this baseline, the Physical and Emotional violence figures are calculated. Table 7.3 reflects the overall losses of women, and Table 7.4 the outcome for men.

¹¹Numbers of both sexes and percentages were identified based on the Namibia Statistics Agency's Labour Force 2018 report's findings (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2019). They were cross-checked with the 2016 Survey (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2017 p. 44).

¹²Nevertheless, it has to be kept in mind that this adjusted figure shall be merely understood as an approach to computing the actual losses that occurred. For reasons of readability, the detailed tables and calculations are not depicted in the main text. They are instead showcased in Chapter 16.

7.4. Results

Table 7.3.: Results of the lost economic output: women.

Forms of violence	Health state ¹³	Probability [%]	Women [numbers]	Time off work [d]	Economic output [N\$]
Physical violence			70,478 ¹⁴		
Mental or emotional problems			21,848 ¹⁶		
	Acute stress disorder ¹⁷	0.949 ¹⁸	20,754	21	86,730,966
	Mild/ moderate post-traumatic stress disorder	0.0351	766	257	39,175,538
	Severe post-traumatic stress disorder	0.0150	328	257	16,774,904
Physical health problems ¹⁹					
	Minor injury	[0.46 ²⁰	[32,420]	–	–
	Minor bruising or black eye	0.40	28,191	3	16,830,027
	Scratches	0.13	9,162	1	1,823,238
	Other physical injuries	0.04	2,819	3	1,682,943
	Moderate injuries	[0.20]	[14,096]	–	–
	Severe bruising	0.15	10,572	10	21,038,280
	Bleeding from cuts	0.08	5,638	2	2,243,924
	Severe injuries	[0.06]	[4,229]	–	–
	Internal injuries	0.02	1,410	6	1,683,540

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¹³Based on the findings of Dolan *et al.* 2005, Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, Walby 2004, Walby and Allen 2004, p. 38

¹⁴For insights of the calculation, see the paragraph: Case number data.

¹⁵Walby and Allen 2004, p. 34 do not provide a figure for this context.

¹⁶Thirty-one per cent of overall 70,478 women, 15 to 49 years old, who suffered such harm were 21,848 women. The figure of 31 per cent derives from Walby 2004 and represents the overall ratio of women suffering from mental or emotional problems (Walby and Allen 2004, p. 34).

¹⁷However, Walby does not provide further in-debt data. Hence, other options are explored. Dolan *et al.* 2005, p. 974; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 34 offer more detailed probabilities for mental harm in the category of wounding. It is assumed that the adverse health state output deriving from physical violence is equal to wounding. Consequently, the wounding probabilities are applied. They are employed for all mental or emotional consequences, including the three health categories of mental or emotional problems, mild/moderate post-traumatic stress disorder, and severe post-traumatic stress disorder. For further details, see Chapter 16 in the Appendix.

¹⁸Out of 21,848. The number 21,848 serves as a baseline for all three adverse health states listed under mental or emotional problems. All probabilities are derived from Walby and Allen 2004, p. 34.

¹⁹The Walby 2004 prevalences of minor injuries for women is 0.46, for moderate injuries 0.20, and severe injuries 0.06 (Walby and Allen 2004, p. 34). Nonetheless, since Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 34 do not provide the respective time off [in work[days]], these factors are not utilised. As a result, only the subcategories of, for instance, minor bruising or black eye, scratches, or other physical injuries, are utilised. Multiple responses were allowed; therefore, the percentages will not sum up to 100.

²⁰Out of 70,478. The number serves as a baseline for all health states under minor injuries, moderate injuries, and severe injuries. From minor bruising or black eyes until internal injuries, all probabilities are derived from Walby and Allen 2004, p. 34.

Continue Table 7.3

Forms of Health state violence	Probability [%]	Women [numbers]	Time off work [d]	Economic output [N\$]
Broken bones/teeth ²¹	[0.06]	[4,229 ²²		
Broken bones	0.4754	2,010	31	12,399,690
Broken nose	0.2125	898	11	1,965,722
Broken or lost teeth	0.1484	627	2	249,546
Chipped teeth	0.1638	693	2	275,814
Sexual violence ²³		[18,896]		
Mental or emotional problems ²⁴		[18,896 ²⁵		
Acute stress disorder	1.000	18,896	21	78,966,384
Mild/moderate post-traumatic stress disorder	0.343	6,481	257	331,457,783
Severe post-traumatic stress disorder	0.147	2,778	257	142,075,254
Drug abuse	0.023	435	835	72,281,775
Alcohol abuse	0.018	340	417	28,214,220
Depression [moderate, short-term]	0.200	3,779	89	66,929,869
Suicide	0.001	19	6,421	24,277,801
Obesity/eating disorder	0.050	945	835	157,025,925
Anxiety	0.050	945	259	48,706,245
Sexual dysfunction ²⁶	0.780	14,739	30	87,991,830
Unwanted pregnancy	0.025	472	- ²⁷	-
Physical health problems		[18,896]		
Broken bones	0.037	699	31	4,312,131
Minor bruise/black eye	0.192	3,628	3	2,165,916
Severe bruising	0.111	2,098	10	4,175,020

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²¹Walby and Allen [2004] p. 34 provide only an overall factor for broken bones and teeth resulting from physical violence, which is 0.06 for women. Therefore other options were explored to calculate the subcategories. Dolan *et al.* [2005] Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] provide a solution. The scholars have researched more in-depth data; however, for the category of wounding only, and list detailed probabilities for broken bones, nose, or lost broken and chipped teeth. It is assumed that physical violence and wounding have an equally adverse health state outcome. As a result, these categories are applied and utilised. For details, see Chapter [16] in the Appendix.

²²The objective is to keep calculations as close as possible to the Walby findings derived from GBV research specifically. Thus, the probabilities are set in relation to Walby's (Walby and Allen [2004] p. 34) total factor for broken bones and teeth as a consequence of GBV, which is, as said, six per cent [0.06] of women. Hence, the proportions in the rows, 0.4754 for broken bones, 0.2125 for a broken nose, 0.1484 for broken or lost teeth, and 0.1638 for chipped teeth are calculated based on a cohort of 5,707 women. 5,707 is the six per cent of 95,113 women who, in total, suffered from GBV.

²³In detail, 3.70 per cent of Namibian women aged 15 to 49 have experienced sexual violence in the past 12 months, including perpetrators such as [former] partner/husbands, as well as other siblings [father, mother, brother], employer/person to work with, or, and police/soldiers (MoHSS and ICF International [2014] p. 300). Thus, in total, 25,501 women suffered from sexual violence, and thereof, 74.10 per cent received a GDP per capita income from some form of employment, which results in a cohort of 18,896 women.

²⁴All probabilities derive from Dolan's (Dolan *et al.* [2005] p. 974); Dubourg's (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] p. 34) rape category.

²⁵This figure serves as a baseline for all adverse health states listed under mental or emotional problems and physical health problems.

²⁶Gynaecological problems cover persistent issues with sexual response, including pain or abnormal vaginal bleeding (Jefferson Health [2018] Mayo Clinic [2018]).

²⁷For further details, see Section [7.5]

Continue Table 7.3

Forms of Health state violence	Probability [%]	Women [numbers]	Time off work [d]	Economic output [N\$]
Other injury	0.033	624	3	372,528
HIV diagnoses ²⁸	0.2580	4,875	1,690	1,639,511,250
Gonorrhoea	0.040	756	3	451,332
Chlamydial infection	0.020	378	3	225,666
Trichomoniasis	0.120	2,268	3	1,353,996
Bacterial vaginosis	0.190	3,590	3	2,143,230
Abortion	0.025	472	7	657,496
Miscarriage ²⁹	0.006	113	7	157,409
Overall loss [N\$]				2,896,327,192

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.
Source: Own representation.

Table 7.4 presents the overall losses estimated for men.

Table 7.4.: Results of the lost economic output: men.

Forms of Health state ³⁰ violence	Probability [%]	Men [numbers]	Time off work [d]	Economic output [N\$]
Physical violence		22,499 ³¹		
Mental or emotional problems		[22,499] ³³		
Acute Stress disorder	0.9499 ³⁴	1,924	21	8,040,396
Mild/moderate PTSD	0.0351	71	257	3,631,153
Severe PTSD	0.0150	30	257	1,534,290
Physical health ³⁵				
Minor injury	[0.41] ³⁶	[9,225]		

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²⁸For details, see Section 6.4

²⁹This paper does not compute the consequence of unwanted pregnancy. Dolan *et al.* 2005, p. 974 provide a ratio for the European context, though. However, the figure cannot be transferred to the Southern African context. For more information, read Section 7.5

³⁰Based on the findings of Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Walby 2004; Walby and Allen 2004, p. 38

³¹For insights into the calculation, see the paragraph on case number data.

³²Walby and Allen 2004, p. 34 do not provide a figure.

³³In total, 2,025 men have mental or emotional problems. [Because nine per cent of the overall 22,499 men suffer from such harm]. The factor 0.09 symbolises the overall proportion of mental or emotional harm derived from physical violence. The figure is based on research of Walby and Allen 2004, p. 34. However, Walby and Allen 2004 do not provide further data. In contrast, Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 estimate detailed probabilities. For the detailed calculations, see Chapter 16 in the Appendix.

³⁴Out of 22,499 men.

³⁵The Walby 2004 figures of minor injury for men is 0.41, for moderate injuries is 0.14, and for severe injuries, 0.01. However, these ratios are not utilised, as Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 34 do not provide the particular time off [in work[days]]. For further details, see Table 7.3

³⁶Out of 22,499 men. For further details, see Table 7.3

Continue Table 7.4

Forms of Health state violence	Probability [%]	Men [numbers]	Time off work [d]	Economic output [N\$]
Minor bruising or black eye	0.21	4,725	3	2,820,825
Scratches	0.25	5,625	1	1,119,375
Other physical injuries	0.03	675	3	402,975
Moderate injuries	[0.14]	[3,150]		
Severe bruising	0.05	1,125	10	2,238,750
Bleeding from cuts	0.11	2,475	2	985,050
Internal injuries	0.01	225	6	268,650
Broken bones/teeth ³⁷	[0.009]	[202 ³⁸]	1	
Broken bones	0.4754	96	31	592,224
Broken nose	0.2125	43	11	94,127
Broken or lost teeth	0.1484	30	2	11,940
Chipped teeth	0.1638	33	2	13,134
Sexual violence ³⁹		–		
	Overall loss men	[N\$]		21,752,889
	Overall loss women	[N\$]		2,896,327,192
	\sum overall loss	[N\$]		2,918,080,081
	Share of GDP	[% ⁴⁰]		1.64

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

7.5. Conclusion

7.5.1. Summary of findings

The calculated lost economic output is significantly higher than the one of the KPMG South Africa 2014 study.⁴¹ The overall estimated lost economic output, [N\$] for both women and men, is N\$ 2,918,080,081, which is 1.64 per cent of the 2018 GDP.

³⁷Walby and Allen 2004 provide only a ratio for broken bones/teeth resulting from physical violence, which is 0.009 for men. Hence, figures of Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 for the category of wounding are used again and are set into relation to the Walby's (Walby and Allen 2004, p. 34) overall proportion of 0.009. The objective is to keep calculations as close as possible to the outcome figures derived from GBV research specifically. For the details see, Table 7.3 and Chapter 16.

³⁸The objective is to keep calculations as close as possible to the Walby findings derived from GBV research specifically. Thus, the probabilities are set in relation to Walby's (Walby and Allen 2004, p. 34) total factor for broken bones and teeth due to GBV, which is. Hence, the proportions in the rows, 0.4754 for broken bones, 0.2125 for a broken nose, 0.1484 for broken or lost teeth, and 0.1638 for chipped teeth are calculated based on a cohort of 202 men.

³⁹The census data was too small to conduct estimates for sexual violence (MoHSS and ICF International 2014).

⁴⁰The GDP in the current LCU was N\$ 178.052 billion in 2018 (World Bank 2018e).

⁴¹However, this outcome has been expected. The KPMG South Africa 2014 paper has several methodical shortcomings. KPMG South Africa 2014, p. 2 calculates the overall cost of all categories, with 0.90–1.30 per cent of GDP.

-
- Women bear a share of above 1.63 per cent, while men encounter only 0.01 per cent of the overall losses.
 - Sexual violence depicts the most significant cost-proportion, although their case numbers are notably lower when compared to incidents of physical violence. Only for women, losses through HIV accumulate to over N\$ 1.6 billion and hence state a significant issue of concern⁴²
 - The adverse health state mild and moderate PTSD deriving from sexual violence is N\$ 331,457,783 and represents the second-highest proportion of the cost for women, as the economic implications amount to a 0.19 per cent GDP share alone. This is followed by eating disorders, with around N\$ 157 million and severe PTSD with N\$ 142 million. Adverse health conditions resulting from physical violence that leverage the highest losses are acute stress disorders, with around N\$ 87 million for women and around N\$ eight million for men, respectively.
 - For men, such mental impact poses a significant burden too, and acute stress disorder losses [N\$ 8,042,994] amount to nearly 40 [36.96] per cent of all costs for men.

Section 7.5.2 puts the outcome into the context of other international researchers to discuss the findings in greater detail.

7.5.2. Comparison with other countries

The data is set in relation to other paper's outcomes. Table 7.5 compares the lost economic output findings with other international literature.⁴³

⁴²The calculations utilise a prevalence proportion from the South African Jewkes *et al.* 2010 p. 6 research of 0.258. The Dolan *et al.* 2005 Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 proportion of 0.000001 is not utilised.

⁴³The Danish Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010 paper has been taken out for reasons of accessibility. Further, the Finnish Heiskanen and Piispa 2001 study has been removed from all reviews too, as the primary data was surveyed before 2000, [in 1998].

Table 7.5.: Comparison of lost economic output.

Country ⁴⁴	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of Lost economic output [%] ⁴⁵	Share of Lost economic output on overall costs [%] ⁴⁶
Developed countries						
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003	4.79	0.05	0.02 ⁴⁷	31.03 ⁴⁸
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996	1.95	0.98	- ⁴⁹	-
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	1.00	0.47	0.00 ⁵⁰	0.72
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia 2016	[11.13]	1.35	0.12 ⁵¹	8.64
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	7.10	0.76	0.03 ⁵²	3.90

Continue on next page

⁴⁴For more detailed information, including all footnotes, see Section 3.4.1 Table 3.2 Due to reasons of access, the Helweg-Larsen *et al.* (Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010) from Denmark and the Heiskanen and Piispa (Heiskanen and Piispa 2001) from Finland are not included in any of the comparisons.

⁴⁵The figure presents the ratio of the lost economic output and the GDP share. Figures have been rounded up. All primary GDP data is listed in Section 3.4.1 and Chapter 16

⁴⁶The figure presents the ratio of the health cost-share [of GDP] and the overall proportion of cost [of GDP]. Figures have been rounded up.

⁴⁷The study computes the overall cost to be US\$ 1.8 billion. They include US\$ 0.9 billion in lost productivity from paid work and household chores for survivors of nonfatal IPV, and US\$ 0.9 billion of lifetime earnings lost by survivors of IPV homicide (Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003 p. 2). The U.S. 2003 GDP [in current LCU] was US\$ 11.458 trillion, according to World Bank 2018a

⁴⁸For instance, GPD lost economic output share 0.02 / overall GDP cost-share 0.05.

⁴⁹The paper does not compute the precise overall cost; it only states the assault cases, for instances. For example, the short-term productivity loss for an average assault case was computed to be US\$ 356, and long-term productivity losses were calculated to be US\$ 2,035 (Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996 p. 14).

⁵⁰The detailed figure is 0.003 per cent. Zhang *et al.* estimated the overall cost of C\$ 53,365,196. In detail, the overall economic loss for spousal violence in 2009 through lost wages was C\$ 33,671,686, (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 50) cost through lost household services was estimated to be C\$ 18,901,600, cost of lost education was C\$ 259,081 (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 51), and the economic loss through childcare services was C\$ 532,829 (Zhang *et al.* 2012, p. 52).

⁵¹The impact of violence against women and their children upon production and the business sector is estimated to be A\$ 1.9 billion. The most significant dimension of this loss was from survivors' absenteeism of paid and unpaid employment and the inability to perform household chores or voluntary work, which is A\$ 860 million. Further, it is calculated that perpetrator absenteeism costs [A\$ 443 million], and supplementary management charges, including search, contracting, and training replacements, will constitute overall to A\$ 96 million (KPMG Australia 2016 p. 5).

⁵²The total production-related costs are forecasted to be A\$ 609 million for the year 2021 to 2022 (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009 p. 45).

Continue Table 7.5

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of Lost economic output [%]	Share of Lost economic output on overall costs [%]
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a	5.00	1.07	0.06 ⁵³	5.99
U.K.	2009	Walby 2009	0.60	1.00	0.12 ⁵⁴	12.21
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson 2006	2.60	0.10	0.02 ⁵⁵	25.19
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017	3.00	0.12	0.01 ⁵⁶	4.54
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	1.26	0.03	0.01 ⁵⁷	24.39
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	5.00	0.17	0.03 ⁵⁸	15.96
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	2.00	0.22	0.04 ⁵⁹	16.35
Developing and emerging countries						
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012	25.40	3.19	- ⁶⁰	-
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011	24.00	2.10	0.87 ⁶¹	41.43
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	18.00	3.93	2.13 ⁶²	54.20
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	27.70	-	-	-
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	30.00	-	-	-
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014	20.00–30.00	0.90–1.30	- ⁶³	- ⁶⁴

Continue on next page

⁵³The estimated costs are A\$ 483.9 million (Access Economics 2004a p. 43). The LCU, A\$, is used throughout and converted based on a standardised value (Access Economics 2004a p. 20).

⁵⁴The overall estimated loss is £ 1,920 million (Walby 2009 p. 2).

⁵⁵The estimated production loss was kr 679 to kr 720 million (Envall and Eriksson 2006 p. 9). In line with this study scope, the lower bound estimate of kr 679 million is applied for calculation purposes.

⁵⁶The overall cost is € 172.6 million. They include the loss of productivity through death, which is € 91.7 million (Sacco 2017 p. 111), and the loss of productivity through suicide of € 80.9 million (Sacco 2017 p. 113).

⁵⁷The overall cost of lost productivity is CHF 40 million (Stern *et al.* 2013 p. 26).

⁵⁸The cost resulting from absenteeism is € 575,607,193 (Nectoux *et al.* 2010 p. 394).

⁵⁹The cost to employers is € 385,302,088 (Villagómez 2010 p. 6). Please note this study goes in this category beyond the scope of cost to employers and measures the economic losses for the survivors themselves.

⁶⁰Duvvury only lists the average losses per incident. She does not provide an overall estimate (Duvvury and Carney 2012 p. 82).

⁶¹Siddique 2011 p. 42 computes a total GDP income loss of 0.87 per cent.

⁶²The overall cost is 2.13 per cent of GDP. The figure is composed of first, the losses from missed income, which is 1.93 per cent of GDP and second, of unemployment, which is 0.20 per cent of GDP (Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 p. 28).

⁶³The paper does not provide an overall figure for lost earnings. KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 29 only states the individual cost to survivors.

⁶⁴The listed figures include morbidity for survivors only (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 30).

Continue Table 7.5

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of Lost economic output [%]	Share of Lost economic output on overall costs [%]
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine	10.00	0.23	0.00 ⁶⁵	0.05
Namibia	2021	Breuer	17.50 ⁶⁶	6.01	1.64	27.28

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

The following deductions can be made based on the findings:

1. Developed countries:

- a) The lowest GDP share commences at 0.003 per cent in the Canadian paper and was followed by a 0.01 per cent of GDP share in the German and Swiss studies, respectively (Sacco 2017, Stern *et al.* 2013, Zhang *et al.* 2012).⁶⁷
- b) The Australian KPMG and the British study estimate both with 0.12 per cent the highest GDP loss. However, the Australian KPMG study has a prevalence of 11.13 per cent,⁶⁸ while the British paper indicates a prevalence of 0.60 per cent; hence, it displays a fraction of the Australian cases only.⁶⁹ This fact demonstrates again how holistically and in-debt the British method is (KPMG Australia 2016, Walby 2009).⁷⁰
- c) The proportion of economic loss on the total cost differs widely. It commences with a ratio of only 0.72 per cent in the Canadian 2012 Zhang *et al.* study and increases up to 31 per cent, as in the U.S. 2003 NCIP&C report (Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003, Zhang *et al.* 2012).

⁶⁵The detailed figure is 0.0001 per cent. The total cost of this category was US\$ 96,500. The minimum cost of irreversible losses [deaths] was US\$ 44.1 thousand [US\$ 44,100], and losses due to injuries and incapacity were US\$ 52.4 thousand [US\$ 52,400] (UNFPA Ukraine 2017, p. 33).

⁶⁶For more information on the used primary data, see Chapter 6.

⁶⁷Germany's prevalence is 3.00, and the Swiss 1.26 per cent. Although the Swiss prevalence ratio is less than half of the German Sacco study, the computed loss in terms of GDP share is equal. Stern *et al.*'s method is more detailed, as it calculates not only losses through death and suicide, as Sacco does (Sacco 2017, p. 111,113), but also includes the losses resulting from illness and invalidity (Stern *et al.* 2013, p. 27).

⁶⁸Regarding the 11.30 per cent in KPMG Australia 2016, the primary data refers to *since the age of 15, not to within the past 12 months* (Australian Bureau of Statistics 2012).

⁶⁹This also applies when using the UN data for Australia for this period, although the rate is lower now. According to data of the Australian Bureau of Statistics 2012, UN Women 2018a, the ratio of physical and or sexual IPV in the last 12 months was two per cent only, for instance. For more information, see Chapter 15.

⁷⁰For more details, see Chapter 3.

In summary, systematic variations mainly have yielded this diversity in output. This again stresses the significant impact of the applied methodical set-up on the outcome.

2. Developing and emerging countries:

- a) According to Table 7.5 nearly 60 per cent – four out of seven – of the studies did not adequately estimate the lost economic output. As a consequence, their overall GDP results are downsized considerably.
- b) Nonetheless, those that have included this category fully reflect a high loss in GDP share. The lost economic output of Siddique 2011 amounts to over 40 per cent of all losses, and Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 even report a share of nearly 55 per cent.
- c) The research of Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 on Colombia is comparable to the Namibian study in both prevalence ratio and GDP share. The author reports an Economic Loss of 2.13 per cent based on a prevalence ratio of 18 per cent. The Namibian estimates reflect a share of 1.64 per cent deriving from a 17.50 per cent prevalence.⁷¹

However, the Colombian and Namibian prevalence is similar. Thus, a theoretical simulation is conducted to interpret the Namibian results in more detail against other literature. The outcome of the studies that have been fully calculating this category is hypothetically adjusted to the Namibian prevalence ratio of 17.50 per cent. Table 7.6 depicts the findings in greater detail.

⁷¹For more information on the composition of the 17.50 per cent, see Chapter 6

Table 7.6.: Comparison of adjusted lost economic output.

Country ⁷²	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New Prevalence [%]	Old GDP share of Lost economic output [%] ⁷³	New GDP share of Lost economic output [%] ⁷⁴	Increase of costs [%] ⁷⁵
Developed countries							
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC)	4.79	17.50	0.02	0.07	250
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema	1.95	17.50	–	–	–
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i>	1.00	17.50	0.003	0.05	1,567
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia	[11.13]	17.50	0.12	0.19	58
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C)	7.10	17.50	0.03	0.07	133
Australia	2004	Access Economics	5.00	17.50	0.06	0.21	250
U.K.	2009	Walby	0.60	17.50	0.12	3.50	2,817
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson	2.60	17.50	0.02	0.13	550
Germany	2017	Sacco	3.00	17.50	0.01	0.06	500
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i>	1.26	17.50	0.01	0.14	1,300
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i>	5.00	17.50	0.03	0.11	267
Spain	2010	Villagómez	2.00	17.50	0.04	0.35	775
Developing and emerging countries							
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney	25.40	17.50	–	–	–
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique	24.00	17.50	0.87	0.63	–28
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres	18.00	17.50	2.13	2.07	–3.00
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i>	27.70	17.50	–	–	–

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⁷²For more detailed information, including all footnotes, see Section 3.4.1. For a more detailed explanation of the arithmetic, including all relevant footnotes, see Table 7.5. All studies will be set in comparison, even when methodologically immature, to establish the most holistically overview possible.

⁷³The column presents the ratio of the lost economic output and GDP share. The figures are rounded up.

⁷⁴The column depicts a theoretical simulation when applying a Namibian prevalence ratio of 17.50 per cent. The following arithmetic has been used: [old GDP share [%]/old Prevalence [%]] · Namibian prevalence ratio of 17.50 per cent = adjusted GDP share [%]. Any rounding differences during the different steps of estimations are acknowledged.

⁷⁵This column presents the difference between the new and old GDP shares, divided by the old GDP shares.

Continue Table 7.6

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New Prevalence [%]	Old GDP share of Lost economic output [%]	New GDP share of Lost economic output [%]	Increase of costs [%]
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	30.00	17.50	–	–	–
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014	20.00	17.50	–	–	–
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine 2017	10.00	17.50	0.00 ⁷⁶	0.00 ⁷⁷	100
Namibia	2021	Breuer 2021	17.50	17.50	1.64	1.64	0.00

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.
Source: Own representation.

The following deductions can be conducted based on the findings:

1. Developed countries:

- a) The GDP share increased from 58 per cent in the KPMG Australia 2016 study to up to 2,817 per cent in the British Walby 2009 report, which methodical set-up serves as a baseline to this paper. Further, the Walby 2009 publication is the only paper with a higher theoretical new GDP share of lost economic output, namely, 3.50 per cent, compared to the Namibian outcome of 1.64 per cent.

2. Developing and emerging countries:

- a) The baseline data of the developing economies showcased majorly already a higher prevalence compared to Namibia; consequently, the findings depict a different development⁷⁸. In summary, the GDP cost-share has decreased. However, after adjusting the prevalence, the Ribero and Sánchez Torres study shows with 2.07 per cent of GDP still a slightly higher cost-share than the Namibian 1.64 per cent ratio, and hence, it is among the few papers with a similar outcome.

Figure 7.1 showcases the data in greater detail.

In summary, compared to the other literature, the estimated results are relatively high. The two studies of Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004, Walby 2009 state similar results, as both use a rather detailed approach as well⁷⁹.

⁷⁶Detailed figure 0.0001 per cent.

⁷⁷Detailed figure 0.0002 per cent.

⁷⁸The GDP share decreased by 28 per cent in the Siddique 2011 study on Bangladesh and three per cent in the Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 paper on Colombia. In detail, Siddique had a decrease of 28 per cent in GDP share based on a 27 per cent drop in prevalence [17.50 per cent – 24.00 per cent/24.00 per cent]. Ribero and Sánchez Torres show a three per cent decline in GDP ratio, originating from a 2.80 per cent reduction in prevalence [17.50 per cent – 18.00 per cent/18.00 per cent]. The decline in prevalence ratio and GDP share is equivalent. Nonetheless, in the case of Ukraine, due to rounding differences, a different outcome grew evident. The increase of costs of 100 per cent grew proportionally more extensive compared to its rise in the prevalence ratio, with an increase of 75 per cent only [17.50 per cent – 10.00 per cent/10.00 per cent].

⁷⁹For more information, see Chapters 3 and 5.

Legend: 1. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) [2003]. 2. Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996]. 3. Zhang *et al.* [2012]. 4. KPMG Australia [2016]. 5. National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) [2009]. 6. Access Economics [2004a]. 7. Walby [2009]. 8. Envall and Eriksson [2006]. 9. Sacco [2017]. 10. Stern *et al.* [2013]. 11. Nectoux *et al.* [2010]. 12. Villagómez [2010]. 13. Duvvury and Carney [2012]. 14. Siddique [2011]. 15. Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004]. 16. Duvvury *et al.* [2009] (for Morocco), 17. Duvvury *et al.* [2009] (for Uganda), 18. KPMG South Africa [2014]. 19. UNFPA Ukraine [2017] and 20. Breuer [2021].

Figure 7.1.: Comparison of adjusted lost economic output.

In order to continue, Section 7.5.3 will report on different aspects and obstacles that became apparent during the evaluation process.

7.5.3. Further discussion

The following paragraphs review the calculation of the economic costs of mental health problems, rape, and sexual assault in more detail.

Economic costs of mental health problems resulting from physical violence

Walby and Allen [2004] p. 34 state that 31 per cent of women and nine per cent of men suffered from mental distress. However, Walby and Allen [2004] do not provide a detailed conclusion on psychological problems caused by physical abuse. As a result, this study uses the detailed data from Dolan’s (Dolan *et al.* [2005] p. 972) and Dubourg’s (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] p. 34) category, called “other wounding” to compute the economic loss that derives from mental health problems.⁸⁰ Hence, the losses from acute stress disorders, mid/moderate PTSDs, and severe PTSDs could be calculated. Further, substitute categories were set in proportion to Walby’s

⁸⁰Dubourg’s and Dolan’s category “other wounding” (Dolan *et al.* [2005] p. 972) is the most similar to Walby’s category, called “injuries sustained in the worst incident of Domestic Violence” (Walby and Allen [2004] p. 34). Further, the estimations include the health loss from acute stress disorder for non-sexual assaults too (Dolan *et al.* [2005] p. 972).

findings to keep the exact proportions.⁸¹ Nonetheless, for the physical violence probabilities, the data on drug- and alcohol abuse, obesity, or anxiety were not given by Walby, Dolan, and Dubourg⁸² and thus could not be estimated. Consequently, the calculated economic loss depicts an underestimation. Further, for the category of sexual violence, the available research and data support the calculation of losses from short-term and moderate depression. However, the Namibian ratios do not distinguish between mild, moderate, severe, short-term, or long-term depression.⁸³ Consequently, there might be an underestimation of costs in this area too. More in-depth research is needed to fill these gaps and to provide better information. Hence, the missing data for sexual violence translates into a general problem to calculate the costs of rape. The next paragraph will explain this matter in more detail.

Economic costs of rape

The available data indicates that rape reported to the police in South Africa represents only the tip of the iceberg. Non-consensual sex in marriage and relationships is believed to be common and is usually not well reported in surveys. Besides, forced intercourse is a prevalent problem in schools, workplaces, and other peer group settings. Hence rape statistics for South Africa are currently elusive, and international comparisons need to be approached cautiously. Besides the already known underreporting of incidents, in addition, most developing nations lack the infrastructure of accurate crime reporting (Jewkes and Abrahams 2002).⁸⁴ Therefore, figures probably present an underestimation of actual expenses incurred. In general, the calculation of the economic loss of rape includes the estimation of financial impacts resulting from unwanted pregnancy, abortion, including the associated female mortality, psychological and maternal consequences. These topics are discussed in the next paragraph.

Unwanted pregnancy

Research conducted for the E.U. indicates that rape and sexual assault lead in four to five per cent to an unwanted pregnancy (Walby and Allen 2004, p. 35).⁸⁵ There is no reliable data on unwanted pregnancies caused by rape for the Namibian context yet. Further, contraceptive methods, such as birth control, are less common compared to the E.U. and the U.S, for

⁸¹For details, see Chapter 16.

⁸²For details, see Walby and Allen 2004, p. 34; Dolan *et al.* 2005, p. 972; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 34.

⁸³For example, according to Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 38, moderate, short-term depression accounted for 89 days off-work, and severe, long-term depression constitutes 835 days of lost work.

⁸⁴Further, as indicated, the costs resulting from psychological abuse, including a detailed estimate of various types of depression, in the form of mild, moderate, severe, short or long-term depression is not carried out for rape cases by Walby and Allen 2004, p. 35, Dolan *et al.* 2005, p. 974; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 34. As a result, only the category of moderate, short-term depression could be computed for the crime type of rape (Dolan *et al.* 2005, p. 974). Although Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 38 distinguish between different forms of depression for other violent crimes. For instance, according to the authors, long-term, severe depression amounts to the highest ratio of lost workdays. However, for rape, this detailed allocation is not made, and consequently, the cost cannot be estimated in detail.

⁸⁵Of these, 50 per cent underwent an abortion (Holmes, Resnick, and Best 1996, p. 320–325). Nonetheless, this research is conducted for developed countries. In Namibia, procedures of abortion are nearly impossible to perform, as it is generally prohibited by law (Dianne 2017).

instance. Besides, fertility ratios in Namibia are at 3.6 children per woman higher too (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 65). Consequently, the probability of unwanted pregnancy, and thus, the associated costs are assumed to be more considerable.

Abortion

For the developed nations, the costs deriving from the termination of pregnancy (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 p. 41–43) as well as such of abortion [in case it is legal] can be estimated (Dolan *et al.* 2005, p. 974). For instance, Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 41–43 calculated the costs for Great Britain. However, such data is not available in Namibia. Abortion is pushed into the area of illegality because of its lengthy administrative procedures and as it is only allowed in rare cases, among others (Dianne 2017). Consequently, death and injuries from unsafe practices are a current topic (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 93) that causes a high financial burden to society as well. In summary, reliable data is not accessible, and thus, the overall computed cost-share likely represents an underestimation⁸⁶

Female mortality ratio

Another issue that cannot be fully accounted for is the female mortality ratio due to abortion and complications in pregnancy or childbirth. The number of women and girls who died worldwide from complications of pregnancy and childbirth was 289,000 in 2013. Almost all of these deaths [99 per cent] occurred in developing and emerging nations (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 93). The percentage of Namibian maternal deaths for the age cohort of 15 to 49 years is 8.60 per cent (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 96). However, the calculation of costs resulting from mortality due to complications from unwanted pregnancies caused by rape cannot be made, as such detailed information is not available in Namibia [yet].

Psychological consequences

The literature on the economic implications of abortions and unwanted pregnancies is limited; thus, it is further challenging to calculate the financial burden of psychological impacts on mothers and their [unwanted] children. As stated, such expenses cannot be estimated yet, and in consequence, more research and data are needed.

Maternal and neonatal health

Among Namibian women aged 15 to 49 who are pregnant, 5.50 per cent have ever experienced physical violence during their pregnancy (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 302). GBV correlates with decreased maternal and neonatal health. According to Silverman *et al.* 2006 women who reported GBV in the year before pregnancy were at increased risk of:

- high blood pressure or oedema [adjusted OR 1.37–1.40],
- vaginal bleeding [adjusted OR 1.54–1.66],
- kidney or urinary tract infection [adjusted OR 1.43–1.55],

⁸⁶In general, the provision of safety services, as it is allowed by law, could reduce maternal deaths and injuries caused by unsafe abortions (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 93).

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- dehydration, severe nausea, or vomiting [adjusted OR 1.48–1.63],
 - hospital visits related to morbidity [adjusted OR 1.45–1.48],
 - preterm childbirth [adjusted OR 1.37],
 - a low birth weight of the infant [adjusted OR 1.17], and
 - an infant needing intensive care [adjusted OR of 1.31–1.33] (Silverman *et al.* 2006, p. 140–148).

Moreover, women reporting GBV during but not before their pregnancy experienced higher ratios of all subsets of these concerns too. Nonetheless, there are not any established approaches yet on how to calculate such losses. Further, the impact of violence during pregnancy may have long-term effects on the newborn as well. These [lifetime] economic losses are not part of this study’s cost estimate but are envisaged to increase the overall expenses further.

Economic costs of sexual assault

This category should be interpreted as an incomplete account of the full extent of GBV as it does not include many other kinds of sexual assault, including stalking, unwanted pressure, or spreading rumours. According to the U.N., sexual harassment and assault are defined as; “Actual or attempted rape, or sexual assault, unwanted pressure for sexual favours, unwanted deliberate touching, leaning over, cornering, or pinching, unwanted sexual looks or gestures, telling lies or spreading rumours about a person’s personal sex life” (U.S. Equal Employment Opportunity Commission 2018; UN Women 2018b). The category is computed by Dolan *et al.* 2005, p. 966 and in detail, by Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 33–34. Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 43–44 clearly distinguish the associated Intangible cost of rape. However, MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 96 does not define what the study’s notion of sexual violence covers explicitly. Therefore, it remains unclear whether the report’s data includes sexual assault as well.

To conclude, the calculation of such specific types of costs is currently not entirely feasible, and better approaches are needed in the future.

7.6. Summary

Chapter 7 computed the lost economic output. The calculation is based on datasets of Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Walby 2004; Walby 2009. The therapy cost was partially converted with World Bank 2018e data. The case numbers were estimated based on the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b data and based on research by Jewkes *et al.* 2010. The calculated loss is 1.64 per cent of the Namibian gross domestic product in 2018. This result is one of the highest among the examined studies. However, it must be noted that, especially in developing and emerging countries, in almost 60 per cent of the studies, no adequate calculations were carried out. When the prevalence ratios are theoretically raised to the Namibian level, the overall results changed in summary as follows: the British Walby 2004 study has a significantly higher cost-share than in Namibia. The Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 paper also still depicts a higher GDP share for the developing and emerging countries. The chosen methodology in this paper is very detailed and holistic. The costs for both men and women were also included, which often is not conducted in research. All expenses related to mental health restrictions were calculated too.

In order to continue, Chapter 8 will present the calculation of the health service costs.

8. Health service costs

8.1. Introduction

GBV has consequences for the survivor's physical and mental health and bears costs for societies to provide adequate health services. Chapter 8 calculates the health service costs. The method used is based on work by Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, as their QALY data is applied. Chapter 8 describes the primary data used, and basic data from Dubourg 2005 and the NDHS 2014 are applied. Treatment data derives from Dubourg's 2005 categories and NAMPOL 2012 to 2015 case numbers, and based on such, key multiplier figures are calculated. The NHDS-based survey data are compared with the NAMPOL statistic to get a better approximation of the actual number of cases. A summary of the results is then presented and discussed (Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; MoHSS and ICF International 2014; Namibian Police (NAMPOL) 2012). In Section 8.5.2, comparison is made with other countries. In order to achieve detailed insights, the prevalence ratios were raised to the Namibian level. The data will be discussed further in Section 8.5.3. The results and problems that occurred during the calculation will also be presented.

8.2. Approach

The approach of Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 was identified as the most appropriate to compute the health service costs for this context.

The following paragraph provides a summary of the method.

Health-state approach

The model developed by Dolan *et al.*; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns to estimate the adverse health states has been identified as being best appropriate to determine the health service costs for the scope of this study. In summary, the method is robustly underpinned and has higher replicability and feasibility compared to other models. The main advantage is that the requirements for data are low, and information is frequently available¹. As already explained, the Quality of Life Years [QALY] losses constitutes the basis of this method. The approach modelled QALY health losses from the prevalence of injuries of different violent crimes reported

¹For details, see Chapters 3 and 5

to national surveys (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005), and added psychological trauma outcomes to each type of crime (Walby and Olive 2014). For the category of rape, the probability of other adverse mental health state outcome was calculated for different consequences too. They include, among others, drug and alcohol abuse, depression, suicide, obesity, eating disorders, anxiety, or sexual dysfunction (Dolan *et al.* 2005). Hence, the model has established the foundation to estimate the average health treatment costs for each crime category.² This study uses data from The Namibian Police 2018 and the Namibian NDHS, MoHSS and ICF International 2014 to calculate multipliers. In summary, the following primary data sources are used within estimations.

8.3. Data

Section 8.3 presents a review of the primary literature data applied in this cost class.³

Basic data

- USAID 2017: data on the total cost of inpatient care per visit and the average cost of general inpatient care per day in public, district hospitals, and private health facilities (Cico, Jones, and Musau 2017 p. 14 f.). which is N\$ 414 in public, district hospitals, and N\$ 1,805 in private health facilities (Cico, Jones, and Musau 2017 p. 15).
- NDHS 2014: the estimates utilise census and prevalence data from the 2013 Namibian National Survey [NDHS] (MoHSS and ICF International 2014).⁴ The next paragraph depicts the detailed calculation of the treatment costs data.

Treatment cost data

The vast majority of the population [85 per cent] is not covered by any medical aid plan and relies on the public sector funding to provide health care. The public health sector charges generally smaller user fees. On the other hand, health coverage is also offered through diverse private medical aid funds; however, this type of insurance is unaffordable for most citizens (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 274). As there is a large gap between public and private health service costs, the costs for both are calculated separately. Table 8.1 presents the computed treatment cost data.

The following paragraph will explain further details of the computed numbers.

²Please read Section 6.2 for detailed information on the reasons why Dolan's and Dubourg's findings apply to Namibia as well.

³Chapter 6 describes the fundamental data that serves as a baseline for each category. This outline summarises them.

⁴For more information, see Chapter 6.

Table 8.1.: Health service treatment costs.

Categories	Public health facilities, treatment cost [N\$], in 2018	Private health facilities, treatment cost [N\$], in 2018
Homicide	1,462	5,033
Wounding	2,443	10,650
Sexual offences	13,778	51,666
Common Assault	1,462	5,032

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Homicide

According to the USAID 2017 report, the total cost of inpatient care per visit is N\$ 1,239 in public, district hospitals and N\$ 4,265 in private health facilities (Cico, Jones, and Musau 2017 p. 14). The team reported all costs in 2015 Namibian dollars (Cico, Jones, and Musau 2017 p. 7). The Consumer Price Index [CPI] index 2015–2018 is 1.18 [152,292/128,905]. [The CPI [2010=100] was 128,905 in 2015 and 152,292 in 2018] (World Bank 2020a). In 2018 Namibia dollars, the cost is N\$ 1,462.02 in public, district hospitals, and N\$ 5,032.7 in private health facilities. Dubourg provides the per-day hospital stay length for different crime types, including wounding or rape (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 p. 43), but not for a homicide case. Due to the nature of the crime, it is rated in this paper with the average cost of one visit.

Wounding

According to the USAID 2017 report, the average cost of general inpatient care per day is N\$ 414 in public, district hospitals and N\$ 1,805 in private health facilities (Cico, Jones, and Musau 2017 p. 15). The team reported all costs in 2015 Namibian dollars (Cico, Jones, and Musau 2017 p. 7). The CPI index 2015–2018 is 1.18 (World Bank 2020a). In 2018 Namibia dollars, the cost is N\$ 488.52 in district hospitals and N\$ 2,129.9 in private health facilities. According to Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 p. 43 wounding cases related to GBV incidents require five days of treatment. Therefore, the cost is multiplied each by five and is N\$ 2,442.6 in public, district hospitals and N\$ 10,649.5 in private health facilities.

Sexual offences

According to Christofides *et al.* 2006, Tab. 7a, the average cost of a single rape case, including medical therapy provided only on that particular day but without trauma or HIV follow-up assistance, is R 6,320. The paper was published in 2006, and the data was surveyed in 2004. It is assumed that the cost can be transferred to Namibia, as the Namibia dollar is paired to the South African Rand, with an exchange rate of 1:1 (XE 2020). The CPI index 2004–2018 is 2.18. [152.292/69.812. The CPI [2010=100] was 69.812 in 2004 and 152.292 in 2018] (World Bank 2020a). In 2018 Namibia dollars, the cost is N\$ 13,777.6 [R 13,777.6]. Christofides *et al.* derive the data from the “Thuthuzela Care Centre – Rape Crisis programme” (Christofides *et al.* 2006, Tab. 7a). The team does not distinguish between public, district hospitals, and private health facilities. According to the findings of homicide and wounding, private health care is

on average, 3.75 times higher than public health care.⁵ In 2018 Namibia dollars, the cost for public health care is N\$ 13,777.6, and for private health care N\$ 51,666.

Common Assault

According to Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns (2005) p. 43, common assault cases require one hospital day. However, this paper rates this crime type with the Namibian cost of inpatient care per visit, not per day, because the average Namibian price for one visit is more holistic and fit the Dubourg category structure better, compared to the per-day cost (Cico, Jones, and Musau (2017) p. 14 f.). In 2018 Namibia dollars, the cost of inpatient care per visit is N\$ 1,462.02 in public, district hospitals, and N\$ 5,032.70 in private health facilities. [The detailed calculation can be found under the category Homicide]. Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns (2005) p. 43 researched that common assault cases related to GBV incidents require one day of treatment; hence, the cost is multiplied by a factor of 1.

The following paragraph outlines the detailed calculation of the case numbers and multiplier data.

Case numbers and multiplier data

- NAMPOL 2012–2015: in the first step, the yearly NAMPOL case numbers are evaluated. Therefore, police records on GBV crimes surveyed for three years are used and are broken down to a per annum period (Hartman (2016)), and then the data is inflated to 2018 figures, see Table 8.2⁶

Nonetheless, NAMPOL, and in general, any police records, reflect a significant underrepresentation of the real numbers. Sexual crime is the most underreported offence worldwide, especially in Africa (Forde (2018)). As a result, correct census data is needed to compute the case numbers based on the NDHS prevalence ratios. Table 8.3 summarises the calculations to obtain more realistic case numbers.

In Table 8.4 the NDHS prevalence percentages will be applied to this census data.

⁵[(3.44 + 4.36 + 3.44)/3], Homicide factor: 3.44 (Private: N\$ 5,033, Public: N\$ 1,462), Wounding factor: 4.36 (Private: N\$ 10,650, Public: N\$ 2,443), and Common assault factor: 3.44 (Private: N\$ 5,032 Public: N\$ 1,462)]

⁶For more information on issues surrounding multiplier calculations, see Section 6.4

Table 8.2.: Calculation of case numbers based on NAMPOL data.

Crime category ⁷	NAMPOL data 2012–2015 [numbers] (Hartman 2016) ⁸	Overall incidents, p.a. [numbers] ⁹	Inflated 2018 NAMPOL data, p.a. [numbers] (Hartman 2016) ¹⁰
Homicide	734	245	260
Wounding	23,312 ¹¹	7,770 ¹²	8,162
Sexual offences	2,839 ¹³	946	1,003
Common Assault	18,054	6,018	6,379

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Table 8.3.: Calculation of case numbers based on census and NDHS data I: women.

Current female population [numbers] in 2018 ¹⁴	15 to 49 years [numbers] in 2018 ¹⁵	Suffering from physical violence in the past 12 months [13.80%] [numbers] in 2018 ¹⁶	Suffering from sexual violence in the past 12 months [3.70%] [numbers] in 2018 ¹⁷
1,328,333 (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b)	689,222 (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b)	95,113	25,501

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

⁷Estimates are based on Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 p. 7, 19, 41 (Tab. 4.1) and 43.

⁸The numbers were calculated based on NAMPOL records for the three years of 2012 to 2015, which is the most recent and comprehensive data (Hartman 2016).

⁹Based on the three years (Hartman 2016), the per annum data was calculated since any other published NAMPOL statistics were not that comprehensive (Namibian Police (NAMPOL) 2012).

¹⁰The NAMPOL data is from 2012–2015. The data is used because they were at the point of research, the most holistic findings available. However, the output is indicated as a proportion of the 2018 GDP. Hence, the numbers were adjusted to 2018 figures. The Namibian population was 2,448,255 in 2018. In 2015 it was 2,314,904 citizens (World Bank 2020c). The factor is around 1.06. Hence, all NAMPOL figures are inflated by factor 1.06.

¹¹The figures include the wounding impact of severe assault and attempted murder. In three years, in summary, the statistics have recorded 22,174 cases of severe assault and 1,138 cases of attempted murder (Hartman 2016).

¹²Overall, a combined number of 7391 severe assaults and 379 attempted murder cases were filed in a single year (Hartman 2016).

¹³The NAMPOL data only include rape cases (Hartman 2016) and no other sexual offence data, like sexual assault, for instance.

Table 8.4.: Calculation of case numbers based on census and NDHS data II: women.

Crime categories ¹⁸	NDHS ratios [%]	Affected female population [numbers]	Total yearly cases [numbers]
Homicide	–	–	245
Wounding	34.80	95,113	33,099
	<i>Serious wounding</i>		
	<i>Other woundings</i>		
Sexual offences	3.70	689,222	25,501
Common assault	27.70	95,113	26,346

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

The next paragraphs provide further explanation of the calculations.

NDHS ratios [%]:

According to the NDHS, the ratios were surveyed for spousal violence only (MoHSS and ICF International ²⁰¹⁴ p. 311). The assumption is made that the proportions are transferable to the overall cohort of survivors. As a result, the ratio [13.80 per cent] is applied to the overall number of the current female population, 15 to 49 years, suffering from physical violence in the past 12 months in 2018¹⁹

Homicide

The NDHS does not state homicide or mortality data (MoHSS and ICF International ²⁰¹⁴ p. 300); therefore, the calculations use NAMPOL records, which can be used for this crime type.

Wounding

The wounding data combines serious wounding [as deep wounds, broken bones, broken teeth, or any other serious injury] and different wounding prevalences [including eye injuries, sprains, dislocations, or burns]. The prevalences were surveyed for women only. The wounding ratio of 34.80 per cent combines severe wounding [as deep wounds, broken bones, broken teeth, or any other serious injury] and the additional wounding prevalence [including eye injuries, sprains, dislocations, or burns]. Overall, the 34.80 per cent is a combination of 15.50 per cent and 19.30 per cent depicted in the subsequent row. This ratio includes physical violence only.

¹⁴This calculation could only be conducted for women; as for men, there was not enough data available (MoHSS and ICF International ²⁰¹⁴ p. 312–314).

¹⁵This age cohort is chosen as the U.N. development goals on GBV, mainly includes the age cohort 15 to 49 (UN Women ^{2018a}).

¹⁶For more information on the composition of the 17.50 per cent, see Section ^{6.4}

¹⁷In detail, 3.70 per cent of Namibian women aged 15 to 49 often or sometimes have experienced sexual abuse in the past 12 months before the study, including perpetrators as [former] partner/husbands as well as other siblings [father, mother, brother], or employer (MoHSS and ICF International ²⁰¹⁴ p. 300).

¹⁸The categories are based on the findings of Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns ²⁰⁰⁵ p. 19, 43.

¹⁹See Chapter ¹⁷ in the Appendix for more information.

Sexual abuse is listed separately in the table column sexual offences. The category of serious wounding includes deep wounds, broken bones, broken teeth, or any other serious injury. A ratio of 15.50 per cent of Namibian women who have experienced physical violence in the past 12 months suffered deep wounds, broken bones, broken teeth, or any other serious injury. The category of other woundings includes eye injuries, sprains, dislocations, or burns. In sum, 19.30 per cent of Namibian women who experienced physical violence in the past 12 months suffered eye injuries, sprains, dislocations, or burns (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 311).

Sexual offences

The NDHS titles this category “sexual violence” (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 300). The number of 689,222 is derived from the following calculation: the current female population ratio, aged 15 to 49 years, suffering from sexual violence in the past 12 months, is 3.70 per cent (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 300). Please note that the sexual offence case number calculation differs from the one in Section 7.3. In Chapter 7, the lost economic output is calculated, and thus, the formula integrates the 3.20 per cent of Namibian women aged 20 to 49, who never had sexual intercourse to avoid bias (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 50). Here, the 3.70 per cent figure representing the intercourse ratio under the age of 15 [without the additional 3.20 per cent ratio who never had sexual contact] is applied to compute the case numbers for sexual offences.

Common assault

In detail, 27.70 per cent of Namibian women who experienced physical violence in the past 12 months suffered from cuts, bruises, or aches (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 311). This figure includes physical abuse only, as sexual violence is listed separately under sexual offences.²⁰

Table 8.5 compares the NDHS results with the NAMPOL numbers to achieve better insights into the set of multipliers.²¹

In summary, the comparison depicts similar findings to other research in the Southern African region with a comparable proportion of underreporting.²² As a result, the baseline for all calculations is the NDHS single year’s estimates.

The next paragraph elaborates on further issues that influence the case number data.

²⁰For more information on the calculation of the number 95,113, see the explanation in the row of wounding.

²¹See Section 6.4 for more details.

²²There is an underreporting in the NAMPOL data. Nonetheless, the direct comparison between NAMPOL and NDHS data aims to back the utilisation of the latter one. Consequently, this paper’s calculations utilise grounded data derived from the extensive, nationwide panel surveys in the NDHS (MoHSS and ICF International 2014; Namibian Police (NAMPOL) 2012).

²³The NDHS does not record homicide/mortality data (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 300). The NAMPOL data that can be used for this category is thus applied.

²⁴Cases of severe assault 7,391 and attempted murder 46 combined.

Table 8.5.: Comparison of NDHS and NAMPOL data.

Categories	NDHS based cases, p.a. [numbers]	NAMPOL cases, p.a. [numbers]	Multiplier [numbers]
Homicide	245	245	1 ²³
Wounding	33,099	7,770 ²⁴	4
Sexual offences	25,501	946	27
Common Assault	26,346	6,018	4

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Problems in computing health service costs in Namibia

However, when reading the listed GBV case numbers, the issue has to be taken into consideration that a variety of obstacles prevent survivors from obtaining health services. In consequence, because of such barriers, the actual economic costs are assumed to be lower, as a major part of the population is actually hindered from receiving adequate health care treatment. The case numbers are further adjusted, as there is a large gap between private and public costs of service provision. In Namibia, the vast majority of the population [85 per cent] is not covered by any medical aid plan and relies on the public sector funding to provide health care. The public health sector charges generally smaller user fees that are better affordable to the general public. On the other hand, health coverage is also offered through diverse private medical aid funds; however, this type of insurance is unaffordable for most citizens (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#), p. 274). In order to compute realistic case numbers, this situation has to be acknowledged in the data, and separate calculations for private and public health service costs have to be carried out, and the following division, showcased in Table [8.6](#) is made.

Table 8.6.: Ratios to adjust case numbers.

Category	Ratio [%]
Women without access to medical aid services	31
Female clients of private service providers	10
Female clients of public service providers	59
Total GBV female cohort in need for health services	100

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Women without access to medical aid services

When reading the high GBV case numbers, the fact has to be kept in mind that many hurdles prevent individuals from receiving medical services and treatment. In the 2014 NDHS, Namibian women age 15–49 were asked what factors have hindered them from seeking medical care when they are sick. The main barriers are in descending order:

1. a large distance to a health facility [31 per cent],
2. to get money for treatment [28 per cent],
3. the fear of not wanting to go alone [15 per cent],

4. to get permission to go for treatment [6 per cent] (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 114) ²⁵

Consequently, because of such barriers, the real economic costs are assumed to be lower, as a major part of the population is actually prevented from receiving adequate health care treatment. In total, 31 per cent of women are hindered due to issues of large distances to health care providers [this percentage does not include the additional listed obstacles such as restricted financial means, among others, to go for treatment] of accessing basic health care services. ²⁶

Female clients of private service providers

As said, only a certain part of the population has access to medical care. For instance, the source of advice or treatment for children with fever is for 12 per cent of the population, any private-sector source (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 166). Eleven per cent of women and nine per cent of men have some type of employer-based health medical aid coverage (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 274). This data is in line with the ratios for HIV testing. In total, ten per cent of women utilise private health care facilities for HIV testing (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 229). Within these calculations, the ten per cent ratio is used as a multiplier and is applied to the NDHS data to extract the private health care cohort.

Female clients of public service providers

The remaining share within this construction is 59 per cent [100 per cent – 31 per cent – 10 per cent]. In order to evaluate whether this assumption is valid, the data is referenced with maternal data in the NDHS that reflect the percentages of how many women had contact with public health facilities. According to the NDHS, 82 per cent of births took place in public

²⁵The report does not state from whom (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 114).

²⁶The NDHS provided detailed insights on the topic. The number of eligible women interviewed in the report was 9,176 (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 9). Double answers of obstacles that hindered access to medical treatment were allowed. In detail, the following percentages were surveyed: for the age cohort 35–49: getting permission to go for treatment = 5.70 per cent, getting money for treatment = 29.10 per cent, distance to health facility = 33.30 per cent, not wanting to go alone = 13.90 per cent, at least one problem accessing health care = 44.10 per cent, which is 126.10 per cent in total, as double counting was allowed (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 114). Single obstacles are analysed in detail too. For instance, the issue of getting money for treatment was for the age 15–19 = 26.80 per cent of 1,906 women in this age cohort, 20–34 = 27.00 per cent of 4,535 women in this age cohort, and for age 35–49 = 29.10 per cent of 2,735 women in this age cohort, which sums up to the total of 9,176 women interviewed. When calculating: 26.80 per cent · 1,906 women in this age cohort + 27.00 per cent · 4,535 women in this age cohort + 29.10 per cent · 2,735 women in this age cohort = 2,531 women in all age cohorts, which is 27.58 per cent [2,531/9,176] of all women in the total sample, who reported this problem. Further, the NDHS states that the most common factor impeding women from accessing health care for themselves is, for 31 per cent, the distance to a health facility. Due to the previously mentioned double counting, it is unclear how many women reported obstacles in general, and the NDHS does not provide this figure either. Hence, a minimum of 31 per cent of women is hindered due to large distances [this percentage does not include the additional mentioned obstacles such as restricted financial means or getting the permission to go for treatment, among others] of accessing primary health care services. Therefore, the figure presents the minimum percentage of women that experienced obstacles. The data refers to seeking health care when being sick and are not specifically geared towards GBV cases. However, it is assumed that women would report the same barriers they face when being ill, during pregnancy or childbirth, also in situations of GBV.

health facilities, five per cent in private facilities, and 12 per cent at home (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 105). If the 31 per cent of women who reported not having had access to health services in the GBV sample is taken into account, this pattern is shown in the GBV cohort as well, and theoretically, 85 per cent of women in the GBV cohort, had contact to public health care facilities²⁷. The data is also in alignment with the findings of Breuer 2015, p. 48, who surveyed Namibian GBV survivors regarding their satisfaction with [public health] care institutions. The results state that nearly half of the sample group [47 per cent] had contact with a public hospital.

Table 8.7 presents the adjusted case numbers.

Table 8.7.: Adjusted GBV case numbers.

Categories	Cases p.a. [numbers]	Cases without cohort that does not have access to health care services, p.a. [numbers] [31%]	Private health facilities, adjusted cases p.a. [numbers] [10%]	Public health facilities, adjusted cases p.a. [numbers] [59%]
Homicide	245	76	25 [24.5]	145 [144.55]
Wounding	33,099	10,261	3,310	19,528
Sexual abuse	25,501	7,905	2,550	15,046
Common Assault	26,346	8,167	2,635	15,544

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Section 8.4 depicts the results obtained from the presented unit cost data and overall case numbers.

8.4. Results

Table 8.8 displays the results when these percentages are included and applied to the overall case numbers to produce an estimate that reflects the Namibian reality better.

²⁷ $\frac{59\%}{69\%} = 85\%$, $\frac{10\%}{69\%} = 15\%$, $[\sum 100\%]$; $100\% - 31\% = 69\%$.

²⁸ The GDP in the current LCU was N\$ 178.052 billion in 2018 (World Bank 2018e).

Table 8.8.: Adjusted results of the total health service costs.

Categories	Public health facilities, treatment cost [N\$] in 2018	Public health facilities, adjusted cases p.a. [numbers]	Private health facilities, treatment cost [N\$] in 2018	Private health facilities, adjusted cases p.a. [numbers]	Overall costs [N\$]
Homicide	1,462	145	5,033	25	337,815
Wounding	2,443	19,528	10,650	3,310	82,958,404
Sexual offences	13,778	15,046	51,666	2,550	339,052,088
Common Assault	1,462	15,544	5,032	2,635	35,984,648
				Total	458,332,955
				Share of GDP [%]	0.26

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

8.5. Conclusion

8.5.1. Summary of findings

The total health service costs are N\$ 458,332,955 and present 0.26 per cent of the national GDP. Sexual offences have the highest treatment cost per case and present with N\$ 339,052,088 the largest cost-share. The loss through sexual offences alone amounts already to a share of 0.19 per cent of GDP, whereas homicide depicts the lowest proportion, with a total cost of N\$ 337,815 and 0.0002 per cent of GDP, respectively.

Although the costing was separated in public and private health care provider spending and the share of 31 per cent that resembles women who do not have access to treatment services is omitted, the calculated health service costs are disproportionately high compared to other research. It has to be further kept in mind that the outcome does not even include male survivors due to the unavailability of incident data, or other long-term impacts, as the consequences of HIV/AIDS. In detail, when comparing the results with other developing and emerging nations, the following findings presented in Section 8.5.2 became evident.

8.5.2. Comparison with other countries

Table 8.9 presents the GDP health cost-share of each paper, which was calculated in this study to contextualise these findings better.

Table 8.9.: Comparison of health service costs.

Country ²⁹	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of health service costs [%] ³⁰	Share of health service costs on overall costs [%] ³¹
Developed countries						
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003	4.79	0.05	0.04 ³²	69.8 ³³
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996	1.95	0.98	0.23 ³⁴	23.47
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	1.00	0.47	0.00 ³⁵	0.93
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia 2016	[11.13]	1.35	0.09 ³⁶	6.36
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	7.10	0.76	0.02 ³⁷	2.85
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a	5.00	1.07	0.05 ³⁸	4.81
U.K.	2009	Walby 2009	0.60	1.00	0.11 ³⁹	11.00

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²⁹For detailed information, including all footnotes, see Table 3.2

³⁰The figure presents the ratio of the health service costs and the GDP share. Figures have been rounded up. All GDP data are listed in Table 3.2 Overview of selected GBV cost studies worldwide.

³¹The figure presents the ratio of the health service cost-share [of GDP] and the overall GDP cost-share. Figures have been rounded up.

³²The health service costs are US\$ four billion [US\$ 4,050,211,000] overall. They include mental health and medical care spendings. Medical care cost includes expenses of the outpatient clinic and emergency department visits, ambulance transports, paramedic care, physicians, physical therapy, dental visits, and inpatient hospitalisation (Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003 p. 40).

³³The figure displays the ratio of the GDP health service cost-share of 0.04, divided by the total GDP cost-share of 0.05. health service costs display the majority of spending in the NCIP&C study (Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003 p. 40, Tab. 12). The same arithmetic is applied to all other listed research.

³⁴The health service costs of US\$ 15.750 billion are composed of the following expenses: the government pays US\$ eight billion annually for restorative and emergency services and one-fourth of the US\$ 11 billion [US\$ 2.75 billion] in health insurance payments. Employers spend almost US\$ five billion on GBV related activities, primarily in their health insurance spending (Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996 p. 19).

³⁵The detailed figure is 0.004 per cent. The overall estimated health service cost was C\$ 68,970,265 in 2009. The number entails costs of physician visits [C\$ 189,212], (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 42) hospital and ambulance costs [C\$ 5,949,691], (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 43) costs of acute hospitalisation [C\$ 14,786,935], (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 44) and costs of mental health spending [C\$ 48,044,427] (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 46).

³⁶The impact of violence on the private and public health systems is estimated to cost survivors, their communities, and the government A\$ 1.4 billion (KPMG Australia 2016 p. 5).

³⁷The overall health service costs are estimated to be A\$ 445 million from 2021 to 2022 (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009 p. 41).

³⁸The total health cost is A\$ 388.2 million (Access Economics 2004a, part I, 34).

³⁹Health care cost was £ 1,730 million in 2008 (Walby 2009 p. 8).

Continue Table 8.9

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of health service costs [%]	Share of health service costs on overall costs [%]
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson 2006	2.60	0.10	0.00 ⁴⁰	0.78
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017	3.00	0.12	0.01 ⁴¹	11.60
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	1.26	0.03	0.01 ⁴²	21.34
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	5.00	0.17	0.01 ⁴³	8.03
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	2.00	0.22	0.05 ⁴⁴	15.75
Developing and emerging countries						
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012	25.40	3.19	0.00 ⁴⁵	0.00 ⁴⁶
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011	24.00	2.10	0.04 ⁴⁷	1.90
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	18.00	3.93	0.01 ⁴⁸	0.25
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	27.70	–	– ⁴⁹	–
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	30.00	–	– ⁵⁰	–
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014	20.00–30.00	0.90–1.30	– ⁵¹	–

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⁴⁰The detailed figure is 0.001 per cent. The health care and medical services costs are kr million 21 to 38 (Envall and Eriksson 2006 p. 9). In line with this paper's approach, the more conservative estimate of kr million 21 is used.

⁴¹The total cost is €440,903,511. In detail, the expenses for physical harm are €287,225,965 (Sacco 2017 p. 93). The cost of treating depression is €9,100,000 (Sacco 2017 p. 94). The overall losses through suicide [tried and executed] are €144,577,546 (Sacco 2017 p. 96).

⁴²The overall cost is CHF 35 million. The costs resulting from psychological consequences are CHF 20 million. The losses resulting from physical harm are CHF 15 million (Stern *et al.* 2013 p. 21).

⁴³The overall direct medical costs are €289,821,671 (Nectoux *et al.* 2010 p. 394).

⁴⁴The costs for physical and mental health services are €371,089,780 (Villagómez 2010 p. 5).

⁴⁵The detailed figure is 0.000000003 per cent. The approximate ₺68 million [₺68,030,000] health care cost is composed of ₺65 million [₺65,124,000] for direct damages and ₺2.9 million [₺2,906,000] of losses to service provisions (Duvvury and Carney 2012 p. 65). The Vietnamese 2010 GDP [in current LCU] was ₺2.158 quadrillion.

⁴⁶The detailed figure is 0.0000001 per cent. The paper states that the overall potential opportunity cost and productivity loss of DV sum up to 3.19 per cent of the 2010 GDP (Duvvury and Carney 2012 p. 78).

⁴⁷The overall cost is Taka, ₳2,805,941,070. In detail, the medical costs for survivors and their families were ₳1,941,070 (Siddique 2011 p. 43); government health care spending, including the budget of the directorate general of health, were ₳2,804,000,000 (Siddique 2011 p. 46). Cost to non-state organisations could not be determined based on the information given in the report (Siddique 2011 p. 49–51).

⁴⁸The cost [Costos de Tratamiento y Atención – Medicina Legal] was Mex\$ 16,476 million (Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 p. 32).

⁴⁹Duvvury *et al.* 2009 do not provide any total and nationwide spending calculation. The single out-of-pocket cost for a one-time service in Morocco was US\$ 41 (Duvvury *et al.* 2009 p. 10), and for Uganda, it was US\$ 5 (Duvvury *et al.* 2009 p. 10). Please, see the correction note in Duvvury *et al.* 2009 p. 15.

⁵⁰See the footnote under Morocco.

⁵¹A calculation cannot be made since only the cost of morbidity and mortality was computed, which is R 25 billion [exact figure R 25,204,817,522]. Additional spending, as the cost of private healthcare (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 37) is not estimated either (KPMG South Africa 2014 see the full report).

Continue Table 8.9

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of health service costs [%]	Share of health service costs on overall costs [%]
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine	10.00	0.23	0.00 ⁵²	1.44
Namibia	2021	Breuer	17.50	6.01	0.26	4.29

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Based on these findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Developed countries: the used method is in its detail comparable to such used in studies published in developed countries.⁵³ However, due to the lower GBV prevalence, the GDP health cost-share of developed economies is considerably lower in consequence.⁵⁴
2. Developing and emerging countries: the prevalences are similarly high.⁵⁵ However, the applied approaches are not as holistic.⁵⁶ Further, data on other African countries, such as South Africa, Uganda, and Morocco, cannot be included in this comparison, as relevant information is missing or important health data was not calculated.⁵⁷ In consequence, also among the developing and emerging countries, none of the other studies calculated such a high health service cost-share as the Namibian one.

In order to understand the Namibian findings better, in a theoretical simulation, the prevalence of the other studies is hypothetically aligned to the Namibian 17.50 per cent, and their new GDP health cost-share is evaluated [Table 8.10].

⁵²The detailed figure is 0.003 per cent. The overall cost of healthcare services utilised by women who survived violence was US\$ three million [in detail, US\$ 2,999,038] in 2015 (UNFPA Ukraine 2017 p. 74). Costs are presented in US\$(UNFPA Ukraine 2017 p. 49). The Ukrainian GDP in current USD was US\$91.031 billion in 2015.

⁵³See Section 3.4

⁵⁴The Namibian prevalence is 17.50 per cent. In the U.S. Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996 study, it is 1.95 per cent, in the Australian Access Economics 2004a survey, it is five per cent, and in the Spanish Villagómez 2010 paper, it is only two per cent.

⁵⁵Although it has to be kept in mind that countries like Vietnam, Bangladesh, or Ukraine differ from their cultural and economic situation to the Namibian context too.

⁵⁶See, for instance, the Siddique paper on Bangladesh (Siddique 2011).

⁵⁷See, for instance, the Duvvury *et al.* report on Uganda (Duvvury *et al.* 2009) or the KPMG paper on South Africa (KPMG South Africa 2014).

Table 8.10.: Comparison of adjusted health service costs.

Country ⁵⁸	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New prevalence [%]	Old GDP share of health costs [%]	New GDP share of health costs [%]	Cost increase [%]
Developed countries							
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003	4.79	17.50	0.04	0.15	275
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996	1.95	17.50	0.23	2.06	796
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	1.00	17.50	0.00 ⁵⁹	0.07	1,650
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia 2016	[11.13]	17.50	0.09	0.14	56
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	7.10	17.50	0.02	0.05	150
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a	5.00	17.50	0.05	0.18	260
U.K.	2009	Walby 2009	0.60	17.50	0.11	3.21	2,818
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson 2006	2.60	17.50	0.00 ⁶⁰	0.01	900
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017	3.00	17.50	0.01	0.06	500
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	1.26	17.50	0.01	0.14	1,300
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	5.00	17.50	0.01	0.04	200
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	2.00	17.50	0.03	0.26	767
Developing and emerging countries							
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012	25.40	17.50	0.00 ⁶¹	0.00 ⁶²	-33
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011	24.00	17.50	0.04	0.03	-25
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	18.00	17.50	0.01	0.01	0
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	27.70	17.50	-	-	-
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	30.00	17.50	-	-	-
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014	20.00-30.00	17.50	0.01	0.01	0

Continue on next page

⁵⁸For more detailed information, including all footnotes, see Table 3.2⁵⁹Detailed figure 0.004 per cent.⁶⁰Detailed figure 0.001 per cent.⁶¹Detailed figure 0.000000003 per cent.⁶²Detailed figure 0.000000002 per cent.

Continue Table 8.10

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New prevalence [%]	Old GDP share of health costs [%]	New GDP share of health costs [%]	Cost increase [%]
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine	10.00	17.50	0.00 ⁶³	0.00 ⁶⁴	67
Namibia	2021	Breuer	17.50	17.50	0.26	0.26	0.00

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.
Source: Own representation.

As expected, a significant increase in the cost-share has occurred. For the developed countries, the growth begins from 56 per cent in the KPMG Australia 2016 report to over 2,800 per cent in the British Walby 2009 study, whose approach has been used for these calculations. The following graphic, Figure 8.1, shows the data in detail.

Legend: 1. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003. 2. Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996. 3. Zhang *et al.* 2012. 4. KPMG Australia 2016. 5. National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009. 6. Access Economics 2004a. 7. Walby 2009. 8. Envall and Eriksson 2006. 9. Sacco 2017. 10. Stern *et al.* 2013. 11. Nectoux *et al.* 2010. 12. Villagómez 2010. 13. Duvvury and Carney 2012. 14. Siddique 2011. 15. Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004. 16. Duvvury *et al.* 2009 (for Morocco). 17. Duvvury *et al.* 2009 (for Uganda). 18. KPMG South Africa 2014. 19. UNFPA Ukraine 2017 and 20. Breuer 2021.

Figure 8.1.: Comparison of adjusted health service costs.

During the process of research, further issues became evident. There are specific obstacles for individuals to access health care services in Namibia, which, in consequence, affects the study's results. In order to continue, Section 8.5.3 will discuss these aspects.

⁶³Detailed figure 0.003 per cent.

⁶⁴Detailed figure 0.005 per cent.

8.5.3. Further discussion

Problems in accessing health care in Namibia

Investment is needed to deliver quality health care. For instance, health infrastructure in Namibia requires investments in buildings or equipment. Since ineffective and inefficient management of health service provision at national and regional levels has led to a decreased quality of public health care provision (World Health Organization (WHO) 2018d). When reading the high case numbers, the fact has to be kept in mind that several hurdles prevent individuals from receiving medical services, including treatment. In the 2014 NDHS, Namibian women aged 15–49 were asked what factors have prevented them from seeking medical care when sick. The main barriers are in descending order:

1. a large distance to a health facility [31 per cent],
2. to get money for treatment [28 per cent],
3. the fear of not wanting to go alone [15 per cent],
4. to get permission to go for treatment [6 per cent] (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 114) ⁶⁵

In summary, such obstacles are disproportionately reported from women:

- who are employed not for cash, or who are unemployed,
- from the poorest households,
- without education,
- with five or more children,
- who were formerly married,
- from rural areas, especially from women in the Kavango area (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 114).

Such women are more at risk of having at least stated one of the above-listed problems. The share of women who indicated such problems decreased with higher levels of education and household income. Consequently, because of such barriers, the real economic cost is assumed to be lower, as a significant part of the population is hindered from receiving adequate health care treatment. For instance, 27.58 per cent of women are hindered due to personal restricted financial means from accessing primary health care services. However, this percentage does not include any additionally listed obstacles, such as large distances to clinics or getting permission to go for treatment. ⁶⁶ Therefore, it is assumed that the actual cohort of excluded survivors may be even higher.

On the other hand, in contrast, the poor quality of public health services may increase cost in the long term. Prior to this study, research has been carried out with a cohort of 80 affected to assess the degree of satisfaction of Namibian survivors with public services, including public health care provisions. Responders stated regarding their satisfaction with services, and

⁶⁵The report does not state from whom (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 114).

⁶⁶The NDHS did not specify the total proportion of how many women are hindered from receiving treatment in total. The survey also allowed for double counting; hence the factor cannot be determined precisely (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 114).

whether the staff of public hospitals was of help, that: “No they are not. They take life, it is a human life, but they take it lightly” (Breuer 2015 p. 49). Regarding the fastness and efficiency of support, survivors further added: “They were very slow. Even if you are dying here, you must wait. Even die here. They will not care. They will step over you, or they will stand and talk. They will not even come and help you. First, they will stand and talk many things before they come” (Breuer 2015 p. 50). Regarding the availability of help, women from different ethnic belongings replied: “If [you] cannot speak English, you do not get help” (Breuer 2015 p. 50–52). It is assumed that such a pattern may decrease costs in the short-term but will contribute to a rise in the long-term due to accumulated additional trauma and wounding that was not appropriately treated in the first place.

8.6. Summary

This category bases its calculations on the health-state approach. The case numbers were computed based on NHDS data for physical and sexual violence (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). The overall cost-share is 0.26 per cent of the gross domestic product. The sexual assault category had the highest total expenses. However, it must be considered that the long-term costs of HIV and AIDS were not included. This result should, therefore, be read as a conservative estimation. When comparing the outcome with other literature’s findings, the prevalence proportions were raised to the Namibian level. Only a few studies have calculated a comparably high cost-share. It must be added that research in developing and emerging countries omit significant cost segments. Among the industrialised countries, the total cost of Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996; Villagómez 2010; Walby 2004; Walby 2009 would be theoretically higher or equal to the Namibian findings. When considering the overall results, it must be taken into account that many women experience several difficulties accessing health services, especially women who are located in the financially poorer cohorts, who have a lower level of education, or who have five or more children. It is assumed that such obstacles decrease costs in the short-term but will stimulate a rise in the long-term due to accumulated additional trauma and wounding that was not cured properly in the first place.

In order to continue, Chapter 9 presents the calculation of the legal costs.

9. Legal costs

9.1. Introduction

The losses the Criminal Justice System [CJS] encounters to address GBV fluctuate depending on the structure of the national framework. In general, costs include spending on police services, law enforcement, and public protection. They cover the cost associated with the serving of protection orders, federal and local administration, legal assistance, survivor's compensation, as well as the prosecution and incarceration of perpetrators. Only a few studies attempted to compute all of such costs.¹ The used method in this paper is the budget-share approach. The model will be described in Section 9.2, with its advantages and disadvantages. In Section 9.3, the used data basis is presented. The primary data derives from the Ministry of Finance 2018; MoHSS and ICF International 2014. The case number and multiplier data are calculated from records of MoHSS and ICF International 2014; Namibian Police (NAMPOL) 2012. Section 9.4 presents the results, Section 9.5 the conclusion, and Section 9.6 summarises the results.

In order to continue, the proportional budget-share approach, which has been found best appropriate to estimate the losses for the scope of this study, is briefly summarised.

9.2. Approach

Budget-share approach

The application of the budget-share approach, or also called the proportional expenditure approach as applied in, for instance, Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010; Institute for Women of Andalusia 2003; Walby 2004 can be roughly summarised by the following steps:

1. Step I – Establishment of the overall budget and GBV spending for the reference year, disaggregated by age cohorts.
2. Step II – The calculation of case numbers and appropriate multipliers.
3. Step III – Multiplication of this proportion to the overall budget.

In summary, the following advantages and disadvantages define the approach:

¹For more information, see Chapter 3.

-
1. Advantages – The method captures the vast reality of [public] spending. It is based on data, which is likely to be available, and its computed proportions offer a reliable indicator of the actual cost that occurred (Walby and Olive [2014](#), p. 76).
 2. Disadvantages – This approach may be associated with a set of possible distortions since estimates do not derive from precise unit cost data. Nonetheless, in the event of any data unavailability, the approach offers a viable solution.

Due to its robustness, simplicity, and feasibility, the method is applied to the Namibian context. Section [9.3](#) presents further information on the utilised datasets.

9.3. Data

The following paragraphs summarise the data used to compute the legal costs linked to GBV in Namibia. In order to estimate the different cost classes, such as associated legal assistance, crime prevention, or public forensic services, the following primary data is used.

Basic data

Chapter [6](#) describes the primary data that serves as a baseline for each category in detail. Again, the prevalence data from the 2013 Namibian National Survey on GBV (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#)) is employed as a cross-reference.² The detailed computation of the unit costs and case number data is described in the next paragraphs.

Budget data on legal costs

The calculations are based on the budget information from the Ministry of Finance [2018](#). The Ministry of Finance [2018](#) report displays government spending on all GBV related matters within the Namibian law enforcement and administration.³

- Ministry of Finance [2018](#): the estimates of the revenue, income and expenditure forecast from 01 April 2018 to 31 March 2021 entails detailed cost information and includes government spending on the:
 1. Office of the Ombudsman, including legal aid (Ministry of Finance [2018](#), p. 262)
 2. Magistracy (Ministry of Finance [2018](#), p. 343), High Court (Ministry of Finance [2018](#), p. 347), Lower Courts (Ministry of Finance [2018](#), p. 348) and
 3. Ministry of Safety and Security, including
 - a) main division on combating of crime (Ministry of Finance [2018](#), p. 93 f.)
 - b) training and development (Ministry of Finance [2018](#), p. 95)
 - c) forensic science services (Ministry of Finance [2018](#), p. 100)
 - d) correctional operations (Ministry of Finance [2018](#), p. 102)

²See Chapter [18](#) in the Appendix.

³Note that other costs, such as personal [unit] cost of legal procedures for divorces, are calculated separately in Chapter [11](#) Personal costs.

-
- e) corporate management (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 104), and
 - f) rehabilitation and integration (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 106).

Case number data

Multipliers are developed to compute the most realistic case data. The following information is used for this purpose:

- Ministry of Safety and Security 2018: the press release of the report on national crime prevention and road safety operations (Ministry of Safety and Security, Head of Public Relations Division, Dep. Comm. Edwin Kanguatjivi, Namibian Police Force 2018) provides a review of all criminal activities the Namibian Police Force has registered within a specific time frame⁴. The data is utilised to compute the difference between the registered and actual GBV cases⁵.

Table 9.1.: Total NAMPOL crime data.

Registered NAMPOL crime cases [numbers]	
Overall	67,333 (Namibian Police (NAMPOL) 2012 p. 7)

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

- NAMPOL 2012 to 2015: the database entails a three-year panel survey of registered GBV incidents⁶.

Multiplier data

The following description explains the calculation of the relevant multipliers.

- A general-cost multiplier of 22.25 per cent: 2013, 2014, and 2015 NAMPOL data on GBV (Hartman 2016) are set in relation to 2012 to 2013 overall NAMPOL crime records (Namibian Police (NAMPOL) 2012 p. 7). The computed multiplier of 22.25 per cent⁷ is applied to more general costing categories, including the legal aid division, the main division magistracy, the main division of Lower courts, or the main division of training and development.

Multipliers are adjusted within the different subcategories based on the following literature.

⁴However, police data does not present the reality of GBV cases. As discussed in Chapter 6 see further Chapter 16. This becomes clear when evaluating the data, as the report only depicts an overall of 552 GBV incidents for the time frame of 2017 to 2018 (Ministry of Safety and Security, Head of Public Relations Division, Dep. Comm. Edwin Kanguatjivi, Namibian Police Force 2018, p. 6).

⁵For more information, see Chapter 18 in the Appendix.

⁶The case numbers have been partially already used in the cost category of health service costs, in Chapter 8.

⁷Overall GBV cases/total criminal cases: 14,979/67,333. For more information on the calculations, see Chapter 18 in the Appendix.

- A multiplier of 70 per cent for cost related to the High Court: the statement of Shapwa 2017 depicts that 70 per cent of High Court criminal cases are GBV related⁸. This proportion is used to tailor the cost classes of the High Court division [in general], including the respective caseload in the High Court.
- A multiplier of ten per cent for cost related to the Correctional Facilities: the source Informante 2018 defines a ten per cent offender' population within the Namibian Correctional Facilities that have committed GBV associated crimes. The tailored multipliers are used for the cost categories of correctional operations, corporate management [within correctional facilities], rehabilitation, and reintegration.

Based on this data, the following results are calculated.

9.4. Results

Table 9.2 showcases all results in detail.

Table 9.2.: Results of the total legal costs.

Category ⁹	Main Operations	2018–2019 budget [N\$] ¹⁰	Multiplier [%]	Costs related to GBV cases [N\$]
Ministry of Justice				
Office of the Ombudsman		19,408,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 262)	22.25	4,318,280
Division – Legal aid		25,679,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 263)		5,713,578
Division – Legal services		14,130,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 265)		3,143,925
Division – Magistracy	Handling of all matters within the jurisdiction of the Lower Court ¹¹	73,284,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 343)		16,305,690
Division – High Court	High Court ¹²	41,495,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 347)	70.00	29,046,500
Division – Lower Court	and Lower Court ¹³	108,371,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 348)	22.25	24,112,548

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⁸The multiplier is applied to the 2018 census data, as this study's outcome is calculated as a proportion of the 2018 GDP.

⁹Categories are based on the Ministry of Finance's report (Ministry of Finance 2018).

¹⁰The report reflects the "Estimates of revenue, income, and expenditure, 01 April 2018 to 31 March 2021," Republic of Namibia [2018] (Ministry of Finance 2018).

¹¹They include criminal, civil, child welfare, domestic violence, and maintenance cases.

¹²For instance, judicial support and administrative work.

¹³Activities regarding bail, court fines, maintenance payments, civil payments, and clearing a backlog of criminal cases.

Continue Table 9.2				
Category	Main Operations	2018–2019 budget [N\$]	Multiplier [%]	Costs related to GBV cases [N\$]
Division – Judicial Commission Secretariat	Provision of administrative support to the Judicial Service Commission and the Magistrates’ Commission.	4,063,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 349)		904,018
Ministry of Safety and Security				
Division – Combating of crime	All activities to combat crime ¹⁴	3,113,300,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 94)		692,709,250
Division – Training and Development	Skill development for the members of the Force ¹⁵	88,629,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 95)		19,719,953
Division – Forensic Science Services	Provision of scientific evidence to crime-related cases.	21,178,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 100)		4,712,105
Division – Correctional Operations	Operation and maintenance of accommodation facilities in the Correctional Facilities ¹⁶	727,677,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 103)	10.00	72,767,700
Division – Corporate Management	Compliance and control of Correctional facilities ¹⁷	55,569,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 105)		5,556,900
Division – Rehabilitation and Reintegration	Controlled release of entitled offender.	37,093,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 106)		3,709,300
			Total Share of GDP [%] ¹⁸	882,719,745 0.50

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.
Source: Own representation.

¹⁴As the procurement of vehicles and equipment, the development of the Crime Combating Strategy, and all linked field operations.

¹⁵For crime analysis and prevention.

¹⁶As clothing, food, or medical support for inmates.

¹⁷As the implementation of policies.

¹⁸The GDP in the current LCU was N\$ 178.052 billion in 2018 (World Bank 2018e).

9.5. Conclusion

9.5.1. Summary of findings

The total legal costs related to GBV constitute N\$ 882,719,745 [of the 2018 to 2019 budget cycle] and 0.50 per cent of the 2018 GDP. The expenses of the Combating of Crime Division alone present both the highest overall cost with N\$ 3,113,300,000 and the highest share of GBV related expenses with N\$ 692,709,250. The Division produces nearly 80 per cent of all GBV expenses¹⁹ and holds alone already a share of 0.39 per cent of the 2018 GDP. Whereas the other cost categories together, as expenses on legal aid, Lower Courts, or rehabilitation, and reintegration, only amount to around 20 per cent of all costs, and thus only to 0.11 per cent of the national GDP. The data did not allow for a separation among men and women. Nonetheless, based on other analyses, as found within the lost economic output calculation²⁰ men are bound to much lower case levels compared to their female counterparts. In general, the literature agrees that women are burdened with a significant share of the cost too (Sacco 2017 Walby 2009 World Health Organization (WHO) 2016b). When comparing the results of both other developed and developing countries, the findings described in Section 9.5.2 became evident.

9.5.2. Comparison with other countries

Table 9.3 puts the findings into context to other research results to achieve a better understanding and adds the GDP share of related legal spending to all analyses.

Table 9.3.: Comparison of legal costs.

Country ²¹	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of legal costs [%] ²²	Share of legal costs on overall costs [%] ²³
Developed countries						
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003	4.79	0.05	- ²⁴	-

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¹⁹692,709,250/882,719,745.

²⁰See Chapter 7

²¹For more detailed information, including all footnotes, see Table 3.2

²²The figure illustrates the ratio of legal costs and the GDP share. Figures have been rounded up.

²³The figure presents the ratio of the legal costs-share [of GDP] and the overall proportion of cost [of GDP]. Figures have been rounded up.

²⁴The report does not estimate the legal costs.

Continue Table 9.3

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of legal costs [%]	Share of legal costs on overall costs [%]
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996	1.95	0.98	0.25	–
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	1.00	0.47	0.03 ²⁶	7.35
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia 2016	[11.13]	1.35	0.10 ²⁷	7.73
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	7.10	0.76	0.02 ²⁸	2.06
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a	5.00	1.07	0.04 ²⁹	3.69
U.K.	2009	Walby 2009	0.60	1.00	0.02 ³⁰	2.46
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson 2006	2.60	0.10	0.04 ³¹	40.74
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017	3.00	0.12	0.01 ³²	10.78
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	1.26	0.03	0.01 ³³	29.88
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	5.00	0.17	0.01 ³⁴	4.90

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²⁵The paper does not calculate the total amount of legal costs. It only states the unit cost per survivor and family member. The research includes data on the number of hours of work and wages lost by family members aiding survivors and being involved with survivors in the legal system. The first component adds about US\$ 5 to US\$ 10 per survivor, and the second adds about US\$ 10 to US\$ 20 per survivor (Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996 p. 14). However, Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996 do not provide any overall outcome, case numbers, or multiplier to self-compute the total expenses.

²⁶The overall estimated legal costs are C\$ 545,184,737 (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 23).

²⁷The impact on the Justice System, other services, and the funeral sectors is estimated to be A\$ 1.7 billion (KPMG Australia 2016 p. 6). However, it has to be kept in mind that the paper does not state the occurred cost to the justice system alone.

²⁸Legal costs are A\$ 321.9 million. Related administrative expenses could reach A\$ 555 million in 2021 to 2022 (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009 p. 53, see bullet point 8.3).

²⁹The yearly legal costs amount to A\$ 298 million (Access Economics 2004a p. 53).

³⁰In 2008, civil legal services cost British society £ 387 million a year. The figures include legal actions as injunctions or divorce (Walby 2009 p. 8).

³¹The cost to the Criminal Justice System, including public prosecutors, courts, prison, and probation services, is kr 1,098–1,189 million. In line with this study's scope, the conservative estimate of kr 1,098 million is taken (Envall and Eriksson 2006 p. 9).

³²The overall cost of the Judicial System, including police and justice, is € 409.60 million. In detail, they comprise: 1. Cost of police operations and administration of € 108.9 million (Sacco 2017 p. 41); 2. Cost of Justice, as Violence Protection Procedure of € 16.9 million (Sacco 2017 p. 48); 3. Cost of the judicial criminal proceedings of € 23.6 million (Sacco 2017 p. 51); 4. Cost of Detention, including murder and manslaughter of € 96.2 million (Sacco 2017 p. 53); 5. Additional losses in case of separation due to DV of € 19.3 million (Sacco 2017 p. 57); 6. Experts' fees of € 73.8 million (Sacco 2017 p. 64); 7. Legal fees: the overall cost to both parties was € 68.9 million (Sacco 2017 p. 66); and 8. high-risk management costs of € 2.0 million (Sacco 2017 p. 70).

³³The overall cost is CHF 49 million (Stern *et al.* 2013 p. 13).

³⁴The cost of the civil justice [Justice civile] is € 11,515,429, for the criminal justice [Justice pénale] is € 45,950,291 and for incarceration [Incarcérations] it is € 119,274,942 (Nectoux *et al.* 2010 p. 394). They sum up to € 176,740,662.

Continue Table 9.3

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of legal costs [%]	Share of legal costs on overall costs [%]
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	2.00	0.22	0.01 ³⁵	2.58
Developing and emerging countries						
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012	25.40	3.19	- ³⁶	-
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011	24.00	2.10	0.01 ³⁷	0.48
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	18.00	3.93	0.33 ³⁸	8.40
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	27.70	-	-	-
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	30.00	-	-	-
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014	20.00–30.00	0.90–1.30	0.01 ³⁹	0.77–1.11
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine 2017	10.00	0.23	0.01 ⁴⁰	4.87
Namibia	2021	Breuer 2021	17.50	6.01	0.50	8.14

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

³⁵The judicial expenses are €60.7 million (Villagómez 2010, p. 5).

³⁶The study includes the costs of court hearings, which were, for instance, đ [Vietnamese dong] đ1,425,000 (Duvvury and Carney 2012 p. 71) or unit prices of police services of đ1,583,000, for example (Duvvury and Carney 2012 p. 70). Nevertheless, an overall figure is not provided (Duvvury and Carney 2012 p. 81).

³⁷The report does not provide the overall legal costs. It instead splits up costs into expenses incurred to the individual, state or non-state (Siddique 2011, p. 50), and thus provides the following sub-categories: legal [formal and informal] costs to the survivors and families; Taka, ₳0.34 crore [Taka, ₳3,434,584] (Siddique 2011 p. 43); Cost to the state – Category C – Home, including police, recurrent budget; Taka, ₳48.10 crore, ₳0.75 crore and 47.35]; Category E – Ministry of Law and Justice and Parliamentary Affairs; Taka, ₳5.76 crore recurrent budget; Taka, ₳1.00 crore and development budget; Taka, ₳4.76 crore] (Siddique 2011 p. 46). The overall legal costs sum up to Taka, ₳54.20 crore [542,000,000].

³⁸The overall legal costs are pesos, Mex\$ 744,113,549,446. They are composed of 1. Budget Assignment 2002 – Office of the Attorney General of the Nation I [Asignación Presupuestal 2002 – Fiscalía General de la Nación] – pesos, Mex\$ 700,328,923,916; 2. Undersecretary for security issues and citizen coexistence [Subsecretaria para asuntos de seguridad y convivencias ciudadanas] – pesos, Mex\$ 1,144,677,160; 3. Office of the Attorney General of the Nation II [Fiscalía General de la Nación] – pesos, Mex\$ 42,639,948,370 (Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 p. 34).

³⁹The overall legal costs are R 265,228,974. The study is subdivided into cost categories that occurred to the government, NGOs, and individuals. There is not a clear subdivision of legal costs. Legal spending is listed under losses that relate to public expenses. Overall expenses to the government are R 513,551,244, and total legal expenses incurred to the government are R 265,228,974. Legal costs are composed of the following categories 1. South African Police Service – R 110,727,545: the figure includes GBV related costs of training for vehicles, research and public awareness, new survivor-friendly rooms, staffing, and costs of protection orders. The data was sourced from self-reports; 2. Justice and Constitutional Development – R 106,855,823. This number includes expenses for staff, research, and GBV programmes, including the establishment of 42 Sexual Offence Courts and the maintenance of the National Register of Sexual Offenders. The data stems from self-reports of staff; 3. National Prosecuting Authority – R 47,645,606. The data covers the administrative costs of running an average Care Centre and is based on estimates only (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 32 f.). The paper does not calculate the legal out-of-pocket costs, such as private legal fees paid directly by the survivors (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 29).

⁴⁰The overall legal costs were US\$ 10,141,187 in 2015 (UNFPA Ukraine 2017 p. 76).

Compared to other studies conducted for both developing and developed countries, the computed legal costs-share of 0.50 per cent of GDP is disproportionately high. In summary, the following deductions can be made based on the findings. Again, the studies⁴¹ conducted within an African context are less complete, with relevant information and costing categories missing, as in the studies for Morocco, Uganda (Duvvury *et al.* 2009), or South Africa, for instance (KPMG South Africa 2014). In summary, the GDP share of legal costs ranges from 0.01 in Bangladesh, South Africa, and Ukraine to 0.33 per cent in Colombia. The data of other African countries are not included in the comparison, as relevant information is missing or as legal costs were not fully computed. Overall, none of the other papers calculated such a high legal GDP costs-share. In order to interpret the Namibian results with greater detail, the theoretical simulation is again conducted. As done in the previous chapters, the academic work that fulfils the eligibility criteria listed in Chapter 3 was taken, and their prevalence ratios were adjusted to the Namibian level of 17.50 per cent. Table 9.4 presents the new hypothetical legal GDP cost-proportion.

Table 9.4.: Comparison of adjusted legal costs.

Country ⁴²	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New prevalence [%]	Old GDP share of legal costs [%]	New GDP share of legal costs [%]	Increase of costs [%]
Developed countries							
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003	4.79	17.50	–	–	–
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996	1.95	17.50	–	–	–
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	1.00	17.50	0.03	0.53	1,667
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia 2016	[11.13]	17.50	0.10	0.16	60
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	7.10	17.50	0.02	0.05	150

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1. Developed countries:

- a) Method – As mentioned already within the other cost categories, the used approach in this paper is in its level of comprehensiveness comparable to those applied in developed countries.
- b) Culture – Due to its high prevalence, is the Namibian share of 0.50 significantly higher than the share of 0.01, for instance, in Germany (Sacco 2017), Switzerland (Stern *et al.* 2013), France (Nectoux *et al.* 2010), or Spain (Villagómez 2010),.

⁴²For more detailed information, including all footnotes, see Table 3.2

Continue Table 9.4

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New prevalence [%]	Old GDP share of legal costs [%]	New GDP share of legal costs [%]	Increase of costs [%]
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a	5.00	17.50	0.04	0.14	250
U.K.	2009	Walby 2009	0.60	17.50	0.02	0.58	2,800
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson 2006	2.60	17.50	0.04	0.27	575
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017	3.00	17.50	0.01	0.06	500
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	1.26	17.50	0.01	0.14	1,300
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	5.00	17.50	0.01	0.03	200
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	2.00	17.50	0.01	0.09	800
Developing and emerging countries							
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012	25.40	17.50	–	–	–
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011	24.00	17.50	0.01	0.01	0.00 ⁴³
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	18.00	17.50	0.33	0.32	–3.00
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	27.70	17.50	–	–	–
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	30.00	17.50	–	–	–
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014	20.00–30.00	17.50	0.01	0.01	0.00 ⁴⁴
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine 2017	10.00	17.50	0.01	0.02	100
Namibia	2021	Breuer 2021	17.50	17.50	0.50	0.50	0.00

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Based on the showcased figures, the following aspects became apparent:

1. Similar results to other categories: for developed countries, the rise commences at 60 per cent to a maximum of 2,800 per cent⁴⁵ For the developing nations, there is no or only little modification.⁴⁶
2. Similar results to other research: the new GDP share spent on legal costs ranges from a minimum of 0.01 per cent in South Africa and Bangladesh to a maximum of 0.53 per cent in Canada and 0.58 per cent in the U.K. The Namibian value of 0.50 is now theoretically similar to the Canadian and British findings, as both methodical set-ups are similar in their level of thoroughness.⁴⁷

Figure 9.1 depicts the results in more detail.

⁴³The numbers are rounded to two figures behind the comma; hence, the variation is not depicted in Table 9.4.

⁴⁴Ibid.

⁴⁵For instance, health costs had a minimum increase of 60 per cent in the KPMG Australia 2016 study and maximum growth of 2,800 per cent in the British Walby 2009 estimation.

⁴⁶Except for the case of Ukraine.

⁴⁷See Chapters 3 and 5

Legend: 1. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) [2003]. 2. Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996]. 3. Zhang *et al.* [2012]. 4. KPMG Australia [2016]. 5. National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) [2009]. 6. Access Economics [2004a]. 7. Walby [2009]. 8. Envall and Eriksson [2006]. 9. Sacco [2017]. 10. Stern *et al.* [2013]. 11. Nectoux *et al.* [2010]. 12. Villagómez [2010]. 13. Duvvury and Carney [2012]. 14. Siddique [2011]. 15. Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004]. 16. Duvvury *et al.* [2009] (for Morocco), 17. Duvvury *et al.* [2009] (for Uganda), 18. KPMG South Africa [2014]. 19. UNFPA Ukraine [2017] and 20. Breuer [2021].

Figure 9.1.: Comparison of adjusted legal costs.

Still, during the process of estimation, other details became visible. Repeatedly, the Namibian judiciary system burdens individuals with severe obstacles to access legal aid and justice in general (Gender Research and Advocacy Project [2012] Hubbard *et al.* [2006]). As a result, only a limited number of survivors receive legal assistance, and the costs are assumed to be higher in reality. Section 9.5.3 will discuss these aspects further.

9.5.3. Further discussion

Problems in assessing the legal costs in Namibia

When interpreting the results, the fact has to be kept in mind that many obstacles hinder individuals from receiving legal support and fair judgment. The comprehensive “Assessment of the operation of the Combating of Rape Act, 8 of 2000,” (Hubbard *et al.* [2006]), and the extensive report of “Seeking safety. Domestic violence in Namibia and the Combating of Domestic Violence Act 4 of 2003,” (Gender Research and Advocacy Project [2012] indicate several problems within the Namibian police and judiciary system. Among other things, the research reveals a –

1. Lack of coordination among institutions: the lack of close cooperation among stakeholders involved in the criminal justice process leads to several issues. The problem is aggravated by high staff turnover within the police and the judicial system (Hubbard *et al.* [2006] p. 57).
2. Delays: individuals report long delays within the criminal investigation system (Hubbard *et al.* [2006] p. 57). Applicants must spend an extended time frame in a state of uncertainty and are unable to move forward with their GBV or rape case (Hubbard *et al.* [2006] p. 58) which enhances the chance of case withdrawals as well.

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3. Lack of proper communication among institutions: there is a breakdown in communications among police, prosecutors, courts, and the National Forensic Science Institute (Hubbard *et al.* 2006 p. 83, 100).⁴⁸
 4. Lack of skills and knowledge: often, effective police response is prohibited due to a shortage of vehicles, petrol, or the absence of trained staff to deal with child rape complainants, among others (Hubbard *et al.* 2006 p. IV). Poor literacy and writing skills of police officers hamper evidence collection and the creation of relevant testimonies that can serve in the court too (Hubbard *et al.* 2006 p. 84).
 5. Problem to professionally deal with GBV or rape cases of vulnerable groups: studies have found that in half of the GBV cases, which involve individuals with disabilities, the perpetrator was reportedly known to the [rape] survivor. Offenders ranged from [step] fathers to landlords of the complainants. Further, 16 per cent of rape cases involved minors under the age of ten, with more than six per cent, including children under the age of six (Hubbard *et al.* 2006 p. 9). Due to the inefficient police and judicial system, respective families often do not lose custody of their children. Thus, siblings must convince and even force the police to act (Gender Research and Advocacy Project 2012 p. 120). The fragile judicial system is not fully equipped yet to fully support vulnerable groups, such as minors and the disabled (Hubbard *et al.* 2006 p. 10). It thus extends the period of suffering and increases the long-term cost of society as a whole.
 6. Lack of proper evidence collection –
 - a) Inappropriate handling: often, samples taken by medical staff do not yield helpful proof because no proper techniques for collecting the evidence was applied. Often such samples are misplaced because of inaccurate communication. For instance, body fluids are not refrigerated, samples are not correctly air-dried or are not delivered within a reasonable time frame to the laboratory (Hubbard *et al.* 2006 p. 34).
 - b) Unprofessional administration: for instance, lab results are placed into the wrong docket, or the lab reference number does not match the police reference. As a result, proof gets lost, and proper prosecution cannot occur (Hubbard *et al.* 2006 p. 37).
 - c) Missing equipment: for instance, kits to collect evidence from rape incidents are not available in many locations due to a lack of professional staff, transport, or financial resources (Hubbard *et al.* 2006 p. 29).
 7. Resistance to report and address problems: individuals sometimes claim that police staff refused to disclose their names and hide their official name tags to survivors who wanted to report any mismanagement (Hubbard *et al.* 2006 p. 21).
 8. Shortage of staff: GBV police units usually do not have an officer on duty who is available after hours due to shortness or miscommunication among staff members (Hubbard *et al.* 2006 p. 21).

Consequently, the problems mentioned before lead to –

1. Higher long-term costs: if the evidence is lost due to unprofessional handling, in consequence, no judgment will be conducted. As a result, survivors, especially the disabled

⁴⁸For instance, courts are told that scientific lab results are not yet ready, although they are waiting to be collected (Hubbard *et al.* 2006 p. V).

and children are not protected adequately, and their suffering and trauma are prolonged. In the long-term, the cost increases for society as a whole.

2. Survivor's costs are inflated artificially: due to delays in the judicial system, parties often travel and appear in court, only to receive notice that the judiciary postpones ruling. As a result, personal expenses for survivors and their siblings have increased artificially. On the other hand;
3. Costs of government are kept artificially low: due to insufficient police and judicial systems, survivors do not have proper access to the CJS. For instance, obstacles to receiving legal aid are high. If affected citizens want to complain about mismanagement within the police and judicial departments, artificial barriers are created [e.g., police staff loses the case files]. Thus, survivors often withdraw their claims or give up and do not obtain the fair judgment they are entitled to receive.

Especially the last point of the government costs, which are kept unnaturally low, has to be considered when reading the findings of Section 9.5.1. If all individuals had proper access to the legal system, the yearly costs might have been higher. The current status quo is that a large group of survivors capitulates because they do not have the physical, mental or financial strength to go against the institutional system. Hence, those costs do not appear on the government bill. However, there is no valid data on how many survivors are prevented from acquiring legal services; hence this cohort could not be taken adequately into account in this paper, which may have led to a certain degree of distortion.

9.6. Summary

Legal costs were calculated by using the budget-share approach. Based on the available data, the method was identified to be the best applicable. A holistic data basis was chosen for the calculation. The majority of data derived from the Namibian Ministry of Finance 2018. The number of cases was calculated based on crime statistics. As it is known that these statistics do not reflect a realistic number of incidents, multipliers were used in this cost category as well. They are based on the research and publications of the High Court, the Correctional Facilities, or the NDHS (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 Shapwa 2017 The Namibian High Court 2018). The cost contributes to 0.50 per cent of the 2018 gross domestic product. Spendings of the Combating of Crime Division represent the highest expenditure proportion. If the finding is compared with the results of other international studies, in which the prevalence ratio is theoretically raised to the Namibian level, the countries of Great Britain or Canada will display higher percentages. In general, the data did not allow for a separation among the two genders. It must also be taken into account that those affected experience various hurdles to access the legal system. For example, the authorities are not fully equipped yet to punish offences involving minors or people with disabilities successfully. Those affected are not helped quickly enough out of their respective situations, so the trauma and suffering are unnecessarily prolonged. As a consequence, in the long run, the cost of GBV increases. Although a high budget is reserved, the majority of those affected have limited access to the legal system. Hence, it is assumed that the actual cost is lower, as the GBV budget that the government is earmarking, is in reality, not entirely spent on its intended scope. For example, if survivors want to complain about poor treatment and mismanagement within the police,

they can only do so in very few cases. The respective police officers sometimes deny their names or other important data (Hubbard *et al.* 2006, p. 21), preventing efficient procedures.

In order to continue, Chapter 10 will present the computation of the social welfare costs.

10. Social welfare costs and special service costs

10.1. Introduction

Social welfare costs and special service costs can be both privately or publicly funded. They generally include spending on social welfare entities that support survivors, their children, but also abusive partners. Services may be provided through public ministries, community centres, individual social workers, churches, NGOs, or private agencies, among others. They can entail expenses on administration, public policy, research, prevention, supportive programmes, or general social welfare benefits (Day, McKenna, and Bowlus 2005). Section 10.2 presents the method used for the cost calculation. As with the legal costs, the budget-share approach is used again in this category. This method is also applied by various studies for this cost class, among others, in the works of Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010; Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004; Walby 2004; Walby 2009. The advantages of this method are that it is particularly suitable for the data situation in Namibia. The data used comes mainly from the budget statements of the Namibian Ministry of Finance 2018. However, other comprehensive datasets are as well examined and include various renowned NGOs, like women shelters, or aid hotlines, the U.N., or the various German aid agencies and ministries involved, which are particularly strongly presented in Namibia (Andima 2014; Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2019a; Solidaritätsdienst International e. V. (SODI) 2018; United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017). Furthermore, the budget lines of the Social Security Commission, the Ministry of Education, the Ministry of Health, and Poverty Alleviation are analysed. Again, various multipliers are used to align the number of cases stated by the police or official statistics to a realistic level. The multipliers in this Chapter are based on the work of Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Jewkes *et al.* 2010; Walby 2004; Walby 2009. Section 10.4 then presents the results, and Section 10.5 offers an overall conclusion. The results are summarised and compared with studies published in other countries. In Section 10.5.3, there is further discussion about the outcome and different findings that occurred during the calculation process.

Section 10.2 summarises the applied approach.

10.2. Approach

As briefly touched upon before, the concept of social welfare entails broader social protection, which for instance, comprises:

- housing aid, like subsidised housing or grants,

- financial assistance, including employee benefits and social welfare support,
- family support, intervention, and Child Protection.¹

The applied proportional expenditure approach has to compute a holistic review of all of such costs.

Budget-share approach

Walby [2004](#), Helweg-Larsen *et al.* [2010](#), Institute for Women of Andalusia [2003](#) or Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004](#) employ the method to compute social welfare spending in a GBV context.² The approach utilises a framework budget dedicated to social welfare spending. This overall budget is set in relation to the total case numbers or tailored multipliers. The objective is to estimate the cost of a specific population of GBV survivors, including their families and children. Table [10.1](#) provides a brief review of the structure.

1. Multiplication by the proportion of children referred because of abuse or neglect.
2. Multiplication by the ratio of GBV overlaps.

Table 10.1.: Budget-share approach.

Budget	Budget – data source	Share	Share – data source
For instance, the cost of children’s social care	Administrative data from private and public entities – Annual financial returns and financial statements		Administrative data from private and public entities – Annual financial returns and financial statements

Source: Own representation based on Walby and Olive [2014](#) p. 77.

In short, the approach depicts the following advantages and disadvantages:

1. Advantages:
 - a) Robustness – Data is based on actual government and service provider budgets and the number of survivors who access such services.
 - b) Feasibility – The data requirements are moderate, and the data is likely to be available.
 - c) Replicability – Public and private entities, funded by tax revenues, generally report data on services utilised by GBV survivors (Walby and Olive [2014](#) p. 76).
2. Disadvantages:
 - a) Distortions – The approach may be associated with a certain degree of distortion, as values are not obtained from exact unit data.

¹Child abuse co-exists in large proportions of situations in which individuals are exposed to GBV and is hence often included in this cost category (Walby and Olive [2014](#)).

²This approach is already discussed under Chapter [5](#) and in Chapter [8](#) as the estimate of the legal costs is based on the same method. Thus, Section [10.2](#) only provides a summary.

Nevertheless, in the case of data unavailability, the approach provides an opportunity to compute the cost of such services³. Thus, any possible shortcomings are acknowledged. In summary, the approach is robust, simplistic, and feasible, and therefore, appropriate for the Namibian situation. In order to continue, Section 10.3 presents the utilised datasets.

10.3. Data

Section 10.3 presents an overview of the data employed to calculate the social welfare costs⁴. The estimates are based on the following primary data to determine the various cost classes, including research, child protection, or the provision of emergency relief.

Budget data on social welfare

Budget data originates from the following seven entities:

1. Ministry of Finance 2018 (Ministry of Finance 2018):
 - a) Ministry of Gender 2018, for the following cost categories:
 - i. Office of the Minister (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 190)
 - ii. administration and planning (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 191–192)
 - iii. gender equality and research (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 193–194)
 - iv. community empowerment (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 195–196)
 - v. childcare facilities and protection (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 197)
 - vi. child care services (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 198–199).
 - b) Ministry of Social Welfare 2018, includes the following expenses:
 - i. development of social welfare services, as health and social services, or the provision of emergency relief programmes, (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 211–212) and
 - ii. special disease programmes (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 219).
2. NGO data for the time frame of 2014–2018:
 - a) Lifeline/Childline 2018 (Itana 2018) and REGAIN 2016 (Solidaritätsdienst International e. V. (SODI) 2018)⁵ NGOs that provide [psychological] counselling and support or offer prevention programmes.
 - b) Friendly Haven 2016 (Andima 2014 Solidaritätsdienst International e. V. (SODI) 2018): an NGO that provides emergency accommodation and shelter to survivors of GBV.⁶
3. International donor community data for the time frame of 2014–2018:
 - a) U.N. 2016 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017)⁷

³This estimate operates with multiplier data instead of overall case numbers. For more information, see Section 6.4

⁴For more information, see Chapter 6

⁵The included budget was planned until 2018; therefore, the figures were not inflated.

⁶Ibid.

⁷The budget is listed under the United Nations Partnership Framework [UNPAF] 2014–2018. Hence, the data is not inflated to 2018 values (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017).

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- b) UNCHR 2017, (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 81)⁸
 - c) E.U. 2015 (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015)⁹
 - d) BMZ [Federal Ministry of Economic Cooperation and Development] 2019 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2019a)¹⁰
4. the Social Security Commission 2016 (Social Security Commission 2013, p. 47)¹¹ covers the costs of sick leave and death benefits.
 5. Ministry of Education 2018 (Ministry of Finance 2018) administers the budget for:
 - a) programmes and quality assurance (Ministry of Finance 2018, p. 162),
 - b) adult education (Ministry of Finance 2018, p. 172–173),
 - c) the HIV and Aids monitoring unit (Ministry of Finance 2018, p. 174).
 6. Health and social services 2018 (Ministry of Finance 2018) covers the expenses for:
 - a) referral hospital services (Ministry of Finance 2018, p. 205–206),
 - b) regional health and social welfare services (Ministry of Finance 2018, p. 207–208),
 - c) development of social welfare services (Ministry of Finance 2018, p. 212),
 - d) special disease programmes (Ministry of Finance 2018, p. 219).
 7. The Poverty Eradication and Social Welfare Program conducts:
 - a) poverty eradication and social welfare programmes (Ministry of Finance 2018, p. 484),
 - b) social assistance (Ministry of Finance 2018, p. 490), and
 - c) food provision programmes (Ministry of Finance 2018, p. 491).

Multiplier data

- NDHS 2014: the prevalence ratios of physical and sexual violence from the NDHS for both men and women are applied (MoHSS and ICF International 2014)¹²
- Walby 2004: the study applies Walby’s ratios on injuries that are sustained in the worst incident of DV for all physical violence cases to both men and women (Walby 2004 p. 34). Further, it uses the paper’s prevalences on mental problems resulting from sexual violence. However, the data is applied to women only, as statistics of sexual violence for men were either too small (Walby 2004 p. 35) or were not available in Namibia (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 300).

⁸Ibid.

⁹The data stems from the European National Indicative Program, which spanned over six years from 2014 to 2020 (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015). Hence, the per annum data applies to the 2018 time frame.

¹⁰The project has been budgeted for several years, and the per annum data is extracted for 2018 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018 Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2019a).

¹¹The figures are from 2013. Later, publications are not as holistic at the point of research. Hence, the data is levelled by the Namibian CPI for the period of 2013 to 2018 [CPI Namibia 2018/CPI Namibia 2013; $152.3/102.92 = 1.48$] (World Bank 2016).

¹²For more information on the composition of the 17.50 per cent prevalence ratio, see Section 6.4. Since direct information on physical violence enacted against men was not available, data on Namibian women, who have enacted violence against their partners, is used. The data states that 4.60 per cent of Namibian women aged 15 to 49 said to have committed physical violence against their partners in the past 12 months (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 313).

- Dolan [2005] (Dolan *et al.* [2005] p. 974); Dubourg (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] p. 34): the calculations utilise the authors' probabilities on adverse physical health states resulting from sexual violence.
- Jewkes [2018] Jewkes *et al.* [2010] the HIV estimates apply parts of the Jewkes 2010 HIV/AIDS prevalence probabilities for South Africa.¹³

In order to continue, Chapter [10] presents the estimated cost of social welfare.

10.4. Results

Table 10.2.: Results of the social welfare costs.

Category	Main operations ¹⁴	2018–2019 Budget [N\$]	Multiplier [%] ¹⁵	Costs [N\$]
Ministry of Gender				
Office of the Minister	To guide all government policies and operations regarding Women's Affairs and Child Welfare.	4,673,000 (Ministry of Finance [2018] p. 190)	17.50	817,775
Administration and planning	To offer and to ensure training of staff, including HIV/AIDS mainstreaming.	1,176,780,000 (Ministry of Finance [2018] p. 192)	14.90	17,534,022
Gender equality and research	Implementing gender policies and programmes, including gender-responsive budgeting.	30,437,000 (Ministry of Finance [2018] p. 193 f.)	17.50	5,326,475
Community empowerment	Support of income-generating activities, including training of vulnerable groups.	39,835,000 (Ministry of Finance [2018] p. 195 f.)	29.17	11,619,870
Childcare facilities and protection	To provide shelter, care, protection, and educational support to vulnerable [women], including the expansion of social protection services for children.	14,699,000 (Ministry of Finance [2018] p. 197)	73.50	10,803,765

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¹³For detailed information, see Section [6.4]

¹⁴The column lists an overview of the primary operations in every department.

¹⁵For detailed information on the calculation of the multiplier, see Chapter [19] in the Appendix.

Continue Table 10.2

Category	Main operations	2018–2019 Budget [N\$]	Multiplier [%]	Costs [N\$]
Childcare services	To safeguard the provision of services, as the provision of care for children and vulnerable groups [women].	1,005,051,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 198–199)	43.75	439,709,813
Ministry of Social Welfare				
Provision of emergency relief	To provide emergency relief to the aged, disabled, and other vulnerable groups [women], including the support of Welfare organisations, nursing, and Children's homes.	25,215,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 211)	14.00	3,530,100
Special Disease programmes	To implement policies and programmes, including the reduction of socio-economic losses due to HIV.	33,715,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 219)	14.26	4,807,759
Important NGOs				
GBV emergency accommodation	Friendly Haven, for instance, which offers shelter to GBV survivors, including their young children (Solidaritätsdienst International e. V. (SODI) 2018).	2,351,499 (Andima 2014 Solidaritätsdienst International e. V. (SODI) 2018)	100	2,351,499
GBV counselling and educational activities	LifeLine/ChildLine Namibia, for instance, as one of the leading Child Welfare CSOs in Namibia (LifeLine/ChildLine 2019), as well as the REGAIN Trust, which has geared all its activities to the prevention of GBV (Solidaritätsdienst International e. V. (SODI) 2018).	2,929,005 ¹⁶	100	2,929,005

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¹⁶The LifeLine/ChildLine 2019 budget was around N\$ 1,952,670, and REGAIN had an amount of N\$ 976,335 per year for the surveyed period (LifeLine/ChildLine 2019 Solidaritätsdienst International e. V. (SODI) 2018).

Continue Table 10.2

Category	Main operations	2018–2019 Budget [N\$]	Multiplier [%]	Costs [N\$]
International donor community				
U.N. (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017) ¹⁷				
Pillar 1	Institutional environment	1,786,199 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 37–39)	11.79	210,593
Pillar 2	Education and skills	3,573,323 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 39–40)	12.70	453,812
Pillar 3	Health	22,364,026 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 41–65)	9.00	2,012,762
Pillar 4	Poverty reduction	95,747,662 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 65–71)	47.67	45,642,911
UNCHR				
Overall activities		298,696 (Executive Committee of the High Commissioner 2016 p. 14) ¹⁸	17.50	52,272 ¹⁹

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¹⁷The report shows the data for 2016 to 2017 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 19). However, they were published for the United Nations Partnership Framework (UNFPA) of 2014–2018. It is assumed that the core has remained the same for the period of 2018 too. The costs are listed in US\$. Hence, the average exchange rate of US\$ 1 to N\$ 13.2311 in 2018 is used (Exchangerates 2020).

¹⁸The UNHCR contributed US\$ 43,740 to refugees living in Namibia in 2015 (Executive Committee of the High Commissioner 2016 p. 14). [In summary, 1,659 refugees were officially registered in Namibia in 2015] (Executive Committee of the High Commissioner 2016 p. 24). The 2018 budget and financial spending were at the time of research not available [yet]. Hence, the 2015 data is used. The US\$ 43,740 is multiplied by a factor of 0.52 to account for female survivors only, as listed in the UNHCR activities. [Namibia male to female ratio was at the level of 93.81 males per 100 females in 2015. $(100/193.81 = 0.5159692)$] The number is set to the average exchange US\$–N\$ ratio in 2015 [average bid 12.75] (Oanda 2018) and was levelled by the Namibian CPI for the period of 2015 to 2018 [CPI Namibia 2018/CPI Namibia 2015; $132.5/128.9 = 1.03$] (World Bank 2020d).

¹⁹The 298,696 is set into relation with 17.50 per cent. For more information on the composition of the 17.50 per cent, see Section 6.4. The ratios of the female cohort of refugees specifically may differ, as women in a situation of war are at higher risk of violence (World Health Organization (WHO) 2019). Nevertheless, no other research data is available for such a specific context in Namibia. In short, the following calculation is made – US\$ 43,740 · 0.52 [UNHCR activities for women only] · 17.50 per cent [GBV ratio] · 12.75 [Exchange ratio US\$ to N\$ in 2015] · 1.03 [CPI increase of 2015–2018] (World Bank 2020d).

Continue Table 10.2

Category	Main operations	2018–2019 Budget [N\$]	Multiplier [%]	Costs [N\$]
E.U. (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015) ²⁰				
Education and skills	E.U. development aid pays particular attention to the empowerment of women, which is integrated into all its pillars of activities (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015 p. 10).	93,558,000 (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015 p. 3)	8.75	8,186,325
Agriculture		51,976,667 (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015 p. 3)	8.75	4,547,958
Other measures/support to civil society		15,593,000 (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015 p. 3)	11.67	1,819,703
Support measures		15,593,000 (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015 p. 3)	8.75	1,364,388

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²⁰The data stems from the European National Indicative Program, which spanned over six years from 2014 to 2020 (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015). All figures [Education and Skills €36 million, agriculture €20 million, other support to civil society € six million, support measures € six million] are divided by six to generate a per annum figure, which is multiplied by the average exchange rate of € 1:N\$ 15.593 for 2018 (Exchangerates 2018).

Continue Table 10.2

Category	Main operations	2018–2019 Budget [N\$]	Multiplier [%]	Costs [N\$]
BMZ (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2019a ²¹)				
Promotion of vocational education (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2018c) ²²	The prevention of GBV is a central concern to the German development cooperation. ²³	61,124,560 ²⁴	4.38	2,677,256
Student and specialist funds ²⁵		7,640,570 ²⁶	5.83	445,445
Program to promote the competitiveness of the Namibian economy ²⁷		31,186,000 ²⁸	2.92	910,631

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²¹All the following numbers represent the per annum data [which is derived from the total budget]. The figures are multiplied by the average €–N\$ exchange rate of 1: 15.593 in 2018 (Exchangerates 2018).

²²The original German terms are presented in the next footnotes. In this case, it is “Förderung der Beruflichen Bildung.” All original project names are as well to be found under the respective BMZ Project review (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018).

²³It is defined in both strategies, in the BMZ equal opportunity concept of 2014 and the second Gender Action Plan of the German Development Policy for 2016 to 2020. In summary, GBV prevention runs in all measures and activities of the BMZ (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2019b). The per-annum figures are applied for 2018.

²⁴The program with the ID of DE-1-201122019 has an overall budget of €19,600,000 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018). The amount is divided by the project period of five years. [2012–2017, and it is expected to be continued after; therefore, it is included in Section 10.4]. See the GIZ evaluation report (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2018b) and the GIZ project evaluation (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2019b) for more information on the generation of the per annum data. The figure is multiplied by the average exchange rate of €1:N\$15.593 for 2018 (Exchangerates 2018).

²⁵Studien – und Fachkräftefond.

²⁶The overall student and specialist funds [Studien – und Fachkräftefonds] with the project ID of DE-1-201135128 has a budget of €4,900,000 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018). The project spans over ten years, from 2011 to 2021 (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2011).

²⁷Programm zur Förderung der Wettbewerbsfähigkeit der namibischen Wirtschaft.

²⁸The project has the following ID DE-1-201321819 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018). The overall budget sum of €6,000,000 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018) Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ), Stabsstelle Evaluierung 2018) is divided through the project term of three years [2015–2018] (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2014b).

Continue Table 10.2

Category	Main operations	2018–2019 Budget [N\$]	Multiplier [%]	Costs [N\$]
Groundwater management in Northern Namibia ²⁹		9,636,474 ³⁰	5.00	481,824
Partnerships of local banks ³¹		7,287,129 ³²	2.92	212,784
Municipal resource management ³³		19,491,250 ³⁴	5.83	1,136,340
Transport, mobility, and logistics ³⁵		39,734,928 ³⁶	3.50	1,390,722
Biodiversity and climate change ³⁷		31,186,000 ³⁸	4.38	1,365,947

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²⁹Grundwassermanagement im Norden Namibias.

³⁰The project with the ID of DE-1-201324722 has a budget of € 3,090,000 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018) and spans over five years from 2014 to 2019 (BGR, The Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources 2019a).

³¹Sparkassenpartnerschaften.

³²The project with the ID of DE-1-201510049 has a budget of € 1,402,000 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018) and spans over three years (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2014a). The ID related project period is not indicated within the official GIZ data (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2019c), nor within the official project evaluation data pool. Hence, the three-year time frame of the related project “Förderung der Wettbewerbsfähigkeit der namibischen Wirtschaft” is used (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2014a).

³³Kommunales Ressourcenmanagement.

³⁴The project has the ID of DE-1-201522093 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018). The overall budget sum of € 5,000,000 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018) is divided through the project time frame of three years [2016–2019] (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2016a).

³⁵Verkehr, Mobilität und Logistik.

³⁶The project with the ID of DE-1-201522101 has an overall budget sum of € 12,741,271 and is divided through the project period of five years [2016–2021] (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2016c). Please note the other sources indicate a different budget volume of € 12,500,000. For more information, read the BMZ and GIZ project evaluation report (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018, Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ), Stabsstelle Evaluierung 2018).

³⁷Biodiversität und Klimawandel.

³⁸The project with the ID DE-1-201522119 has a dedicated budget of € 6,000,000 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018), it spans from 2017 to 2020 (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2017a).

Continue Table 10.2

Category	Main operations	2018–2019 Budget [N\$]	Multiplier [%]	Costs [N\$]
	Support of the land reform ³⁹	25,988,333 ⁴⁰	17.50	4,547,958
	Sustainable use of the mineral raw material potential of Namibia ⁴¹	11,954,633 ⁴²	5.83	696,955
	Promotion of the vocational training, including the Namibia Training Authority [NTA] and the Namibian Chamber of Commerce [NCCI] ⁴³	4,142,540 ⁴⁴	2.92	120,962

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³⁹Unterstützung der Landreform.

⁴⁰The project with the ID DE-1-201522143 has a budget of € 5,000,000 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018) and runs over a time frame of three years (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2017c) from 2017 to 2020 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018).

⁴¹Nachhaltige Nutzung des mineralischen Rohstoffpotentials Namibias.

⁴²The project with the ID of DE-1-201522150 has a budget of € 2,300,000 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018) and spans over three years from 2017 to 2020. The ID related project period is neither indicated within the official GIZ data (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2019d), nor within the official project evaluation data pool (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2019a), nor in the BGR data (BGR, The Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources 2019b). The BGR statement lists the time frame of 2012 to 2020 (BGR, The Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources 2019b). However, the respective BMZ budget started already in 2017 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018). Hence, to comply with the BMZ information, the period of 2017 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018) to 2020 (BGR, The Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources 2019b) is used as an underlying time frame.

⁴³Förderung, der NTA und der Chamber of Commerce [NCCI].

⁴⁴The project with the ID of DE-1-201610203 and the assigned budget of € 797,000 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018) spans over three years (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2014a). The ID related project period is not indicated within the official GIZ data (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2019d), nor within the official project evaluation data (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2019a). Hence, the three-year time frame of the project “Förderung der Wettbewerbsfähigkeit der namibischen Wirtschaft,” which relates in its content to this activity, is used (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2014a).

Continue Table 10.2

Category	Main operations	2018–2019 Budget [N\$]	Multiplier [%]	Costs [N\$]
Sustainable Development Goals – initiative		15,593,000 ⁴⁵	17.50	2,728,775
Agricultural advice to beneficiaries of the land reform ⁴⁶		140,962,887 ⁴⁷	11.67	16,450,369
Use of the bush biomass ⁴⁸		51,976,667 ⁴⁹	3.50	1,819,183
Social Security Commission (Social Security Commission 2013 p. 47) ⁵⁰				
Sick leave benefits		4,394,971	12.97	570,028
Death benefits		2,192,435	0.04	877
Ministry of Education (Ministry of Finance 2018 ⁵¹)				
Programmes and quality assurance	Implementation of programmes, including the counselling of children with special needs.	22,200,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 162)	5.83	1,294,260
Adult education	The provision of learning opportunities for adults to participate in economic life, and to enhance their level of livelihood.	309,259,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 173)	8.75	27,060,163

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⁴⁵The project with the ID of DE-1-201622372 has a budget of €3,000,000 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018) and runs from 2017 to 2020 (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ), Status: laufendes Projekt 2017).

⁴⁶Landwirtschaftliche Beratung für Begünstigte der Landreform.

⁴⁷The project with the ID of DE-1-201622380 has a budget of €2,055,000 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018) and stretches over three years from 2017 to 2020 (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2017b).

⁴⁸Nutzung von Busch-biomasse.

⁴⁹The project with the ID of DE-1-201720648 with its assigned budget of €10,000,000 (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018) spans over three years from 2018 to 2021 (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2013).

⁵⁰The overall expenses for sick leaves are N\$16,969,000 and for death benefit N\$8,465,000 (Social Security Commission 2013 p. 47). The figures are multiplied by 17.50 per cent. For more information on the composition of the 17.50 per cent, see Section 6.4. The Social Security Commission data is from 2013. Later, publications were not accessible at the time of research. Hence, the data is levelled by the Namibian CPI for the period of 2013 to 2018 [$\frac{\text{CPI Namibia 2018}}{\text{CPI Namibia 2013}} = \frac{152.3}{102.92} = 1.48$] (World Bank 2016).

⁵¹The 2018 to 2019 budget cycle is applied (Ministry of Finance 2018).

Continue Table 10.2

Category	Main operations	2018–2019 Budget [N\$]	Multiplier [%]	Costs [N\$]
HIV and Aids monitoring unit	Programmes geared to reduce the transmission of HIV, including the mitigation of its social and economic impacts.	2,158,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 174)	3.39	73,156
Health and Social Services (Ministry of Finance 2018)				
Referral hospital services	The development of health workers' skills throughout all significant clinical disciplines.	1,959,880,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 206)	7.00	137,191,600
Regional Health and Social Welfare services	The improvement of the quality of services, including Family Health.	2,715,282,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 208)	7.00	190,069,740
Development of Social Welfare services	The provision of emergency relief to vulnerable groups, including support to Welfare organisations and children's homes.	25,215,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 212)	14.00	3,530,100
Special Disease programmes	The evaluation of programmes to prevent and mitigate possibilities of death, illness, and socio-economic losses that derive from HIV.	33,715,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 219)	4.52	1,523,918
Poverty Eradication and Social Welfare [additional programmes] (Ministry of Finance 2018)				
Poverty Eradication and Social Welfare programmes	All Namibian poverty eradication and Social Welfare programmes include the economic empowerment of	3,439,013,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 484)	17.50	601,827,275
Social Assistance	Namibian women as a core principle (Ministry of Finance 2018).	3,329,227,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 490)	11.29	375,869,728
Food provision programmes		67,560,000 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 491)	11.67	7,884,252

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Continue Table **10.2**

Category	Main operations	2018–2019 Budget [N\$]	Multiplier [%]	Costs [N\$]
Food Banks	Recipients of budget transfers	0 (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 491 ⁵²)	17.50	0
Total				1,945,601,054
Share of GDP [%] ⁵³				1.09

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.
Source: Own representation.

10.5. Conclusion

10.5.1. Summary of findings

The overall cost of social welfare expenses amount to N\$ 1,945,601,054 and constitutes 1.09 per cent of the 2018 GDP. The following two categories have the highest proportion of cost:

1. Core services are overall N\$ 1,167,766,743, and its expenses include Regional Health and Social Welfare services of N\$ 190,069,740; Poverty Eradication and Social Welfare programmes of N\$ 601,827,275; and Social Assistance of N\$ 375,869,728.
2. Childcare services amount to N\$ 439,709,813.

Only the costs of these two classes already constitute more than 80 per cent of all social welfare spending. In contrast, all other cost categories combined, including expenditures on community empowerment, childcare facilities, child protection, all [international] donor contributions combined, public sick leave, death benefits, poverty eradication, and all food provision together, amount *only* to around 17 per cent of all overall social welfare spending. To understand and discuss the results in more detail, they are again set into context with other research findings.

10.5.2. Comparison with other countries

Table **10.3** analyses the different GDP cost-shares of the other identified studies.

⁵²The budget was N\$ 30,945,403 for 2016 to 2017. It got omitted for the cycle of 2018–2019.

⁵³The GDP in the current LCU was N\$ 178.052 billion in 2018 (World Bank **2018e**).

Table 10.3.: Comparison of social welfare costs.

Country ⁵⁴	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of social welfare expenses [%] ⁵⁵	Share of social welfare expenses on overall costs [%] ⁵⁶
Developed countries						
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003	4.79	0.05	57	–
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996	1.95	0.98	58	–
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	1.00	0.47	0.03 ⁵⁹	7.10
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia 2016	[11.13]	1.35	0.10 ⁶⁰	7.27
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	7.10	0.76	0.02 ⁶¹	2.37

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⁵⁴For more detailed information, including all footnotes, see Table 3.2

⁵⁵The figure presents the ratio of social welfare costs and the GDP cost-share. Figures have been rounded up.

⁵⁶The figure presents the ratio of the social welfare proportion of cost [of GDP] and the overall proportion of cost [of GDP]. Figures have been rounded up.

⁵⁷The paper does not estimate social welfare costs.

⁵⁸The report does not state an overall sum of social welfare spending. It only displays the unit cost per survivor and family members. Further, it does not provide any data on case numbers or multipliers linked to the unit costs in order to conduct an estimation for this overview's purpose. Concrete, it writes that the "recent data on social/survivor service intensity and cost also is lacking" (Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996 p. 25).

⁵⁹The overall estimated social welfare costs are C\$ 526,855,799. They entail social service operating expenses, e.g. for shelters C\$ 285,420,000, (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 64) costs of crisis lines C\$ 611,017, (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 64) costs of support centres C\$ 120,283,245, (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 65) costs of survivor services C\$ 4,281,537, (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 65) other governmental expenditure on a federal level C\$ 9,030,687, (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 77) and the provincial and territorial level C\$ 107,229,313 (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 79).

⁶⁰The study lists social welfare expenses under Transfer costs. They are estimated to be A\$ 1.6 billion. In detail, the figure combines the 1) diminutions of lost income taxes from survivors, perpetrators, and employers; 2) additional social welfare payments and 3) survivor compensations and other government services. However, it is essential to acknowledge that point 1) is not part of this study's social welfare payment calculations due to data restrictions. However, the number under 1) cannot be removed from the total budget, as the paper does not state the single figure. Thus, the cost-share outlined in this column is higher compared to the other studies listed (KPMG Australia 2016, p. 6).

⁶¹Administrative and other costs are (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009 p. 53): A) A\$ 555 million, and B) transfer costs are expected to be A\$ 569 million, for 2021 to 2022 (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009 p. 61). However, the following has to be kept in mind – A) The overall estimates for administrative and other costs include 1) legal system costs [as incarceration, court, and private legal fees]; 2) temporary accommodation costs, and 3) other costs [as counselling, or perpetrator programmes] (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009 p. 53). However, in this paper,

Continue Table 10.3

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of social welfare expenses [%]	Share of social welfare expenses on overall costs [%]
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a	5.00	1.07	0.08 ⁶²	7.33
U.K.	2009	Walby 2009	0.60	1.00	0.03 ⁶³	3.05
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson 2006	2.60	0.10	0.03 ⁶⁴	31.87
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017	3.00	0.12	0.01 ⁶⁵	5.09
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	1.26	0.03	0.01 ⁶⁶	28.05
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	5.00	0.17	0.01 ⁶⁷	5.22
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	2.00	0.22	0.06 ⁶⁸	26.64

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legal spending is computed separately in Chapter 9. Hence, only $\frac{2}{3}$, namely A\$370 million of the overall indicated costs are used, and the $\frac{1}{3}$ share attributed to the legal spending is omitted, as the legal costs have already been calculated in Chapter 9. In detail, the study includes under B] transfer costs, the 1] losses of income taxes of survivors, perpetrators, and employers; 2] additional induced social welfare payments; 3] compensation payments, and other government services (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009 p. 61).

⁶²This following calculation is established for this overview: the overall cost of A\$ 592.4 million for the financial year of 2002 to 2003 is composed of 1] total temporary accommodation costs of A\$ 88.1 million (Access Economics 2004a p. 57); 2] administrative and other expenses, including counselling, and perpetrator programmes of A\$ 94.3 million [thereof paid by the government – A\$ 56.9 million, community – A\$ 36.1 million, family and friends – A\$ 1.3 million] (Access Economics 2004a p. 58); and 3] losses of economic efficiency associated with transfer payments of A\$ 410 million (Access Economics 2004a p. 63).

⁶³The overall cost of public services is £ 479 million. They include social services of £ 283 million and expenses for housing and shelter of £ 196 million in 2008 (Walby 2009 p. 8).

⁶⁴The overall social welfare spending computed for this review is kr 859 million. They are composed of costs for: 1] social services, which are between kr 706–1,149 million; 2] women's shelters kr 73–79 million; 3] public sector treatments for violent men kr 44 million; 4] central public agencies kr 17–18 million, and 5] social administration kr 19 million (Envall and Eriksson 2006 p. 9). In line with this research's approach, always the conservative value is employed.

⁶⁵The overall cost of € 193.3 million is composed of expenses for women's shelters [Frauenhäuser] of € 133 million and counselling services [Opfer – und Täterberatung] of € 60.3 million (Sacco 2017 p. 121). The study does not include transfer costs [Transfereinkommen] due to a lack of data (Sacco 2017 p. 106).

⁶⁶The total costs are CHF 46 million. They are composed of expenses for support services of CHF 37 million (Stern *et al.* 2013 p. 16) the sum of special and coordination services of CHF three million (Stern *et al.* 2013 p. 19), and transfer costs of CHF six million (Stern *et al.* 2013 p. 24).

⁶⁷The social welfare expenses [in the study under coûts directs non médicaux] of € 188,386,231, computed for this review, include cost of administration [administration pénitentiaire] € 84,239,463; family support [soutien familial] € 2,070,686; income support [revenue de solidarité active] € 11,265,206; accommodation [hébergement] € 58,071,904; and housing assistance [aides au logement] € 15,612,951 (Nectoux *et al.* 2010 p. 394).

⁶⁸The overall social expenses are € 627,898,654 (Villagómez 2010 p. 5).

Continue Table 10.3

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of social welfare expenses [%]	Share of social welfare expenses on overall costs [%]
Developing and emerging countries						
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012	25.40	3.19	0.69	–
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011	24.00	2.10	0.01	0.48
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	18.00	3.93	0.06	1.53
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	27.70	–	–	–
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	30.00	–	0.72	–
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014	20.00–30.00	0.90–1.30	0.03	2.31–3.33
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine 2017	10.00	0.23	0.00	0.48
Namibia	2021	Breuer 2021	17.50	6.01	1.09	18.19

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

For the developing and emerging countries, the social welfare cost-share is between 0.001 and 0.06 and is, despite their significantly higher prevalence ratios of 10.00 per cent to

⁶⁹The social welfare costs only include those for the women union of \$54,204,013 (Duvvury and Carney 2012 p. 74), which, however, only represent a fraction of the services included in this study's social welfare estimates. Hence, the findings are not included in this review to avoid distortion in the later comparison of research.

⁷⁰The overall cost computed based on Siddique's figures is Taka, \$55.34 crore [Taka, \$553,400,000]. The report does not present social welfare expenses in a total budget. Instead, the paper splits up the cost into expenses that have occurred to the individual, state, and non-state (Siddique 2011 p. 50). It hence provides the following sub-categories. First, the cost to the country: Category A – Women and Children's Affairs. The respective Secretariat and the Department of Women's Affairs have an overall budget of Taka \$41.29 crore for the financial year of 2010 to 2011. Please note, the Taka \$41.29 crore is the sum of the recurrent allocation of Taka, \$1.85 crore, and Taka, \$16.70 crore, including the development budget of Taka, \$5.85 crore and Taka, \$16.89 crore. Secondly, category B: social welfare is overall Taka, \$14.05 crore. [Taka \$14.05 crore is the sum of the recurrent budget; Taka, \$12.05 crore, and development budget Taka, \$2.00 crore] (Siddique 2011 p. 46).

⁷¹The direct costs in 2002 [Costos Directos del Estado, Consolidado 2002 Violencia Intrafamiliar] adjusted to 2003 Mex\$, that have occurred in the Colombian Institute of Family Welfare ICBF [Instituto Colombiano de Bienestar Familiar] are pesos, Mex\$ 136,349,050,634 (Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 p. 31, 34).

⁷²See the footnote under Morocco.

⁷³The overall social welfare costs are R 1,017,962,832. This calculation includes the following categories: first, Social Development with R 132,377,000. This figure is an aggregate estimate of the reported provincial expenditure on survivor empowerment of the nine provinces for the financial year of 2012 to 2013 (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 32 f.), and secondly, the cost of civil society services of R 885,585,832 (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 34).

⁷⁴The figure is 0.001. The overall social welfare costs are US\$ 1,008,736. They are composed of the total spending for social services of US\$ 745,936 and the 2015 expenses for special services, including the costs of the national GBV hotline of US\$ 262,800 (UNFPA Ukraine 2017 p. 76). According to the authors, the low share results from decreased funding and cost-cutting (UNFPA Ukraine 2017 p. 82).

30.00 per cent, on average again notably lower than compared to the developed countries. In conclusion, only a small cost-share is spent on providing social services.⁷⁵ The used method in this study is very comprehensive, and the results are therefore significantly higher as compared to other research. In order to interpret the Namibian findings better, a theoretical simulation is conducted [again], and the results of the included literature are adjusted to the Namibian prevalence proportion. Table 10.4 showcases the simulation's outcome.

Table 10.4.: Comparison of adjusted social welfare costs.

Country ⁷⁶	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New prevalence [%]	Old GDP share of social welfare costs [%]	New GDP share of social welfare costs [%]	Cost increase [%]
Developed countries							
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003	4.79	17.50	–	–	–
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996	1.95	17.50	–	–	–
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	1.00	17.50	0.03	0.53	1,667
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia 2016	[11.13]	17.50	0.10	0.16	60
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	7.10	17.50	0.02	0.05	150
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a	5.00	17.50	0.08	0.28	250
U.K.	2009	Walby 2009	0.60	17.50	0.03	0.88	2,833
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson 2006	2.60	17.50	0.03	0.20	567
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017	3.00	17.50	0.01	0.06	500
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	1.26	17.50	0.01	0.14	1,300
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	5.00	17.50	0.01	0.03	200
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	2.00	17.50	0.06	0.53	783

Continue on next page

⁷⁵See, for instance, the explanations in the Ukrainian Centre for Social Reforms study (UNFPA Ukraine 2017 p. 82).

⁷⁶For more detailed information, including all footnotes, see Section 3.4

Continue Table 10.4							
Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New prevalence [%]	Old GDP share of social welfare costs [%]	New GDP share of social welfare costs [%]	Cost increase [%]
Developing and emerging countries							
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney	25.40	17.50	–	–	–
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique	24.00	17.50	0.01	0.01 ⁷⁷	0.00 ⁷⁸
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres	18.00	17.50	0.06	0.06	0.00 ⁷⁹
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i>	27.70	17.50	–	–	–
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i>	30.00	17.50	–	–	–
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa	20.00–30.00	17.50	0.03	0.02–0.03	–35 ⁸⁰
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine	10.00	17.50	0.00 ⁸¹	0.00 ⁸²	100
Namibia	2021	Breuer	17.50	17.50	1.09	1.09	0.00

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

In summary, for the developed countries, the GDP share increased from 60 per cent in KPMG Australia 2016 to 2,833 per cent in the British Walby 2009 paper. Figure 10.1 showcases the results in more detail. For the first time, there has occurred no change for the developing and emerging countries outside Europe. The baseline value was relatively insignificant compared to other cost categories, as the examined developing nations spend only minimal amounts on social welfare. Nevertheless, to conclude, the computed Namibian outcome at 1.09 per cent is still high. Only the British Walby 2009 research reached a similar figure with theoretically 0.88 per cent. One reason is that this approach examines the broad scope of budgets and their connection to GBV very holistically. This paper includes, for instance, statements on adult education, referral hospital services, or food banks, as well. As a result, it goes beyond the standard approaches, which are usually applied to compute social welfare benefits, as performed in the majority of listed research.

However, during the calculation process, it becomes again – as already within the other cost categories – evident that although spending is comparatively high, individuals suffer from severe obstacles to access social welfare support programmes, and often only a limited number

⁷⁷Deviations were caused by rounding the values to two digits after the comma.

⁷⁸The numbers are rounded to two figures after the comma; hence the variation is not depicted in Table 10.4

⁷⁹Ibid.

⁸⁰Ibid.

⁸¹Detailed figure 0.001 per cent.

⁸²Detailed figure 0.002 per cent.

Legend: 1. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) [2003]. 2. Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996]. 3. Zhang *et al.* [2012]. 4. KPMG Australia [2016]. 5. National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) [2009]. 6. Access Economics [2004a]. 7. Walby [2009]. 8. Envall and Eriksson [2006]. 9. Sacco [2017]. 10. Stern *et al.* [2013]. 11. Nectoux *et al.* [2010]. 12. Villagómez [2010]. 13. Duvvury and Carney [2012]. 14. Siddique [2011]. 15. Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004]. 16. Duvvury *et al.* [2009] (for Morocco), 17. Duvvury *et al.* [2009] (for Uganda), 18. KPMG South Africa [2014]. 19. UNFPA Ukraine [2017] and 20. Breuer [2021].

Figure 10.1.: Comparison of adjusted social welfare costs.

is entitled to receive such social benefits (Coomer [2019] Delegation of the European Union to Namibia [2018]). This problem is discussed further in Section 10.5.3

10.5.3. Further discussion

There are several obstacles to access social welfare programmes in Namibia. The international and national literature (Coomer [2019] Delegation of the European Union to Namibia [2018] European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation [2015] Ministry of Gender Equality and Child Welfare [2012] stresses several issues within the Namibian Social Welfare system. In summary, the research indicates a:

1. Positive socialisation and education towards GBV: social acceptance of GBV is high. Citizens often believe that a husband is justified to beat his wife under certain circumstances (Ministry of Health and Social Services (MoHSS) [2008] p. 245). Such social values hinder that women and children seek support and services, making it difficult to estimate the exact costs.
2. Problematic gender roles: in line with the aforementioned aspects, such traditional mindsets present a significant obstacle in preventing GBV. For Namibian men, masculinity equals ownership and control over women. Furthermore, Namibian women are often socialised to accept being inferior to men and believe that men are entitled to discipline them (Ministry of Gender Equality and Child Welfare [2012] p. 19). Hence; also national citizens in administration and social welfare organisations, who are supposed to assist survivors, have inherited such values, which in return may prevent the adequate delivery of services.

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3. Insufficient service provisions: as said, such traditional values nourish the inadequate delivery of services (Ministry of Gender Equality and Child Welfare [2012](#), p. 20). Consequently, the cycle repeats itself: the staff is unwilling to provide tangible support, which leads to a lack of quality and quantity of services. In addition, survivors are deterred from reporting and seeking assistance and receiving the budgeted support.

Consequently, such problems lead to the situation that:

1. The majority of survivors do not report nor seeks support, and thus, the budget is not entirely spent.
2. In return, only a fraction of individuals receive services. However, the actual need and the real cost, based on the scope of the problem, are significantly higher.
3. This cultural mindset is often well represented within the mentalities of administration and government. Thus the dedicated budget is likely to be not entirely spent to the benefit of those in need.

In summary, if all survivors in need were serviced [adequately], the actual cost is assumed to be [even] higher.

10.6. Summary

Chapter [10](#) described the social welfare, including the special service costs. The method used was that of the budget-share approach. It was chosen because of its simplicity and robustness. The calculations are based on a very holistic and extensive dataset. The primary data is derived from the Ministry of Finance, including budget data of the Namibian Ministry of Education, Ministry of Health, or Ministry for Poverty Eradication, and various non-governmental organisations, such as the U.N., the E.U., or the German development agencies (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) [2018](#); Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) [2019a](#); Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) [2020](#); European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation [2015](#); Ministry of Finance [2018](#); United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) [2017](#)). Various specific multiplier data was used to compute realistic case numbers, which led to a very comprehensive result (Dolan *et al.* [2005](#); Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#); Jewkes [2018](#); Jewkes *et al.* [2010](#); Walby [2004](#)). The total cost is 1.09 per cent of the gross domestic product. The expenses of combating poverty and the provision of general social welfare programmes comprise the highest cost blocks. It is also worth noting that the expenses for care and protection of affected children represent a considerable part of the spendings. The findings were compared to the results of various other international studies. In sum, the calculated costs are disproportionately high. This is mainly because this study holistically dealt with the different cost sections and went in its scope beyond the general standard. For example, the expenditure of various non-governmental organisations and third agencies was considered as well. These expenses are mostly not borne by the Namibian state but by the international community. The budgets of the most important aid organisations were analysed in detail and extensively. In Section [10.5.3](#), it became clear that certain cultural norms contribute to a likely distortion in the outcome. For instance, positive socialisation towards GBV initiates social acceptance of violence. In certain Namibian regions, husbands believe that they are entitled to hit their wives under

specific conditions if they burn the food, for example (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 289). These norms may be reflected in employees and officials working in national government and administration too. Hence, it is even likely that certain funds will be made available for the prevention of violence, but due to a cultural misperception of [certain] civil servants, they will not be used or will be misused. This creates a sinister cycle. [Some] employees may be unwilling to help those affected, even if the funds are made available, which in return, likely prevents abused citizens from seeking help. As a result, trauma and suffering are prolonged, and costs continue to increase in the long run.

To continue, Chapter 11 presents the calculations of the personal costs.

11. Personal costs

11.1. Introduction

Personal costs affect household consumption to a great extent and decrease the number of goods and services that would be purchased in the absence of such violence. Affected individuals experience different out-of-pocket expenses, such as the costs of personal security, repair of property, or relocation (Day, McKenna, and Bowlus 2005).¹ Section 11.2 presents the applied unit-cost approach, including its advantages and disadvantages, and Section 11.3 describes the used datasets. The applied primary data derives again from the NHDS findings (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). The cost data is taken from representative surveys, including the studies by Rudd, Hubbard, and Engelbrecht 2013, own qualitative surveys, and datasets of Namibian statistical authorities (Breuer 2018, Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016). The case numbers are based on the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b data. For specific subcategories, such as expropriation, percentages from surveys of the Namibian and African auction authorities are used (Ngatjiheue 2015). The case numbers are set in relation to an elaborate set of multiplier data in order to estimate the most realistic outcome possible. Further, data from Namibian courts regarding divorce rates are used, and the ratios of the NDHS regarding marital statuses are applied (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). Regarding the destruction of property as a result of GBV, the proportions of international research are transferred to the Namibian context. The findings are shown in Section 11.4 and are discussed in Section 11.5. The results of Chapter 11 are presented, and the data are compared with those of other international research. Section 11.5.1 raises different literature results to the Namibian prevalence ratio to achieve a deeper understanding. Section 11.5.2 outlines a further discussion of the findings, and the topics that emerged during the calculation of Chapter 11 are discussed further.

11.2. Approach

There are different methods to compute personal costs and out-of-pocket expenses. Based on the findings in Chapter 5, the unit-cost approach was chosen to be best suitable for this paper's context and purpose.

¹The indirect costs through reduced household income due to lost or reduced earnings and the reduction in paid and unpaid household income have been computed in Chapter 7. Lost economic output.

Unit-cost approach

The approach divides the total cost of a specified item within its distinct time period by the amount of a particular utilisation of an activity in order to compute the specific unit cost, which will be multiplied by the relevant case number, and summed up to an overall bill of action (Walby and Olive 2014 p. 76). Based on the literature review, the following three-step approach was defined and is presented as an example of the “unit cost for relocation expenses.”

1. Step I – The calculation of unit costs. For instance, the average price for relocating a two-bedroom apartment.
2. Step II – The estimation of the relevant incidents. For instance, calculating the number of women who suffer from violence AND thus decides to relocate.
3. Step III – The totalling of relevant cases for each unit cost category per annum.

In brief, the advantages and disadvantages can be summarised as the following:

1. Advantages:
 - a) The average unit cost values contribute to higher comparability of research (Walby and Olive 2014 p. 82).
 - b) The weighted low-level unit costs provide a more precise output as compared to the high-level estimates of the budget spending approach, for instance (Walby and Olive 2014 p. 57).
2. Disadvantages:
 - a) In case a detailed level of [administrative] data is not available, the unit costs cannot be calculated (UNFPA Ukraine 2017). In such a case, the comparative budget-share approach may be a better fit (Walby and Olive 2014 p. 57).
 - b) Unit costs isolate expenditures from the rest of the budget and may introduce distortion into the estimates (Walby and Olive 2014 p. 76). For instance, relocation expenses can be included under different national budget categories. As a result, the costs have to be either taken into account under the category of personal costs, for instance, or under the respective other categories, such as social welfare spending, to avoid double counting.

In general, the unit cost model was found to be viable to provide accurate estimates that are both simple and replicable. However, the model’s validity and accuracy depend upon the availability and quality of national data (Walby and Olive 2014 p. 14, 76).

11.3. Data

Section 11.3 presents an overview of the applied data to calculate the personal costs. In order to estimate the different categories, the following primary datasets are used²

²For detailed information on the calculations, see Chapter 20 in the Appendix.

Basic data

Again, the GBV prevalence data from the 2014 NDHS is applied. The data was surveyed in 2013, and the report was published in 2014 (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). The detailed calculation of the unit costs and case numbers are described in the next three paragraphs.

Unit cost data on personal expenses

- The out-of-pocket unit cost of divorce: Rudd, Hubbard, and Engelbrecht 2013 surveyed the costs of different legal-aid entities and attorneys to evaluate data on the average costs of an uncontested divorce. The figures are from 2013. Hence, the data [N\$ 7,500 and N\$ 30,000] was levelled by the Namibian CPI for the period of 2013 to 2018 [CPI Namibia 2018/CPI Namibia 2013; $132.5/102.92 = 1.48$] (World Bank 2020d).
- The out-of-pocket unit cost of a protection order: since a protection order is free of charge in Namibia (Immigration and Refugee Board of Canada 2012), expenses are covered by the government. The government costs were integrated into Chapter 9 legal costs.
- The out-of-pocket unit cost of a relocation: the data stems from a survey of moving companies in 2018. The baseline data is the average cost of relocating a two-bedroom apartment (Breuer 2018).
- The out-of-pocket unit cost of property damage: no data for Namibia or Southern Africa was available; thus, the estimates rely on the unit costs from the Access Economics 2004a, p. 45 report and the Henderson 2000, p. 45 paper³ which were then converted into Namibia dollars⁴.
- The out-of-pocket unit cost of phone security: such security measures are not accessible to survivors in Namibia (Solidaritätsdienst International e. V. (SODI) 2018).
- The out-of-pocket unit cost of repossession: unit costs are calculated from the 2015 Namibia Household Income and Expenditure Survey [NHIES] – which was published in 2016 – and are adjusted to 2018 values (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016 p. 96, 100).

Case number data

- Personal legal costs, relocation expenses, and property damages⁵ The case numbers are based on the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b database and include:
 - The current female population in 2018, 15 to 49 years, that suffer from physical and sexual violence [17.50 per cent, 120,614]⁶ and

³The overall cost for damaged or destroyed property was US\$ 243.7 million from 2002 to 2003 (Access Economics 2004a, p. 45). Figures were adjusted to 2018 values. It is assumed that the data can be transferred to Namibia since GBV depicts globally similar patterns and socioeconomic consequences. See Chapter 6

⁴See Chapter 20 for a detailed calculation of the conversion.

⁵Cost for protection orders and phone security are not computed because such services are either not accessible or covered in another cost category. See the previous paragraph.

⁶For more information on the composition of the 17.50 per cent, see Section 6.4

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- The current male population in 2018, 15 to 49 years that suffer from physical violence [4.60 per cent, 10,324].⁷
 - Cost of repossession: the case numbers are obtained from the 2015/2016 Namibia Household Income and Expenditure Survey [NHIES] (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016 p. 80, 81, 96, 100) and Africa’s Auction Authority register (Ngatjiheue 2015), and are adjusted to 2018 census data.⁸ Based on this information, the national ratio of outstanding debts, which reflects the number of households that went through the process of repossession with the Namibian Auction Authority, is computed.

Multiplier data

- Cost of divorce: the baseline is the national High Court’s main division’s register for all instances of criminal acts, such as property damages, maintenance -, or legal disputes in 2018 (The Namibian High Court 2018).
- Cost of relocation: the information derives from the 2014 NDHS (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). The survey’s GBV, divorce, separation, and living-together probabilities are utilised to compute the share of survivors who relocates because of a divorce or separation caused by GBV.
- Cost of property damage: the research of Henderson 2000 p. 45 on “Impacts and costs of domestic violence on the Australian Business and Corporate Sector” [2000], provides data on the share of women who experienced property damage as a result of GBV. Henderson’s ratios are applied since Namibian data was not available [at the point of research].
- Cost of repossession: the share of 17.50 per cent of Namibian women who experienced physical and sexual violence is applied to all Namibian households that got repossessed (MoHSS and ICF International 2014).

Further information and data on multipliers, case numbers and unit costs are provided in Chapter 20. In order to continue, Section 11.4 presents the estimated personal costs.

11.4. Results

Table 11.1 depicts the results in detail.

⁷In detail, 1,259,465 was the male population in 2018. Thereof, are 660.080 men 15 to 49 years (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b), of which 224,427 men [aged 15 to 49] are living in a union [34 per cent] (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 46). Further, 4.60 per cent of Namibian women aged 15 to 49 committed physical violence against their partners in the past 12 months. [Thus, an estimated number of 10,324 men are subjected to GBV. Please note, men were not directly interviewed] (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 313).

⁸The Namibia Statistics Agency’s data is from 2015. The data is used because it was at the point of research, the most holistic information available. The findings of this paper are presented as a proportion of the 2018 GDP; hence, the NHIES data is adjusted to 2018 values. The Namibian 2018 population was 2,448,255, and the Namibian 2015 population was 2,314,904 citizens (World Bank 2020c). Thus, the increase-in-population factor is around 1.06, and the respective NHIES census data is inflated by factor 1.06.

Table 11.1.: Results of the total personal costs.

Category ⁹	Unit cost [N\$]	Survivors [numbers] ¹⁰	Costs [N\$]
Legal costs for divorce, average non-opposed case	11,100	3,903	43,323,300
Legal costs for divorce, average opposed case	44,400	1,673	73,612,000
Protection order	0 ¹¹	–	0
Relocation expenses	4,500	5,575	25,089,480
Property damage	13,866	23,942	331,978,094
Phone security	0 ¹²	–	0
Repossession	14,965	2,327	34,823,555
		Total	499,092,354
		Share of GDP [%] ¹³	0.28

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

11.5. Conclusion

11.5.1. Summary of findings

This is the category with one of the lowest GDP per cost-share [0.28 per cent]. As a result of the high case numbers with 23,942 incidents, the costliest personal expenses are property damages, that amount to around 70 per cent of all personal costs. The lowest amount display relocation expenses¹⁴. As already done within the previous chapters, to interpret results in more detail, they will be set into relation to the outcome of other publications [see Table 11.2].

⁹For detailed information on the calculations, see Chapter 20.

¹⁰For detailed information on the case number and multiplier calculation, see Chapter 20.

¹¹In Namibia, these costs do not occur as a private expense; as such are covered by the government and were calculated in Chapter 9 legal costs.

¹²See Section 11.3.

¹³The GDP in the current LCU was N\$ 178.052 billion in 2018 (World Bank 2018e).

¹⁴For more information, see Section 11.5.2.

Comparison with other countries

Table 11.2.: Comparison of personal costs.

Country ¹⁵	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of personal costs [%] ¹⁶	Share of personal costs on overall costs [%] ¹⁷
Developed countries						
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC)	4.79	0.05	18	–
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema	1.95	0.98	19	–
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i>	1.00	0.47	20	3.66
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia	[11.13]	1.35	21	51.36
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C)	7.10	0.76	22	22.71
Australia	2004	Access Economics	5.00	1.07	23	31.89
U.K.	2009	Walby	0.60	1.00	24	–
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson	2.60	0.10	25	–
Germany	2017	Sacco	3.00	0.12	26	–
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i>	1.26	0.03	27	–
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i>	5.00	0.17	28	–

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¹⁵For more detailed information, including all footnotes, see Table 3.2

¹⁶The figure presents a factor of personal cost and GDP share Figures have been rounded up.

¹⁷The figure illustrates the ratio of the personal cost-share [of GDP] and the overall proportion of cost [of GDP]. Figures have been rounded up.

¹⁸The paper does not estimate the personal costs.

¹⁹The study calculates property damage only and includes rape and sexual assault cases solely (Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996 p. 9).

²⁰The personal costs of violence against men and women are C\$ 271,262,000 (Zhang *et al.* 2012 p. 80).

²¹The survivors bear A\$ 11.3 billion, or 52 per cent, of the total cost (KPMG Australia 2016 Introduction). It is the costliest estimate within all listed studies, partly caused by the high share of intangibles, that was included in this section (KPMG Australia 2016 p. 5).

²²The overall consumption-related costs are A\$ 3,542 million for 2021 to 2022. The category includes the short-term costs of replacing damaged property and defaulting on bad debt, as well as the long-term costs arising from the loss of economies of scale in consumption (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009 p. 49).

²³In summary, the overall cost is A\$ 2,575,700,000. Expenses include the loss through damaged or destroyed property [A\$ 244 million] and the decrease in the scale of consumption [A\$ 2,331 million] for the year 2002 to 2003 (Access Economics 2004a p. 46).

²⁴Personal costs are not directly listed (Walby 2009 p. 8).

²⁵Personal costs are not estimated (Envall and Eriksson 2006 p. 9).

²⁶Ibid (Sacco 2017 p. 98–114).

²⁷Ibid (Stern *et al.* 2013 p. 2).

²⁸Ibid (Nectoux *et al.* 2010 p. 394).

Continue Table 11.2

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of personal costs [%]	Share of personal costs on overall costs [%]
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	2.00	0.22	0.06 ²⁹	42.66
Developing and emerging countries						
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012	25.40	3.19	– ³⁰	–
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011	24.00	2.10	0.06 ³¹	0.00
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	18.00	3.93	0.27 ³²	6.87
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	27.70	–	– ³³	–
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	30.00	–	– ³⁴	–
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014	20.00–30.00	0.90–1.30	0.77 ³⁵	59.23–85.56
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine 2017	10.00	0.23	0.01 ³⁶	5.18
Namibia	2021	Breuer 2021	17.50	6.01	0.28	4.67

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Based on these findings, the following deductions are made:

1. Developed countries: the cost-share is between 0.02 and 0.70 [based on a prevalence ratio of 1.00 and 11.13 per cent]³⁷. For the first time, the two Australian studies of 2016 (KPMG Australia 2016) [0.70 per cent GDP share], and of 2009 (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009) [0.17 per cent GDP share] have computed a higher or a [similarly] high GDP cost-share as the Namibian results with 0.28 per cent of GDP.

²⁹The total personal costs are €1,005,384,529, which comprises around 40 per cent of the overall expenses and state one of the highest shares within the literature examined. This is because losses include the employment-related costs of €195,876,678 and the Social agenda of €602,944,911 as well (Villagómez 2010 p. 5).

³⁰Personal costs are not calculated (Duvvury and Carney 2012).

³¹The overall sum is Taka, ৳2,349,959. The costs are composed of medical costs to the individuals and families of Taka, ৳1,941,070, and other expenses [to the survivors and families] of Taka, ৳408,889 (Siddique 2011 p. 43). Figures are rounded to two numbers behind the comma. The detailed figure is 0.00003 per cent.

³²The total cost is Mex\$ 601,094,789,385 (Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004, p. 34).

³³Duvvury *et al.* 2009, p. 12 do not estimate the total cost. She only calculates the average price per incident of one-time service use.

³⁴See the footnote under Morocco.

³⁵Personal costs are R25,204,817,522. They cover consumption costs, loss of earnings, and expenses associated with morbidity and mortality (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 29 f.).

³⁶The personal costs of a “typical scenario” were US\$ 10,778 thousand in 2015 (UNFPA Ukraine 2017 p. 79).

³⁷Regarding the 11.30 per cent in KPMG Australia 2016 the primary data refers to *since the age of 15, not to within the past 12 months* (Australian Bureau of Statistics 2012).

2. Developing and emerging countries: a broad range of different outcomes occurs since the applied methods differ substantially for this category³⁸. Outcome ranges from 0.00003 in Siddique²⁰¹¹³⁹ to 0.77 per cent of GDP in KPMG South Africa²⁰¹⁴. Siddique's low outcome of 0.00003 per cent of GDP is based on a higher prevalence [24.00 per cent]. Siddique's approach is not as profound and holistic as compared to such used within other papers. For instance, Ribero and Sánchez Torres²⁰⁰⁴ applied a detailed methodological approach and calculated for Colombia a similar cost-proportion of 0.27 based on an 18.00 per cent prevalence.

Again, other literature findings are hypothetically adjusted to the Namibian prevalence ratio of 17.50 per cent in order to interpret the results in more detail [see Table 11.3].

Table 11.3.: Comparison of adjusted personal costs.

Country ⁴⁰	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New Prevalence [%]	Old GDP share of personal costs [%]	New GDP share of personal costs [%]	Increase of costs [%]
Developed countries							
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC)	4.79	17.50	–	–	–
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema ¹⁹⁹⁶	1.95	17.50	–	–	–
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> ²⁰¹²	1.00	17.50	0.02	0.35	1,650
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia ²⁰¹⁶	[11.13]	17.50	0.70	1.10	57
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) ²⁰⁰⁹	7.10	17.50	0.17	0.42	147
Australia	2004	Access Economics ^{2004a}	5.00	17.50	0.34	1.19	250
U.K.	2009	Walby ²⁰⁰⁹	0.60	17.50	–	–	–
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson ²⁰⁰⁶	2.60	17.50	–	–	–

Continue on next page

³⁸For more information, see Chapter 3.

³⁹The figures are rounded to two numbers in Table 11.2.

⁴⁰For more detailed information, including all footnotes, see Table 3.2.

Continue Table 11.3								
Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New Prevalence [%]	Old GDP share of personal costs [%]	New GDP share of personal costs [%]	Increase of costs [%]	
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017	3.00	17.50	–	–	–	
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	1.26	17.50	–	–	–	
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	5.00	17.50	–	–	–	
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	2.00	17.50	0.09	0.79	778	
Developing and emerging countries								
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012	25.40	17.50	–	–	–	
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011	24.00		0.00 ⁴¹	–33	0.00 ⁴²	
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	18.00	17.50	0.27	0.26	–3.70	
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	27.70	17.50	–	–	–	
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	30.00	17.50	–	–	–	
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014	20.00–30.00	17.50	0.77	0.45–0.67	–13 to –42	
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine 2017	10.00	17.50	0.01	0.02	100	
Namibia	2021	Breuer 2021	17.50	17.50	0.28	0.28	0.00	

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

For the developed countries, the GDP share increased from 57 per cent in Australia (KPMG Australia 2016) to 1,650 per cent in Canada (Stern *et al.* 2013). For the developing and emerging countries, mainly, a decrease in cost occurred. However, the decline is, to its extent, not as significant as in the categories lost economic output and health service costs.⁴³ Figure 11.1 showcases the results in more detail.

Now all cost-shares, except for Bangladesh, Colombia and Ukraine, would be theoretically higher than the Namibian one. However, during the process of computation and research, several obstacles became again evident, which may have influenced the findings and could explain the modest outcome better. The results are discussed in Section 11.5.2

⁴¹Figures are rounded to two numbers behind the comma. The detailed figure is 0.00003 per cent.

⁴²Ibid. Detailed figure 0.00002 per cent.

⁴³See Chapters 7 and 8

Legend: 1. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) [2003]. 2. Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996]. 3. Zhang *et al.* [2012]. 4. KPMG Australia [2016]. 5. National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) [2009]. 6. Access Economics [2004a]. 7. Walby [2009]. 8. Envall and Eriksson [2006]. 9. Sacco [2017]. 10. Stern *et al.* [2013]. 11. Nectoux *et al.* [2010]. 12. Villagómez [2010]. 13. Duvvury and Carney [2012]. 14. Siddique [2011]. 15. Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004]. 16. Duvvury *et al.* [2009] (for Morocco), 17. Duvvury *et al.* [2009] (for Uganda), 18. KPMG South Africa [2014]. 19. UNFPA Ukraine [2017] and 20. Breuer [2021].

Figure 11.1.: Comparison of adjusted personal costs.

11.5.2. Further discussion

Problems in assessing the personal costs in Namibia

Again, the national and international literature states several issues within the system, which influence the personal costs estimates. Among other things, research reveals a:

1. Low help-seeking behaviour: for instance, only 21 per cent of Namibian women who have experienced any form of physical violence during their lifetime have sought help from any source (MoHSS and ICF International [2014] p. 315).
In general, help-seeking behaviour decreased with the women's age and the number of children (MoHSS and ICF International [2014] p. 316).
2. The most common source of support is the survivor's family: the most common element of assistance was the survivor's own family. Forty-eight per cent of individuals have sought help from their own families, whereas social work organisations are a source of support for only five per cent of the abused (Ministry of Health and Social Services (MoHSS) [2008] p. 316).
3. No data on relocation: there is no Namibian data on survivors' relocating due to GBV. Due to this lack, it is only assumed based on the findings of other international research (Access Economics [2004a] Henderson [2000]) that both women and men who are subjected to GBV physically relocate after their divorce or separation. Hence, ratios of women and men who are divorced or separated and who are subjected to GBV are utilised. Thereby taking into consideration the official divorce prevalence, which is only one per cent for women (MoHSS and ICF International [2014] p. 46), will lead to distortion. Separation rarely occurs in Namibia because women often do not become divorced to avoid legal or cultural

consequences. As a result, they tend to stay married but continue to live separately (Legal Assistance Centre (LAC) [2017]). Hence, relocation cost did occur, although the official census data did not indicate so. Therefore, the share of separated women [3.40 per cent] is added to the divorce ratio [one per cent] in the multiplier estimation in order to account for this cohort as well.

4. Problems of divorce: as indicated under point 3] “No data on relocation,” there are several obstacles to receiving a divorce, as Namibia’s divorce law is outdated. The current legislation is based on fault. In consequence, this implies that one spouse has to prove that the other spouse has committed any wrongdoing (Legal Assistance Centre (LAC) [2017]). However, this becomes a problem, as there is a culture of silence surrounding GBV, and in consequence, violence is frequently concealed. Moreover, the policing and evidence system is weak. Further, it is almost impossible to effect a divorce without the support of a lawyer, even when both parties agree on how to divide the assets and the custody of the children. In addition, divorce cases are only heard by the High Court, which is situated in Namibia’s capital city of Windhoek. It increases costs and obstacles further, especially for people living in rural areas with limited financial resources (Indongo and Pazvakawambwa [2015]; Legal Assistance Centre (LAC) [2005a]; Menges [2013]; Namibia Superior Courts [2019]).
5. Property dispossession: property dispossession is officially acknowledged in Namibia. It can occur when women turn widows or sometimes even when they separate. Then the husband’s family takes all possessions from the former female partner and thus increases their vulnerability further (Mogotsi *et al.* [2015]). Particular literature even states that widow dispossession seems to have reached epidemic proportions (Werner [2008]). However, because not much comprehensive research is available for this cultural phenomenon of property grabbing, the cost could not be estimated. Still, women whom the husband’s family expropriates should be acknowledged in the costing literature, and more research is needed in this regard.

Consequently, the mentioned problems lead to:

1. No or decreased help-seeking behaviour: thus, the calculations do not fully depict the reality of spending, as expenses occur in secret and are often hidden by various stakeholders.
2. The most common source of support is the survivor’s own family (Ministry of Health and Social Services (MoHSS) [2008] p. 316): this free-of-charge family support certainly reduces the economic burden of the affected. However, although family members and friends, in most cases, help survivors to relocate, the unit cost factor is applied nevertheless. Since the costs of women who cannot afford a relocation or depend on in-kind support should not be left out in this estimation, and to take the family members’ expenses into account as well.
3. Data on relocation and problems associated with divorce: in total, 1.00 per cent of women and 0.80 per cent of men, age 15–49, are divorced or separated (MoHSS and ICF International [2014] p. 46). The culture of not receiving a divorce, as it is associated with shame, makes it difficult to estimate the actual cost. Due to a lack of data, it is assumed that the cohort of both men and women subjected to GBV relocates as a consequence of divorce and separation. However, there is no secure information, and according to the national census data, Namibians stay officially married. Hence, survivors may move out but stay married though. An indication for this assumption is that there is a gap

between the low divorce ratio of one per cent and the high GBV prevalence (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) p. 30).

4. Property dispossession: various literature states that widow dispossession seems to have reached epidemic proportions (Werner [2008](#)). However, since no data is available, the associated cost of this phenomenon could not be calculated.

Therefore, this calculation of the personal costs can be seen as an estimation of the actual spending.

11.6. Summary

Chapter [11](#) presented all the costs that those affected have to bear personally. The used method is that of the unit-cost approach. It was selected because it delivers a high level of detail and thus creates a holistic cost profile. The used data for out-of-pocket legal spending bases on qualitative research, such as interviews with private and public legal entities. Relocation costs associated with GBV were derived from qualitative interviews and surveys, for instance (Breuer [2018](#), MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#), Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) [2016](#), Rudd, Hubbard, and Engelbrecht [2013](#), Solidaritätsdienst International e. V. (SODI) [2018](#)). The cost of property destruction is based on the research of Henderson [2000](#), whose data is transferred and embedded into the Namibian context. Losses from property dispossession are taken from Namibian survey data of the African Auction entity (Ngatjiheue [2015](#)). Case numbers are calculated based on Namibian and U.N. census data and other regional and national statistical surveys (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#), United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) [2018b](#)). Overall, this cost category calculated with [0.28 per cent] one of the lowest cost-shares within this study. The highest costs are those of property destruction resulting from GBV. They account for almost 70 per cent of the total expenses within this cost class. This is mainly due to the high incidents of damage and destruction. When comparing these results later with the data from other international literature, in which the prevalence proportions are raised to the Namibian level, the following picture emerges: in developing and emerging countries, a large proportion of the studies now shows a higher share of costs than the one calculated for Namibia, which is a different development compared to the other categories. In the final discussion, it becomes clear why this share of costs is lower compared to other publications. According to research, the family's place is the most common refuge for the greater part of Namibian women. A large share, 48 per cent of those affected, seek help from their families (Ministry of Health and Social Services (MoHSS) [2008](#) p. 316). This means that the majority of the costs, such as accommodation or relocation, are paid for by their families. It should also be mentioned that the Namibian divorce rate is low. Only one per cent of women choose a divorce (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) p. 46). Officially, couples remain married; however, relocation is assumed to be made nevertheless. The upholding of marriage often takes place due to cultural and economic reasons. As a result, divorce rates and associated costs are at a very low level. It must be mentioned that the legal hurdles to getting a divorce are extremely high too. The applicant must prove that their spouse acted wrongly (Legal Assistance Centre (LAC) [2017](#)). Due to specific weaknesses in the prosecution and evidence preservation system, this is an additional high hurdle posed under the rule of law. Further, there is also the phenomenon of expropriation in Namibia. For example, single or widowed women are often expropriated by the husband's own family (Werner [2008](#)). This is another reason for women not to seek divorce

or separation. In summary, in Section 11.4 these aspects resulted in a low cost for divorce and relocation. However, the violence still persists and occurs; hence, expenses that can be measured fully, such as the cost of property destruction, is high in relation to other findings.

In order to continue, Chapter 12 will present the calculation of the intangibles, physical, and emotional losses.

12. Intangibles, physical, and emotional impact

12.1. Introduction

Chapter 12 showcases the calculated Intangible costs for adults. The calculations are based on the QALY loss-based WTP approach. The QALY data depict the loss of Quality of Life suffered by GBV survivors. The WTP values add an economic dimension to the QALY figures, and the data shows what a nation is willing to pay to reduce violence. Section 12.2 describes the method used and presents its respective advantages and disadvantages. Section 12.3 showcases the applied data sources. The QALY data of GBV are taken from research by Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005. The case numbers are based on surveys by The Namibian Police 2018 and are adjusted to a realistic level by using suitable multiplier sets that derive from the NDHS (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). The results are shown in Section 12.4. Section 12.5.1 summarises the data briefly, and Section 12.5.2 compares the findings with those from other studies. In Section 12.5.3 the discussion and the presentation of the information and problems that occurred in the process of data collection and calculation take place.

12.2. Approach

QALY-loss-based WTP approach

The method is based on the assumption that a nation is willing to pay a certain amount of money to avoid specific adverse health state outcomes. The overall question raised is how much a society is willing to pay to prevent GBV. The approach estimates the pain and suffering resulting from GBV and thus the lost Quality of Life [measured in years]. The WTP model is utilised by Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Walby 2004; Walby 2009, as it calculates rape and sexual violence losses best. The underlying data is updated regularly, and QALY-losses are available for all crime types, including rape, wounding, sexual, and common assault. Hence, the whole spectrum of GBV cases can be costed. Moreover, the model includes physical injuries and mental health impacts, and thus, can calculate a holistic picture of losses. The approach is understood to be a conservative estimate and does not tend to inflate costs (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005). It only requires minimum data specifications, is consequently easily replicable, comparable and therefore fits this scope (Walby and Olive 2014).

p. 15). Since the method combines two different approaches, the advantages and disadvantages of each are summarised in the next enumeration.¹

1. Advantages:

- QALYs: combine the calculations of both, first, the additional length of life gained through intervention, and second, the quality of life achieved. Hence, it creates a good foundation to conduct a holistic cost debate. The method provides average unit costs that allow for comparison between different interventions (Malek 2000). The approach merges health impacts on mortality and morbidity into one single index; thus, comparison among other treatments becomes possible (Whitehead and Ali 2010). The WTP approach then adds information on what individuals and society are willing to pay to prevent GBV to the QALY data.
- WTP-approach: delivers more accurate estimates, as data is derived from behaviour.² It also covers mental health impacts that are resulting from GBV as well. The model requires a manageable number of data records. As a result, it is easily replicable and feasible to implement. It provides estimates of what citizens are willing to pay to avoid certain crimes and adverse health states. Hence, the method can serve as a helpful advocacy tool for policymakers too (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005).

In summary, the advantages of the recommended QALY-loss-based WTP-model are its methodical robustness and limited data needs (Walby and Olive 2014, p. 15). Nevertheless, caution should be applied when utilising QALY data since they are associated with several methodical challenges (Malek 2000).

2. Disadvantages:

- QALYs: QALY values can derive from various types of surveys conducted in different areas and locations. Therefore, data might not be transferable to all research strings (Bala and Zarkin 2000; Malek 2000). QALYs-data can sometimes be flawed, as they can be received from biased measurement techniques or non-representative sample sizes, for instance (Hirskyj 2007). QALYs do not cover non-health benefits and other social and ethical factors (Malek 2000), such as a faster return to employment or better school performance, although they are of importance (Tinelli, Ryan, and Bond 2010).
- WTP-approach: the method makes certain assumptions regarding the similarity of duration and intensity of injuries. The lack of international data sources on individuals' WTP provides further uncertainty (Walby and Olive 2014). Further, the method produces culturally biased results, especially in nations where GBV is normalised and socially accepted (Duvvury *et al.* 2009).

However, in summary, although the QALY-loss-based WTP approach has flaws, it is one of the few tools currently available that allows for comparisons across disciplines. To continue, Section 12.3 reflects on the primary data sources that are used within estimations.

¹The QALY approach is already explained in detail in Chapter 5

²In comparison, the human capital method solely relies on earnings.

12.3. Data

In order to calculate the different costs, the following primary data sources are utilised to compute unit costs, case numbers, and multipliers³

Basic data

- GBV-QALY-data: the primary data stems from the research of Bolling, Mattinson, and Myhill²⁰⁰²; Budd *et al.*²⁰⁰⁰; Dolan *et al.*²⁰⁰⁵; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns²⁰⁰⁵.

Unit cost and WTP data

- Carthy *et al.*¹⁹⁹⁸ unit cost and WTP data derive from Carthy *et al.*¹⁹⁹⁸ and are used by Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns²⁰⁰⁵ p. 34 too. The unit cost per QALY was estimated for the U.K. in 1997 and was already transferred to various GBV research. The data is adjusted to 2018 Namibian Dollars⁴

Case number data⁵

- NAMPOL 2012–2015: crime statistics from The Namibian Police²⁰¹⁸ are set into relation with the 2014 NDHS, the national population-based victimisation survey, by MoHSS and ICF International²⁰¹⁴. Based on these findings⁶ a set of multipliers for incidents of homicides, wounding, sexual offences, and common assaults as a result of GBV is computed.

Multiplier data

- NDHS 2014 – Since The Namibian Police²⁰¹⁸ data only depict a small fraction of the actual GBV incidents,⁷ the NDHS (MoHSS and ICF International²⁰¹⁴) prevalence proportions of GBV related crimes, and data of Dolan *et al.*²⁰⁰⁵; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns²⁰⁰⁵ are used to compute the extent of the affected population.

Section^{12.4} shows the results that derive from the unit cost and total case number data.

³For more detailed information on the calculation, see Chapter²¹

⁴Ibid.

⁵This cost category uses the same primary data and computation method of case numbers and multiplier data as for the health service costs. For detailed information, see Chapter⁸

⁶See Sections^{6.4} and^{8.3}

⁷Ibid.

12.4. Results

Table 12.1.: Results intangibles, physical, and emotional impact.

Category ⁸	Unit cost of a QALY, in 2018 [N\$]	Cases [numbers] ⁹	Expected QALY loss [in years of full health]	Overall costs of QALY losses, in 2018 [N\$]
	58,862			
Homicide		245	–	–
Wounding		33,099	0.033	64,293,020
Sexual offences		25,501	0.686	1,029,713,345
Common assault		26,346	0.007	10,855,448
			Total Share of GDP [%] ¹⁰	1,104,861,813 0.62

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

12.5. Conclusion

12.5.1. Summary of findings

The overall GDP share is 0.62 per cent. The highest cost-share represents the category of sexual offences. Since it has the highest QALY index, it constitutes with N\$ 1,029,713,345 out of N\$ 1,104,861,813, to above 90 per cent of all losses. The two cost sections that follow are wounding and common assault losses. Similar to the previous chapters, in order to interpret the results more holistically, they will be compared to the outcome of other literature.

⁸See Chapter 21 for more insights on the unit cost, case number, and QALY loss calculations.

⁹See Table 8.4 for more details.

¹⁰The GDP in the current LCU was N\$ 178.052 billion in 2018 (World Bank 2018e).

12.5.2. Comparison with other countries

Table 12.2.: Comparison of Intangible costs.

Country ¹¹	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of intangibles [%] ¹²	Share of intangibles on overall costs [%] ¹³
Developed countries						
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003	4.79	0.05	- ¹⁴	-
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996	1.95	0.98	0.85 ¹⁵	86.75
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	1.00	0.47	0.09 ¹⁶	19.84
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia 2016	[11.13]	1.35	0.64 ¹⁷	47.27
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	7.10	0.76	0.19 ¹⁸	24.89
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a	5.00	1.07	1.01 ¹⁹	94.51
U.K.	2009	Walby 2009	0.60	1.00	0.63 ²⁰	63.28
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson 2006	2.60	0.10	- ²¹	-
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017	3.00	0.12	0.57	[473] ²²

Continue on next page

¹¹For more detailed information, including all footnotes, see Table [3.2](#)

¹²The figure presents the ratio of intangibles and GDP share. Figures have been rounded up to two numbers.

¹³This column presents the fraction of the GDP share of intangibles, in % from the GDP share of overall costs [%]. Both factors are listed in the two columns on the left-hand side.

¹⁴The Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) [2003](#) p. 44 does not estimate the intangibles.

¹⁵The QALY losses for rape and sexual assault are with US\$ 58,000 million of US\$ 67,000 million [overall costs] in 1993, relatively high (Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#) p. 18).

¹⁶The Loss of Life is C\$ 1,472,250,000 (Zhang *et al.* [2012](#) p. 59). Zhang's DALY estimates are not included in this review.

¹⁷Costs from pain, suffering, and premature mortality are estimated to be A\$ 10.4 billion (KPMG Australia [2016](#) p. 5).

¹⁸The total costs of pain, suffering and premature mortality are A\$ 3,883 million (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) [2009](#) p. 37).

¹⁹The costs of pain and suffering are A\$ 7,634.6 million. [Based on the following scenario: base case, gross, and value of a statistical life [VSL] rated with A\$ 6.5 million, according to the report] (Access Economics [2004a](#) p. 30).

²⁰The human and emotional cost was £ 9,954 million in 2008 (Walby [2009](#) p. 2).

²¹The report did not estimate the Intangible cost category (Envall and Eriksson [2006](#) p. 9).

²²The QALY losses are € 17,975,800,000 (Sacco [2017](#) p. 120). The overall cost was € 3,800,000,000 in 2016 (Sacco [2017](#) p. 14), and the German 2016 GDP [in current LCU] was € 3.135 trillion. The € 3.8 billion only contains direct tangible and indirect tangible costs. Thus, the computed QALY losses are higher than the overall cost. It is because Sacco computes these expenses for the total life period.

Continue Table 12.2

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of intangibles [%]	Share of intangibles on overall costs [%]
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	1.26	0.03	0.32 ²³	[1,220 ²⁴
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	5.00	0.17	- ²⁵	-
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	2.00	0.22	- ²⁶	-
Developing and emerging countries						
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012	25.40	3.19	- ²⁷	-
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011	24.00	2.10	- ²⁸	-
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	18.00	3.93	- ²⁹	-
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	27.70	-	- ³⁰	-
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	30.00	-	- ³¹	-
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014	20.00–30.00	0.90–1.30	- ³²	-
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine 2017	10.00	0.23	- ³³	-
Namibia	2021	Breuer 2021	17.50	6.01	0.62	10.33

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

The following deductions can be made based on the presented findings:

²³The study estimates a QALY loss of CHF 2,000 million (Stern *et al.* 2013 p. 28).

²⁴The lost intangibles [lower bound estimate] were CHF 164 million per annum [2011] (Stern *et al.* 2013 p. 10). The lost QALYs were CHF 2,000 million for women only (Stern *et al.* 2013 p. 28). However, Stern *et al.* 2013 do not include them in their overall estimate. Hence, the ratio is disproportionately high.

²⁵The report does not include Intangible costs (Nectoux *et al.* 2010 p. 934).

²⁶The paper does not directly calculate the loss of well-being in its calculation of the indirect costs (Villagómez 2010 p. 6).

²⁷The paper does not estimate the intangibles.

²⁸The study does not list the scope of intangibles calculated in this study under its included indirect costs (Siddique 2011 p. 16 f.).

²⁹The paper does not estimate them (Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 p. 34).

³⁰Ibid.

³¹Ibid.

³²Instead of the QALY metric, the paper applies the disability-adjusted life years [DALYs] approach to adults. DALYs symbolise a year of healthy life lost [due to GBV]. The metric combines Years of Life Lost [YLL] as a consequence of premature mortality and Years Lost due to Disability [YLD]. The YLD concept quantifies the loss of healthy years due to a disability or an adverse health condition linked to GBV. Nevertheless, due to a lack of necessary data, the applied model in the KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 30 study does not account for YLDs and thus does not integrate the cost of pain and suffering into the final estimates. Since this is the most significant portion of the DALY metric, the given figure in the report is too restricted to be used as a comparative basis for this review.

³³The average sum that for most women would be acceptable to compensate for any damages was equal to €42,181 (UNFPA Ukraine 2017 p. 70). However, the report does not calculate an overall national figure (UNFPA Ukraine 2017 p. 79). Hence, the calculation cannot be included.

1. Developed countries:

- a) Cost-shares start off low in this category, from 0.09 per cent in the Canadian Zhang *et al.* 2012 study, to highest, 1.01 per cent in the Australian Access Economics 2004a report, based on a prevalence of 1.00 and 5.00 per cent, respectively.
- b) The result of most other calculations, including Access Economics 2004a, KPMG Australia 2016, Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996, Walby 2009, are larger than this study's outcome; although, the Namibian prevalence ratio is significantly higher.
- c) A high share of the research does not account for intangibles, as 30 per cent – 4 out of 12 studies – did not include the indirect physical and emotional losses associated with GBV. This minimises the studies' overall cost significantly and has to be considered when comparing the literature's total results.

2. Developing and emerging countries: as already mentioned before, a significant share of the studies did not sufficiently calculate the intangibles. In the situation of the developing and emerging countries, this outcome is even more substantial. None of the publications listed above reflects or adequately accounts for such indirect losses. As a consequence, the final GDP cost-share results are downsized considerably.

The theoretical simulation is exercised [again] to interpret the Namibian results more comprehensively, and Table 12.3 displays the adjusted findings.

Table 12.3.: Comparison of adjusted Intangible costs.

Country ³⁴	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New prevalence [%]	Old GDP share of Intangible costs [%]	New GDP share of Intangible costs [%]	Increase of costs [%]
Developed countries							
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003	4.79	17.50	–	–	–
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996	1.95	17.50	0.85	7.63	798
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	1.00	17.50	0.09	1.58	1,656
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia 2016	[11.13]	17.50	0.64	1.01	58
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	7.10	17.50	0.19	0.47	147
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a	5.00	17.50	1.01	3.54	250
U.K.	2009	Walby 2009	0.60	17.50	0.63	18.38	2,817

Continue on next page

³⁴For more detailed information, including all footnotes, see Table 3.2

Continue Table 12.3

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New prevalence [%]	Old GDP share of Intangible costs [%]	New GDP share of Intangible costs [%]	Increase of costs [%]
			(Walby 2009 p. 6)				
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson 2006	2.60	17.50	–	–	–
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017	3.00	17.50	0.57	3.33	484
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	1.26	17.50	0.32	4.44	1,288
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	5.00	17.50	–	–	–
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	2.00	17.50	–	–	–
Developing and emerging countries							
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012	25.40	17.50	–	–	–
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011	24.00	17.50	–	–	–
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	18.00	17.50	–	–	–
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	27.70	17.50	–	–	–
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	30.00	17.50	–	–	–
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014	20.00	17.50	–	–	–
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine 2017	10.00	17.50	–	–	–
Namibia	2021	Breuer 2021	17.50	17.50	0.62	0.62	0.00

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

The GDP cost-share increased, beginning from 58 per cent in KPMG Australia 2016 to 2,817 per cent in Walby 2009 and as expected, the majority of the cost-shares are higher than in Namibia. Such an outcome occurred only in the category of personal costs as well. Figure 12.1 will show the results in more detail.

During the process of calculation, again, several other aspects became apparent, which may have altered the outcome and could explain the modest results³⁵ Section 12.5.3 discusses such in more detail.

12.5.3. Further discussion

Problems in assessing the Intangible costs in Namibia

Generally, the findings have to be read with precaution, as the following concerns are associated with applying the QALY-loss-based WTP approach in Namibia.

- The QALY approach:

³⁵Prior to this study, qualitative research has been conducted to evaluate the barriers to access the social welfare system. For instance, see Breuer 2015

Legend: 1. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) [2003]. 2. Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996]. 3. Zhang *et al.* [2012]. 4. KPMG Australia [2016]. 5. National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) [2009]. 6. Access Economics [2004a]. 7. Walby [2009]. 8. Envall and Eriksson [2006]. 9. Sacco [2017]. 10. Stern *et al.* [2013]. 11. Nectoux *et al.* [2010]. 12. Villagómez [2010]. 13. Duvvury and Carney [2012]. 14. Siddique [2011]. 15. Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004]. 16. Duvvury *et al.* [2009] (for Morocco), 17. Duvvury *et al.* [2009] (for Uganda), 18. KPMG South Africa [2014]. 19. UNFPA Ukraine [2017] and 20. Breuer [2021].

Figure 12.1.: Comparison of adjusted Intangible costs.

1. Primary data often derived from different types of research conducted in various locations (Malek [2000]). This data is transferred from the U.K. and was adjusted to 2018 Namibia dollars. Still, although the QALYs were analysed to be transferable [36] and adjustments to the local realities have been made, as for instance, with the underlying HIV ratios [37] other distortions may have occurred. As estimates are usually influenced by different preferences of societies (Bala and Zarkin [2000]) [38] or time frames examined (Pettitt *et al.* [2016]).
2. The QALYs data on alcohol abuse differ in South Africa. Absolute alcohol consumption per adult was estimated to be 10.3 litres per year in 2000. It is considerably smaller than in various other countries (Ezzati *et al.* [2004]). Still, the volume consumed is more likely to be 20 litres per adult drinker, which is among the world's highest (Rehm *et al.* [2003]). Further, around half of all unnatural deaths in South Africa in 2002 had blood alcohol concentrations higher than or equal to 0.05 grams/100 millilitres (Matzopoulos, Seedat, and Cassim [2002]). Consequently, alcohol abuse, and hence, alcohol-related mortality and associated trauma within Southern African GBV settings are assumed to be higher than for other populations (Dolan *et al.*

³⁶For more details, see Chapters [5], [6] and [21].

³⁷For information on the calculation of the tailored HIV factor, see Section [6.4] or Chapter [21].

³⁸For more details, see Chapter [5]. The Namibian situation may differ from other global results. However, no other appropriate information is yet available, and QALYs are globally often adjusted to be transferred, which was done for the Namibian case too. However, a potential distortion is acknowledged.

[2005] Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005]. Therefore, the underlying alcohol ratios that constitute the QALY losses are likely to produce an undervaluation of cost in Namibia. However, no other appropriate data is yet available to adjust this figure within the respective QALY value; hence, a potential underestimation is acknowledged.

3. QALYs do not include non-health gains, such as social achievements, including a faster return to employment or other educational attainments (Tinelli, Ryan, and Bond [2010]). Further, due to a lack of data, the category of sexual offences should be interpreted as an incomplete account of the full extent of GBV, as it does not include many other types of sexual assault, including stalking or unwanted pressure for sexual favours (U.S. Equal Employment Opportunity Commission [2018]; UN Women [2018b]). To conclude, this estimation may not reflect the reality of all incurred losses. Such lack leads to a certain degree of distortion, and actual losses may differ in fact.

In order to continue, the next paragraph describes potential issues of the WLP method.

- The WLP approach:
 1. May underestimate the cost, as it is likely to underrate the extent of psychological harm and other non-health-related consequences resulting from GBV (Golding [1999]), as inevitable long-term health consequences are omitted. Hence, the presented figures depict a rather conservative estimate.
 2. The applied Dubourg method is backed by the British government (Brand and Price [2000]); however, there is a concern that respondents might be morally pressured to reply differently when asked about GBV in an interview setting. The general lack of data sources on individuals' WTP to decrease GBV places particular challenges (Walby and Olive [2014]). For instance, the Ukrainian study uses the following quote of one survivor to stress the problem scholars face to estimate the respective WTP of GBV, "it is impossible to measure, as I've lost my health, and that is priceless, My life was completely ruined. How can it be measured?" (UNFPA Ukraine [2017], p. 70) Further, as indicated above, moral pressure during the process of an interview could have led to biased outcomes, not only in the global WTP-data in general but in this study, also in the general GBV information surveyed in the NDHS by MoHSS and ICF International [2014], as GBV is often tolerated in Namibia.
 3. In Namibia, GBV is often accepted, and in addition, there is less disposable income available as compared to other nations. However, citizens may still assign a higher financial value to the prevention of GBV, as they feel responding to what is morally right during the pressure of an interview. Nevertheless, outside an interview setting, they may display other spending habits or different sets of moral values.

Hence, in summary, this section's outcome shall be seen as an estimate approaching the actual cost.

12.6. Summary

Chapter [12] has calculated the Physical and Emotional impact on adults. The QALY-loss-based WTP approach, with the QALY datasets, was used because they allow comparability between different research strands, and they holistically calculate a variety of aspects related to GBV. The WTP method provides information about the spending habits within a nation and how

much a society is willing to pay to reduce violence (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#); Walby and Olive [2014](#); Whitehead and Ali [2010](#)). The combination of both approaches provides high methodological validity. The QALY data for the GBV area are taken from research by Dolan *et al.* [2005](#); Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#). The case numbers are based on surveys by The Namibian Police [2018](#) and were drawn to a realistic level using suitable multiplier rates that resulted from the NDHS (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#)). The cost calculated in this category has a share of 0.62 per cent of the gross domestic product. The cost type with the highest expenditure share within this cost class was all expenditures related to sexual offences. Surprisingly, large parts of literature in developed countries did not calculate this cost category. The situation is even more substantial for developing and emerging countries. None of the studies listed calculated this cost category in detail and comprehensively. When pulling the studies that estimated this cost section to the prevalence level in Namibia, a result emerges that has never occurred in any other category so far. The majority of cost-shares is now higher than that calculated in this study. Reasons could be similarities in methodology.

In sum, the transferability of the QALY data to the Namibian context was carefully examined in Chapter [6](#). Typical national conditions such as the increased HIV factor were taken into account and were adjusted accordingly. However, other factors for which there are no local datasets could not be tailored within the underlying calculations. For example, alcohol consumption is very high in Southern Africa (Matzopoulos, Seedat, and Cassim [2002](#); Rehm *et al.* [2003](#)). The calculated losses of Quality of Life associated with alcohol consumption are therefore likely to depict an undervaluation. No other suitable data could be found that allows a reference to GBV within the QALY computations.

In order to continue, Chapter [13](#) presents the calculations of the second-generation costs.

13. Second-generation costs

13.1. Introduction

The negative consequences for children resulting from exposure to violence are not always visible immediately. However, they can occur until adulthood. The fact that children are negatively impacted in homes where GBV between parents occurs is unquestionable (Caspi *et al.* 2002 Cohen *et al.* 2000). Consequences include negative implications on emotional and behavioural functioning, social ability, educational achievements, or cognitive capacity. Some children are more resilient than others towards GBV and can cope with such adverse impacts better. Howell *et al.* 2010 concluded that differences in parenting style, the degree of exposure, and the extent to which the child's mother's mental well-being is impacted are all influential determinants. Chapter 13 aims to calculate the costs of the second-generation holistically. In Section 13.2 the used model, the DALY approach, is presented. Based on the current international literature, this method is, at the moment, the most suitable to determine the losses endured by children. It is based on surveys of the so-called disability-adjusted life years [DALYs], which capture the losses caused by illness and death resulting from GBV. Section 13.3 presents the statistics used in this section. The primary data is grounded in reports of the World Bank 2018g. Specific DALY data derives from the 2016 Global Burden of Disease Study (World Health Organization (WHO) 2020). Case numbers and multipliers are based on surveys by Fang *et al.* 2017 on the harm suffered by children as a consequence of GBV in South Africa. Section 13.4 presents the results, and Section 13.5 provides a final summary. The calculated data is compared with the findings of other studies. In a subsequent theoretical comparison, the outcome of specific international literature is raised to the prevalence ratio of Namibia to contextualise the results better.

13.2. Approach

DALY approach

DALYs enjoy popularity among the current literature of health economics and are equally used in developed and developing countries. They were modelled in 1990 by scholars of the

¹Heise, Pitanguy, and Germain 1994 calculated that globally, 9.50 million DALYs are lost due to rape and DV [based on 1994 figures]. Lozano 1999 states in his 1999 study that in Mexico City, rape and IPV were the third most relevant causes of DALYs lost, after diabetes and child-birth related complications, and they were even higher than those lost due to road accidents.

World Bank and Harvard University to quantify the weight of disease and disability among nations. The method computes the gap of an individual's current and ideal health state in treatment (Lajoie [2015](#)). It can be used to calculate the burden of different diseases and the consequences of various forms of violence. The hypothesis is applied that a person's lifetime is the most appropriate indicator for the burden of disease, which includes the time lost due to disability or other forms of premature mortality, respectively (Young [2004](#)). In summary, DALYs are calculated in the following way:

$$\text{Years of life lost due to premature mortality [YLL]} + \text{Years lived with disability [YLD]} \quad (13.1)$$

In order to continue, Section [13.3](#) presents the used data.

13.3. Data

The following data is utilised within the calculations:

Basic data

The World Bank [2018g](#) census data is applied to create a respective base cohort for all subsequent calculations.

DALY data

DALY estimates from the 2016 Global Burden of Disease Study are utilised [2](#) for those aged 15–29 [3](#) to determine disease-induced DALY losses (World Health Organization (WHO) [2020](#)).

Multiplier data

The outcome of the South African Fang *et al.* [2017](#) paper “The Economic Burden of Violence against Children in South Africa” is used. In detail, the following three findings are applied [4](#)

1. Calculation of Population Attributable Fractions [PAFs]: PAFs represent the combination of the prevalence of a risk factor, such as violence against children, and the relative occurrence of a specific disease, like a broken arm. Fang *et al.* computed a PAF for each of these adverse health state outcomes [5](#)
2. Cape Area Panel Study [CAPS]: in addition, the review applies data from the Cape Area Panel Study [CAPS]. For seven years, the CAPS records the development of a

²No more recent data was available at the time of research.

³The equivalent DALY category for individuals aged 15–29 is used. Based on the 2018 World Bank's census data, it was 708,225 citizens (World Bank [2018g](#)). For further details, read Chapter [22](#)

⁴The South African and Namibian context is similar, according to research. See, for instance, Jewkes, Loveday, and Hetty [2005](#) on the rape culture in South Africa and Namibia or the economic comparison of Namibia and South Africa (Country Economy [2019](#)). Thus, the information and method from the South African research were assumed to be applicable for this review.

⁵See Chapter [22](#)

representative sample cohort of South African minors residing in Cape Town as they progress from adolescence to adulthood. In detail, correlations are made between the different types of violence against children, including emotional, sexual and physical violence, and related risk behaviours, such as violence ratios, poverty probabilities, or drug and alcohol abuse rates. Later the Heckman two-stage approach⁶ is employed to correct for selection bias.

3. Calculation of DALYs: based on this data, the lost DALYs are computed. They include losses resulting from lethal violence, adverse physical, and psychological health state outcomes, or reductions in earnings. To estimate the monetary value of DALY losses, the review utilises the findings from the World Health Organization (WHO)²⁰⁰¹ and Brown²⁰⁰⁸. Both studies assume that one DALY per annum equals the yearly national GDP per-capita figure. However, due to the possibility of morbidity from diseases preceding the occurrence of childhood violence, the paper computed DALY data only for children above the age of 15.

Based on this data, the following estimations were conducted.

13.4. Results

Table 13.1 summarises all the costs estimated for the second-generation.

Table 13.1.: Results of the DALY losses for sexual violence.

Health state outcomes	DALY loss [in years of full health] ⁷	PAF [fraction] ⁸	Affected population [numbers] ⁹	Unit cost of a DALY, in 2018 [N\$] ¹⁰	Overall DALY loss, in 2018 [N\$]
			708,225	72,726	
Depressive disorders	4.7	0.06 ¹¹	425		145,270,185
Anxiety disorders	3.2	0.06	425		98,907,360
Alcohol abuse disorders	2.3	0.1 ¹²	708		118,427,018
Drug abuse disorders	3.4	0.14	992		245,290,253
STDs [excluding HIV]	1.1	0.03	2,125		169,997,025
HIV	45.4	0.05 ¹³	354		1,168,823,182
Interpersonal violence	15.9	0.074	524		605,923,942
Self-harm	5.4	0.12	850		333,812,340
				Total	2,886,451,304
				Share of GDP [%] ¹⁴	1.62

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

⁶See, for instance, Kim and Jang²⁰¹⁰; Moon, Balasubramanian, and Rimal²⁰⁰⁵ for more information on the approach.

13.5. Conclusion

13.5.1. Summary of findings

The overall GDP cost-share is 1.62 per cent. The highest loss of N\$1,168,823,182 derives from HIV infections. They assert around 41 per cent of all costs for the second-generation. The lowest amount displays the consequences of anxiety disorders. It is assumed that most survivors manage them without medical support due to a lack of financial means or large distances to public and private health care providers (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). As already performed within the other cost sections, to understand the results better, they will be compared in Table 13.2 to the outcome of other studies¹⁵

⁷The DALY category 15–29 years is utilised to determine disease-induced DALY losses. The employed DALY losses base on the 2016 Global Burden of Disease Study (World Health Organization (WHO) 2020).

⁸The PAF values represent both genders. If data was not available for both, the value for women was taken.

⁹See the detailed census data in Chapter 22. The underlying number used is 708,225 citizens (World Bank 2018g).

¹⁰One DALY per annum is equal to the national GDP per capita data per annum (Fang *et al.* 2017). This number depicts the Namibian 2018 GDP per capita (World Bank 2018c).

¹¹The value was available for women only.

¹²The value represents women. The figure for female children is 0.1, and for male children is 0.07 (Fang *et al.* 2017 p. 7).

¹³Ibid.

¹⁴The GDP in the current LCU was N\$ 178.052 billion in 2018 (World Bank 2018c).

¹⁵This chapter does not include spendings on Child Welfare services; as such are covered in Chapter 10. Further, the costs of child homicides are not computed either, as the case numbers broken down by age group were not fully available. Moreover, lost lifetime earnings are not calculated either, as this study only estimates the losses per annum. However, the lost economic output of minors above 15 years is computed in Chapter 7.

13.5.2. Comparison with other countries

Table 13.2.: Comparison of second-generation costs.

Country ¹⁶	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of the second-generation costs [%]	Share of second-generation costs [%] ¹⁷
Developed countries						
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003	4.79	0.05	–	–
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996	1.95	0.98	0.70 18	71.64
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	1.00	0.47	0.01 19	3.11
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia 2016	[11.13]	1.35	0.02 20	1.51
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	7.10	0.76	0.01 21	1.79
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a	5.00	1.07	0.03 22	2.73
U.K.	2009	Walby 2009	0.60	1.00	–	–
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson 2006	2.60	0.10	–	–
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017	3.00	0.12	0.02 23	14.82
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	1.26	0.03	–	–
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	5.00	0.17	0.00 24	2.08
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	2.00	0.22	0.05 25	25.03

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¹⁶For more detailed information, including all footnotes, see Table [3.2](#)

¹⁷The figure presents the ratio of the second-generation cost-share [of GDP] and the overall cost-shares [GDP]. Figures have been rounded up.

¹⁸Costs were US\$ 48,000 million (Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#) p. 17).

¹⁹The sum is C\$ 230,402,921. The details include medical costs of C\$ 1,138,321 (Zhang *et al.* [2012](#) p. 71); missed school days, resulting in losses of C\$ 1,383,400 (Zhang *et al.* [2012](#) p. 72); and the lost future income of C\$ 227,881,200 (Zhang *et al.* [2012](#) p. 74). Note, this study only projects the income lost in the future over a period of one year.

²⁰The cost of the second-generation was A\$ 333 million (KPMG Australia [2016](#) p. 11).

²¹The cost of the second-generation was A\$ 280 million (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) [2009](#) p. 7).

²²The cost of the second-generation was A\$ 220.3 million (Access Economics [2004b](#) p. 47).

²³The cost of the second-generation was € 563,091,016 (Sacco [2017](#) p. 116).

²⁴The detailed figure is 0.004 per cent. The cost for children's deaths was € 75,000,000 (Nectoux *et al.* [2010](#) p. 394).

²⁵The cost was € 589,921,751 (Villagómez [2010](#) p. 5).

Continue Table 13.2

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share of overall costs [%]	GDP share of the second-generation costs [%]	Share of second-generation costs [%]
Developing and emerging countries						
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012	25.40	3.19	26	–
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011	24.00	2.10	27	–
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	18.00	3.93	28	–
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	27.70	–	–	–
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	30.00	–	–	–
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014	20.00–30.00	0.90–1.30	–	–
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine 2017	10.00	0.23	–	–
Namibia	2021	Breuer 2021	17.50	6.01	1.62	26.99

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

The following deductions can be made based on the previous data:

1. Developed countries:

- a) The cost portion in this category commences low at 0.004 per cent in Nectoux *et al.* 2010, and ranges up to 0.70 per cent in Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996. However, the results of this study are significantly higher, and none of the other studies recorded such a high proportion.
- b) A large part, 30 per cent – 4 of 12 studies – does not calculate the second-generation losses.

2. Developing and emerging countries:

- a) In this section, the selected publications did not account for such losses at all. In consequence, this minimises the studies' overall outcome drastically and has to be acknowledged when comparing the total results of literature later.

In order to contextualise the Namibian results better, a theoretical simulation is [again] carried out. As done in the previous chapters, the prevalence ratios are adjusted to the Namibian level of 17.50 per cent. Table 13.3 illustrates the new hypothetical GDP proportions.

²⁶The study includes the costs for women and children; however, the costs for children are not separately stated.

²⁷Ibid.

²⁸Ibid.

Table 13.3.: Comparison of adjusted second-generation costs.

Country ²⁹	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New prevalence [%]	Old GDP share of second-generation costs [%]	New GDP share of second-generation costs [%]	Increase of costs [%]
Developed countries							
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003	4.79	17.50	–	–	
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996	1.95	17.50	0.70	6.28	797
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	1.00	17.50	0.01	0.18	1,700
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia 2016	[11.13]	17.50	0.02	0.03	50
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	7.10	17.50	0.01	0.02	100
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a	5.00	17.50	0.03	0.11	267
U.K.	2009	Walby 2009	0.60	17.50	–	–	
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson 2006	2.60	17.50	–	–	
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017	3.00	17.50	0.02	0.12	500
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	1.26	17.50	–	–	
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	5.00	17.50	0.00 ³⁰	0.01	150
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	2.00	17.50	0.05	0.44	780

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²⁹For more detailed information, including all footnotes, see Table 3.2³⁰The detailed figure is 0.004 per cent (Nectoux *et al.* 2010 p. 394).

Continue Table 13.3							
Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New prevalence [%]	Old GDP share of second-generation costs [%]	New GDP share of second-generation costs [%]	Increase of costs [%]
Developing and emerging countries							
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012	25.40	17.50	–	–	–
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011	24.00	17.50	–	–	–
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	18.00	17.50	–	–	–
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	27.70	17.50	–	–	–
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	30.00	17.50	–	–	–
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014	20.00–30.00	17.50	–	–	–
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine 2017	10.00	17.50	–	–	–
Namibia	2021	Breuer 2021	17.50	17.50	1.62	1.62	0.00

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.
Source: Own representation.

Based on the findings in Table 13.3, the following became evident:

1. For developed nations, the increase commences at 50 per cent to a maximum of 1,700 per cent.
2. This study's findings are disproportionally high, as the adjusted GDP shares would theoretically range from a minimum of 0.01 per cent in the Nectoux *et al.* 2010 paper to a maximum of 6.28 per cent in the Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996 study. The Namibian share of 1.62 is again in the higher range, as the applied methodical set-up by Fang *et al.* 2017 is very extensive.³¹

Figure 13.1 displays the results in more detail.

13.5.3. Further discussion

DALYs have been developed for and by the World Health Organization (World Health Organization (WHO) 2001) to account for and to estimate the burden of disease, especially for developing and emerging countries, or to gear funding better. DALY data has been applied worldwide due to their standard, robust metric, and holistic estimates. The Fang *et al.* 2017 findings were chosen to apply to the Namibian context³² as the paper calculates a significant number of lost DALYs due to sexual, physical, emotional violence, and neglect. According to the

³¹See Chapters 3 and 5

³²Until 1990 and 1994, respectively, Namibia was under South African control. Although both countries are independent and differ, they share certain cultural and economic similarities (Country Economy 2019)

Legend: 1. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) [2003]. 2. Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996]. 3. Zhang *et al.* [2012]. 4. KPMG Australia [2016]. 5. National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) [2009]. 6. Access Economics [2004a]. 7. Walby [2009]. 8. Envall and Eriksson [2006]. 9. Sacco [2017]. 10. Stern *et al.* [2013]. 11. Nectoux *et al.* [2010]. 12. Villagómez [2010]. 13. Duvvury and Carney [2012]. 14. Siddique [2011]. 15. Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004]. 16. Duvvury *et al.* [2009] (for Morocco), 17. Duvvury *et al.* [2009] (for Uganda), 18. KPMG South Africa [2014]. 19. UNFPA Ukraine [2017] and 20. Breuer [2021].

Figure 13.1.: Comparison of adjusted second-generation costs.

calculations of Fang *et al.* [2017] p. 1, the estimated economic value of DALYs lost to violence against children [including both fatal and nonfatal] in South Africa was 4.30 per cent of South Africa’s gross domestic product in 2015. This is the highest estimated GDP loss calculated in comparison to all other studies examined. See Table [13.4] for more insights.

Table 13.4.: Comparison of second-generation cost’ studies.

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%]	Cost for women	Cost for children	GDP share [%]
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney [2012]	25.40	✓	✓	3.19
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique [2011]	24.00	✓	✓	2.10 (Siddique [2011] p. 50)
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004]	18.00	✓	✓	3.93 (Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004] p. 36)
South Africa	2017	Fang <i>et al.</i> [2017]	33 ³³	–	✓	4.30

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Jewkes, Loveday, and Hetty [2005]. See, for instance, Jewkes, Loveday, and Hetty [2005] on the rape culture in South Africa and Namibia. Thus, the data from Fang *et al.* [2017] was applied in this review.

³³Children only.

The South African study by Fang *et al.* (2017) only calculates the costs for children and still estimates the highest share of GDP costs. This shows how comprehensive the employed DALY method is to measure the loss of health in the lives of children economically and explains the high GDP share.

13.6. Summary

Chapter 13 calculated the cost of GBV for the next generation. The findings are based on the DALY approach. The DALY data derived from the 2016 Global Burden of Disease Study (World Health Organization (WHO) 2020). Case numbers and multiplier data are based on South African survey data by Fang *et al.* (2017), regarding GBV related losses suffered by children. These include losses resulting from lethal violence or adverse physical, and psychological health states associated with physical and emotional violence experienced during childhood. The share of costs is 1.62 per cent of the gross domestic product. The highest expenses result from losses related to HIV and AIDS. They cover around 40 per cent of all costs for the second-generation. The losses due to mental illnesses such as anxiety disorders are also high. When comparing the outcome with findings from other studies, it emerges that the result of this study is disproportionately large again. However, it must be added that almost 30 per cent of the publications in developed countries did not calculate this cost section. The situation is more considerable for research published in developing and emerging countries. None of the papers reviewed adds to this cost category. This notably reduces the total outcome of these studies and must be considered when comparing the final overall results.

In order to continue, Chapter 14 depicts the study's total findings.

14. Conclusion

14.1. Introduction

Chapter 14 provides an overview of all results and depicts the outcome of all cost categories, including 1. lost economic output, 2. health service costs, 3. legal costs, 4. social welfare costs and special service costs, 5. personal costs, 6. intangibles, physical, and emotional impact, and 7. second-generation costs. Section 14.3 compares all other relevant publications, and the results of the studies are raised again to the Namibian prevalence ratio. At the same time, the tested hypothesis is discussed. In Section 14.4 there is a further discussion of distinct topics that emerged during the calculations. The issue of certain data restrictions is dealt with, problems associated with gross domestic product estimations in developing and emerging countries, and the obstacles to the collection of such are discussed. The methodological challenges that arose within this study are also presented. In addition, the hurdles facing those who seek help with official public agencies are described. Finally, the consequences of these problems and their effects on cost calculations are listed. Furthermore, other cost classes are addressed that could not be calculated in this study, based on the restrictive datasets or methodological shortcomings, among others. Finally, a look into the future is given, and needed methodological developments and requirements are depicted.

14.2. Overview of findings

Table 14.1 provides a summary of all results.

Table 14.1.: Total costs of all categories.

Cost category	GDP share [%]	Total costs [N\$]	Includes
Lost economic output	1.64	2,918,080,081	All gender
Health service costs	0.26	458,332,955	Women ¹
Legal costs	0.50	882,719,745	All gender
Social welfare costs	1.09	1,945,601,054	All gender
Personal costs	0.28	499,092,354	All gender
Intangibles, physical, and emotional impact	0.62	1,104,861,813	Women ²
Second-generation costs	1.62	2,886,451,304	[mostly] All gender ³
Total [without second-generation costs]	4.39	7,808,688,002	
Total	6.01	10,695,139,306	

Source: Own representation.

Lost economic output

The calculation was derived from datasets of Dolan *et al.* [2005] Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005]; Walby [2004]; Walby [2009]. The therapy cost was partially converted with World Bank [2018e] data. The case numbers were estimated based on the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) [2018b] data and research by Jewkes *et al.* [2010]. The calculated loss was 1.64 per cent of the Namibian gross domestic product in 2018. This result is one of the highest among the examined studies. However, it must be noted that, especially in developing and emerging countries, no adequate estimations are carried out in almost 60 per cent of the publications. When the prevalence ratios are theoretically raised to the Namibian level, the overall results changed: the British Walby study has a significantly higher cost-share than Namibia. For the developing and emerging countries, the Ribero and Sánchez Torres paper also depicts, as expected, a much higher GDP share (Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004] Walby [2004] Walby [2009]). The chosen methodology in this paper is very detailed and holistic. The costs for both men and women are also included, which only occurs in very few publications. All expenses related to mental health restrictions are calculated too.

Health service costs

This category bases its calculations on the health-state approach. The case numbers were computed based on NHDS data for physical and sexual violence (MoHSS and ICF International [2014]). The overall cost-share is 0.26 per cent of the gross domestic product. Sexual offences have the highest treatment cost per case and present with N\$ 339,052,088, the largest cost-share. The loss through sexual offences alone amounts already to a share of 0.19 per cent of GDP. In contrast, homicide depicts the lowest proportion, with a total cost of N\$ 337,815 and 0.0002 per cent of GDP, respectively. Although the costing was separated in public and private health care provider spendings and the share of 31 per cent, that resembles women who do not have access to treatment services is omitted, the calculated health service costs are disproportionately high compared to other publications. It has to be further kept in mind that the outcome does not even include male survivors due to the unavailability of incident data or other long-term impacts, such as the consequences of HIV/AIDS. This number should, therefore, be read as a conservative estimation. When comparing the outcome with other literature's findings, the prevalence proportions were raised to the Namibian level. Again, only a few studies have calculated a comparably high cost-share. It must be added that research in developing and emerging countries omit significant cost segments within this cost segment. Among the industrialised countries, the total cost of the studies from Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996] Villagómez [2010]; Walby [2004]; Walby [2009] would be theoretically higher than the Namibian result. When considering the overall results, it must be taken into account that many women experience several difficulties accessing health services, especially women located

¹Due to restricted case numbers and multiplier data.

²Ibid.

³The PAFs were given for men and women, but no overall PAF values for alcohol abuse disorders and interpersonal violence, so the PAFs were only selected for women. Furthermore, only PAF values for women were provided in the study for depressive disorders and HIV. See Fang *et al.* [2017] p. 7 for further information.

in financially poorer cohorts with a lower level of education or have five or more children. It is assumed that such obstacles decrease costs in the short-term but will stimulate a rise in the long-term due to accumulated additional trauma and wounding that was not cured properly in the first place.

Legal services

Legal costs were calculated by using the budget-share approach. Based on the available data, the method was identified to be the best suitable. A holistic data basis was chosen for the estimation. The majority of data derives from the Namibian Ministry of Finance [2018](#). The number of cases was calculated based on different crime statistics (Ministry of Safety and Security, Head of Public Relations Division, Dep. Comm. Edwin Kanguatjivi, Namibian Police Force [2018](#)). As it is known that these statistics do not reflect a realistic number of incidents, multipliers were used in this cost category as well. They are based on the research and publications of the High Court, the Correctional Facilities, or the NDHS (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#); Shapwa [2017](#); The Namibian High Court [2018](#)). The cost contributes to 0.50 per cent of the 2018 gross domestic product. The overall cost of legal matters linked to GBV constitutes N\$ 882,719,745 [of the 2018 to 2019 budget cycle] and 0.50 per cent of the 2018 GDP. The expenses of the Combating of Crime Division alone present both the highest overall cost with N\$ 3,113,300,000 and the highest share of GBV related expenses with N\$ 692,709,250. The Division produces nearly 80 per cent of all legal GBV expenses and holds alone already a share of 0.39 per cent of the 2018 GDP.

Whereas the other cost categories together, as expenses on legal aid, Lower Courts, or rehabilitation, and reintegration, only amount to around 20 per cent of all costs and only to 0.11 per cent of the national GDP. Nevertheless, the data did not allow for a separation among men and women. Nonetheless, based on other analyses, as found within the lost economic output calculation⁴ men are bound to much lower case levels than their female counterparts. In general, the literature agrees that women are burdened with a significant share of cost (Sacco [2017](#); Walby [2009](#); World Health Organization (WHO) [2016b](#)). If the finding is compared with the results of other international studies, in which the prevalence rate is theoretically raised to the Namibian level, the countries of Great Britain or Canada will display higher losses. The data did not allow for a separation among the two genders. It must also be taken into account that those affected experience various hurdles to access the CJS. For example, authorities are often not fully equipped yet to successfully pursue offences involving minors or citizens with disabilities. Those affected are not helped quickly enough out of their respective situations, so the trauma and suffering are unnecessarily prolonged.

As a consequence, in the long run, the cost of GBV increases. Although a high budget is reserved, most of those affected have limited access to the legal system. Hence, it is assumed that the actual cost incurred is lower since the GBV budget that the government is earmarking is, in reality, not entirely spent on its actual scope. For example, if survivors want to complain about poor treatment and mismanagement within the public system, they cannot always do

⁴See Chapter [7](#)

so. The respective police officers sometimes deny their names or other important data, which prevents efficient complaint procedures.

Social welfare and special services

The applied method was that of the budget-share approach. The calculations are based on a very holistic and extensive dataset. The primary data is derived from the Ministry of Finance, including budget data of the Namibian Ministry of Education, Ministry of Health, or Ministry for Poverty Eradication, and various non-governmental organisations, such as the U.N., the E.U., or the German development agencies (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) [2018](#); Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) [2019a](#); Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) [2020](#); European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation [2015](#); Ministry of Finance [2018](#); United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) [2017](#)). Various specific multiplier data was used to compute realistic case numbers, making the results of this study very comprehensive (Dolan *et al.* [2005](#); Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#); Jewkes [2018](#); Jewkes *et al.* [2010](#); Walby [2004](#)). The overall cost amount to N\$ 1,945,601,054 and constitute to 1.09 per cent of the 2018 GDP. The costs of combating poverty and the provision of general social welfare programmes comprise the highest cost blocks. It is also worth noting that the expenses for care and protection of affected children represent a considerable part of the spendings. Only the costs of these two classes already constitute around 83 per cent of all social welfare spending. In comparison, all other cost categories combined, including expenditures on community empowerment, childcare facilities, all [international] donor contributions combined, public sick leave, death benefits, poverty eradication, and all food provision together, amount *only* to around 17 per cent of all total social welfare spending. The findings were compared to the results of various other international publications. In sum, the calculated costs are again disproportionately high. This is mainly because this study holistically dealt with the different cost sections and went in its scope beyond and more profound than more general approaches. For example, the expenditure of the various non-governmental organisations and third agencies was considered as well. The budgets of the most important aid organisations were analysed in detail and comprehensively. These expenses are mostly not borne by the Namibian state but by the international community. In the further discussion, it became clear that certain cultural norms contribute to a likely distortion in the outcome. For instance, positive socialisation towards GBV initiates social acceptance of violence. In specific Namibian regions, husbands believe that they are entitled to hit their wives under certain conditions, for example, if they burn the food (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) p. 289). These norms are likely reflected in employees and officials working for the national government and administration. It may be and is even likely that certain funds will be made available to prevent violence. Still, due to a cultural misperception of [certain] civil servants, they will not be adequately used or misused. It creates a sinister cycle. Employees might be unwilling to help those affected, even if the funds are made available. This can prevent abused citizens from seeking help. As a result, trauma and suffering are prolonged, and costs continue to increase in the long run.

Personal costs

The used method is that of the unit-cost approach. It was selected because it delivers a high level of detail and creates a holistic cost profile. In particular, the applied data for out-of-pocket legal spending bases on qualitative research, such as interviews with private and public legal

entities. Relocation costs associated with GBV were derived from qualitative interviews and surveys (Breuer [2018](#) MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) [2016](#); Rudd, Hubbard, and Engelbrecht [2013](#) Solidaritätsdienst International e. V. (SODI) [2018](#)). The cost of property destruction is based on the research of Henderson [2000](#), which is transferred and embedded into the Namibian context. Losses from property dispossession are taken from Namibian survey data of the African Auction entity (Ngatjiheue [2015](#)). Case numbers are calculated based on Namibian and U.N. census data or are based on other regional and national statistical surveys (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) [2018b](#)). This is the category with one of the lowest GDP per cost-shares [0.28 per cent]. As a result of the high case numbers, the costliest personal expenses are property damages that amount to around 70 per cent of all personal costs. The lowest amount display relocation expenses, as most family members often support their affected relatives directly themselves. Overall, this cost category calculates one of the lowest cost-shares within this study. When comparing these results later with the data from other international literature, in which the prevalence proportions are raised to the Namibian level, the following picture emerges: in developing and emerging countries, a large proportion of the studies now show a higher share of costs than the one calculated for Namibia, which is a different development compared to the other categories. In the final discussion, it becomes clear why this share of costs is lower than other research. For the greater part of Namibian women, the place of the family is the most common refuge. A large share of 48 per cent of those affected seeks help from their families. This means that most of the costs, such as accommodation or relocation, are paid for by the survivor's families or themselves. It should also be mentioned that the Namibian divorce rate is low. Only one per cent of women choose a divorce. Officially, couples remain married; however, relocation is assumed to be made nevertheless. The upholding of marriage happens mainly due to cultural and economic reasons. As a result, divorce rates and costs are at a low level. It must be mentioned that the legal hurdles to getting a divorce are high. The applicant must prove that their spouse acted wrongly. In combination with a weak police and evidence preservation system, this is a very high hurdle posed under the rule of law. In addition, there is also the phenomenon of expropriation in Namibia. For example, single or widowed women are often confiscated by the husband's own family. This is another reason for women not to seek divorce or separation. In summary, these aspects result in statistically low costs for divorce or relocation. However, the violence persists and occurs, hence expenses that can be measured fully, such as the cost of property destruction, are high.

Intangibles

The QALY-loss-based WTP approach, including the QALY datasets, is used to allow comparability between different research strands. They holistically calculate a variety of aspects related to GBV. The WTP method provides information about the spending habits within a nation and how much a society is willing to pay to reduce violence. The combination of both methods provides high methodological validity. Other approaches indicate only a one-time snapshot of a disability or mortality, whereas the DALY metric accounts for the burden of living with a disability for the remaining lifetime. Thus, they reflect the GBV consequences for children in the most holistic way (Hong [2011](#)). The QALY data for the GBV area are taken from Dolan *et al.* [2005](#) Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#). The case numbers are based on surveys by The Namibian Police [2018](#) and were drawn to a realistic level using suitable multiplier rates from the NDHS (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#)). The cost calculated in this category has a share of 0.62 per cent of the gross domestic product. The section with the highest expenditure

proportion within this cost class was all expenditures related to sexual offences. Since it has the highest QALY index, it constitutes with N\$1,029,713,345 out of N\$1,104,861,813, to above 90 per cent of all losses. The two cost sections that follow are wounding and common assault losses. Surprisingly, large parts of literature in developed countries did not calculate this cost category. The situation is even more distinct for the developing and emerging countries. None of the studies listed calculate this cost section in detail and comprehensively. When pulling the studies that estimated this cost category to the prevalence level in Namibia, a result emerges that has never occurred in any other category. The main part of the cost-share is now higher than that calculated in this study. Reasons could be similarities in methodology.

Further, the transferability of the QALY data to the Namibian context was carefully examined in Chapter 6. Typical national conditions such as the increased HIV factor were taken into account and were adjusted accordingly. However, other factors for which there are no local datasets could not be tailored within the underlying calculations. For example, alcohol consumption and abuse are very high in Southern Africa. Losses in Quality of Life associated with alcohol consumption are therefore likely to depict an undervaluation. However, no relevant data could be found that allows a reference to GBV within the QALY computations.

Second-generation costs

The findings are based on the DALY approach. The DALY data derives from the 2016 Global Burden of Disease Study (World Health Organization (WHO) 2020). Case numbers and multiplier data are based on South African survey data by Fang *et al.* 2017 regarding GBV related losses suffered by children. These include losses resulting from lethal violence or adverse physical and psychological health state outcomes associated with physical and emotional violence experienced during childhood. The overall GDP cost-share is 1.62 per cent. The highest loss of N\$1,261,700,005 derives from HIV infections. They assert around 41 per cent of all costs for the second-generation. The lowest amount displays the consequences of anxiety disorders. It is assumed that most survivors manage them without medical support due to a lack of financial means or large distances to public and private health care providers (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). The losses due to mental illnesses such as anxiety disorders are also high. When comparing the output with the findings from other publications, it emerges that the outcome of this study is disproportionately high. However, it must be added that almost 30 per cent of the papers in developed countries did not calculate this cost category. The situation is more sizeable for research published in developing and emerging countries. None of the studies reviewed adds to this cost category. This significantly reduces the total cost of these studies and must be considered when comparing the overall results.

Section 14.3 will compare the results more closely with those of other publications.

14.3. Comparison with other studies

The results must be read with the following facts in mind. Some studies base their calculations only on data for women; others base their outcome on the number of cases for men and women. See the Swiss study by Stern *et al.* 2013 which covers both genders, for instance. The numerous definitions of GBV also lead to different results. Some limit themselves to

Domestic Violence [DV]; others include abuse by state institutions such as the police in their case numbers. Furthermore, the age restriction in the cohorts also leads to contrasting results. For example, the KPMG South Africa [2014](#) study uses a cohort of 15 to 80-year-olds, whereas other studies, as Stern *et al.* [2013](#), only start with the age cohort of 18-year-olds or end with 65-year-olds. While on the contrary, others, such as the KPMG Australia [2016](#) publication in its used primary data of the Australian Bureau of Statistics [2012](#) does not define an age limit. As a result, possible distortions do not only extend to the various methods but also to the underlying definitions and data that have been used. Table [14.2](#) presents the GDP shares of each cost class of all selected studies ⁵

In industrialised countries, the lost economic output cost-share fluctuates from 0.003 to 0.12 per cent and in the developing countries from 0.0001 to 2.13 per cent. The Namibian share is 1.64 and is only topped by the Colombian study.

The health service costs share is in the range of 0.001 to 0.23 per cent in the developed countries, and in the section of the developing and emerging countries, it is 0.00 [0.000000003] to 0.04 per cent. For Namibia, the overall cost-share is 0.26 per cent of the gross domestic product, with the sexual assault category displaying the highest total expenses. This is mainly since the studies in the developing countries did not carry out detailed analyses. For example, Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004](#), p. 32 only evaluate the costs in the medical-legal field [Costos de Tratamiento y Atención – Medicina Legal], or Duvvury *et al.* [2009](#), p. 10 solely compute the out-of-pocket cost, which constitutes only a minor part of all expected losses.

Legal costs range from 0.01 to 0.10 per cent in industrialised and between 0.01 and 0.33 per cent in developing and emerging countries. The calculated Namibian cost-share is above average at 0.50. This is mainly due to the fact that the studies in developing countries, which have a comparatively high prevalence, depict specific methodological weaknesses. For example, in the survey by Duvvury and Carney [2012](#), p. 81 no information was given on the total costs, or the KPMG South Africa [2014](#) publication does not break down the expenses in detail either.

For the cost category of social welfare costs and special service costs, the cost-share of the developed countries is in the range of 0.01–0.10 per cent. A share of 0.001–0.06 per cent is computed for developing and emerging countries. The cost-share in Namibia is again above average at 1.09 per cent. This is because the studies of the developing and emerging countries with a comparatively high GBV prevalence reveal methodological weaknesses. For example,

⁵In Table [14.2](#) the proportions do not sum up to 100 per cent because not all calculations are included, for example, due to methodological weaknesses, or because cost categories were recorded that are not calculated in this study, for example, the potential loss of taxes.

⁶Table [14.2](#) shows the summed up individual values for the cost categories collected in this study. The total results of Table [14.2](#) therefore, deviate from the results in Table [3.2](#)

⁷In this table, the values are shown with up to three decimal places so that the overall result can be summarized in more detail.

⁸Detailed figure 0.000000003 per cent.

⁹Ibid.

¹⁰Detailed figure 0.00003 per cent.

¹¹Detailed figure 0.0001 per cent.

Table 14.2.: Comparison of all subcategory calculations.

Country	Year	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	Lost economic output [%]	Health service costs [%]	Legal costs [%]	Social welfare costs [%]	Personal costs [%]	Intangibles [%]	Second-generation costs [%]	Total costs [%] ⁵
Developed countries											
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) ²⁰⁰³	4.79	0.02	0.04	–	–	–	–	–	0.06
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema ¹⁹⁹⁶	1.95	–	0.23	–	–	–	0.85	0.70	1.78
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> ²⁰¹²	1.00	0.003 ⁷	0.004	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.09	0.01	0.19
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia ²⁰¹⁶	[11.13]	0.12	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.70	0.64	0.02	1.77
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) ²⁰⁰⁹	7.10	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.17	0.19	0.01	0.46
Australia	2004	Access Economics ^{2004a}	5.00	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.08	0.34	1.01	0.03	1.61
U.K.	2009	Walby ²⁰⁰⁹	0.60	0.12	0.11	0.02	0.03	–	0.63	–	0.91
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson ²⁰⁰⁶	2.60	0.02	0.001	0.04	0.03	–	–	–	0.09
Germany	2017	Sacco ²⁰¹⁷	3.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	–	0.57	0.02	0.63
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> ²⁰¹³	1.26	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	–	0.32	–	0.36
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> ²⁰¹⁰	5.00	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	–	–	0.004	0.06
Spain	2010	Villagómez ²⁰¹⁰	2.00	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.06	0.09	–	0.05	0.28
Developing and emerging countries											
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney ²⁰¹²	25.40	–	0.00 ⁸	–	–	–	–	–	0.00 ⁹
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique ²⁰¹¹	24.00	0.87	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.00 ¹⁰	–	–	0.93
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres ²⁰⁰⁴	18.00	2.13	0.01	0.33	0.06	0.27	–	–	2.80
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> ²⁰⁰⁹	27.70	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> ²⁰⁰⁹	30.00	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa ²⁰¹⁴	20.00–30.00	–	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.77	–	–	0.82
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine ²⁰¹⁷	10.00	0.00 ¹¹	0.003	0.01	0.001	0.01	–	–	0.02
Namibia	2021	Breuer ²⁰²¹	17.50	1.64	0.26	0.50	1.09	0.28	0.62	1.62	6.01

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Duvvury and Carney [2012](#), p. 74 only calculate the women union's cost, which constitutes only a small percentage of the total expenditure share. Further, Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004](#), p. 31, 34 only collect the direct costs that occurred in the Colombian Institute of Family Welfare ICBF [Instituto Colombiano de Bienestar Familiar], for instance. This study also integrates costs to the international community, such as expenditure by the U.N. or the German BMZ; these expenses per se are not incurred as costs by the Namibian government, but still represent expenses for other governments and the international community per se, so that these were included in detail too. Of course, this expands the cost area measured in terms of the share of Namibia's gross domestic product.

The personal costs for developed countries are 0.02–0.70 per cent and for developing and emerging countries 0.00¹²–0.77 per cent respectively. The Namibian share is 0.26 per cent. It must be mentioned that, for instance, the South African study includes consumption costs and loss of earnings in its section “Costs to victims” (KPMG South Africa [2014](#), p. 29 f.). These were calculated in this study in other cost sections. In sum, the share of Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004](#) of 0.27 per cent is comparable to the Namibian result of 0.28 per cent. Both studies are based on a similar methodological structure.

For the intangibles, physical, and emotional impact section, the proportion of developed countries is in the range of 0.09–1.01 per cent. The share of developing and emerging countries could not be estimated due to a lack of data or methodological weaknesses. The Namibian percentage was calculated at 0.62 per cent. In this area, it became evident that the research, especially in the industrialised countries, had used very far-reaching and profound methods. For example, the Access Economics [2004a](#) study, which has a prevalence of five per cent, has computed a very high cost-share of 1.01 per cent. The same is true for the papers by Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#), KPMG Australia [2016](#), Walby [2009](#), or Sacco [2017](#). Studies in developing countries are in stark contrast to this finding. Most of the costs were not recorded, or they had significant methodological weaknesses that made comparison difficult.

The cost class of the second-generation shows in developed countries a cost-share of 0.004–0.70 per cent. The losses for the developing and emerging countries were not calculated, nor were the costs listed individually so that the category could not be extrapolated. For the most part, however, the expenditure has not been calculated, which significantly reduces its overall share of GDP.

In order to contextualise the Namibian results better, a theoretical simulation is again carried out. As done previously, the prevalence ratios are adjusted to the Namibian level of 17.50 per cent. Table [14.3](#) illustrates the new hypothetical GDP proportions ¹⁷

¹²The detailed figure for Bangladesh in Siddique [2011](#) is 0.00003 per cent.

¹³Detailed figure 0.000000002 per cent.

¹⁴Ibid.

¹⁵Detailed figure 0.00002 per cent.

¹⁶Detailed figure 0.0002 per cent.

¹⁷In Table [14.3](#) the proportions do not necessarily sum up to 100 per cent because not all calculations are included, for example, due to methodological weaknesses or because cost categories were recorded that are not calculated in this study, inter alia, the loss of taxes. Some studies calculate the costs for children;

Table 14.3.: Comparison of all adjusted subcategory calculations.

Country	Year	Author	New prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New lost economic output [%]	New health service costs [%]	New legal costs [%]	New social welfare costs [%]	New personal costs [%]	New intangibles [%]	New second-generation costs [%]	Total costs [%]
Developed countries											
			17.50								
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003	0.07	0.15	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.22
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996	-	2.06	-	-	-	-	7.63	6.28	15.97
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	0.05	0.07	0.53	0.53	0.35	1.58	0.18	3.29	
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia 2016	0.19	0.14	0.16	0.16	1.10	1.01	0.03	2.79	
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	0.07	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.42	0.47	0.02	1.13	
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a	0.21	0.18	0.14	0.28	1.19	3.54	0.11	5.65	
U.K.	2009	Walby 2009	3.50	3.21	0.58	0.88	-	18.38	-	26.55	
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson 2006	0.13	0.01	0.27	0.20	-	-	-	0.61	
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	-	3.33	0.12	3.69	
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	-	4.44	-	5.00	
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	0.11	0.03	0.03	0.03	-	-	0.01	0.21	
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	0.35	0.26	0.09	0.53	0.79	-	0.44	2.46	
Developing and emerging countries											
			17.50								
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012	-	0.00 ¹³	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.00 ¹⁴
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011	0.63	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.00 ¹⁵	-	-	0.68	
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	2.07	0.01	0.32	0.06	0.26	-	-	2.72	
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014	-	0.01	0.01	0.02-0.03	0.45-0.67	-	-	0.49-0.72	
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine 2017	0.00 ¹⁶	0.005	0.02	0.002	0.02	-	-	0.05	
Namibia	2021	Breuer 2021	1.64	0.26	0.50	1.09	0.28	0.62	1.62	6.01	

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Lost economic output: compared to the other literature, the estimated results are relatively high. Two studies, Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004](#), Walby [2009](#), would theoretically indicate similar results, as both use a detailed method as well.¹⁸

Health service costs: in developed countries, the theoretical new value ranges from 0.01 in Sweden to a theoretical 3.21 per cent in the U.K. In developing countries, there would be a new theoretical value of 0.00 [0.000000002] in Vietnam, up to the theoretical 0.03 per cent in Bangladesh. The Namibian costs of 0.26 per cent are well in the upper range. Only a few studies have calculated a comparably high cost-share. It must be added that research in developing and emerging countries omit significant cost segments. Among the industrialised countries, the total cost of Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#), Villagómez [2010](#), Walby [2004](#), Walby [2009](#) would be theoretically higher or equal to the Namibian findings. For developing and emerging countries, the applied model is not as comprehensive.¹⁹ For example, studies that have been conducted in an African context have left out significant health service costs²⁰ or do not compute them at all.²¹

legal costs: compared to other studies conducted for both developing and developed countries, the computed Namibian Legal costs-share of 0.50 per cent of GDP is rather high. In conclusion, the following deductions can be made based on the findings. Regarding the applied methods in developing and emerging countries, it can be said²² that the studies carried out within an African context are less complete, with relevant information and costing data missing, as in the paper of Morocco (Duvvury *et al.* [2009](#)), Uganda (Duvvury *et al.* [2009](#)), or South Africa (KPMG South Africa [2014](#)). In summary, in the developing countries, the GDP share of legal costs would hypothetically range from 0.01 in KPMG South Africa [2014](#), Siddique [2011](#) to 0.32 per cent in the Colombian Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004](#) paper. Overall, none of the studies calculated such high legal costs GDP share as for Namibia at 0.50 per cent.

Social welfare costs and special service costs: the developing and emerging countries examined tend to spend only minimal amounts on social welfare than the western hemisphere. Nevertheless, the computed Namibian outcome of 1.09 per cent is still high. Only the British research of Walby [2009](#) would display a similarly high figure, with now 0.88 per cent. One reason is that this approach examines the broad scope of budgets and their connection to GBV intensively. This paper includes, for instance, statements on adult education, referral hospital services, food banks or international development cooperation as well. These expenses are mostly not borne by the Namibian state but by the international community. As a result, it

for example, see Duvvury and Carney [2012](#), Siddique [2011](#) or Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004](#). However, these were not included in the respective sub-overviews of this review because they were not individually assignable.

¹⁸For more information, read Chapters [3](#) and [5](#).

¹⁹See, for instance, the Siddique [2011](#) paper on Bangladesh.

²⁰See, for instance, the KPMG South Africa [2014](#) paper.

²¹See the Duvvury *et al.* [2009](#) study on Uganda. Data on other African countries, such as South Africa, Uganda, and Morocco, cannot be included in this comparison, as relevant information is missing or the necessary health data was not calculated.

²²As mentioned already within the other cost categories, the used approach in Namibia is at its level of comprehensiveness comparable to those usually applied in developed countries.

goes beyond the standard approaches, which are usually applied to compute social welfare benefits, as performed in most of the research listed.

Personal costs: for the first time, all cost-shares, except for Bangladesh and Ukraine, would be similar or higher than the Namibian one. Survivors face several barriers, which may have influenced the findings and could explain the modest outcome. For instance, there are several obstacles to receiving a divorce, as Namibia's divorce law is outdated. The current legislation is based on fault. In consequence, this implies that one spouse has to prove that the other spouse has acted wrongly. However, this becomes an issue, as there is, among others, a culture of silence surrounding GBV, and violence is frequently concealed. Moreover, the policing and the evidence system tends to be weak. Further, it is almost impossible to effect a divorce without the support of a lawyer, even when both parties agree on how to divide the assets and the custody of the children. In addition, divorce cases are only heard by the High Court, which is located in Namibia's capital city of Windhoek. It increases costs and obstacles further, especially for people living in rural areas or with limited financial means (Indongo and Pazvakawambwa [2015](#); Legal Assistance Centre (LAC) [2005a](#); Menges [2013](#); Namibia Superior Courts [2019](#)). Such obstacles lead to an artificial decrease in costs and divorces alike.

intangibles, physical, and emotional impact: the majority of cost-share would be theoretically higher than in Namibia. Such an outcome occurred only partly in the category of personal costs too. [23](#)

Second-generation costs: this study's findings are disproportionately high. The GDP share would theoretically range from a minimum of 0.01 per cent in the French Nectoux *et al.* [2010](#) paper to a maximum of 6.28 per cent in the U.S. Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#) study. The Namibian figure of 1.62 per cent is also high, as the employed methodical set-up of Fang *et al.* [2017](#) is very comprehensive. [24](#)

Table [14.4](#) shows the gross domestic product cost-share that was either reported in the study itself or calculated based on the data provided for this study [see column 4]. The last two columns [columns 7 and 8] show the cost-share in the ratio to gross domestic product, which was adjusted to the Namibian prevalence rate in a theoretical simulation.

Column seven shows the new theoretical value based on the total costs stated in the study or, if stated, on the total cost-share presented in the original research. Column eight showcases the value that only includes the cost categories that were calculated in this study.

²³The underlying primary data was transferred from the U.K. and was adjusted to 2018 Namibia dollars. Still, although the QALYs were analysed to be transferable, and adjustments to the local realities have been made, other distortions may have occurred with the original HIV ratios, for instance. For more details, see Chapters [5](#), [6](#) and [21](#). For information on the calculation of the tailored HIV factor, see Section [6.4](#) or Chapter [21](#).

²⁴See Chapters [3](#) and [5](#)

Table 14.4.: Total GDP shares.

Country	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share [%] ²⁵	GDP share of total costs [selected categories] [%] ²⁶	New prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New GDP share [%] ²⁷	New GDP share of total costs [selected categories] [%] ²⁸
Developed countries							
U.S.	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC)	4.79	0.05	0.06	17.50	0.18	0.22
U.S.	2003 Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996	1.95	0.98	1.78	17.50	8.79	15.97
Canada	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	1.00	0.47	0.19	17.50	8.23	3.33
Australia	KPMG Australia 2016	[11.13]	1.35	1.77	17.50	2.12	2.78
Australia	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	7.10	0.76	0.46	17.50	1.87	1.13
Australia	Access Economics 2004a	5.00	1.07	1.61	17.50	3.74	5.64
U.K.	Walby 2009	0.60	1.00	0.91	17.50	29.17	26.54
Sweden	Envall and Eriksson 2006	2.60	0.10	0.09	17.50	0.67	0.61
Germany	Sacco 2017	3.00	0.12	0.63	17.50	0.70	3.68
Switzerland	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	1.26	0.03	0.36	17.50	0.42	5.00
France	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	5.00	0.17	0.06	17.50	0.60	0.21
Spain	Villagómez 2010	2.00	0.22	0.28	17.50	1.93	2.45
Developing and emerging countries							
Vietnam	Duvvury and Carney 2012	25.40	3.19	0.00 ²⁹	17.50	2.20	0.00 ³⁰
Bangladesh	Siddique 2011	24.00	2.10	0.93	17.50	1.53	0.68
Colombia	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	18.00	3.93	2.80	17.50	3.82	2.72
Morocco	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	27.70	–	–	17.50	–	–
Uganda	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	30.00	–	–	17.50	–	–
South Africa	KPMG South Africa 2014	20.00–30.00	0.90–1.30	0.82	17.50	0.76–0.79	0.72
Ukraine	UNFPA Ukraine 2017	10.00	0.23	0.02	17.50	0.40	0.03
Namibia	Breuer 2021	17.50	6.01	6.01	17.50	6.01	6.01

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors. The numbers are rounded to two figures after the comma.

Source: Own representation.

In Table 14.4 GDP share [%] [see column 4] and GDP share of total costs [selected categories] [%] [see column 5] do not fully match, as the latter only represents the cost categories that were computed in this study. In some cases, the values in the original studies are lower. After all, the stated total cost-share often did not include the intangibles or the second-generation costs because these have been listed separately, for instance. Alternatively, it is lower because, among others, only the unit costs were specified for certain cost classes in the original study. Or rather, it represents a higher value because cost categories are calculated in the original publications that are not included in this study, such as tax losses. The same situation applies to the last two columns with the values of New GDP share [%] and New GDP share of total costs [selected categories] [%].

When comparing the figures in Table 14.4 the original GDP shares [%] range from:

1. Developed countries: 0.03 to 1.35 per cent.
2. Developing and emerging countries: 0.23 to 3.93 per cent.

When analysing the GDP share of total costs [selected categories] [%] in Table 14.4 the GDP shares [%] range from:

1. Developed countries: 0.06 to 1.78 per cent.
2. Developing and emerging countries: 0.00 [0.000000003] to 2.80 per cent³¹ [The Namibian share is 6.01 per cent].

If analysing the value of the New GDP share of total costs [selected categories] [%], the following development emerges:

1. Developed countries: 0.21–26.54 per cent.

²⁵The figure represents the computed share in Table 3.2 which was either given in the original paper or which was calculated for this overview based on researched data.

²⁶The figures depict the values computed in Table 14.2

²⁷The figures are the GDP cost-shares from column four in Table 14.4 which have been raised to the Namibian prevalence of 17.50 per cent.

²⁸The figures are the cost-shares from column five in Table 14.4 which have been raised to the Namibian prevalence of 17.50 per cent. For further explanation, Table 14.3 showcases in its last column “Total costs [%]” the exact summed up partial results of the sub-cost categories, which are displayed in its previous columns. Whereas Table 14.4 shows in its last column “New GDP share of total costs [selected categories] [%]” the rounded total result value to the adjusted prevalence of 17.50 per cent from column 5, “GDP share of total costs [selected categories] [%].” Since Table 14.3 shows the sums of the exact new individual results of each cost category, and Table 14.4 works with the rounded total value of all cost categories, rounding differences between the two tables are displayed.

²⁹Detailed figure 0.000000003 per cent.

³⁰The starting value for Vietnam in column 5 was 0.000000003 per cent. The value was too small to be displayed correctly here.

³¹The 2003 GDP share Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004, p. 43 compute is 3.93 per cent. For example, among others, this value was not achieved in the overview in Table 14.4. Only the cost categories that are also discussed in this paper are added up there.

2. Developing and emerging countries: 0.00³²-2.72 per cent. [The Namibian share is 6.01 per cent].

Figure 14.1 showcases the results in more detail.

Legend: 1. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003, 2. Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996, 3. Zhang *et al.* 2012, 4. KPMG Australia 2016, 5. National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009, 6. Access Economics 2004a, 7. Walby 2009, 8. Envall and Eriksson 2006, 9. Sacco 2017, 10. Stern *et al.* 2013, 11. Nectoux *et al.* 2010, 12. Villagómez 2010, 13. Duvvury and Carney 2012, 14. Siddique 2011, 15. Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004, 16. Duvvury *et al.* 2009 (for Morocco), 17. Duvvury *et al.* 2009 (for Uganda), 18. KPMG South Africa 2014, 19. UNFPA Ukraine 2017 and 20. Breuer 2021

Figure 14.1.: Comparison of total costs.

Of course, this calculation is only a theoretical application; the share in the U.K. of 26.54 per cent, like others, is, of course, not applicable. This calculation is only intended to provide better insights into the methodology. Further, if the Colombian study of Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 had calculated the cost categories of the intangibles, physical, and emotional impact and the second-generation costs, the losses would likely be equivalent to the Namibian results. As expected for emerging markets, none of the studies would have computed such a high GDP share. Table 14.5 shows the studies that calculate a theoretical comparatively similar or higher value than the Namibian findings for the cost categories analysed in this study.

As said, other research omitted significant cost sections, which resulted in an artificial cost reduction, and therefore, lower results compared to the Namibian findings. Table 14.6 displays certain studies that have left out essential categories [and calculated lower costs, based on the adjusted GDP share of 17.50 per cent]³³

³²The starting value for Vietnam in column 5 was 0.000000003 per cent. The value was too small to be displayed correctly as the prevalence theoretically decreased from 25.40 to 17.50 per cent.

³³These values are also shown in Table 14.4 column seven.

Table 14.5.: Overview of selected GBV costing studies I.

Country	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share [%]	GDP share of total costs [selected categories] [%]	New prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New GDP share [%]	New GDP share of total costs [selected categories] [%]
Developed countries							
U.S.	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996	1.95	0.98	1.78	17.50	8.79	15.97
Australia	Access Economics 2004a	5.00	1.07	1.61		3.74	5.64
U.K.	Walby 2009	0.60	1.00	0.91		29.17	26.54
Germany	Sacco 2017	3.00	0.12	0.63		0.70	3.68
Switzerland	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	1.26	0.03	0.36		0.42	5.00
Developing and emerging countries							
Namibia	Breuer 2021	17.50	6.01	6.01	17.50	6.01	6.01

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors. The numbers are rounded to two figures after the comma.

Source: Own representation.

In conclusion, the more comprehensive a study includes a particular cost section, the higher the GDP proportion converts in research for Australia, the E.U. (including Switzerland and the U.K), Canada or the U.S. Nonetheless, this does not apply to the context of the developing and emerging countries. This phenomenon has already been observed within the scope of emerging markets in general. There, a higher prevalence ratio usually translates into smaller country spendings' in terms of GDP share. The reason for such lower estimates is often that a more conservative or outdated approach is applied due to higher data gaps, a more restricted government budget, and spending compared to developed countries. Further, what becomes evident is that minor differences in methods on how to determine the three cost categories of lost economic output, intangibles, and second-generation, lead to significant deviations in the overall outcome. These variations even outweigh the difference in leaving out particular cost classes, such as personal or legal costs.

Table 14.6.: Overview of selected GBV costing studies II.

Country	Author	Prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	GDP share [%]	GDP share of total costs [selected categories] [%]	New prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New GDP share [%]	New GDP share of total costs [selected categories] [%]
Developed countries							
U.S.	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC)	4.79	0.05	0.06	17.50	0.18	0.22
Canada	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	1.00	0.47	0.19		8.23	3.33
Australia	KPMG Australia 2016	[11.13]	1.35	1.77		2.12	2.78
Australia	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C)	7.10	0.76	0.46		1.87	1.13
Sweden	Envall and Eriksson	2.60	0.10	0.09		0.67	0.61
France	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	5.00	0.17	0.06		0.60	0.21
Spain	Villagómez 2010	2.00	0.22	0.28		1.93	2.45
Developing and emerging countries							
Vietnam	Duvvury and Carney	25.40	3.19	0.00 ³⁴	17.50	2.20	0.00
Bangladesh	Siddique 2011	24.00	2.10	0.93		1.53	0.68
Colombia	Ribero and Sánchez Torres	18.00	3.93	2.80		3.82	2.72
Morocco	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	27.70	–	–		–	–
Uganda	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	30.00	–	–		–	–
South Africa	KPMG South Africa	20.00–30.00	0.90–1.30	0.82		0.76–0.79	0.72
Ukraine	UNFPA Ukraine	10.00	0.23	0.02		0.40	0.03
Namibia	Breuer 2021	17.50	6.01	6.01		6.01	6.01

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors. The numbers are rounded to two figures after the comma.

Source: Own representation.

³⁴Detailed figure 0.000000003 per cent.

Hypothesis

When examining the four studies that best compute the lost economic output, intangibles and second-generation costs, namely the ones of Duvvury *et al.* 2013; Fang *et al.* 2017; Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004; Walby 2009, the following became evident³⁵

1. Walby 2009 computations are based on a prevalence ratio of 0.60 per cent and a GDP share of one per cent. If the prevalence were the same as in Namibia with 17.50 per cent, the new GDP share would increase to hypothetically 27 per cent.
2. Duvvury *et al.* 2013 compute a 1.60 per cent GDP ratio³⁶ solely on the lost economic output category. While theoretically assuming that each of the other seven categories would have half the share each, namely costs of 0.80 per cent, the new GDP share would be 7.20 per cent.
3. Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 calculate a 3.93 per cent ratio³⁷. Still, the authors leave out the intangibles. Such have contributed to a significant cost rise and have, in certain studies, increased the overall cost by over 400 per cent. [See Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996]. A new GDP share that theoretically includes the intangibles would amount moderately to above five per cent.
4. Fang *et al.* 2017 compute only one category, namely the second-generation costs, in very much detail and nevertheless estimate a GDP share of 4.30 per cent. While theoretically assuming that the remainder of the seven categories has only ten per cent of this share, namely 0.43 each, the new GDP share would be 7.31 per cent.

Based on the previous calculations and presented results, the following hypothesis was tested:

The cost of Gender-Based Violence [GBV], including second-generation losses, is projected to be around six per cent and excluding second-generation costs; it is likely to be approximately four per cent of Namibia's 2018 national GDP.

The hypothesis can be confirmed. The calculated share is 6.01 per cent of the 2018 national Namibian GDP or 4.39 per cent excluding second-generation costs. It resembles the current spending of survivors, but also of the state and other institutions as earmarked international donor money, and includes Intangible losses, as well as the costs of the second-generation comprehensively. The major losses are carried by the lost economic output of survivors that cannot participate equally in economic life. Thus, the national economy as a whole becomes restrained. Children burden another significant part. Further, due to the introduced physical and mental harm during their youth, minors will suffer from various economic and health conditions throughout their childhood and later adulthood. Thus diminishes great potential from a nation as a whole.

³⁵For a detailed overview, see Chapter 4. The following enumeration shows the costs displayed in the primary literature.

³⁶The study estimates the lost economic output in Vietnam for 2011. The total production loss represents 1.60 per cent of the 2011 GDP in Vietnam (Duvvury *et al.* 2013, p. 36).

³⁷The 2003 GDP Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004 list in their paper is Mex\$ 223,191,924,278,883, and the GDP share the authors compute is 3.93 per cent for 2003 (Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004, p. 43). See also Tables 3.2 and 14.4

Section 14.4 discusses other significant findings further that became apparent during the process of calculation.

14.4. Further discussion

Section 14.4 reflects on the main limitations associated with estimating the economic costs of violence. In brief, they can be summarised as:

1. Various approaches: differences in the applied method among studies.
2. Different GBV terms: absence of consent about the GBV definition.
3. Data gaps: assessments are often attained from data surveyed for other purposes.
4. Limited sample groups: most research is based on non-representative sample groups or omits male and child survivors.
5. Differences in the survey periods: as depicted in the lifetime vs annual prevalence proportions.
6. Underreporting of GBV: this is a problem worldwide, but especially in the SADC region.
7. Computation of prevalence proportions: papers do not always clearly indicate whether they utilise the number of incidents or other prevalence ratios and how they adjust figures to potential underreporting.
8. Survey limitations: the wording of questions affects the answers given. For example, citizens may report a higher WTP to combat GBV under an artificial interview setting pressure.

The following outline presents the most crucial aspects in greater detail.

Data restrictions

Robust and complete cost estimations, including an examination of the connections between GBV, economic growth, and advancement, are restricted by significant data gaps. Often, cost reviews are limited by incomplete and fragmentary data in most emerging markets. Strong constraints in low- and middle-income countries are that there exists no annual analysis of crime victimisation ratios, as conducted in the United States or other OECD countries. Hence, a comprehensive examination of the impacts on economic growth is constrained by a lack of data on prevalence proportions. As an economy experiences structural development, recent prevalence data, along with other vital parameters, such as current GDP per capita data, are required to map the dynamic consequences of economic loss. The following subparagraph explores certain obstacles surrounding the GDP statistics in developing countries, specifically regarding the GDP data.

Problems with GDP data in developing and emerging countries

There are several barriers regarding the accurate estimation of GDP data in Africa and Southern Africa, respectively. In brief, this outline explains the concerns about national GDP per capita data, informal markets, and selection bias in GDP statistics that primarily occur in developing and emerging countries (The Economist 2014b). IMF findings imply that the informal economy in Sub-Saharan Africa continues to be among the most comprehensive in the world (Medina, Jonelis, and Cangul 2017). The GDP breakdown, for instance, usually does

not recognise the income produced through black markets or parallel economies (Doepke 2020). Further, the GDP statistics suffer setbacks in their documentation. For instance, data is surveyed only on an irregular basis, among others (The Economist 2014b).³⁸ Consequently, the reporting and estimation of the cost to GDP might undergo specific inadequacies. To conduct meaningful assessments, governments will have to secure investments in proper data collection and strengthen existing data practices, especially at service points in the health or judicial departments. Appropriate GBV cost estimates are crucial information to design an ongoing public policy. This would result in enhanced social welfare and individual well-being and would back the voice and participation of all citizens. The U.N. has designed a set of GBV indicators and provided guidelines for compiling and selecting demographic data (García-Moreno *et al.* 2013 World Health Organization (WHO) 2013b). These guidelines present national administration worldwide with direction on accumulating, examining, and distributing data on GBV. Such an initiative aims to establish a global GBV database and close the current gaps (Duvvury *et al.* 2013 p. 45–51).

The following paragraph reflects on the different methodological challenges when estimating and comparing cost reviews.

Methodological challenges

It has to be kept in mind that the estimate's accuracy is not only determined by the underlying data but also by the thoroughness of the approach itself. The following paragraph discusses this matter in more detail.

Many factors influence the precision of analytical cost assessments. Notwithstanding, it is not easy to compare published research if the relevant primary, underlying data and method is not explicitly stated and explained. Several studies solely publish the outcome and only provide little or no information on the applied approach or baseline data used. The exactness of costing assessments depends on different determinants, including the size and quality of cohort data, the proper use of proxy determinants, or the precise adjustment of the prevalence proportion. As not all of such information was available or could not always be found within the primary literature used within the various papers listed, the presented comparison of studies may be subjected to a certain degree of distortion. The different applied approaches individually used in each publication to estimate the prevalence ratios may have led to an inevitable distortion as well. Certain studies have used a lifetime prevalence ratio, while others have applied the most recent per annum data. The prevalence ratios have been adjusted to an equal baseline during all calculations to allow for comparisons among papers. However, during this process, again, a certain degree of distortion may have occurred. Furthermore, unfortunately, most research uses prevalence ratios without adjusting for the possibility of underestimating. The common perception of GBV is that it is private, and especially in Namibia, it is often a culturally accepted matter. Hence, there is significant underreporting, and only one out of around 27 cases [3.71 per cent] is registered.³⁹ In addition, when applying

³⁸This fact becomes, for instance, evident in The Economist 2014b article on “How Nigeria’s economy grew by 89 per cent overnight.”

³⁹For more details, see Chapter 6.

the average daily GDP per capita data, it is assumed that survivors are drawn randomly from the entire population. However, there is a risk that other determinants will be left out. The data can hide extreme poverty and imbalances in income and living standards, for instance. With a poverty rate of 18.30 per cent in 2018 (World Bank 2020b), an unemployment rate of 33.40 per cent in 2018 (Economics 2018), and an HIV prevalence of 12.10 per cent among adults aged 15 to 49 years in 2017 (UNAIDS 2019), large parts of the Namibian population remain vulnerable (National Planning Commission 2015). Furthermore, the unemployment rate for women is higher than for men. The results suggest that Namibian men are more often in employment and earn higher wages than women. This result indicates that the average GDP per capita may not serve as a suitable indicator for GBV costing. However, the other option would be to tailor the estimates based on a specific set of characteristics, such as the survivor's age, gender, ethnicity, or location. While this can be supported theoretically, the outcome may arguably stimulate greater political efforts targeting higher-income cohorts. This approach could decrease prevention activities against those who are already the most disadvantaged and vulnerable groups in society. It would have socially unacceptable consequences and would contradict the practice of government policy in other areas. Hence, the GDP per capita data are used, and potential flaws are acknowledged.

Further, the mainstream literature tends to generally conduct conservative calculations, and in consequence, to underestimate the costs of GBV often poses more harm than good. Budget allocations that underrate the expenses contribute to a sub-optimal allocation of resources during policy-making. The trend to be more cautious originates from the pressure to avoid public resentment to extremely high-cost figures. However, conclusively, by presenting decreased costs, the extent of the problem is deprecated artificially.

The next paragraph discusses the concrete barriers in receiving services in Namibia, which influence the cost estimates as well.

Problems in assessing services in Namibia

When evaluating the outcomes, it has to be considered that many obstacles prevent survivors from receiving adequate assistance, and barriers span throughout all areas. In summary, the research indicates:

1. Low help-seeking behaviour: for example, only 21 per cent of women who have encountered any form of physical abuse during their lifetime have sought help in Namibia. Usually, help-seeking behaviour decreases with the survivor's age and the number of children (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 315).
2. Positive socialisation and education towards GBV: social approval of GBV is significant. Frequently, citizens assume that a spouse is justified to punish his wife under particular conditions (Ministry of Health and Social Services (MoHSS) 2008 p. 245). Such cultural values prevent women and children from seeking assistance and make it challenging to calculate realistic losses.
3. Problematical gender roles: in order with the discussed viewpoints, the traditional mindset is another vital barrier in stopping GBV. For Namibian men, masculinity often equals possession and control over women. Namibian women are usually socialised to believe in being inferior and accept that men are authorised to discipline them (Ministry of Gender Equality and Child Welfare 2012 p. 19). Consequently; also, citizens in government and

social welfare organisations, who are supposed to support survivors, may have acquired such internal values.

4. Inadequate service provisions: such inherited values nourish the insufficient delivery of services (Ministry of Gender Equality and Child Welfare [2012](#) p. 20). Consequently, the cycle repeats itself. The public staff is not fully ready to render real support. There is a shortage of quality and quantity of services. Hence, survivors are deterred from reporting and receiving support that is budgeted.
5. In the area of health care, the main barriers, which hindered survivors from accessing services, were, among others, large distances to a health facility [31 per cent], to get money for treatment [28 per cent], the fear of not wanting to go alone [15 per cent], or to obtain permission to go for treatment [six per cent] (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) p. 114).⁴⁰
6. For the section of legal support, the main obstacles involved, among others:
 - a) Lack of skills and expertise: often, efficient police response is prohibited due to a shortage of vehicles, petrol, or the absence of qualified staff to administer child rape complainants, for instance (Hubbard *et al.* [2006](#) p. IV). Further, poor literacy skills of police officers often hinder evidence acquisition and the formulation of relevant testimonies that can serve in court (Hubbard *et al.* [2006](#) p. 84).
 - b) Lack of proper evidence collection: for instance, lab results are placed into the wrong dockets, or the lab reference number does not match the police reference. Consequently, the data gets lost, and proper prosecution cannot be conducted (Hubbard *et al.* [2006](#) p. 37).
 - c) The most common reference for support was the survivor's own family: Forty-eight per cent of people have asked for help from their own families. In contrast, social work organisations remained a reservoir of aid for only five per cent. [See Hubbard *et al.* [2006](#) p. 21 and Ministry of Health and Social Services (MoHSS) [2008](#) p. 316].

Consequently, the obstacles discussed earlier may lead to:

1. Higher short-term expenses: the overall cost is assumed to be higher, as a significant part of the population is hindered from receiving services. For instance, certain obstacles have prevented survivors in Namibia from seeking medical care.
2. Higher long-term expenses: for example, if the evidence is lost due to improper administration; as a result, no judgment can be conducted. As a consequence, survivors, especially children, are not protected adequately. Their distress and trauma are prolonged; consequently, impairment and losses increase for a nation as a whole in the long-term.
3. Artificial inflation of personal costs: for instance, due to setbacks in the judiciary system, individuals often travel and appear in court, only to receive notification that the judges have suspended their ruling. As a consequence, private expenses for survivors and their families get artificially increased. On the other hand, there is an:

⁴⁰The report does not state from whom (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) p. 114).

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4. Artificial decrease of government costs: due to insufficient police and judicial operations, survivors do not hold decent access to the CJS. For example, if concerned citizens want to complain about mismanagement within the police and judiciary branches, they may encounter unnatural restrictions [e.g., police staff loses their case files]. As a result, survivors frequently remove their claims, resign, or not receive the fair judgment they are entitled to experience. Especially the last point of the government cost, that are kept unnaturally low, has to be considered when reading the results. If all individuals had proper access to the legal system, the yearly cost would have been higher in consequence. The current status quo is that a large group of survivors capitulates because they do not have the physical, mental or financial strength to *fight* the institutional system.

In summary, if all survivors in demand were serviced [adequately], the actual cost would have been even higher. In addition, trauma and suffering are unnecessarily prolonged, and hence, expenses are exorbitantly inflated.

The following paragraph outlines the cost categories that were not included in this study.

Other costs

Due to a lack of relevant data or technical maturity of the approach, the cost classes, displayed in Table 14.7, could not be included.

Table 14.7.: Overview of omitted costs.

Cost	Reason
Increased juvenile and adult crime, as a reason to GBV exposure during childhood.	Data was not available at the point of research.
Children's school performance, including missed days, failing, or poor marks.	Data was not available at the point of research.
Economic violence, like withholding income or household funds, among others.	Both, data and technical maturity of the approach was not available at the point of research.
Business and employment costs: including consequences to co-workers covering for the survivor, the rise in overtime payments to other employees, or the cost of contracting and training replacement staff.	Data was not available at the point of research.
Cost in terms of loss of freedom for incarcerated perpetrators.	Data was not available at the point of research.
Lost tax revenues to the state.	Data was not available at the point of research.

Source: Own representation.

The omitting of specific costs due to a lack of data has contributed to a certain degree of underestimation. For instance, the scope of this analysis omits the losses from emotional violence or does not include multiplier effects, such as the holistic, long-term consequences of HIV/AIDS as a result of GBV. The following paragraph discusses which steps are necessary to compute such in the near future.

Future outlook

In general, there are two domains where there is a demand for more analysis and data compilation: 1] investigation on the consequences of GBV, including the well-being of children; and 2] global-wide data collection to promote comparable results. In summary, the key recommendations involve an:

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1. Increase in the capability of public statistic's departments regarding GBV data collection: it is necessary to produce more sound assessments on the impacts upon economic development. The expertise of general statistics agencies to develop and maintain a centralised data policy has to be enhanced. Such requirements include improved knowledge regarding methods or specific ethical concerns. Another option is the introduction of regular national data collection, as conducted in the U.S. or the U.K., among others, which are anonymous, self-filled surveys on the economic impact of GBV. Of course, there may be a certain challenge in adopting a method of self-filled questionnaires, especially in Namibia, a country with lower literacy rates and a hard-to-reach population. However, novel methods have been utilised to collect Namibian HIV information, which could be used for this purpose.
 2. Increase the availability of robust methods: better approaches are required to estimate the economic impacts of GBV in a sufficiently accurate manner. Due to a shortage of suitable techniques, distinct cost categories had to be omitted. Further, for instance, the literature on the economic implications of abortions and unwanted pregnancies is limited; thus, it is further challenging to calculate the financial burden of the psychological consequences of mothers and their [unwanted] children, among others.

In a nutshell, as described, a specific part of the expenses could not be estimated [yet]. In summary, more research and reliable data are needed to enhance the accuracy of estimates in the near future.

14.5. Summary

Section [14.5](#) described the detailed findings of this study. When comparing the costs with the results from other studies, the conclusion depicted in Table [14.3](#) was reached. For the sake of clarity and simplicity, the outcome is [again] displayed in Table [14.8](#).

In summary, the Lost economic output category costs are in the upper range compared to other studies. For the health service costs, the applied method in developing countries is mostly not as comprehensive, making a comparison for this category difficult. The applied approach in this study is comparable to that used in industrialised countries. The calculated legal costs are high. It should be noted that the studies conducted in developing and emerging countries are often methodologically incomplete, which makes comparison again problematic. The applied method in the category of social welfare and special service costs goes beyond the standard analysis, which is usually applied to compute social welfare benefits, as performed in most of the research listed. As a result, the costs calculated in this category are disproportionately high too. However, the personal cost results of other international literature exceed the calculated

⁴¹Detailed figure 0.000000002 per cent.

⁴²Ibid.

⁴³Detailed figure 0.00002 per cent.

⁴⁴Detailed figure 0.0002 per cent.

Table 14.8.: Comparison of all adjusted subcategory calculations.

Country	Year	Author	New prevalence [%] [last 12 months]	New lost economic output [%]	New health service costs [%]	New legal costs [%]	New social welfare costs [%]	New personal costs [%]	New intangibles [%]	New second-generation costs [%]	Total costs [%]
Developed countries											
			17.50								
U.S.	2003	Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003	0.07	0.15	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.22
U.S.	1996	Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996	–	2.06	–	–	–	–	7.63	6.28	15.97
Canada	2012	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012	0.05	0.07	0.53	0.53	0.35	1.58	0.18	–	3.29
Australia	2016	KPMG Australia 2016	0.19	0.14	0.16	0.16	1.10	1.01	0.03	–	2.79
Australia	2009	National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009	0.07	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.42	0.47	0.02	–	1.13
Australia	2004	Access Economics 2004a	0.21	0.18	0.14	0.28	1.19	3.54	0.11	–	5.65
U.K.	2009	Walby 2009	3.50	3.21	0.58	0.88	–	18.38	–	–	26.55
Sweden	2006	Envall and Eriksson 2006	0.13	0.01	0.27	0.20	–	–	–	–	0.61
Germany	2017	Sacco 2017	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	–	3.33	0.12	–	3.69
Switzerland	2013	Stern <i>et al.</i> 2013	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	–	4.44	–	–	5.00
France	2012	Nectoux <i>et al.</i> 2010	0.11	0.03	0.03	0.03	–	–	0.01	–	0.21
Spain	2010	Villagómez 2010	0.35	0.26	0.09	0.53	0.79	–	0.44	–	2.46
Developing and emerging countries											
			17.50								
Vietnam	2012	Duvvury and Carney 2012	–	0.00 ⁴¹	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.00 ⁴²
Bangladesh	2011	Siddique 2011	0.63	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.00 ⁴³	–	–	–	0.68
Colombia	2004	Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004	2.07	0.01	0.32	0.06	0.26	–	–	–	2.72
Morocco	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Uganda	2009	Duvvury <i>et al.</i> 2009	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
South Africa	2014	KPMG South Africa 2014	–	0.01	0.01	0.02–0.03	0.45–0.67	–	–	–	0.49–0.72
Ukraine	2017	UNFPA Ukraine 2017	0.00 ⁴⁴	0.005	0.02	0.002	0.02	–	–	–	0.05
Namibia	2021	Breuer 2021	1.64	0.26	0.50	1.09	0.28	0.62	1.62	–	6.01

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

data, as the estimated cost-share of this study is in the lower range. In the cost class of the intangibles, physical, and emotional impact, international literature computes a higher cost-share than shown in this study. The assumptions made in this section tend to be more conservative, which reflects in the overall result. The second-generation costs category, in turn, has a very high share of costs compared to other research. This is mainly because the used method is extensive in its level of detail and scope.

Based on the findings, the established hypothesis could be confirmed. The costs that occurred are around six per cent of the gross domestic product. It must be noted once again that the cost-share calculated covers different areas of life and also includes the costs incurred to the second-generation too. In the further discussion, it was pointed out that some technical hurdles define studies that calculate the cost of violence as a proportion of the gross domestic product. These also include data restrictions and a lack of robust databases. They span across problems within gross domestic product surveys, which are often based on outdated data in developing and emerging countries, among others. Furthermore, numerous studies are characterised by certain scientific issues, as there is only a weak methodological basis to compute specific cost categories, which makes detailed costing often difficult. Furthermore, in Namibia, officials have sometimes internalised the culture of GBV; therefore, it is in many cases challenging for survivors of violence to access essential services so that earmarked budgets may not be adequately spent.

Part II.
Appendix

The Appendix is broken down into the following categories:

1. literature review,
2. lost economic output,
3. health service costs,
4. legal costs,
5. social welfare costs and special service costs,
6. personal costs,
7. intangibles, physical, and emotional impact,
8. second-generation costs, and
9. other data.

The Appendix provides further information, calculation, and data. It starts with additional details on the Literature review.

15. Literature review

Chapter [15](#) offers more insights into the conducted calculations of the prevalence and GDP share of Chapter [3](#). The prevalence ratio indicates the proportion of the population affected by GBV in relation to the total local population. Most studies only survey the proportion of the female population. If the selected literature also records the proportion of men, this is mentioned explicitly. Often this number is not given in the studies and was calculated for this overview, respectively. The prevalence ratio and the GDP share are compared with each other and must be viewed in context. For example, studies in developing and emerging countries usually only calculate a small proportion of the costs compared to the national GDP, although the prevalence ratio is usually very high. The explanations begin with the computations for developed countries.

15.1. Developed countries

If the data was not provided or computed in the specific paper listed, the following calculations used census, GBV and GDP data of UN Women [2018a](#), World Bank [2018a](#), World Bank [2018g](#)

U.S. – 2003 – Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC)

- The computed GBV prevalence is 4.79 per cent: the incidence data reflects 5.30 million IPV cases among U.S. women aged 18 and older each year, within the past 12 months, based on 2003 estimates (Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) [2003](#), p. 19). According to the World Bank census data, the overall number of women, 18–80+ years, in 2003 was 110,756,253 (World Bank [2018g](#)). For the detailed census data, see Chapter [23](#).
- The computed GDP share is 0.05 per cent: the total cost is US\$ 5.8 billion [$\text{US\$ } 5.8 \times 10^9$] (Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) [2003](#), p. 32). The U.S. 2003 GDP [in current LCU] was US\$ 11.458 trillion.

U.S. – 1996 – Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema

- The computed GBV prevalence is 1.95 per cent. The paper computes all costs in 1993 dollars (Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#), p. 9). Regarding the prevalence data in the study, Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#) included only the data of the two million spousal survivors with severe enough abuse to cause injury. Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#) use per annum data from the Straus and Gelles [1986](#) study. Straus and Gelles [1986](#) estimated that two million citizens suffered annually from severe spousal violence. The

authors interpreted the data as violence with at least one minor case of physical injury (Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#) p. 6). It is assumed that victimisation has occurred within the last 12 months, although this is not explicitly stated. Miller and his team [1996] use this finding for their calculations, although the Straus and Gelles article was published already in 1986. Consequently, there is a mismatch between both time frames. Further, Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#) do not explain how they adjusted the Straus and Gelles [1986] data for the altered population census of 1993. The 1993 U.S. female census data for the population aged 15–64 and 65 and above was 104,458,091. For the age range of 18 to above 80, the World Bank listed 102,480,546 women in 1996.¹ Please note, since the authors explicitly leave out children, this calculation employs only the age range of above 18 from the census data. For detailed information, see Chapter [23](#). Further, the authors use different prevalence proportions for the various cost categories. However, data from other research could not be used for this calculation, as, for instance, the official U.N. data for the U.S. mainly exist for the time after 2000 (UN Women [2018a](#)). Therefore, the stated prevalence calculated for 1996, which is the year of publication, should only be read as a proxy.

- The computed GDP share is 0.98 per cent: the cost, according to the study, was US\$ 67 billion [in detail, US\$ 67,000,000,000] in 1993 (Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema [1996](#) p. 18). The 1993 GDP in current US\$ was 6.859 trillion [in detail, US\$ 6,859,000,000,000] (World Bank [2018a](#)). As the cost is stated, among other things, in US\$ 67 billion [in detail, US\$ 67,000,000,000], the 1993 GDP in current US\$ is used for the sub-cost categories.

Canada – 2012 – Zhang *et al.*

- Prevalence [%] – 1.00: Zhang *et al.* use several prevalence ratios within their predictions. Thus, other literature was examined. The Canadian Centre for Justice Statistics [2011](#); UN Women [2019b](#) data states a proportion of one per cent. This figure includes currently-partnered women over 15 years who have experienced physical and, or sexual violence by a current partner within the last 12 months. Consequently, this proportion is applied.
- GDP share [%] – 0.47: the overall conservative estimate, presented in current LCU, (Zhang *et al.* [2012](#) p. 56, 127) is C\$ 7.4 billion [in detail, C\$ 7,420,301,324] in 2009 C\$ (Zhang *et al.* [2012](#) p. 2, 80). The Canadian 2009 GDP [in current LCU] was C\$ 1.567 trillion [in detail, C\$ 1,567,000,000,000] (World Bank [2018a](#)). Zhang *et al.* have included both men and women; hence, the outcome is over-proportionally high compared to other findings.

¹The 102,480,546 figure is used in this calculation, although it presents the year 1996 because the 1993 data were not as detailed (See Chapter [23](#)).

Australia – 2016 – KPMG Australia

- Prevalence [%] – 11.13: the prevalence data from KPMG Australia [2016](#) states 1,033,910 affected female citizens. The statistics include women from the age of 15 based on 2012 estimates. Census data for the number of women in this respective age group was 9,286,413 in 2012. For more detailed information, see Chapter [23](#). Please note that the census data until *age 80+* was chosen as no age limit is indicated in the 2012 PSS report, which presents the primary database. Based on these figures, the prevalence ratio would be 11.13 per cent. Nonetheless, primary data in the Australian Bureau of Statistics [2012](#), refer to “since the age of 15, not to within the past 12 months.” However, most literature listed uses the baseline of “the past 12 months.” As a result, the ratio is significantly higher compared to other studies reviewed. According to data of the Australian Bureau of Statistics [2012](#), UN Women [2018a](#), the ratio of physical and or sexual IPV in the last 12 months was two per cent only. Anyhow, to avoid distortion, the 11.13 per cent was chosen, as the study’s cost estimate is based on this prevalence.
- GDP share [%] – 1.35: the total cost of violence against women and their children was A\$ 22 billion [in detail, A\$ 22,000,000,000] per annum for the financial year of 2015 (KPMG Australia [2016](#) Foreword). The costs are stated in the LCU: A\$(KPMG Australia [2016](#) p. 6). The Australian GDP [in current LCU] was A\$ 1.625 trillion in 2015 [in detail, A\$ 1,625,000,000,000] (World Bank [2018a](#)).

Australia – 2009 – National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C)

- Prevalence [%] – 7.10: the prevalence data in the study include 747,483 affected based on a 2021 to 2022 population forecast (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) [2009](#), p. 32) if no action is taken. The census data for the number of women in the age group 15 to 80+ will be 10,525,000 in 2021 (World Bank [2018g](#)). Please note, the concrete age group is not defined in the Australian report (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) [2009](#), p. 32). Thus, the age range 15 to 80+, as done in the Australian KPMG study, was chosen. For detailed census data, see Chapter [23](#).
- GDP share [%] – 0.76: the costs, according to the study, is A\$ 15.6 billion [in detail, A\$ 15,600,000,000] for the years of 2021 to 2022 (National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) [2009](#) overview). The Australian 2021 GDP forecast is US\$ 1.551 trillion [in current US\$] (Statista [2018](#)). The US\$ to A\$ exchange rate forecast is 1:1.322 (Wallet Investor [2018](#)). The Australian 2021 GDP forecast [in current LCU: A\$] is expected to be 2.050 trillion [in detail, A\$ 2,050,422,000,000] (World Bank [2018a](#)).

Australia – 2004 – Access Economics

- Prevalence [%] – 5.00: is listed directly in Access Economics [2004a](#), p. 15.
- GDP share [%] – 1.07: according to the study, the cost was around A\$ 8.1 billion [in detail, A\$ 8,078,000,000], including pain and suffering for the financial year of 2002 to 2003 (Access Economics [2004a](#) p. VII). Costs are expressed in the LCU, A\$(Access Economics [2004a](#) p. 20). The Australian 2002 GDP [in current LCU] was around A\$ 754 billion [in detail, A\$ 754,253,000,000] (World Bank [2018a](#)).

U.K. – 2009 – Walby

- Prevalence [%] – 0.60: this is indicated directly by Walby [2009] p. 6.
- GDP share [%] – 1.00: the cost, according to the study were £ 15 billion. [In detail, £ 15,730,000,000 for the year of 2008 (Walby [2009] p. 2)]. The U.K. 2008 GDP [in current LCU] was £ 1.59 trillion [in detail, £ 1,590,000,000,000] (World Bank [2018a]). The computed GDP share for Walby [2009] was rounded from 0.99 to 1.00 per cent.

Denmark – 2010 – Helweg-Larsen *et al.*

- Prevalence [%] – 2.01: the report lists a total number of 35,500 survivors for the past 12 months period (Helweg-Larsen *et al.* [2010] p. 11. See Table “Total number of survivors in DNK”). Overall, 1,762,355 women aged 16 to 64 lived in Denmark in 2010 (World Bank [2018g]). See Table [23.5] in Chapter [23]
- GDP share [%] – 0.004: the cost according to the study was € 70 million [in detail, € 70,000,000] in 2010 (Helweg-Larsen *et al.* [2010] p. 9). The Danish 2010 GDP [in current LCU] was € 1.811 trillion [in detail, € 1,811,000,000,000] (World Bank [2018a]).

Sweden – 2006 – Envall and Eriksson

- Prevalence [%] – 2.60: Envall and Eriksson [2006] assume that at least 75,000 women in Sweden are subjected to IPV in some form every year. The review does not define a specific age range. The census data for the range of 15 to 64 years state 2,882,254 women, which were then chosen to calculate the prevalence ratio (World Bank [2018g]). For details, see Table [23.7] in Chapter [23]
- GDP share [%] – 0.10: Envall and Eriksson base their estimates on 2004 figures. The overall lower bound estimate is kr 2,695 million [in detail, between kr 2,695 million and kr 3,300 million a year, kr 2,695,000,000–kr 3,300,000,000] for 2004 (Envall and Eriksson [2006] p. 9). In line with this study’s stance, the lower-bound estimate was chosen. The Swedish 2004 GDP [in current LCU] was kr 2.83 trillion [in detail, kr 2,830,000,000,000] (World Bank [2018a]). The computed GDP share for Envall and Eriksson [2006] was rounded from 0.095 to 0.10 per cent.

Finland – 2001 – Heiskanen and Piispa

- Prevalence [%] – 5.00: Heiskanen and Piispa [2001] base their data on a survey of 7,000 women, which was undertaken in their previous study called “Faith, hope, battering: a survey of men’s violence against women in Finland” (Heiskanen, Piispa, and Aromaa [1998]). However, the U.N. Global Database on violence against women provides more updated information. The U.N. statistics list a five per cent ratio for women aged 18 to 74 years. The data refers to the past 12 months and is based on 2014 estimates (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights [2014]; UN Women [2018a]). [Note, see argumentation on, for instance, the Sacco [2017] paper below].
- GDP share [%] – 0.08: the study, published in 2001, is grounded in 1998 data. The 1998 results are already indicated in Euro. The costs, according to research, were € 101 million [in detail, € 101,000,000] for 1998 (Heiskanen and Piispa [2001]). The Finnish 1998 GDP [in current LCU] was around € 120 billion [in detail, € 120,474,000,000] (World Bank [2018a]).

Germany – 2017 – Sacco

- Prevalence [%] – 3.00: the Sacco [2017](#) report employs a different set of prevalence ratios. Sacco uses case numbers from police and judicial statistics for direct cost estimations (Sacco [2017](#) p. 48–51). The used data for calculations of indirect costs, like unemployment or loss of productivity, derives from the Bundesministerium für Familie, Senioren, Frauen und Jugend. Concrete, Sacco used a figure of 24,623,340 females, which represents women between 20 and 64 years. The cohort of women affected by DV [25 per cent of 24,623,340] was 6,155,835. However, the 25 per cent ratio refers to a lifetime prevalence (Bundesministerium für Familie, Senioren, Frauen und Jugend (BMFSFJ) [2013](#)). Deriving from this 25 per cent lifetime ratio, Sacco estimates a yearly figure of 139,905 survivors (Sacco [2017](#) p. 105, 108, 116). Nevertheless, the author does not explain in detail, based on which ratio and data [source] the per annum figure of 139,905 survivors is computed from the lifetime figure of 6,155,835. Hence, other literature is examined. International research from the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights and the U.N. Women’s Global Database on Violence against Women states a lifetime prevalence of 22 per cent, which is similar to the 25 per cent figure presented by Sacco (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation [2015](#) UN Women [2019d](#)). In contrast, both the E.U. and the U.N. Database on Violence against Women state a yearly ratio of three per cent; and thus indicate a significant contrast to the Sacco research because the stated per annum figure of 139,905 survivors represents only a 0.57 per cent share of the 24,623,340 women between 20 and 64. Sacco did not indicate precisely how she computed her figures. Further, the author uses different prevalence ratios and case numbers to calculate the various cost categories. Hence, U.N.Women und E.U. estimates of three per cent are used (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation [2015](#) UN Women [2019d](#)). A possible distortion is acknowledged.
- GDP share [%] – 0.12: the calculation bases among other on 2016 data (Sacco [2017](#) p. 33, 101); hence, the 2016 GDP data (Sacco [2017](#) p. 100) is employed. The cost was € 3.8 billion [in detail, € 3,800,000,000] in 2016 (Sacco [2017](#) p. 14). The German 2016 GDP [in current LCU] was € 3.16 trillion [in detail, € 3,160,000,000,000] (World Bank [2018a](#)).

Switzerland – 2013 – Stern *et al.*

- Prevalence [%] – 1.26: the prevalence data in the Stern *et al.* [2013](#), p. 8 paper includes an age cohort of 16 to 36 years and uses the past 12 months time frame. The primary data derives from Killias *et al.* [2012](#) estimates. According to Killias *et al.* [2012](#), during the past 12 months, overall, 1.26 per cent, thereof, around 0.90 per cent of women and 0.35 per cent of men, have experienced physical or sexual abuse by their current partner or ex-partner in heterosexual or gay and lesbian relationships. Nonetheless, with a similar method, international literature reflects a different prevalence ratio of approximately 2.5 times this figure. Stern *et al.*; thus, conducted two scenarios. One scenario is based on the prevalence ratio derived from a study by Killias *et al.*; in 2012. The second, higher prevalence ratio scenario is based on international literature estimates. However, in line with this study’s stance, the lower bound estimate is chosen (Stern *et al.* [2013](#) p. 8). However, mainstream literature computes costs generally for women only or includes men only for specific cost categories. Hence, the Stern *et al.* [2013](#) study is very holistic, which was kept in mind during the literature comparison.

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- GDP share [%] – 0.03: the cost, according to the research, was CHF 164 million [in detail, CHF 164,000,000] in 2011 (Stern *et al.* 2013, p. 10). The Swiss 2011 GDP [in current LCU] was CHF 621.256 billion [in detail, CHF 621,256,000,000] (World Bank 2018a). It has to be kept in mind that in addition to the annual tangible costs of between CHF 164 [lower estimate] and CHF 287 million [higher estimate], the additional [lifelong] Intangible cost of IPV has to be added. They amount to almost CHF two billion (Stern *et al.* 2013, p. 12). Nonetheless, the intangibles are not estimated for the year 2011. They instead present lifelong costs. Thus, again, with the stance of this study, the lower-bound figure of CHF 164 million is chosen.

France – 2010 – Nectoux *et al.*

- Prevalence [%] – 5.00: Nectoux *et al.* 2010, p. 394 use multiple ratios for different cost categories. Hence, other research had to be analysed. According to the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights 2014 UN Women 2018a database, the indicated number is the prevalence ratio for women aged 18 to 74, within the past 12 months, based on 2014 data.
- GDP share [%] – 0.17: nonetheless, the study was published in 2012 and is partially based on 2010 data. However, the paper lists the costs for the year 2012. According to the paper, the cost was € 3.6 billion [in detail, € 3,607,529,051] in 2012 (Nectoux *et al.* 2010, p. 394). The French 2012 GDP [in current LCU] was € 2.089 trillion [in detail, € 2,089,000,000,000] (World Bank 2018a).

Spain – 2010 – Villagómez

- Prevalence [%] – 2.00: the author includes the prevalence ratio for women above 18 years. The ratio derives from 2002 data. However, it is not indicated in Villagómez 2010, p. 2, whether the data is based on the past 12 months period. Villagómez 2010 uses primary data from the “La violence contras las mujeres. Resultados de la macroencuesta” report (Instituto de la Mujer 2000). The survey depicts different prevalence ratios for varying time frames and types of violence. Hence, the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights 2014 UN Women 2018a database had to be used again, which state a two per cent GBV ratio for the last 12 months.
- GDP share [%] – 0.22: the costs, according to the Villagómez 2010 study, were € 2,356.8 million [in detail, € 2,356,800,000] for the year of 2010. The Spanish 2010 GDP [in current LCU] was € 1.073 trillion [in detail, € 1,073,000,000,000] (World Bank 2018a).

15.2. Developing and emerging countries

Vietnam – 2012 – Duvvury and Carney

- Prevalence [%] – 25.40: according to Duvvury and Carney [2012](#) p. 13, 25.40 per cent of women have experienced violence in the last 12 months.
- GDP share [%] – 3.19: the paper states that the overall potential opportunity cost and productivity losses of DV sum up to 3.19 per cent of the 2010 GDP (Duvvury and Carney [2012](#) p. 78). The Vietnamese 2010 GDP [in current LCU] was $\text{đ}2.158$ quadrillion [in detail $\text{đ}2,158,000,000,000,000$] (World Bank [2018a](#)).

Bangladesh – 2011 – Siddique

- Prevalence [%] – 24.00: Siddique calculates the cost of a one-year time frame (Siddique [2011](#) p. 46), which is based on different ratios (Siddique [2011](#) p. 39). Hence, the report does not indicate any overall prevalence factor. Thus, again, U.N.Women's data is used. According to U.N.Women and the 2009 release of the National Institute of Population Research and Training published in Bangladesh, the prevalence of physical or sexual violence was 24 per cent in the past 12 months (National Institute of Population Research and Training, Mitra and Associates, and Macro International [2011](#); UN Women [2019a](#)).
- GDP share [%] – 2.10: the overall cost of all categories combined was around Taka, $\text{₳}143,580$ million [in detail, Taka, $\text{₳}143,580,000,000$, or Taka, $\text{₳}14,358$ crore], which is, according to the paper, 2.10 per cent of the national GDP. However, Siddique does not state the national GDP figure he employed for his 2010 cost estimates (Siddique [2011](#) p. 50). Based on the following calculation, it derives that Taka, $\text{₳}143,580$ million is 2.10 per cent of GDP; hence around Taka, $\text{₳}6,837,143$ million [in detail, Taka, $\text{₳}6,837,142,857,143$, or Taka, $\text{₳}6,837,143$ crore] is 100 per cent of GDP; thus is – Taka, $\text{₳}6,837$ billion – the overall underlying GDP figure Siddique employed in his estimations. In contrast, according to World Bank data, the GDP [in current LCU] was Taka $\text{₳}7.975$ trillion in 2010, and the GDP [in constant LCU] was Taka $\text{₳}6.071$ trillion in 2010 (World Bank [2018a](#)). Please note that the exact underlying GDP figure Siddique employed in his paper was essential to later calculate the GDP cost-share of the sub-cost categories for this review.

Colombia – 2004 – Ribero and Sánchez Torres

- Prevalence [%] – 18.00: the prevalence ratio derives from a survey, that was explicitly conducted for the Ribero and Sánchez Torres study by the Centro de Estudios Sobre Desarrollo Económico (Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004](#) p. 38). Still, the author uses different prevalences for different types of sexual or physical abuse (Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004](#) p. 35). Hence, the international data from U.N.Women, including the 2015 Pro Familia Colombia national survey, had to be used. This analysis states that physical and sexual violence prevalence was 18 per cent in Colombia during the past 12 months (Lopez and Bolanos [2016](#); UN Women [2019c](#)).
- GDP share [%] – 3.93: the 2003 GDP Ribero and Sánchez Torres list in their paper is Mex\$ 223,191,924,278,883, and the GDP share the authors compute is 3.93 per cent for 2003 (Ribero and Sánchez Torres [2004](#) p. 43).

Morocco – 2009 – Duvvury *et al.*

- Prevalence [%] – 27.70: the Duvvury *et al.* 2009, p. 8 study states that the number of incidents per 1,000 women was 277 in the past 12 months.
- GDP share [%] – n.a.: the paper does not compute nor indicate the overall cost of Morocco (Duvvury *et al.* 2009 p. 12). Hence, the GDP share could not be calculated.

Uganda – 2009 – Duvvury *et al.*

- Prevalence [%] – 30.00: Duvvury *et al.* 2009 p. 8 state that a total of 638 women reported at least one incident of violence during the past 12 months. However, it is not clear whether this data is based on a sample cohort of 1,000 women as well, as conducted for Morocco, see the paragraph above, as the paper does not indicate the size of the overall sample group. Therefore, no prevalence ratio could have been computed (Duvvury *et al.* 2009 p. 7). Hence, the global U.N. Women data, including the Uganda 2016 Demographic and Health Survey, had to be used. Both studies state a prevalence ratio of 30 per cent for physical and sexual violence in the past 12 months (Uganda Bureau of Statistics (UBOS) and ICF 2018; UN Women 2019f).
- GDP share [%] – n.a.: Duvvury *et al.* 2009 do not list a summary of the overall national cost.

South Africa – 2014 – KPMG South Africa

- Prevalence [%] – 20.00–30.00: the costing is based on a prevalence ratio of 20 to 30 per cent (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 39–40). The official U.N. data was not available at the point of research (UN Women 2019e). Thus, the KPMG findings had to be used, although they reflect only a broader scope.
- GDP share [%] – 0.90–1.30: KPMG South Africa 2014, p. 28–29 already indicates the overall computed GDP cost-share at 0.90 to 1.30 per cent. The loss was between R 28.4 billion and R 42.4 billion from 2012 to 2013 (KPMG South Africa 2014 p. 2). The South African GDP, in the current LCU, was R 3.254 trillion [in detail, R 3,254,000,000,000] in 2012, according to World Bank 2018a figures. This exact value was again of importance to calculate relevant sub-categories for this review.

Ukraine – 2017 – UNFPA Ukraine

- Prevalence [%] – 10.00: the study states, “thus, based on the findings of the 2014 UNFPA survey in Ukraine, 8.80 per cent of women aged 15–49 were subjected to physical violence during the last 12 months, while 2.50 per cent of women of this age reported sexual abuse” (UNFPA Ukraine 2017, p. 71). It is assumed that the 2.50 per cent also refers to a 12 months time frame, as the referral time frame is not clearly indicated. The used primary source does not state this information either (UNFPA, GfK Ukraine 2015). Thus, the 2008 data from U.N.Women, the Ukrainian Centre for Social Reforms [UCSR] and the State Statistical Committee [SSC] is used (Center for Social Reforms (UCSR), State Statistical Committee (SSC) [Ukraine] 2008; UN Women 2019g). Like the report, they state a prevalence ratio of ten per cent for physical and sexual IPV within the last 12 months.
- GDP share [%] – 0.23: costs are indicated in US\$(UNFPA Ukraine 2017 p. 49). According to the full coverage scenario model, the overall aggregated cost was around US\$ 208 million

[in detail, as listed US\$ 208,051.9 thousand, or US\$ 208,051,900], (UNFPA Ukraine [2017](#) p. 79) and thus amounted to 0.23 per cent of GDP. The study – published in 2017 – was based on 2015 GDP data (UNFPA Ukraine [2017](#) p. 33). According to the World Bank [2018a](#), the 2015 GDP [in current US\$] was US\$ 91.031 billion [in detail, US\$ 91,031,000,000] and [in current LCU] ₺1.989 trillion [in detail, ₺1,989,000,000,000] (World Bank [2018a](#)).

Overall, developed, developing and emerging countries are analysed separately since both differ in terms of data availability, governance structure, and severeness of the problem. The prevalence of developed countries ranged between 0.60 and 7.10 per cent. [For the 11.13 per cent in KPMG Australia [2016](#), the primary data refers to *since the age of 15*, not to *within the past 12 months* (Australian Bureau of Statistics [2012](#))]. Whereas the ratios for developing nations span between ten and 30 per cent, with African and Southern Asian countries depicting among the highest values. Costs in terms of GDP share differ between 0.03² and 1.07 per cent for developed countries and between 0.23 and 3.39 per cent for developing and emerging countries [see Table [15.1](#)].

Table 15.1.: Overview of GBV prevalence and GDP share.

	Prevalence ratio [%]	GDP share [%]
Developed countries	0.60–7.10 ³	0.03–1.07 ⁴
Developing and emerging countries	10.00–30.00	0.23–3.93

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Section [15.3](#) presents the additional studies that were not included in Section [3.3.2](#) under second-generation costs.

²Without the Danish 0.004 per cent, as the study was in Part I later excluded.

³For the 11.30 per cent in KPMG Australia [2016](#), the primary data refers to *since the age of 15*, not to *within the past 12 months* (Australian Bureau of Statistics [2012](#)).

⁴Ibid.

15.3. Second-generation costs: excluded studies

Table 15.2 gives an overview of which literature was examined in addition to the analysis of the costs of the second-generation, but which was later excluded due to various issues.

Table 15.2.: Excluded second-generation cost literature.

Region	Country	Year	Author	
North America	U.S.	2012	Gelles and Perlman 2012	Method – DALY approach delivers more comprehensive results. ⁵
	U.S.	2012	Fang <i>et al.</i> 2012	Outdated – More recent and updated methods are available. Fang <i>et al.</i> 2017 was chosen.
	U.S.	2009	Zielinski 2009	Scope and method too restricted – Study conducts no costing.
	U.S.	2007	Wang and Holton 2007	Method – DALY approach delivers more comprehensive results. ⁶
	U.S.	2001	Fromm-Reed 2001	Outdated – More recent and updated methods are available.
	U.S.	2000	Forjuoh 2000	Scope too restricted – Only costs for hospitalisation.
	U.S.	2000	Cohen <i>et al.</i> 2000	Scope too restricted – Only [mental] health care treatment costs.
	Canada	2003	Bowlus <i>et al.</i> 2003	Scope too restricted – No costs of pain and suffering.
Europe	Germany	2009	Brzank 2009	Scope too broad – Review of studies.
	Germany	2006	Hellbernd and Brzank 2006	Scope too restricted – Focuses on pregnancy and birth.
South America	Nicaragua	2003	Åsling-Monemi <i>et al.</i> 2003	Scope too restricted – Infant and child mortality.
	Brazil	2002	da Silva Mendonça, Alves, and Filho 2002	Scope too restricted – Only hospital cost.
Africa	South Africa	2009	Seedat <i>et al.</i> 2009	Scope and method too restricted – No cost estimate.

Source: Own representation.

⁵See Fang *et al.*'s paper on South Africa in the next row.

⁶See footnote under Gelles *et al.* 2012 above.

15.4. Summary

Chapter [15](#) presented the detailed calculations and investigations made for the literature review analysis. Initially, the estimates for prevalence and GDP cost-share for industrialised countries and later developing countries were presented. It was then briefly explained in Table [15.2](#), which literature was additionally examined to analyse the second-generation costs, but which was later excluded due to various restrictions.

The following Chapter [16](#) presents the more detailed analyses made for the lost economic output cost category.

16. Lost economic output

16.1. Introduction

Chapter 16 discusses additional details on the lost economic output. There, all-important calculations and steps are summarised, which were not addressed in the main part. Section 16.2 shows the Duvvury *et al.* 2013 approach. This method was selected as adequate in the literature and method section but could not be confirmed in its results. The results of this method are therefore shown in this Appendix. Section 16.2.1 presents the database for the Duvvury *et al.* 2013 method. Section 16.2.2 discusses the Duvvury *et al.* 2013 method results and showcases its weaknesses, and in Section 16.2.3, the results are presented. There, all points are taken up and are summarised. Section 16.3 presents the multiplier data and explains how they differ within the methods of Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Duvvury *et al.* 2013. Specifically, the primary database on which the calculations are derived is presented. Section 16.4 describes the method of Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 in detail. Section 16.5 deals specifically with the database of women, men, NAMPOL, the last and worst incident, the various household categories, and the per capita gross domestic product. It shows how the different case numbers are calculated based on which sources. A distinction is made between the case numbers for women and men. Section 16.6 describes the outcome that has resulted from the method used. The results are presented in various tables. The division is again made between the results for men and women. Section 16.7 provides further information and explanations that did not find a place in the main part. The calculations of mental health problems, physical limitations, information on the QALY-GBV data used, and their portability are presented in detail. Data on physical injury surveys, emotional violence calculations, or underlying data on HIV/AIDS factors are also discussed. In order to continue, Section 16.2 explains the approach of Duvvury *et al.* 2013 and the derivation of case numbers and multipliers.

16.2. Approach of Duvvury *et al.* 2013

Section 3.4 classified the most qualified literature, and Section 5.2 reviewed the methodical approach to compute the lost economic output best. Section 16.2 applies the identified method of Duvvury *et al.* 2013. Duvvury *et al.* calculate the economic impact by estimating the loss of productivity and production using the production data of a few principal sectors to a national economy. In summary,

1. The analytical approach is grounded in the sectoral distribution of women's workforce participation in significant economic areas.

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2. The multi-sectoral approach would be agreeable to analyse the pattern and magnitude of the input of women in diverse sectors of production in Namibia. The analysis exhibits the impact of structural transformation in the economy and women's employment, including their long-term contribution to the gross domestic product. Moreover, according to Duvvury *et al.*, the multi-sectoral approach can reveal the augmented dynamics between GBV and economic growth.
 3. The advantages of the method are that it has few data requirements.¹

$$DV_i = (LFP_i^w \cdot PR) + (LFP_i^m \cdot PR) \quad (16.1)$$

LFP_i^w is the number of women, and LFP_i^m is the number of men employed in sector i . PR reflects the GBV prevalence. The total cases of violence in a sector i are calculated as:

$$TIV_i = DV_i \cdot IR \quad (16.2)$$

DV_i represents the DV cohort in sector i , and IR shows the incidence rate of violence, defined as the average number of incidents. The total lost working days are determined using Equations (16.1) and (16.2):

$$TD_i = (TIV_i \cdot a_i^w \cdot LDVW) + (TIV_i \cdot a_i^m \cdot LDVM) \quad (16.3)$$

TIV_i is the total value from Equation (16.2), which provides the total number of cases in sector i . Furthermore, a_i^w is the proportion of absolute events that lead to absenteeism in women, and a_i^m is the number of events that lead to absenteeism in men. $LDVW$ is the average number of days women miss per incident. In addition, $LDVM$ is the average number of days that men miss per incident.

$$ILDV = \sum (TIV_i \cdot LDVW) + (TIV_i \cdot LDVM) \quad (\text{Equation } 3.5)$$

$$ILDV = \sum (TIV_i \cdot LDVW) + (TIV_i \cdot LDVM) \quad (\text{Equation } 3.5)$$

In order to continue, Section 16.2.1 presents the findings of the Duvvury *et al.* model.

16.2.1. Data

Basic data

Apart from the 2013 Namibian Demographic and Health Survey findings (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 313), the following primary data is utilised:

1. The NCIP&C report, on "Costs of Intimate Partner Violence against Women in the United States," from the National Centre for Injury Prevention and Control, Atlanta in 2003 (Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003). Findings from the Disease

¹Duvvury *et al.* use this equation, which is also presented in Chapter 3. Duvvury *et al.* 2013 establish and apply this calculation within their estimates for the Vietnamese economy.

Control survey are used to crosscheck and underpin the results of Duvvury *et al.* [2013] regarding the lost economic output of stay-at-homes and women who perform household chores or who are not employed for cash.

2. Walby and Allen [2004] findings, in the paper “Domestic violence, sexual assault and stalking: findings from the British Crime Survey.” The underlying structure is used for the calculation of the overall economic loss in Section [16.2.2]

The following paragraph describes the used treatment and case number data.

Treatment cost data

1. The Namibian Paylab [2018] data: the statistics are utilised to compute the average daily gross salary [N\$] in 2018.
2. Trading Economics [2018]; World Bank [2018b] data: the information is applied to compute the economic losses in relation to GDP.
3. A various set of exchange ratios (XE [2018a]; XE [2018b]): the rates are applied to convert the global results to LCUs.

Case number data

1. The 2018 Namibian Labour Force Survey from Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) [2019]: the findings on the economic sectors clustered according to gender are applied.
2. The United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA). Population division [2018] statistics: 2018 census data, on, for instance, the current female population is employed.
3. The World Bank’s overall population (World Bank [2018f]) and labour force data (World Bank [2018d]): the research is used to compute the overall labour capacity available.
4. Namibia Statistics Agency’s “Namibia Household Income and Expenditure Survey (NHIES) 2015/2016 Report” (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) [2016]): the findings are used for crosschecking of primary data sources from the World Bank, as well as of different sets of census data and labour statistics (World Bank [2018d]; World Bank [2018f]).

In order to continue, Section [16.2.2] will sum up the findings.

16.2.2. Calculation of costs

The first step of the Duvvury *et al.* [2013] approach is to estimate the labour force per sector in the market. Table [16.1] reflects the overall number of citizens experiencing sexual and physical violence, clustered to industry.

In brief, the GBV prevalence ratio is multiplied by the number of men and women working in that specific sector. Industries, figures, and percentages of both sexes derive from the 2018 Namibian Statistics Agency’s labour force survey findings (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) [2019]). The next step is to compute the lost days for both men and women. According to Duvvury *et al.* [2013] the figure for both sexes is subdivided into the number of men and women employed in an individual economic sector.

Table [16.2] depicts the figures for men.

The proportion of overall incidents resulting in missed work is multiplied by the number of workdays lost due to GBV, which is 7.8 days for both women and men (Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003)². The average daily gross salary in Namibia dollar [N\$]³ is then utilised to compute the lost economic output for both sexes [see Table 16.3].

The number of women and men employed in the respective sector is linked to the number of citizens experiencing violence, which is 28 per cent⁶ of women and 4.60 per cent of men in Namibia (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 313)⁷. In a third step, as indicated in Table 16.3,

²The 2003 Disease Control study states that the average time lost as a consequence of physical assault was 7.2 days for paid work and 8.4 days for unpaid work, like household chores, for instance. Hence, the time lost is, on average, 7.8 days. Workdays lost resulting from rape are 8.1 days for paid work and 13.5 days for household chores (Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003 p. 26). For reasons of stringency, this estimate employs the data for physical assault rather than rape because the 15.50 per cent ratio in Table 16.1 is related to physical, not to sexual assault since the primary data did not survey the levels of wounding resulting from sexual assault. Further, Duvvury stated in her 2013 research for the World Bank, 5.5 days missed per incident for women and 6.5 days for men (Duvvury *et al.* 2013 p. 36). However, the 2003 Disease Control figures are methodically more robust and therefore were chosen. For instance, the 2003 Disease Control report was based on a sample of 16,000 men and women (Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003 p. 7). In contrast, the 2013 Duvvury study has a sample size of 1,053 women only (Duvvury *et al.* 2013 p. 35).

³The average monthly gross salary in Namibia dollar has been divided by 30 days (Paylab 2018). The lost economic output for men is based on the same daily gross salary as for women. However, research as the 2016 Namibia Labour Force Survey Report (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2017 p. 15) suggests that Namibian men are on average more often employed and receive higher wages than their female counterparts. This conclusion implies that the monthly average wage per head and sector may not be a comprehensive indicator to estimate the lost economic output. Still, the alternative would be to tailor estimates of lost production and productivity to the specific survivor's characteristics such as age, gender, ethnic group, or residence. Although this may be justified theoretically from an economic point of view, the consequence would be a higher valuation of the prevention of crimes against those at higher income levels. For more information, see the subsequent subsections in this Appendix.

⁴Sectors, numbers of both sexes, and ratios are based on the findings of the Namibia Statistics Agency's [NSA] 2018 Labour Force Survey Report (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2019 p. 112).

⁵Ibid.

⁶Overall, 33 per cent of ever-married women aged 15 to 49 reported ever having experienced physical, sexual, or emotional violence from their spouse, and 28 per cent report having experienced such violence in the past 12 months (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 295). Please note that different prevalence ratios are applied in Dolan *et al.* 2005, Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, Duvvury *et al.* 2013. For Duvvury *et al.* 2013 the prevalence ratio of 28 per cent is applied. During the Dolan *et al.* 2005, Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 estimations, the proportion of 17.50 per cent is employed. For more details, see Section 16.3.

⁷In detail, 4.60 per cent of Namibian women aged 15 to 49 have committed physical violence against their partner in the past 12 months (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 313). However, data does not derive from interviews held directly with Namibian men. They originate from surveys with women regarding their violent patterns of behaviour against their intimate partners (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 311).

Table 16.1.: Calculation of the lost economic output, Duvvury *et al.* 2013: women I.

Sector ⁴	Women employed in sector i [numbers]	Women experiencing violence in sector i [28%], [numbers]	Proportion of overall incidents resulting in missed work for women [15.50%], [numbers]
Armed forces	2,495	699	108
Legislators and managers	5,237	1,466	227
Professionals	30,775	8,617	1,336
Technicians and associate professionals	20,464	5,730	888
Clerks	29,375	8,225	1,275
Service and sales	64,358	18,020	2,793
Skilled agriculture	61,589	17,245	2,673
Craft and trade	24,155	6,763	1,048
Machine operators	1,410	395	61
Elementary occupation	116,120	32,514	5,040
Not stated	8,255	2,311	358
Overall	364,233	101,985	15,808

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation based on the Namibia Statistics Agency 2018 Labour Force Survey (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) [2019](#)) and NDHS 2014 data (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#)).

Table 16.2.: Calculation of the lost economic output, Duvvury *et al.* 2013: men I.

Sector ⁵	Men employed in sector i [numbers]	Men experiencing violence in sector i [4.60%], [numbers]	Proportion of overall incidents resulting in missed work for men [5.20%], [numbers]
Armed forces	6,980	321	17
Legislators and managers	6,588	303	16
Professionals	22,256	1,024	53
Technicians and associate professionals	17,538	807	42
Clerks	9,756	449	23
Service and sales	41,415	1,905	99
Skilled agriculture	49,075	2,257	117
Craft and trade	66,277	3,049	159
Machine operators	32,134	1,478	77
Elementary occupation	95,126	4,376	228
Not stated	14,362	661	34
Overall	361,507	16,629	865

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation based on the Namibia Statistics Agency 2018 Labour Force Survey (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) [2019](#)) and NDHS 2014 data (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#)).

this outcome is multiplied by the proportion of overall incidents resulting in missed workdays, which is 15.50 per cent⁸ for women and 5.20 per cent for men.⁹

⁸In sum, 15.50 per cent of women report deep wounds, broken bones, broken teeth, or any other serious injury from physical violence within the past 12 months. It is relevant to note that this figure only includes

Table 16.3.: Calculation of the lost economic output, Duvvury *et al.*: women II.

Sector	Proportion of overall incidents resulting in missed work for women [15.50%] [numbers]	Overall workdays lost for women [7.8 days] [d]	Category ¹⁰	Average daily gross salary in 2018 [N\$]	Lost economic output for women in 2018 [N\$]
Armed forces	108	845	Security and protection	646	545,250
Legislators and managers	227	1,773	Management	1,187	2,104,053
Professionals	1,336	10,418	Economy, finance, accountancy	941	9,800,516
Technicians and associate professionals	888	6,927	Mechanical engineering	860	5,959,243
Clerks	1,275	9,944	Administration	512	5,088,358
Service and sales	2,793	21,786	Commerce	592	12,894,685
Skilled agriculture	2,673	20,849	Agriculture, food industry	847	17,664,060
Craft and trade	1,048	8,177	Service industries.	217	1,771,673
Machine operators	61	477	Electrical and Power Engineering ¹¹	860	410,283
Elementary occupation	5,040	39,309	General labour	208	8,189,363
Not stated	358	–	–	–	–
Total	15,808	120,506			64,427,483

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation based on the Home Office 2004 report (Walby and Allen 2004), the National centre for Injury Prevention and Control survey (Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003), and Paylab data (Paylab 2018).

Table 16.4 depicts the figures for men.

physical and not sexual violence. The data for at-the-moment married women refers to the current husband or partner, and the figures for divorced, separated, or widowed women reference the most recent partner (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 311).

⁹In contrast to the women, the data of men is not available nor reported in Namibia (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 311). Thus, the outcome of other literature is reviewed. Research in Vietnam suggests a ratio of seven per cent (Duvvury *et al.* 2013 p. 36). British literature indicates a proportion of 5.20 per cent. In the U.K., five per cent of men were subject to non-sexual domestic abuse, threats, or force, whereas 0.20 per cent suffered from any form of sexual assault. The 0.20 figure combines minor and more severe incidents (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 44). In line with this study's approach, the lower bound estimate of 5.20 per cent is chosen. Further, the same assumption as for women is made, namely that such forms of abuse result in missed workdays for men too.

¹⁰The categories are derived from the Namibian Paylab 2018 data.

¹¹This is the most similar category.

Table 16.4.: Calculation of the lost economic output, Duvvury *et al.*: men II.

Sector	Proportion of overall incidents resulting in missed workdays for men [5.20%] [numbers]	Overall workdays lost due to violence for men [7.8 days] [in days]	Category ¹²	Average gross daily salary in 2018 [N\$ ¹³]	Lost economic output for men in 2018 [N\$]
Armed forces	17	130	Security and protection	646	84,072
Legislators and managers	16	123	Management	1,187	145,881
Professionals	53	415	Economy, finance, accountancy	941	390,633
Technicians and associate professionals	42	327	Mechanical engineering	860	281,483
Clerks	23	182	Administration	512	93,141
Service and sales	99	773	Commerce	592	457,338
Skilled agriculture	117	916	Agriculture, food industry	847	775,745
Craft and trade	159	1,237	Service industries.	217	267,923
Machine operators	77	600	Electrical and Power Engineering ¹⁴	860	515,347
Elementary occupation	228	1,775	General labour	208	369,755
Not stated	34	–	–	–	–
Total	865	6,477			3,381,320
Overall GDP [% ¹⁵]					67,808,803 0.04

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation based on the Home Office 2004 report (Walby and Allen 2004), the National centre for Injury Prevention and Control survey (Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003), and Paylab data (Paylab 2018).

The overall lost economic output for both women and men is N\$ 67,808,803, which is around 0.04 per cent of the Namibian GDP for 2018. However, during the application of the Duvvury *et al.* 2013 approach, certain shortcomings became evident. A summary of such is listed in Section 16.2.3.

16.2.3. Conclusion

The following shortcomings got apparent during the process of estimation:

¹²Ibid.

¹³Categories are equal to those listed for women in Table 16.3

¹⁴This is the most similar category.

¹⁵The GDP in the current LCU was N\$ 178.052 billion in 2018 (World Bank 2018e).

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1. The approach omits one-quarter of the available labour force: according to the Namibia Household Income and Expenditure Survey, only around half of the population receives salaries and wages in Namibia (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016 p. 98)¹⁶. More than 70 per cent [76.60 per cent] of the labour force receives other forms of income, including salaries and wages¹⁷ and 23.30 per cent do not belong to any economic sector and live from pensions [11 per cent], remittances and grants [9.60 per cent], or drought, and in-kind receipts [2.70 per cent]. Consequently, around a quarter of citizens are not employed in a specific sector and thus are not covered under the Duvvury *et al.* 2013 model¹⁸. Hence, the losses of these citizens are omitted. Indeed, the unemployed and the disabled who benefit from government grants do not have such a significant lost economic output due to GBV. Of course, if the data are put in relation to the GDP per capita, these backgrounds should be taken into account in order to be able to interpret the results correctly [see Chapter 7]. However, leaving such groups out of all costing categories would potentially distort the overall results.
 2. The model does not include the significant black market industry in Africa: the average government grants or pensions were around N\$ 1,250 in 2018 (Izaaks 2018) and the 2018 per capita income per month was N\$ 72,726 [in current LCU] (World Bank 2018e). However, the cost of living compared to the per capita income is high. For instance, the average monthly rent for an 85 m² furnished bedroom was around N\$ 10,929 in 2018 (My Property 2020)¹⁹. Hence, citizens often run their private businesses next to their primary area of employment. Additional income generation activities usually include trading small items, such as foods or working as domestic help (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016). The Duvvury *et al.* 2013 method does not take this additional stream of revenue fully

¹⁶In detail, the report (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016 p. 98) states that:

- Salaries and wages are received from only 53.60 per cent.
- Another half, 46.30 per cent, are reported to be benefiting from:
 - a) pensions [11 per cent],
 - b) subsistence farming [10.60 per cent],
 - c) business income [9.10 per cent],
 - d) remittances and Grants [9.60 per cent],
 - e) drought and in-kind receipts [2.70 per cent],
 - f) commercial farming [0.30 per cent], or
 - g) others [three per cent].

¹⁷According to the Namibia Household Income and Expenditure survey (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016 p. 98), 76.60 per cent receive income from one of the following sources:

- a) salaries and wages [53.60 per cent],
- b) subsistence farming [10.60 per cent],
- c) business income [9.10 per cent],
- d) commercial farming [0.30 per cent], or
- e) others [three per cent].

¹⁸Numbers of both sexes and percentages are chosen based on the findings in the Namibia Statistics Agency's Labour Force 2018 report (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2019) and were crosschecked with the 2016 Survey (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2017 p. 44).

¹⁹The costs of daily living, such as the supply of electricity, are also very high (Breuer 2020).

into account. Thereby, it further increases the gap between actual and predicted losses of income through GBV²⁰

3. High-income inequalities: Namibia is a higher middle-income country (World Bank 2018e). Nonetheless, the country depicts extreme inequalities in income distribution and living standards. For instance, the average per capita consumption of a Khoisan-speaking citizen was N\$ 7,088²¹ per annum. The one of an Oshiwambo citizen was N\$ 23,626²² per annum, and the per capita income of a German-speaking Namibian citizen was around N\$ 199,330 per year²³ (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016, p. 97). Citizens with more substantial per capita income primarily run private businesses such as tourist lodges with revenue streams that are significantly higher than the average Namibian salaries and wages displayed in Tables 16.3 and 16.4. Consequently, there occurs a notable distortion when implementing the Duvvury model, as such disequilibrium is not reflected [proportionally]²⁴
4. Lack of medicinal background in data: in order to estimate the loss of working days, Duvvury *et al.* 2013 utilised interview data from qualitative surveys. However, the gathered data might not reflect a realistic picture. For instance, findings in the Disease Control survey (Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003) indicate that women who stay at home and perform household chores have reported a significantly higher loss of workdays than their female counterparts who are employed for cash. In summary, salaried survivors return earlier to work than stay-at-homes. The rationale behind this may be that women fear losing their occupation and consequently report back earlier, although they are not fully recovered. Precise medicinal data that states what kind of adverse health state accounts for what average healing period – for instance, a broken nose or bone requires 21 days of healing – would deliver a more precise outcome. Such data could take out the rationale found in qualitative interviews where survivors reported back earlier to work due to financial strains, although not fully healed yet and thus would deliver more objective information.

Due to these shortcomings²⁵ which became evident during and after applying the method, the work of Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 is employed for this context, as the approach displays certain methodical advancements to estimate the lost economic output from productivity. Section 16.3 explains the different set of multipliers used.

²⁰It needs to be added that these costs are also not fully taken into account in Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005

²¹This was around € 420 for the survey period.

²²This was € 1,400 for the survey period.

²³In Euro-terms, this was € 12,000 for the survey period.

²⁴It must be added that Dolan *et al.*; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns address these costs a little more in their model but do not fully take them into account either.

²⁵In particular, the listed point four leads to an underestimation of the costs compared to the method of Dolan *et al.*; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns.

16.3. Different multiplier in Dolan *et al.* 2005; Duvvury *et al.* 2013

In both the Duvvury and the Dolan-Dubourg [2005] (Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Duvvury *et al.* 2013) approach, a part of the calculation is grounded in the 2014 NDHS data (MoHSS and ICF International 2014).²⁶

The 2013 GBV module reviews information on all relationship statuses in the age range of 15 to 49 for citizens who suffer from GBV. The subsample includes one woman per household. Designed weights were utilised to ensure that the GBV cohort was nationally representative and correct for selection bias (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 297). At the time of research, the NDHS was the only national representative dataset available on GBV.

Different prevalence ratios are applied during the process of calculation for the models of Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Duvvury *et al.* 2013:

1. Duvvury *et al.* 2013 for Duvvury *et al.*, 2013, the prevalence ratio of 28 per cent is applied. The 28 per cent ratio expresses best the GBV term applied in the Duvvury *et al.* 2013 paper. In detail, overall, 33 per cent of ever-married women aged 15 to 49 report ever having experienced physical, sexual, or emotional violence from their spouse, and 28 per cent reported having experienced such violence in the past 12 months (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 295).
2. Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; in contrast, in the Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 estimations, a percentage of 17.50 per cent is employed. Why was a 17.50 per cent ratio chosen over a 20 per cent ratio?
 - The 20 per cent ratio symbolises the present offset of spousal violence: 20 per cent of ever-married women in Namibia have experienced physical or sexual violence. Their current or most recent husband enacted the abuse over the past 12 months (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 310). However, this study's definition goes beyond spousal violence and includes GBV enacted by third persons such as stepfathers, police, or soldiers. Thus, another ratio was chosen:
 - Namely, 17.50 per cent²⁷ of women who have experienced physical and sexual violence by all intimate partners, family members, or third parties over the past 12 months.²⁸ In order to continue, Section 16.4 depicts more detail on the approach of Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005.

²⁶See Chapter 6 for more detailed data and Section 7.3 for more details on which data is specifically employed in each category.

²⁷For more information on the composition of the 17.50 per cent, see Section 6.4

²⁸The occurrence of violence enacted by third parties such as police or soldiers is less frequent; hence the ratio is smaller than the DV probability of 20 per cent.

16.4. Approach of Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005

16.5. Calculation of case numbers

For a general review of the primary data used, see Chapter 6. Section 16.5 depicts more in-debt information on the different datasets used within the calculations.

Data on women's age

The GBV definition of this paper includes perpetrators, as from family, siblings, neighbours, or strangers as well. As a result, being single does not imply that GBV does not occur. Therefore, instead of choosing an *ever-partnered women* baseline cohort, the *female population [15 to 49 years of age]* baseline-dataset is used to calculate physical and sexual violence, respectively (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b). The overall decision to choose the 15 to 49-year cohort was made to align the calculations to the NDHS baseline study outcome. The report used this age range based on the U.N. Millennium Development Goals [MDGs], which internationally agreed to measure the occurrence of GBV within this age span (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. xix) 29

Data on men

The lost economic output category also covers the cost of men. Nonetheless, physical violence data for men exists only based on the “percentage of Namibian women aged 15 to 49 who said to have committed physical violence against their partners in the past 12 months” (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 46). Concrete, the NDHS estimates that 6.20 per cent of women have ever, and 4.20 per cent have committed physical violence against their partners in the past 12 months (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 313). However, as stated, the men were not asked personally how many incidents of physical abuse they have suffered. Therefore figures have to be read with precaution.

Data from NAMPOL

Domestic and sexual violence is internationally the most underreported crime (United Nations (UN), Secretary-General 2016 p. 6). It also applies to Namibia (Hubbard *et al.* 2006 p. 4). Therefore, police records constitute an insufficient basis for computing multipliers 30 Hence, the findings from the 2014 NDHS (MoHSS and ICF International 2014) is utilised rather than NAMPOL statistics (The Namibian Police 2018). Table 16.5 gives an overview of the detailed data that is used to calculate specific losses.

²⁹For more information, see Development Goals (United Nations (UN) 2019).

³⁰See Chapter 6 for more information.

Table 16.5.: Overview of specific adverse health states prevalences.

Types of violence	Physical violence [%] [in the past 12 months]	Sexual violence [%] [in the past 12 months]
Cuts, bruises, or aches	27.70	30.00
Eye injuries, sprains, dislocations, or burns	19.30	29.00
Deep wounds, broken bones, broken teeth, or any other serious injury	15.50	26.70
Any of these injuries	36.00	44.40

Source: Own representation based on the 2014 NDHS (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 311).

Data from Dolan *et al.*; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns

The 2014 NDHS indeed provides a detailed analysis, but certain data is too widespread to be applied. For instance, physical injuries resulting from DV, including their ratios, are stated in the NDHS (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 305, 311). Nonetheless, often more detailed statistics are needed to conduct proper assessments based on the chosen method. Hence, the findings from Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 are utilised in certain cases. [See Table 7.3 for further information].

Data on the last year and the worst incident

1. The data on the last year: last year's dataset, including violent acts within the last 12 months, is used. Because it may be possible that events long ago have been overlooked, compared to more recent events [within a 12-months time frame]. In return, this choice may have led to a higher under-reporting of violent incidents (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 15) and an underestimation of costs. Over the many years of a lifespan, there are more opportunities for GBV incidents than in just one year. The *last year's* selection thus presents a small subset of *since ever*. Nonetheless, in summary, the last year's datasets are less likely to be biased through the loss of memory and thus have been applied.
2. Data on the worst incident: Walby's final probabilities only reflect injuries sustained in the worst episodes of domestic abuse (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 34). In line with the argumentation on data from last year in the previous bullet point, DV typically starts early in a relationship. If domestic abuse is a repeated and frequent act, it began during the first year of a partnership for 49 per cent of the females and 39 per cent of male complainants. Generally, it usually starts during the first five years of a relationship for 90 per cent of British women and 85 per cent of British men (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 63). The same pattern has been identified for the Namibian context as well (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 310). However, also the NDHS data report only on one incident, namely the worst. As a result, it leaves out [other] repeated events that occurred during that last year's period. This choice is continuously made in international research too, following the same reasoning applied in the previous sections, as loss of memory and recall may have led to distortion and bias. Notwithstanding, in reality, events are likely to be higher, and individuals suffer from more than one, sometimes many, episodes of abuse (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 38). Therefore, this calculation is likely to present an underestimation of occurred expenses.
3. Incidents that cannot be accounted for: according to Walby and Allen, there is a smaller group, namely, the cohort of the heavily abused. Such occurrences are observed within the Namibian context as well. On average, 3.14 per cent of Namibian women aged 15–49

have experienced physical violence often in the past 12 months (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 298). Consequently, potential additional cumulative injuries are not captured, which eventually may have led to a further underestimation of expenses (Walby and Allen 2004, p. 25). Further, it is possible that separate incidents, like emotional abuse, sexual violence, or physical violence, occurred together in one event as well, and later they are summarised into one single episode by the survivor. Moreover, it is also likely that one case of abuse spreads over several hours. Thus, there could be an underestimation of the resulting adverse mental and physical health states too (Walby and Allen 2004, p. 21). However, the approach of the *last year's and the worst incident* has been chosen, in line with the international stance, as the cohort of the more heavily abused may cause bias.

Data on household categories

The NDHS collects data on individual households only. Thus, individuals who are not living in private homes were excluded from the survey. This may affect estimates, as some of the most recent or heavily abused are more likely to be living in women's shelters or other temporary accommodation, be staying with friends or being homeless (Walby and Allen 2004, p. 9).

Total labour force

Concerning the GDP per capita data, the overall number of days off is multiplied by N\$ 215,³¹ which is an estimate of the average daily output per head in Namibia for 2018 (World Bank 2018c). Calculating the lost economic output in this way assumes that survivors are drawn from the entire population at random. This procedure recognises that survivors may not be members of the total labour force available. Nonetheless, it still accounts for their productivity loss, if they are stay-at-homes or housewives. It moreover takes into account the non-productive time, such as weekends or out of office hours (Dolan *et al.* 2005, Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005).³² Nevertheless, Namibia is a middle-income country with extreme inequalities in revenue distribution and living standards among the various ethnic groups and regions (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016). Hence, differences and regional discrepancies are not fully acknowledged by the method. However, this shortfall is recognised. Regional breakdowns of the Namibian GDP are not produced as quickly as the national figure (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2018), which means that this approach allows the estimates to be kept more readily up-to-date. Further, regarding the GDP per capita-share, as said in the main part I, only around 70 per cent of citizens receive a GDP per capita income, which is at its level similar to the national median figure (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016, p. 98). Besides, considering these regional discrepancies would imply that policymakers may overlook areas with groups of citizens with a

³¹In the calculations that were finally included in the main part in Chapter 7, another GDP per capita rate of N\$ 199 was used, as this was based on newer values. This calculation in Section 16.2.2 has not been adapted to the new rate. They were only utilised in this section of the study to show that the Duvvury *et al.* 2013 method described is disadvantageous, [which could also be showcased with the old value]. Note, in Tables 7.3 and 7.4 in Section 7.4 the calculations are based on the 2018 Namibian GDP per capita [current LCU] of N\$ 72,725,957 (World Bank 2018e), which was divided by 365.25 days. This resulted in a Namibian GDP per capita and day in 2018 of around N\$ 199 per day.

³²For a more detailed explanation, see Chapters 5 and 6. However, these advantages are at the expense of omitting other factors, such as regional discrepancies.

lower GDP per capita output. For instance, a woman who became disabled through GBV may not exhibit a high economic value to society or policymakers. [See, for example, the article – A broken life – ruined by Gender-Based Violence] (Nangisai 2016).

Case numbers for men and women

The following tables describe other case numbers that were not included in the main text but were still important as building blocks.

Table 16.6 reflects the used case number data for both men and women.

Table 16.6.: Namibian female population in 2018.

Category	Women [numbers]
The current female population, in 2018	1,328,333 (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b)
The current female population 15 to 49 years, in 2018	689,222 (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b)
The current female population 15 to 49 years, suffering from physical and sexual violence [17.50%], in 2018 ³³	120,614
The current female population, 15 to 49 years, suffering from physical violence [13.80%], in 2018 ³⁴	95,113
The current female population, 15 to 49 years, suffering from physical violence [13.80%], and who received a GDP per capita income similar to the median value, in 2018 ³⁵	70,479

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation based on UNDESA data (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b).

In the following, Table 16.7 displays the baseline data used for men.

³³For more information on the composition of the 17.50 per cent, see Section 6.4

³⁴In detail, 13.80 per cent of 689,222 Namibian women aged 15 to 49 often have or sometimes have experienced physical violence (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 298) in the past 12 months before the survey.

³⁵It is 74.10 per cent of 95,113 individuals. Only 74.10 per cent, according to the Namibia Household Income and Expenditure Survey, receives a GDP per capita income (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016 p. 98). Since 25.90 per cent does not belong to any specific economic sector and live from remittances and grants [9.60 per cent], drought, and in-kind receipts [2.70 per cent], subsistence farming [10.60 per cent], or others [3 per cent].

Table 16.7.: Namibian male population in 2018.

Category	Men [numbers]
The current male population [numbers], in 2018	1,259,465 (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b)
The current male population 15 to 49 years in 2018 ³⁶	660,080 (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b)
The current male population 15 to 49 years, living in a union, in 2018 ³⁷	224,427
The current male population, 15 to 49 years, living in a union, subjected to GBV physical violence in the past 12 months [4.60%], in 2018 ³⁸	10,324
The current male population, 15 to 49 years, living in a union, subjected to GBV physical violence in the past 12 months [4.60%] and who received a GDP per capita income similar to the median value, in 2018 ³⁹	7,650
The current male population, 15 to 49 years, living in a union, subjected to GBV sexual violence in the past 12 months, in 2018 ⁴⁰	–

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation based on UNDESA data (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b).

In order to continue, Section 16.6 showcases the overall results.

16.6. Calculation of costs

The following two tables describe the economic losses for men and women in a different type of calculation. In the main text, the factor of 74.10 per cent was used for each individual cost category. This describes the cohort found in employment. In the following two tables, a more broad approach was taken, and the starting quota for women was multiplied by the rate of

³⁶This age cohort is chosen as the U.N. development goals on GBV, mainly includes the age cohort 15 to 49 (UN Women 2018a).

³⁷The percentage of men who currently lives in a union is 34 per cent (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 47).

³⁸In detail, 4.60 per cent of Namibian women aged 15–49 have committed physical violence against their partners during the past 12 months (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 313).

³⁹However, only 74.10 per cent of citizens receive a GDP per capita income, which is at its level similar to the national median figure (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016 p. 98). Hence, the figure for 7,650 individuals is employed.

⁴⁰Data on men is only available for physical, not for sexual violence (MoHSS and ICF International 2014).

74.10 per cent. The results are briefly presented below. They were not used in the main text because the other approach gave more detailed results.

For men, the following calculations are based on the number of cases presented in the previous section, see Table 16.7 which only considers the men who are suffering from GBV and are in a relationship. This approach was rejected in the main text, and the cohort of all men affected by GBV was chosen, regardless of their relationship status.

Table 16.8 presents the calculated lost output for women.

Table 16.8.: Results of the lost economic output with altered GDP share: women.

Forms of Health state ⁴¹ violence	Probability per incident [%]	Women [numbers]	Time off work [d]	Lost economic output [N\$] ⁴²
Physical violence		70,479 ⁴³		
Mental or emotional problems	0.31 ⁴⁴	[21,848] ⁴⁵		
Acute stress disorder	0.9499 ⁴⁶	20,753	21	93,705,117
Mild/ moderate post-traumatic stress disorder	0.0351	767	257	42,380,585
Severe post-traumatic stress disorder	0.0150	328	257	18,139,850
Physical health problems ⁴⁷				
Minor injury	[0.46] ⁴⁸	[32,420]	–	–
Minor bruising or black eye	0.40	28,192	3	18,183,582
Scratches	0.13	9,162	1	1,969,888
Other physical injuries	0.04	2,819	3	1,818,358
Moderate injuries	[0.20]	[14,096]	–	–
Severe bruising	0.15	10,572	10	22,729,478
Severe injuries	[0.06]	[4,229]	–	–
Internal injuries	0.02	1,410	6	1,818,358
Broken bones/teeth ⁴⁹	[0.06]	[4,229] ⁵⁰	–	–

Continue on next page

⁴¹Based on the findings of Walby, Dolan, and Dubourg (Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Walby 2004; Walby and Allen 2004, p. 38).

⁴²The Namibian GDP per capita in the current LCU was N\$ 78,479.66 in 2018. Based on the overall 365.25 days per year, this is around N\$ 215 per day (World Bank 2018e).

⁴³For insights into the calculation, see the paragraph on case numbers.

⁴⁴Walby and Allen 2004, p. 34 do not provide a ratio.

⁴⁵Thirty-one per cent of overall 70,479 women, 15 to 49 years, who suffered such harm were 21,848 women. For further details, see the footnote under mental or emotional problems in Table 7.3 or Table 16.9.

⁴⁶Out of 21,848 women. For further details, see the footnotes under “Acute stress disorder” in Table 7.3.

⁴⁷For further details, see the footnotes under “Physical health problems” in Table 7.3.

⁴⁸Out of 70,479 women. The number serves as a baseline for all health states under minor injury, moderate injuries, and severe injuries. All probabilities, from minor bruising or black eye, until internal injuries are derived from Walby and Allen 2004, p. 34.

⁴⁹For details, see footnote under “Broken bones/teeth” in Table 7.3.

⁵⁰For details, see footnote under “Broken bones/teeth” in Table 7.3. The proportions in the rows – 0.4754 for broken bones, 0.2125 for a broken nose, 0.1484 for broken or lost teeth, and 0.1638 for chipped teeth are calculated based on a cohort of 4,229 women. The number 4,229 is the six per cent of 70,479 women who, in total, suffered from GBV.

Continue Table 16.8

Forms of violence	Health state	Probability per incident [%]	Women [numbers]	Time off work [d]	Lost economic output [N\$]
	Broken bones	0.4754	2,010	31	13,398,116
	Broken nose	0.2125	898	11	2,124,835
	Broken or lost teeth	0.1484	627	2	269,786
	Chipped teeth	0.1638	693	2	297,844
Sexual violence ⁵¹			[18,292]		
	Mental or emotional problems ⁵²		[18,292] ⁵³		
	Acute stress disorder	1.000	18,292	21	82,588,380
	Mild/moderate post-traumatic stress disorder	0.343	6,274	257	346,678,490
	Severe post-traumatic stress disorder	0.147	2,689	257	148,576,496
	Drug abuse	0.023	421	835	75,529,040
	Alcohol abuse	0.018	329	417	29,519,447
	Depression [moderate] – short-term	0.200	3,658	89	70,003,484
	Suicide	0.001	18	6,421	25,252,380
	Obesity/eating disorder	0.050	915	835	164,193,565
	Anxiety	0.050	915	259	50,929,501
	Sexual dysfunction	0.780	14,268	30	92,027,052
	Unwanted pregnancy	0.025	457	- ⁵⁴	-
	Physical health problems		[18,292]		
	Broken bones	0.037	677	31	4,510,899
	Minor bruise/black eye	0.192	3,512	3	2,265,281
	Severe bruising	0.111	2,030	10	4,365,386
	Other injury	0.033	604	3	389,345
	HIV diagnoses ⁵⁵	0.2580	4,719	1,690	1,714,770,736
	Gonorrhoea	0.040	732	3	471,934
	Chlamydial infection	0.020	366	3	235,967
	Trichomoniasis	0.120	2,195	3	1,415,801
	Bacterial vaginosis	0.190	3,475	3	2,241,685
	Abortion	0.025	457	7	688,237

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⁵¹In detail, 3.70 per cent of Namibian women aged 15 to 49 had experienced sexual violence in the past 12 months before the NDHS took place, including from perpetrators such as [former] partner/husbands, as well as other siblings [father, mother, brother], employer/person to work with, or, and police/soldiers (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 299). Based on the estimates before, this is an overall number of 24,685 women. Sexual assault cases were not estimated due to a lack of valid data (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). However, according to the Namibia Household Income and Expenditure Survey (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016 p. 98), only 74.10 per cent of citizens receive a GDP per capita income, which is at its level similar to the national median figure. Hence, the number of 18,292 women is used for the estimates.

⁵²All probabilities are derived from Dolan's (Dolan *et al.* 2005 p. 974); Dubourg's (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 p. 34) rape-category findings.

⁵³This figure serves as a baseline for all adverse health states listed under mental or emotional problems and physical health problems.

⁵⁴Detailed data was not available. See Section 7.5.3 paragraph "Unwanted pregnancy" for more details.

⁵⁵For details, see Section 6.4

Continue Table 16.8

Forms of Health state violence	Probability per incident [%]	Women [numbers]	Time off work [d]	Lost economic output [N\$]
Miscarriage ⁵⁶	0.006	0.006	7	165,177
Overall loss [N\$]				3,036,078,556

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.
Source: Own representation.

Table 16.9 states the findings for men.

Table 16.9.: Results of the lost economic output with altered GDP share: men.

Form of Health state violence	Probability per incident [%]	Men [numbers]	Time off work [days]	Lost economic output [N\$]
Physical violence		7,650 ⁵⁷		
Mental or emotional problems	0.09 ⁵⁸	[689] ⁵⁹		
Acute Stress disorder	0.9499 ⁶⁰	654	21	2,952,880
Mild/moderate PTSD	0.0351	24	257	1,333,807
Severe PTSD	0.0150	10	257	571,632
Physical health problems ⁶¹				
Minor injury	[0.41] ⁶²	[3,137]		
Minor bruising or black eye	0.21	1,607	3	1,036,193
Scratches	0.25	1,913	1	411,188
Other physical injuries	0.03	230	3	148,028
Moderate injuries	[0.14]	[1,071]		
Severe bruising	0.05	383	10	822,375
Bleeding from cuts	0.11	842	2	361,845
Internal injuries	0.01	77	6	98,685

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⁵⁶This paper does not compute the consequences of an unwanted pregnancy. Dolan *et al.* 2005 p. 974 provide a ratio for the European context, though. However, the figure cannot be transferred to the Southern African situation. For more information, read Section 7.5.3

⁵⁷For insights into the calculation, see the paragraph on case number data.

⁵⁸Walby and Allen 2004 p. 34 do not provide a ratio.

⁵⁹In detail, 689 men have mental or emotional problems, nine per cent of overall, 7,650 men suffer from such harm. The factor 0.09 symbolises the overall proportion of mental or emotional harm derived from physical violence. The figure is based on Walby and Allen 2004 p. 34. However, Walby and Allen 2004 do not provide further information. In contrast, Dolan *et al.* 2005, Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 state detailed probabilities. For the exact calculations, see Table 16.9

⁶⁰Out of 689 men. For further details, see Table 7.4, under Physical violence, especially the footnotes under mental or emotional problems.

⁶¹The Walby 2004 figures of minor injuries for men is 0.41, for moderate injuries, it is 0.14, and for severe injuries, it is 0.01. However, these ratios are not utilised, as Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 34 do not provide the particular time off work[days]. For further details, see Tables 7.3 and 7.4

⁶²Out of 7,650 men. For further details, see Tables 7.3 and 7.4

Continue Table 16.9

Form of violence	Health state	Probability per incident [%]	Men [numbers]	Time off work [days]	Lost economic output [N\$]
	Broken bones/teeth ⁶³	[0.009]	[69] ⁶⁴	[1]	
	Broken bones	0.4754	33	31	218,141
	Broken nose	0.2125	15	11	34,595
	Broken or lost teeth	0.1484	10	2	4,393
	Chipped teeth	0.1638	11	2	4,849
Sexual violence ⁶⁵			–		
			Overall loss men	[N\$]	7,998,609
			Overall loss women	[N\$]	3,036,078,556
			∑ overall loss	[N\$]	3,044,077,165
			Share of GDP	[%] ⁶⁶	1.71

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Section 16.7 provides more information and additional explanations of calculations.

16.7. Further explanations

Section 16.7 offers more details on the calculation of mental and physical health problems, with further explanations on QALY data, physical injuries, emotional violence, and the HIV prevalence ratio.

The economic costs of mental health problems

Table 16.10 reflects the calculations of mental health issues in more detail.

⁶³Walby provides only a ratio for broken bones/teeth resulting from physical violence, which is 0.009 for men. Hence, the figures of Dolan *et al.* 2005, Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 for the category of wounding are used (again) and are set into relation to the Walby's (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 34) overall proportion of 0.009. The objective is to keep calculations as close as possible to the outcome figures derived from GBV research specifically. For more details, see Table 7.3 or Table 7.4.

⁶⁴The objective is to keep calculations as close as possible to the Walby findings derived from GBV research specifically. Thus, the probabilities are set in relation to Walby's (Walby and Allen 2004 p. 34) total factor for broken bones and teeth as a consequence of GBV, which is, as said, 0.90 per cent [0.009] of men. Hence, the proportions in the rows, 0.4754 for broken bones, 0.2125 for a broken nose, 0.1484 for broken or lost teeth, and 0.1638 for chipped teeth are calculated based on a cohort of 69 men. The number 69 is the 0.90 per cent of 7,650 men who, in total, were subjected to GBV.

⁶⁵The census data was too small to conduct estimates for sexual violence (MoHSS and ICF International 2014).

⁶⁶The GDP in the current LCU was N\$ 178.052 billion in 2018 (World Bank 2018e).

Table 16.10.: Stress disorder calculations.

Categories ⁶⁷	Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns ²⁰⁰⁵ figures	Used probabilities ⁶⁸
Acute Stress disorder	0.5500	0.9499
Mild/moderate post-traumatic stress disorder	0.0203	0.0351
Severe post-traumatic stress disorder	0.0087	0.0150
Sum	0.5790	1.0000

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.
Source: Own representation.

In addition, the next paragraph explains further details of the physical health calculations.

The economic costs of physical health problems

Table 16.11 states more information on the physical health state computations.

Table 16.11.: Calculations on broken bones.

Categories ⁶⁹	Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns ²⁰⁰⁵ figures	Probabilities ⁷⁰
Broken bones	0.0801	0.4754
Broken nose	0.0358	0.2125
Broken or lost teeth	0.0250	0.1484
Chipped teeth	0.0276	0.1638
Sum	0.1685	1.0000

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.
Source: Own representation.

The following paragraph explains the details of the QALY data calculation.

⁶⁷Walby and Allen²⁰⁰⁴ do not provide further detailed data. Hence, other options are explored. Dolan *et al.*; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns offer more specific probabilities for mental harm in the category of wounding. See Dolan [2005] (Dolan *et al.* ²⁰⁰⁵ p. 974); Dubourg (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns ²⁰⁰⁵ p. 34). It is assumed that the adverse health state output deriving from physical violence is equal to wounding. Consequently, the wounding probabilities are transferred and applied.

⁶⁸In the second step, the results are set in relation to the primary findings of Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns²⁰⁰⁵ which are depicted in the first column. In summary, all adverse health states have an overall probability of 0.5790. For example, according to Dolan *et al.* ²⁰⁰⁵; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns²⁰⁰⁵, acute stress disorder has a probability of 0.5500. Thus, for instance, the following was computed: 0.5500 of 0.5790 is 0.9499. The figures are indicated with four decimal places in the original source. Therefore, these computations are also provided in such a way to avoid any possible distortion.

⁶⁹See Table 16.9 Stress disorder calculation.

⁷⁰In summary, all adverse health states have an overall probability of 0.1685. For example, according to Dolan *et al.* ²⁰⁰⁵; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns²⁰⁰⁵, broken bones have a likelihood of 0.0801 specifically. Thus, the following was computed 0.0801 of 0.1685 is 0.4754. For more information, see Table 16.10

QALY data

Dolan *et al.* [2005], Bolling, Mattinson, and Myhill [2002], Budd *et al.* [2000] in Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] have surveyed the majority of the primary data. Adjustment weights from the disability measurements of the Global Burden of Disease survey, by Murray and Lopez [1996], Tab. 4.4 were utilised. However, the weight was estimated by Murray and Lopez already in 1996. The need for more recent data is acknowledged. Regarding the transferability of GBV-QALY data, in general, the research found that specific GBV patterns are observed to be similar worldwide (Heise, Pitanguy, and Germain [1994]). The García-Moreno *et al.* [2013] report on “Global and regional estimates of violence against women: prevalence and health effects of intimate partner violence and non-partner sexual violence,” developed by the World Health Organization, the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine and the South African Medical Research Council, displays the first global systematic analysis of such kind. The survey incorporated all published and unpublished global research of GBV and had no restrictions on language or the year of publication. It identifies similar patterns on the impact of GBV onto selected health states outcomes worldwide, such as AIDS/HIV, sexually transmitted infections, reduced birth weight, premature birth, [induced] abortion and mental impacts as alcohol abuse, suicide, and depression, as well as death from homicide (García-Moreno *et al.* [2013] p. 21). For instance, concerning fatal injuries [homicides], based on an overall of 226 different papers, capturing 1,121 evaluations across 65 nations from 1982 to 2011, a median prevalence of intimate partner homicide of approximately 13 per cent has been computed (García-Moreno *et al.* [2013] p. 23 ff.). Hence, according to research, GBV has globally similar consequences on individuals’ physical and mental health states, and therefore a transferability of QALY data is assumed in this paper.

The following paragraphs describe further details on the estimated losses due to physical harm and HIV/AIDS.

Calculations of physical injuries

Dolan *et al.* [2005], Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005], Walby [2004], Walby and Allen [2004] provide the category data to estimate the lost economic output based on a detailed review of several adverse health states resulting from physical injuries. Nonetheless, for the Namibian context, such information is not available. The 2014 NDHS (MoHSS and ICF International [2014] p. 311) reflects various physical health consequences of GBV. Still, it did not provide a detailed review of injuries needed to carry out economic estimates. For more information, see Table 7.4. As mentioned before, the Namibian GBV ratios are higher than in industrialised countries.⁷¹ However, Walby’s findings and the Namibian research show a similar outcome, in terms of ethnic, urban, and rural ratios or age, as explained in Chapter 6. Therefore, certain European baseline data is utilised if local information was not available.

⁷¹In detail, 31.50 per cent of Namibian women have experienced physical violence since the age of 15 (MoHSS and ICF International [2014] p. 298), whereas 21 per cent of British women have experienced at least one incident of non-sexual domestic threat or force since the age of 16 (Walby and Allen [2004] p. vii).

In order to continue, the subsequent paragraphs shortly illustrate the calculations of emotional violence.

Calculations of emotional violence

Namibian prevalence ratios of emotional violence between spouses are surveyed (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 305). However, detailed data on its impact on an individuals' physical and emotional well-being is neither given by the NDHS (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 311) nor by Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Walby and Allen 2004. As a result, the cost could not be calculated, and more research is necessary in this regard.

Calculations of HIV prevalence ratios

In summary, the HIV estimates from Europe cannot be transferred to the Southern African context due to the higher African prevalence ratios. Due to an increased HIV ratio, the figure given by Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Walby and Allen 2004 of 0.000001 is not applied. Instead, the Jewkes *et al.* 2010 estimates for the South African context of 25.80 per cent are used, as they are transferable, according to Jewkes 2018⁷²

In the continuing, a summary of this chapter is provided.

Summary

In summary, Chapter 16 dealt with the following: the method of Duvvury *et al.* 2013 is initially presented. However, during the calculations and the concrete data surveying, weaknesses in the Namibian application became evident. In detail, the approach calculates only a limited scope of this paper's context and does not reflect the overall cost profile of Namibia. Therefore, these calculations have been removed from Chapter 7. The tables shown in Chapter 16 contain rounding differences in the totals. Since the results presented are based on a large number of sub-calculations. Due to the differences in the methods of Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Duvvury *et al.* 2013 different multiplier data were used for the respective models. The reasons for this use are based on the theoretical foundations of this study. Section 16.4 provided further information on the method of Dolan *et al.*; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns; Duvvury *et al.*, and the database from which the calculations are derived was explained in more detail. Section 16.4 stated further why the Dolan *et al.*; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns approach was chosen over the model of Duvvury *et al.* In summary; it can be said that some data restrictions and obstacles posed particular challenges to apply the method of Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005. However, in general, the calculations are based on valid national and international sets of data.

In order to continue, Chapter 17 presents additional information and assumptions made within the health service cost calculations.

⁷²For further details, read Section 6.4

17. Health service costs

17.1. Introduction

The following part focuses on the detailed data basis used within the category of the health service costs. Section 17.2 presents the calculation of the case numbers based on the NDHS data (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). In addition, further information regarding the time frame concerning violence among spouses, the individual ratios used in the calculations, and some explanatory supplements regarding men are given.

17.2. Calculation of case numbers

Time frame

The NDHS was published in 2014. However, data was surveyed from 2012 to 2013 (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). As a result, the ratios and data can be compared to the NAMPOL records¹ since the police data was surveyed between 2012 and 2015 too. At the point of research, no more up-to-date data was available.² Further, trends in sexual assaults are challenging to estimate due to a high degree of underreporting³ and thus, institutions tend to decline to predict trends in sexual violence.⁴ Hence, the estimates are based on both large-panel NAMPOL statistics and the NDHS findings from 2012 to 2015.

Spousal violence

NDHS data on wounding and common assaults used in Table 8.4 were surveyed for partnered women only. Thus, the proportions of injuries are only available for ever-married women [in the age range of 15 to 49] (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 311). However, this would leave out other perpetrators such as siblings or police officers, which are included in this paper's GBV definition too.⁵ Hence, a strict application of these ratios would narrow down the subsample significantly and would only take into account 43.30 per cent of women who have ever been

¹See Table 8.5

²The figures are inflated to 2018 values. For more information, see Table 8.2

³Overall, only one out of around 27 cases [3.71 per cent] is reported to NAMPOL. See Section 6.4

⁴See the U.S. Brennan Center for Justice 2018 report.

⁵A more extensive GBV definition is chosen in this paper. It goes beyond the mere notion of GBV, as it takes into account violence enacted by third parties, as from other relatives, strangers, or soldiers as well. Please read Chapter 2 for more information.

married or partnered⁶ Therefore, the ratios are applied to all women aged 15 to 49 who have experienced violence in the 12 months preceding the survey in 2013⁷

Whole unit

The ratios do not represent a whole unit; the proportion in Table 8.4 column 3 did not sum up to 100 per cent. The reasons are, among other things, the following:

1. Double counting: during a single incident, multiple crime categories can occur. For instance, sexual offences and wounding could take place together.
2. The police or the survivor may have left out specific crime information: for instance, sexual offences and physical assault could have occurred, but the survivor may have reported only a sexual assault case. Another reason could be, due to trauma, emotional stress, memory loss, or cultural beliefs, the affected person may not see the wounding or sexual offence as a crime. Further, a homicide and a sexual offence case may have occurred, but the police just registered the homicide case, for instance.

Further, there are only NAMPOL case numbers no NDHS ratios for homicide. Sexual assault was calculated as a different category and is thus separate from the physical violence crime categories.

Men

The calculations are only conducted for women because, for men, there are no proportions of the specific physical harm, such as wounding or common assault, that they may have encountered through violence enacted by their female partners (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 312–314). Further, in general, no data on sexual assault is available for men⁸

Conversion of Bangladesh Taka in US\$

Siddique 2011 p. 50 indicates a GDP share of 2.10 per cent based on the national 2010 GDP. Hence, the underlying GDP figure has to be estimated. The 2010 GDP for Bangladesh is only indicated in current US\$ at the World Bank's database. Thus, the conversion from US\$ into ৳ Taka was conducted, in Table 17.1

⁶The NDHS DV-sub-sample includes an overall of 2,226 women aged 15 to 49 years (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 297). The number of ever-married women from that subsample is 963 women (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 305). The ratio of 963/2226 is 43.30 per cent. It means that 43.30 per cent of women aged 15 to 49 years and who experienced violence in the 12 months preceding the survey in 2013 currently are or have been married.

⁷Possible distortions are acknowledged.

⁸See Section 16.5 for more information.

Table 17.1.: Conversion of Bangladesh Taka into U.S. Dollar.

2010 GDP Bangladesh [current US\$ in trillion] ⁹	2010 GDP, in Bangladesh [₳, in trillion] ¹⁰	Overall costs, in Bangladesh [₳, in trillion] ¹⁰	GDP share [%] [overall costs] ¹⁰	GDP share [%] [health costs] ¹¹
66 ¹²	7 ¹³	0.14 ¹⁴	2.1 ¹⁵	0.04 ¹⁶

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

Summary

Chapter 17 focused on the detailed data basis applied within the category of the health service costs. The section further described the conversion of some cost data that were given in Taka ₳ to US\$ data. This additional calculation was necessary to carry out some partial computations for the Siddique 2011 study on Bangladesh included in the literature review.

In order to continue, Chapter 18 will provide more detailed data and information on the calculation of the legal costs.

⁹Data in current or constant LCU [₳] was not available at the World Bank database (World Bank 2018c).

¹⁰Siddique states the costs in Taka ₳ only.

¹¹The value resembles the ratio of health costs and GDP for the respective year. Figures have been rounded up.

¹²The exact figure is US\$ 65,966,000,000,000, according to the World Bank (World Bank 2018a).

¹³The exact figure is ₳ 6,837,142,857,143. The overall cost [in LCU] and GDP cost-share [in %] are given in Siddique 2011, p. 50. From the two 2010 Bangladesh GDP figures, ₳ seven trillion and US\$ 66 trillion, it is derived that the report is based on a US\$ 1: ₳ 0.11, or ₳ 1 to US\$ 9.43 exchange rate [figures are rounded] for 2010. Siddique only indicates that the overall cost is 2.10 per cent of the 2010 GDP (Siddique 2011 p. 50). He does not state the exact GDP figure from which his estimates are derived. As a result, this number had to be calculated based on the given data in the study. The equation for a GDP proportion of cost is $\text{Share}(\%) = \frac{\text{Costs(LCU)}}{\text{GDP(LCU)}}$. It follows: $\text{GDP(LCU)} = \frac{\text{Costs(LCU)}}{\text{Share}(\%)}$, and $\text{GDP} = \frac{143,580,000,000}{2.10\%}$. This estimation had to be conducted to compute the exact figure Siddique uses for his estimations, as it was needed to compute the GDP share for the single cost categories.

¹⁴The exact figure is ₳ 143,580,000,000 [₳ 14,358 crore] (Siddique 2011, p. 50).

¹⁵According to Siddique 2011, p. 50. For more details, see the table's footnotes under the lefthand columns.

¹⁶The health costs were ₳ 2,806 million, according to Siddique. For a detailed composition of all expenses, see the explanations in Table 8.9

18. Legal costs

18.1. Introduction

Chapter 18 describes the data and information regarding the legal costs that have had no place in the main part of this study. Section 18.2 presents further information on the budget-share approach and provides more detailed insights regarding the calculation of case numbers. In summary, the data on men, the time frame, and NAMPOL are presented.

18.2. Calculation of case numbers

Data on men

As mentioned before, especially for sexual violence, men's data is not recorded in Namibia (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). International research depicts the same problems that, in general, numbers are too small to be used for estimates.¹

Time frame

Used NAMPOL crime statistics include periods from 2012 to 2013 (Hartman 2016; Namibian Police (NAMPOL) 2012). Hence, they are comparable to the NDHS survey period of 2012 to 2013 (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). Currently, no more up-to-date research is available. Changes in sexual violence patterns are challenging to track due to a substantial underreporting of cases.² As a result, institutions refuse to predict specific development patterns. Hence, this study did not conduct any predictions or forecasts either, and the NAMPOL large-panel data from 2012 to 2015 (Hartman 2016; Namibian Police (NAMPOL) 2012) is utilised instead.

Data from NAMPOL

The calculation of a general multiplier of 22.25 per cent stems from the following records:³

¹See, for instance, Walby 2004, p. 23.

²Overall, only one out of around 27 cases [3.71 per cent] is reported to NAMPOL. For further details, see Section 6.4.

³Other more specific multipliers were estimated based on tailored data within the literature – when available – and are described in Section 9.3 in more detail.

⁴Data originates from 50,000 gender crimes reported to NAMPOL within a three-year time frame (Hartman 2016).

⁵The data is derived from NAMPOL's crime statistics from 2012 to 2013 (Namibian Police (NAMPOL) 2012).

Table 18.1.: Adjusted GBV case number data.

GBV cases	Crime cases
14,989 ⁶	67,333 ⁷

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.
Source: Own representation.

This study aims to compute the cost of the total caseload, which law enforcement departments handle. Thus, the actual police data depicts a more realistic picture of expenses that have occurred for this cost category. Consequently, this paper applies a ratio of 22.25 per cent that is derived from police data on GBV crime and general crime⁶ rather than the NDHS figures on GBV prevalence, as done within the previous cost categories. The reason is that the Namibian judicial system holds various unnatural barriers⁷ that hinder individuals from accessing the legal system. Thus, police statistics⁸ are the most appropriate baseline for this cost category to calculate multipliers from, as they depict how many cases *made it through* the administrative system.

Summary

Chapter 18 briefly provided more detailed data regarding the calculation of case numbers and multipliers that did not have a place in the main part. These calculations were of importance to have formed more realistic case numbers for Chapter 9

⁶14,989/67,333. See Table 9.1 for further details on figure 67,333.

⁷See Section 9.5.3.

⁸Judicial data was not holistically available.

19. Social welfare costs and special service costs

19.1. Introduction

Chapter 19 explains the application of the budget-share approach in greater detail. Section 19.2 presents the calculated multipliers more comprehensively, and Table 19.1 displays the extensive and comprehensive calculation conducted, including the individual categories, main activities, or formulas.

19.2. Calculation of case numbers

1. The calculation of case numbers are estimated based on different police statistics.
2. The 17.50 per cent over 20 per cent ratio was chosen because:
 - The 20 per cent ratio symbolises the current offset of spousal violence. In detail, 20 per cent of ever-married women in Namibia have experienced physical or sexual violence. Their current or most recent husband enacted the abuse during the past 12 months before the survey (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 310). However, this study's definition goes beyond spousal violence and includes GBV enacted by third persons such as family friends, teachers, police or soldiers as well.¹ As a result, another ratio was chosen, namely –
 - 17.50 per cent of women who have experienced physical and sexual violence enacted by intimate partners, family members, or third parties during the past 12 months. By widening the circle of potential perpetrators, the prevalence decreases from 20 per cent to 17.50 per cent² as abuse enacted by third parties, such as police or soldiers, occurs less frequently [in Namibia, according to national surveys such as the NDHS] (MoHSS and ICF International 2014).
3. Activities: the following activities were eligible and hence were taken into account for the calculation of multipliers:
 - a) Direct measures of prevention, such as social welfare programmes, police services, or educational activities related to GBV.

¹See Chapter 2 for more detailed information.

²For more information on the composition of the 17.50 per cent, see Section 6.4

-
- b) The mitigation of GBV impacts, such as HIV prevention or HIV/AIDs-related matters, as well as poverty reductional activities.
 - c) The support of GBV survivors, through, for instance, shelters, counselling, or grants.
4. The number of activities: the estimation of multipliers is based on the overall number of cases within each department or unit, as:
- a) The main division: Community Empowerment (Ministry of Finance 2018, p. 195 f.) had three main tasks, namely to:
 - i. improve income-generating activities,
 - ii. enhance capacity building of entitled beneficiaries,
 - iii. strengthen the management of community development programmes.
 Thus, in this case, a ratio of 33.30 per cent [$\frac{1}{3}$] is used, for instance. [See bullet points 5 and 6 for the weighting of activities].
 - b) The same process is applied within all other activities. For instance, the Department – Office of the Minister has four primary operations (Ministry of Finance 2018, p. 190); thus, the ratio of 25 per cent is used, or
 - c) The Central division, Gender equality, and Research (Ministry of Finance 2018, p. 193 f.) has five main activities; thus, the prevalence ratio of 20 per cent is applied to each activity. See Table 19.1 for more insights on the formula.
5. Full usage and multiplication of the 17.50 per cent factor: the 17.50 per cent is applied fully for activities whose main task was one of the pursuits listed under point 3. For instance:
- a) The main activities of the department “Childcare facilities and protection” (Ministry of Finance 2018, p. 197) are to:
 - i. provide shelter [hence the 17.50 per cent factor is applied],
 - ii. offer care and protection [17.50 per cent],
 - iii. deliver educational support [17.50 per cent],
 - iv. expand and strengthen the social protection system for children [20 per cent · 17.50 per cent]³
 - v. ensure that services for children and their families are effectively managed, implemented, and monitored [17.50 per cent].

The principle aspect of the division’s activities one, two, three and four is GBV prevention or the support of its survivors; thus, the factor of 17.50 per cent is applied directly. Activity four contains only aspects of GBV prevention or support, as it also comprises other programmes besides GBV, namely the social protection in general.⁴ Hence, only the specific fraction is employed. In detail, the activity’s fraction of [$\frac{1}{5}$], 20 per cent, is used and was set into relation to the GBV proportion of 17.50 per cent [20 per cent · 17.50 per cent]. Consequently, the following formula

³See bullet point 6 for a more detailed explanation.

⁴According to the overarching national “Estimates of revenue, income and expenditure” report from the Ministry of Finance (Ministry of Finance 2018).

is used: $[4 \text{ activities} \cdot 17.50 \text{ per cent}]^5 + [1 \text{ activity} \cdot 20 \text{ per cent} \cdot 17.50 \text{ per cent}]^6 = 73.50 \text{ per cent}$.⁷

6. Partial usage and multiplication of the 17.50 per cent factor: as said, if activities contain items of GBV prevention or related support, listed under the previous bullet point 3, the 17.50 per cent factor is applied. For reasons of stringency, the sample of “Community Empowerment” is used again for further explanations:

- a) The main division, “Community Empowerment” (Ministry of Finance 2018, p. 195 f.) conducts the following activities:
- i. income-generating projects [17.50 per cent],
 - ii. capacity building for targeted beneficiary groups [17.50 per cent], and
 - iii. strengthening the management of community development programmes [17.50 per cent].

All activities contain aspects of the actions listed under points three and four. As a result, the following formula is used: $3 \text{ activities} \cdot 33.30 \text{ per cent} \cdot 17.50 \text{ per cent}$.⁸

- b) In contrast, the health and social services department offers the “provision of emergency relief” (Ministry of Finance 2018, p. 211 f.). In detail, it conducts
- i. provision of emergency relief to the aged, disabled and other groups or individuals in need [17.50 per cent],
 - ii. general social casework [17.50 per cent],
 - iii. the support of welfare organisations [17.50 per cent],
 - iv. Nursing homes [0 per cent], and
 - v. Children’s homes [17.50 per cent].

All tasks contain an aspect of a relevant activity listed under the previous bullet point 3, except for activity iv “nursing homes.” Thus, the following formula is used: $4 \text{ activities} \cdot 20 \text{ per cent} \cdot 17.50 \text{ per cent}$.⁹ In detail, $[4 \text{ activities} \cdot 20 \text{ per cent} \cdot 17.50 \text{ per cent}] + [0 \text{ activities} \cdot 20 \text{ per cent} \cdot 17.50 \text{ per cent}]$.

The detailed calculation of all activities is given in Table 19.1.

7. The ratio of zero per cent is applied if there was no relation to any GBV activity. For instance:

- a) see bullet point iv “Nursing homes” [zero per cent], or
- b) within the U.N. Pillar 1, “institutional environment,” the activity “national anti-corruption and access to information frameworks developed and implemented,” or the activity: “by 2018 national statistical system consistently produces, disseminates

⁵Full factor.

⁶As in this section, GBV activities only constitute a part of the overall scope.

⁷It is relevant to note that this was carried out for a maximum of five activities, as the outcome would have otherwise exceeded 100 per cent. [As $5 \text{ activities} \cdot 17.50 \text{ per cent} = 87.50 \text{ per cent} + 6 \text{ activities} \cdot 17.50 \text{ per cent} = 105 \text{ per cent}$]. Nevertheless, this restriction was only applied once under the section: “Donor money” in pillar 4 on poverty reduction.

⁸For instance, the number 3 represents the number of total activities carried out within this department. The 33.30 per cent depicts the share of one out of all three activities. The 17.50 per cent is the applied GBV prevalence ratio. See as well the sample of “Community Empowerment” under bullet point four.

⁹For instance, the number 4 presents the number of all total activities carried out within the division. The 20 per cent is the share of one activity on all five activities. The 17.50 per cent is the chosen GBV prevalence ratio.

and utilises high quality disaggregated statistical data” were considered as non-relevant and were rated with zero per cent.

8. The distinctive characteristics of the HIV/AIDS ratio:

- If an activity was related to an HIV/AIDS-related topic, then the specific HIV factor is used and set into relation to the GBV prevalence.
 - a) The 25.80 per cent factor: HIV estimates from Europe could not be transferred to the southern African situation because of the higher African prevalence. Due to increased HIV rates, the figure provided by Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005; Walby and Allen 2004 of 0.000001 was not applied. Instead, Jewkes *et al.* 2010 estimates for South Africa were used, which are, according to Jewkes 2018 transferable to the Namibian context. The 25.80 per cent of Jewkes presents the sum of the first, 13.90 per cent of HIV infections which would have been prevented if gender equity and low power ratio of women in a heterosexual relationship had been enhanced. Secondly, 11.90 per cent of HIV infections which would have been avoided if women had not experienced more than one episode of physical or sexual partner violence (Jewkes *et al.* 2010 p. 6). The percentage includes only individuals who suffered from more than one incident of violence during the surveyed period. A possible distortion is acknowledged.
 - i. 14.50 per cent ratio: the general HIV prevalence for women¹⁰ aged 15 to 49 was 14.50 per cent (UNAIDS 2017).¹¹ However, this general factor was NOT employed. According to Jewkes *et al.* 2010 women in a situation with GBV are more vulnerable to HIV/AIDS infections because they usually do not have enough bargaining power within an intimate relationship. In order to express this vulnerability; hence, a higher factor of 25.80 per cent is applied.
 - b) This specific GBV/HIV ratio was set in relation to the prevalence factor of 17.50 per cent, as the GBV related HIV/AIDS prevalence applies only to the GBV cohort. Hence, the coefficient of 4.52 per cent [25.80 per cent · 17.50 per cent] is utilised.
 - c) For instance, this HIV ratio is applied under the Ministry of Gender’s division “administration and planning” (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 191 f.) within the activity “HIV/AIDS mainstreaming,” or under health and social services for “the special disease programmes (Ministry of Finance 2018 p. 219) of HIV/AIDS prevention.” It was not applied under the U.N. “health” pillar under activity, “By 2018, young people (10–24yrs) are equipped to access sexual and reproductive health including HIV information and services” (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 41) or under the same U.N. pillar “health” within the activity “By 2018, skills of health workers in the provision of MNCH, HIV/SRH, and nutrition

¹⁰Sexual violence was only computed for women, as data was not holistically available for men.

¹¹According to UNAIDS, Namibian women aged 15 to 49 had an average HIV prevalence factor of 14.50 per cent [between 12.90 and 15.60 per cent], and men aged 15 to 49 had an average prevalence of 9.50 per cent [between 7.90 per cent and 10.40 per cent], and adults aged 15 to 49 had an HIV prevalence ratio of 12.10 per cent [between 10.70 per cent to 13.00 per cent] (UNAIDS 2017).

-
- services improved” (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 58). Since it was not clear whether the target group, e.g. young people (10–24yrs), is directly affected by HIV/AIDS [already], or the activity had a third target group, e.g. health workers. Therefore, this conservative approach was applied.
- d) The HIV/GBV ratio of 4.52 per cent was again set in relation to the number of overall activities, as described under bullet point 6.
9. A factor of 100 per cent is applied to specific NGOs and agencies that only handle GBV related topics. As,
- a) the Regain Trust, which offers psychological counselling to GBV survivors (Solidaritätsdienst International e. V. (SODI) 2018), and
 - b) Friendly Haven is a women’s shelter that provides a safe place for women and children in need (Andima 2014).
10. Sick leave calculation
- a) The Namibian Social Security Commission grants sick leave benefits to vulnerable citizens (Social Security Commission 2013 p. 47). In order to single out the benefiting GBV beneficiaries, the following formula was applied. First, the ratio of 17.50 per cent was applied. A high share of citizens is either unemployed, self-employed, or benefits from in-kind donations (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2013; World Bank 2019b), and is therefore not fully entitled to receive grants. In detail, only 74.10 per cent of citizens receive a GDP per capita income from some form of employment. Since, according to the Namibia Household Income and Expenditure Survey (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016 p. 98), 25.90 per cent of the population does not belong to any specific economic sector and lives from remittances and grants [9.60 per cent], drought, and in-kind receipts [2.70 per cent], subsistence farming [10.60 per cent], or others [three per cent]. In line with the argumentation in Section 7.5.1 the 74.10 per cent is applied in addition, and in total, the factor of 12.97 per cent [17.50 per cent · 74.10 per cent] is used. It is assumed that remittances and grants do not trigger social security benefits. A possible distortion is acknowledged.

Table 19.1 depicts all underlying formula which is used within each unit in more detail.¹²

¹²As said in Section 5.4 the identification of suitable activities within the budget is a subjective matter of the respective scholar and may lead to falsification.

Table 19.1.: Results of the total social welfare costs.

Category ¹³ Main operations ¹⁴	Formula	Multiplier [%] ¹⁵
Ministry of Gender		
Office of the Minister	$5 \cdot \frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%$	17.50
1. To review policy options and	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
2. suggest and, or	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
3. approve and	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
4. make public the government's	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
5. policies and guidelines in the above-mentioned areas	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Administration and planning	$[4 \cdot \frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	14.90
1. Construction and renovation of Constituency Offices	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	$+$ $[1 \cdot \frac{1}{5} \cdot 4.52\%]$
2. Provide qualified training to staff members	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
3. General administrative services	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
4. HIV/AIDS Mainstreaming and	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
5. Acquisition and maintenance of IT equipment and systems	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Gender equality and research	$5 \cdot \frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%$	17.50
1. Coordination mechanism for Gender Policy implemented	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
2. Gender Responsive Budgeting initiative	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
3. Women Economic programmes	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
4. Women in political parties	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
5. Public and private sectors leadership skills	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Community empowerment	$[2 \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$	29.17
1. Improved support for Income Generating activities	$[\frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$	$+$ 17.50%
2. Capacity building for beneficiaries	[17.50% in full]	
3. Strengthen the management of community development programmes	$[\frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Childcare facilities and protection	$[1 \cdot \frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	73.50
1. Provide shelter	[17.50% in full]	$+$
2. Care, protection and	[17.50% in full]	$[4 \cdot 17.50\%]$
3. Educational support	[17.50% in full]	
4. Expand and strengthen social protection system for children	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
5. Ensure services for children and their families are effectively managed, implemented, and monitored	[17.50% in full]	

Continue on next page

¹³Categories base on the Ministry of Finance's report (Ministry of Finance 2018).

¹⁴The column lists a review of the main operations of every department and stakeholder. If not stated otherwise, data is derived from the Ministry of Finance's report [MOF (Ministry of Finance 2018)]. The column depicts direct quotations.

¹⁵The calculations are always rounded to two places after the comma.

Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
Childcare services		$[2 \cdot 17.50\%]$	43.75
	1. Ensure services for children and their families are effectively managed, implemented, monitored and educated [17.50% in full]	$[2 \cdot \frac{1}{4} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	2. Empower communities and	$[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	3. Provide a continuum of care for children and families [17.50% in full]	$[17.50\%]$	
	4. Provision of Children Grants	$[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Ministry of Social Welfare			
Provision of emergency relief		$[4 \cdot \frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	14.00
	1. Provision of emergency relief to the aged, disabled and other groups	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	2. General social casework	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	3. Support to welfare organisations	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	4. Old Age Homes	[0%]	
	5. Children's homes	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Special disease programmes		$[3 \cdot \frac{1}{4} \cdot 17.50\%]$	14.26
	1. Formulate policies and guidelines	$[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	2. Mobilise resources	$[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	3. Provide training and technical support	$[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	4. Monitor and evaluate the national programmes which are geared towards preventing deaths, reduce illnesses, improve health and socio-economic losses due to HIV	$[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
Important NGOs			
GBV emergency accommodation		100	100 ¹⁶
	1. Friendly Haven, a women's shelter. (Andima 2014)		
GBV counselling and educational activities		100	100 ¹⁷
	1. LifeLine/ChildLine Namibia and REGAIN Trust, who offers psychological counselling to GBV survivors. (Solidaritatsdienst International e. V. (SODI) 2018)		

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¹⁶A ratio of 100 per cent is applied to specific NGOs and agencies that mainly handle GBV related topics.¹⁷Ibid.

Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
International donor community			
U.N. (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017) ¹⁸			
Pillar 1 – Institutional Environment		$[10 \cdot \frac{1}{16} \cdot 17.50\%]$	11.79
1. Row 1 – Output statement 1.1	(United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 37)	$[0\%]$	$+$
2. Row 2 – Output statement 1.3		$[3 \cdot \frac{1}{16} \cdot 4.52\%]$	$+$
3. Row 3 – Output statement 1.4		$+$	$[3 \cdot 0\%]$
4. Row 4 – Output statement 1.4		$[\frac{1}{16} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
5. Row 5 – Output statement 1.4		$[\frac{1}{16} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
6. Row 6 – Output statement 2.2		$[\frac{1}{16} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
7. Row 7 – Output statement 2.2	(United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 38)	$[\frac{1}{16} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
8. Row 8 – Output statement 2.2		$[\frac{1}{16} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
9. Row 9 – Output statement 2.2		$[\frac{1}{16} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
10. Row 10 – Output statement 3.10		$[0\%]$	
11. Row 11 – Output statement 3.10		$[0\%]$	
12. Row 12 – Output statement 3.2		$[\frac{1}{16} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
13. Row 13 – Output statement 3.2	(United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 39)	$[\frac{1}{16} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
14. Row 14 – Output statement 4.2		$[\frac{1}{16} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
15. Row 15 – Output statement 4.2		$[\frac{1}{16} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
16. Row 16 – Output statement 4.3		$[\frac{1}{16} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Pillar 2 – Education and Skills		$[7 \cdot \frac{1}{10} \cdot 17.50\%]$	12.70
1. Row 5 – Output statement 5.1	(United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 39)	$[\frac{1}{10} \cdot 17.50\%]$	$+$
2. Row 6 – Output statement 5.2		$[1 \cdot \frac{1}{10} \cdot 4.52\%]$	$+$
3. Row 7 – Output statement 5.2		$+$	$[2 \cdot 0\%]$
4. Row 1 – Output statement 5.3	(United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 40)	$[0\%]$	
5. Row 2 – Output statement 5.4		$[\frac{1}{10} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
6. Row 3 – Output statement 5.5		$[\frac{1}{10} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
7. Row 4 – Output statement 5.5		$[\frac{1}{10} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
8. Row 5 – Output statement 5.6		$[0\%]$	
9. Row 6 – Output statement 5.8		$[\frac{1}{10} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
10. Row 7 – Output statement 5.8		$[\frac{1}{10} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Pillar 3 – Health		$[55 \cdot \frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	9.00 ¹⁹
1. Row 1 – Output statement 6.1	(United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 41)	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	$+$
2. Row 2 – Output statement 6.1		$[10 \cdot \frac{1}{112} \cdot 4.52\%]$	$+$
3. Row 3 – Output statement 6.1		$+$	$[47 \cdot 0\%]$
		$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	

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¹⁸Costs are listed in US\$. The 2018 average exchange rate for US\$1: N\$ of 13.2311 is used (Exchangerates 2020).

¹⁹In more detail, the figure is 8.997 per cent.

Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
	4. Row 4 – Output statement 6.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	5. Row 1 – Output statement 6.1 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 42)	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	6. Row 2 – Output statement 6.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	7. Row 3 – Output statement 6.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	8. Row 4 – Output statement 6.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	9. Row 1 – Output statement 6.1 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 43)	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	10. Row 2 – Output statement 6.2	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	11. Row 3 – Output statement 6.2	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	12. Row 4 – Output statement 6.2	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	13. Row 1 – Output statement 6.2 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 44)	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	14. Row 2 – Output statement 6.2	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	15. Row 3 – Output statement 6.3	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	16. Row 4 – Output statement 6.3	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	17. Row 1 – Output statement 6.3 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 45)	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	18. Row 2 – Output statement 6.3	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	19. Row 3 – Output statement 6.3	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	20. Row 4 – Output statement 6.3	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	21. Row 1 – Output statement 6.4 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 46)	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
	22. Row 2 – Output statement 6.4	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
	23. Row 3 – Output statement 6.4	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
	24. Row 4 – Output statement 6.5	[0%]	
	25. Row 1 – Output statement 6.5 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 47)	[0%]	
	26. Row 2 – Output statement 6.5	[0%]	
	27. Row 3 – Output statement 6.5	[0%]	
	28. Row 4 – Output statement 6.5	[0%]	
	29. Row 1 – Output statement 6.5 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 48)	[0%]	
	30. Row 2 – Output statement 6.5	[0%]	
	31. Row 3 – Output statement 6.5	[0%]	
	32. Row 4 – Output statement 6.5	[0%]	
	33. Row 1 – Output statement 6.5 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 49)	[0%]	
	34. Row 2 – Output statement 6.5	[0%]	
	35. Row 3 – Output statement 6.6	[0%]	
	36. Row 4 – Output statement 6.6	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	37. Row 1 – Output statement 6.6 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 50)	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	38. Row 2 – Output statement 6.6	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	39. Row 3 – Output statement 6.6	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	40. Row 4 – Output statement 6.6	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	41. Row 1 – Output statement 6.6 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017 p. 51)	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	42. Row 2 – Output statement 6.7	[0%]	
	43. Row 3 – Output statement 6.7	[0%]	

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Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
	44. Row 4 – Output statement 6.7		[0%]
	45. Row 1 – Output statement 6.7 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 52)		[0%]
	46. Row 2 – Output statement 6.7		[0%]
	47. Row 3 – Output statement 6.7		[0%]
	48. Row 4 – Output statement 6.7		[0%]
	49. Row 1 – Output statement 6.7 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 53)		[0%]
	50. Row 2 – Output statement 6.7		[0%]
	51. Row 3 – Output statement 6.7		[0%]
	52. Row 4 – Output statement 6.7		[0%]
	53. Row 1 – Output statement 6.7 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 54)		[0%]
	54. Row 2 – Output statement 6.7		[0%]
	55. Row 3 – Output statement 6.7		[0%]
	56. Row 4 – Output statement 6.7		[0%]
	57. Row 1 – Output statement 6.7 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 55)		[0%]
	58. Row 2 – Output statement 6.7		[0%]
	59. Row 3 – Output statement 6.7		[0%]
	60. Row 4 – Output statement 6.7		[0%]
	61. Row 1 – Output statement 6.7 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 56)		[0%]
	62. Row 2 – Output statement 6.7		[0%]
	63. Row 3 – Output statement 6.7		[0%]
	64. Row 4 – Output statement 6.8		[0%]
	65. Row 1 – Output statement 6.8 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 57)		[0%]
	66. Row 2 – Output statement 6.8		[0%]
	67. Row 3 – Output statement 6.8		[0%]
	68. Row 4 – Output statement 6.8		[0%]
	69. Row 1 – Output statement 6.8 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 58)		[0%]
	70. Row 2 – Output statement 7.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	71. Row 3 – Output statement 7.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	72. Row 4 – Output statement 7.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	73. Row 5 – Output statement 7.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	74. Row 6 – Output statement 7.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	75. Row 1 – Output statement 7.1 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 59)	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	76. Row 2 – Output statement 7.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	77. Row 3 – Output statement 7.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	78. Row 4 – Output statement 7.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	79. Row 5 – Output statement 7.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	80. Row 6 – Output statement 7.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	81. Row 1 – Output statement 7.1 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 60)	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	82. Row 2 – Output statement 7.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	83. Row 3 – Output statement 7.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	84. Row 4 – Output statement 7.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	

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Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
	85. Row 5 – Output statement 7.2	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	86. Row 6 – Output statement 7.2	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	87. Row 1 – Output statement 7.2	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	(United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 61)		
	88. Row 2 – Output statement 7.2	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	89. Row 3 – Output statement 7.2	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	90. Row 4 – Output statement 7.2	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	91. Row 5 – Output statement 7.2	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	92. Row 6 – Output statement 7.2	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	93. Row 1 – Output statement 7.3	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	(United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 62)		
	94. Row 2 – Output statement 7.3	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	95. Row 3 – Output statement 7.3	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	96. Row 4 – Output statement 7.3	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	97. Row 5 – Output statement 7.3	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	98. Row 6 – Output statement 7.1	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	99. Row 1 – Output statement 7.4	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
	(United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 63)		
	100. Row 2 – Output statement 7.4	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
	101. Row 3 – Output statement 7.4	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
	102. Row 4 – Output statement 7.4	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
	103. Row 5 – Output statement 7.4	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
	104. Row 6 – Output statement 7.4	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
	105. Row 1 – Output statement 7.4	$[\frac{1}{112} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
	(United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 64)		
	106. Row 2 – Output statement 7.5	[0%]	
	107. Row 3 – Output statement 7.5	[0%]	
	108. Row 4 – Output statement 7.5	[0%]	
	109. Row 5 – Output statement 7.5	[0%]	
	110. Row 6 – Output statement 7.5	[0%]	
	111. Row 1 – Output statement 7.5	[0%]	
	(United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 65)		
	112. Row 2 – Output statement 7.5	[0%]	

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Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
Pillar 4 – Poverty Reduction		$[21 \cdot \frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	47.67 ²⁰
	1. Row 3 – Output statement 8.1 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 65)	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	+
	2. Row 4 – Output statement 8.1	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	$[2 \cdot 17.50\%]$
	3. Row 5 – Output statement 8.2	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	+
	4. Row 1 – Output statement 9.2 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 66)	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	5. Row 2 – Output statement 9.2	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	6. Row 3 – Output statement 9.5 ²¹	$[17.50\%]$	
	7. Row 4 – Output statement 9.5	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	8. Row 5 – Output statement 9.5	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	9. Row 1 – Output statement 9.5 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 67)	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	10. Row 2 – Output statement 9.5	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	11. Row 3 – Output statement 9.5	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	12. Row 4 – Output statement 9.5	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	13. Row 5 – Output statement 9.5	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	14. Row 1 – Output statement 9.6 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 68)	$[17.50\%]$	
	15. Row 2 – Output statement 9.6	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	16. Row 3 – Output statement 10.1	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	17. Row 4 – Output statement 10.1	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	18. Row 5 – Output statement 10.3	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	19. Row 6 – Output statement 10.3	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	20. Row 1 – Output statement 11.1 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 69)	$[0\%]$	
	21. Row 2 – Output statement 11.2	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	22. Row 3 – Output statement 11.2	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	23. Row 4 – Output statement 11.2	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	24. Row 1 – Output statement 11.2 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 70)	$[0\%]$	
	25. Row 2 – Output statement 11.2	$[0\%]$	
	26. Row 3 – Output statement 11.2	$[0\%]$	
	27. Row 1 – Output statement 11.2 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 71)	$[0\%]$	
	28. Row 2 – Output statement 11.2	$[\frac{1}{29} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	29. Row 3 – Output statement 12.3 (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) 2017, p. 71)	$[0\%]$	

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²⁰The 17.50 per cent is multiplied only twice in the output statement 9.5 and 9.6. As written in Section 19.2 in section “Calculation of case numbers,” under point 5 b, the 17.50 per cent is applied in full for a maximum of five activities, as the ratio would otherwise have exceeded 100 per cent. [As 5 activities·17.50 per cent is 87.50 per cent and 6 activities·17.50 per cent would be 105 per cent]. This restriction is applied only once, namely, in this case.

²¹See Section 19.2 bullet point 5 – Full usage and multiplication of the 17.50 per cent factor.

Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
UNCHR (Executive Committee of the High Commissioner 2016)			
Overall activities			17.50 ²²
E.U. (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015).			
1.	Education and skills	$1 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot 17.50\%$	8.75 ²³
	1. Specific Objective 1 – To improve access and quality in the Early Childhood Development and Pre-primary Education sub-Sectors (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015, p. 3)	$[\frac{1}{2} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	2. Specific Objective 2 – To increase equitable access to and completion of quality Vocational education and training (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015, p. 3)	[0%]	
2.	Agriculture	$1 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot 17.50\%$	8.75
	1. Specific Objective 1 – A strengthened livestock value chain in communal areas of Namibia will improve sustainable livelihoods and employment opportunities for primary producers and other actors in the chain (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015, p. 13)	[0%]	
	2. Specific Objective 2 – Support for entrepreneurship will stimulate engagement in value chains and private sector employment (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015, p. 13)	$[\frac{1}{2} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
3.	Other measures/support to civil society	$2 \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%$	11.67
	1. Development Cooperation Instrument (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015, p. 16)	$[\frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	2. European Instrument for Democracy (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015, p. 16)	[0%]	

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²²A ratio of 17.50% is applied, as the UNCHR supports young women and girls, women with migrant backgrounds, and female refugees. Again, 17.50 per cent includes women who have experienced physical and sexual violence enacted by all intimate partners and family members, as well as third parties over the past 12 months (MoHSS and ICF International 2014). See Section 19.2 bullet point 2, explaining why the 17.50 per cent over the 20 per cent ratio was chosen for more information. However, according to research, it is acknowledged that migrant women or women living in refugee camps often suffer from higher GBV ratios (World Health Organization (WHO) 2019). Consequently, that prevalence ratio may be higher. Thus, this is a rather conservative estimate, and more detailed data is needed for the Namibian case scenario.

²³Rounded two places after the comma.

Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
	3. Human Rights [EIDHR] (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015, p. 16)	$[\frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
4. Support measures		$1 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot 17.50\%$	8.75
	1. Measures to support or accompany the programming, preparation or implementation of actions (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015, p. 16)	$[\frac{1}{2} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	2. Support to the National Authorising Officer (European Union (EU), Delegation to the Republic of Namibia, The Head of Delegation 2015, p. 17)	[0%]	
BMZ (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2019a)			
	Promotion of Vocational education ²⁴ (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2018c)	$1 \cdot \frac{1}{4} \cdot 17.50\%$	4.38
	1. Qualification and training	[0%]	
	2. Teachers training courses	[0%]	
	3. Exchange platforms	[0%]	
	4. Survey on vocational training including HIV/AIDS analysis as a baseline for educational offers	$[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 17.50\%]$ ²⁵	
	Student and specialist funds ²⁶	$1 \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%$	5.83
	1. Objectives Preparation and Examination	[0%]	
	2. Studies and reports	[0%]	
	3. Implementation ²⁷	$[\frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	Program to promote the competitiveness of the Namibian economy ²⁸	$1 \cdot \frac{1}{6} \cdot 17.50\%$	2.92
	Approach – Project measures		
	1. The project actions include training for company executives	[0%]	
	2. Support in product development and the introduction of new technologies	[0%]	

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²⁴The original German terms are presented in all footnotes. In this case, it is – Förderung der Beruflichen Bildung (Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (BMZ) 2018).

²⁵The original German passage is: Wirkungen Qualifizierungsangebote – [0%]; Lehrerweiterbildungskurse – [0%]; Austauschplattformen – [0%]. Die NTA hat eine Zufriedenheitsstudie über berufliche Bildung sowie eine Gender – und HIV/AIDS-analyse beauftragt. Die Analyseergebnisse liefern wichtige Impulse für die Planung und Umsetzung von Bildungsangeboten. $[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 17.50\%]$ (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2018c; Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2019b).

²⁶Studien – und Fachkräftefonds. The content and structure are similar to the category: partnerships of local banks.

²⁷The German original text is: Ziele – 1. Vorbereitung und Prüfung TZ – [0%]; 2. Studien und Gutachten – [0%]; 3. Durchführung TZ – $[\frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$ (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2011).

²⁸Programm zur Förderung der Wettbewerbsfähigkeit der namibischen Wirtschaft.

Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
	3. The Namibian Investment centre [NIC is assisted in the development of strategies to promote foreign direct investment]	[0%]	
	4. Improved business environment	[0%]	
	5. The project, therefore, supports the Chamber of Commerce and Industry in communication and lobbying for the private sector	[0%]	
	6. The initiative includes training to provide business and financial expertise and raise awareness of financial services in general ²⁹	$[\frac{1}{6} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Groundwater management in Northern Namibia ³⁰		$2 \cdot \frac{1}{7} \cdot 17.50\%$	5.00
	Project activities		
	1. Development of a GW Observation Network for the Ohangwena Groundwater System [OGS to provide up-to-date information on GW availability]	[0%]	
	2. Development of an exemplary GW database and an efficient organisation of work processes	[0%]	
	3. Hydrogeological and chemical studies	[0%]	
	4. Development of a simplified model of groundwater flow	[0%]	
	5. Conduct a Need Assessment to identify existing and required capacities for sustainable management	[0%]	
	6. Training of staff in the application of a Decision Supporting System	$[\frac{1}{7} \cdot 17.50\%]$	

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²⁹Vorgehensweise: Projektmaßnahmen 1. Die Projektmaßnahmen umfassen Schulungen für die Führungskräfte von Unternehmen – [0%]; 2. Unterstützung bei der Produktentwicklung und die Einführung neuer Technologien – [0%]; 3. Das namibische Investitionszentrum wird bei der Erarbeitung von Strategien zur Förderung von ausländischen Direktinvestitionen unterstützt – [0%]; 4. verbesserten Geschäftsumfelds bei – beispielsweise durch vereinfachte Prozesse, Anreizsysteme sowie die Förderung des Zugangs zu lokalen und regionalen Märkten – [0%]; 5. Das Projekt unterstützt deshalb die Industrie – und Handelskammer bei der Kommunikation und der Lobbyarbeit für die Privatwirtschaft – [0%]; 6. Die Initiative umfasst Schulungen, in denen kaufmännisches und finanzielles Fachwissen vermittelt werden sowie allgemein für Finanzdienstleistungen sensibilisiert wird – $[\frac{1}{6} \cdot 17.50\%]$ (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2014a).

³⁰Grundwassermanagement im Norden Namibias.

Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
	7. Training of DWAF staff in the application of the database and in the evaluation of hydrochemical data ³¹	$[\frac{1}{7} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Partnerships of local banks ³²	Project activities	$1 \cdot \frac{1}{6} \cdot 17.50\%$	2.92
	1. Training for company executives	[0%]	
	2. Support in product development and the introduction of new technologies	[0%]	
	3. The NIC is assisted in the development of foreign direct investment promotion [FDI strategies to support start-ups and the growth of existing companies]	[0%]	
	4. The project, therefore, supports the Namibian Chamber of Commerce and Industry [NCCI in communication and lobbying for the private sector]	[0%]	
	5. Limited access to financing solutions is a major hurdle for the economy. The Financial Sector Strategy, therefore, foresees a series of reforms and measures to improve access to financing solutions for Namibian companies	[0%]	

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³¹Projektaktivitäten: 1. Entwicklung eines Grundwasserbeobachtungsmeßstellennetzes für das Ohangwena – Grundwassersystem um aktuelle Aussagen zu Grundwasserverfügbarkeit zu treffen – [0%]; 2. Aufbau einer exemplarischen Grundwasserdatenbank und einer effizienten Organization der Arbeitsabläufe – [0%]; 3. Hydrogeologische und -chemische Untersuchungen – [0%]; 4. Entwicklung eines vereinfachten Modells zum Grundwasserfluß – [0%]; 5. Durchführung eines NeedAssessments zur Feststellung vorhandener und benötigter Kapazitäten für eine nachhaltige Bewirtschaftung der Grundwasserressourcen – [0%]; 6. Schulung von Mitarbeitern in der Anwendung eines die Entscheidungsfindung unterstützenden Systems für Grundwassermanagement – [17.50%]; 7. Schulung von Mitarbeitern in der Anwendung der Datenbank und in der Auswertung hydrochemischer Daten – [17.50%] (BGR, The Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources 2019a).

³²Sparkassenpartnerschaften.

Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
	6. In support of these efforts, the project is working with the Namibian Central Bank, Financial Regulator, Development Bank, and other actors to adapt the legal framework, as the Law on Credit Agreements and the Law on Credit Institutions. It examines the extent to which new financing instruments, as venture capital, loan guarantees, and a fund with a risk component, can be realised. Meanwhile, with the support of the project, the Ministry of Finance initiative to promote financial literacy has begun to provide the necessary knowledge to improve access to financing solutions. The initiative includes training to provide business and financial expertise and raise awareness of financial services in general. ³³	$[\frac{1}{6} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Municipal resource management ³⁴	Fields of action	$1 \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%$	5.83
	1. Policy advice on good governance	$[\frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	2. Verification of compliance with national guidelines	[0%]	
	3. Income increase through the use of natural resources ³⁵	[0%]	

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³³Projektmaßnahmen 1. Schulungen für die Führungskräfte von Unternehmen – [0%]; 2. Unterstützung bei der Produktentwicklung und die Einführung neuer Technologien – [0%]; 3. Das namibische Investitionszentrum wird bei der Erarbeitung von Strategien zur Förderung von ausländischen Direktinvestitionen unterstützt, mit denen Unternehmensneugründungen sowie das Wachstum vorhandener Unternehmen begünstigt werden sollen – [0%]; 4. Das Projekt unterstützt deshalb die Industrie – und Handelskammer bei der Kommunikation und der Lobbyarbeit für die Privatwirtschaft – [0%]; 5. Der eingeschränkte Zugang zu Finanzierungslösungen ist für die Wirtschaft eine große Hürde. Die Strategie zur Förderung des Finanzsektors sieht deshalb eine Reihe von Reformen und Maßnahmen vor, die den Zugang zu Finanzierungslösungen für namibische Unternehmen verbessern – [0%]; 6. Zur Unterstützung dieser Bemühungen arbeitet das Projekt mit der namibischen Zentralbank, der Finanzaufsicht, der Entwicklungsbank und anderen Akteuren an der Anpassung der rechtlichen Rahmenbedingungen, beispielsweise am Gesetz über Kreditverträge und am Gesetz über Kreditinstitute. Geprüft wird, inwieweit neue Finanzierungsinstrumente, wie Wagniskapital, Kreditbürgschaften und ein Fonds mit Erstrisikokomponente, realisierbar sind. Inzwischen hat die beim Finanzministerium angesiedelte Initiative zur Förderung des finanziellen Grundwissens mit Unterstützung des Projekts damit begonnen, notwendiges Wissen zu vermitteln, um den Zugang zu Finanzierungslösungen zu verbessern. Die Initiative umfasst Schulungen, in denen kaufmännisches und finanzielles Fachwissen vermittelt werden sowie allgemein für Finanzdienstleistungen sensibilisiert wird – [17.50%] (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2014a).

³⁴Kommunales Ressourcenmanagement.

³⁵Handlungsfelder: 1. Politikberatung zur guten Regierungsführung – Die Position der Frauen wird besonders gestärkt, damit ihre Interessen und Bedarfe bei Entscheidungen angemessen berücksichtigt werden – [17.50%]; 2. Überprüfung der Einhaltung nationaler Richtlinien – [0%]; 3. Einkommenssteigerung durch Nutzung natürlicher Ressourcen – [0%] (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2019c).

Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
Transport, mobility, and logistics ³⁶		$1 \cdot \frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%$	3.50
	Effects		
	1. 26 modern local buses	[0%]	
	2. A new network of routes in the urban area	[0%]	
	3. Non-motorised mobility has been successfully promoted through campaigns, and now the partners are developing a strategy with network development, quality standards as well as a communication strategy and organisation conception	[0%]	
	4. Submission of a draft establishing a Road Safety Agency and improving the performance management and the organisational restructuring of the management of the Road Fund	[0%]	
	5. Bachelor's and Master's degree programmes in civil engineering developed and accredited – A quarter of enrolled students in the Bachelor's degree program are women ³⁷	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Biodiversity and climate change ³⁸		$1 \cdot \frac{1}{4} \cdot 17.50\%$	4.38
	Method		
	1. Integration of the environmentally sustainable development goals into national development planning	[0%]	
	2. Strengthening environmental impact assessment [Strategic Environmental Assessment and Environmental Impact Assessment]	[0%]	
	3. Creating a regulatory framework for access to and access to and use of genetic resources [Access and Benefit Sharing]	$[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	4. Joint implementation of the three Rio conventions ³⁹	[0%]	

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³⁶Verkehr, Mobilität und Logistik.

³⁷Wirkungen: 1. 26 moderne Nahverkehrsbusse – [0%]; 2. einem neuen Streckennetz im Stadtgebiet – [0%]; 3. Nicht-motorisierte Mobilität wurde durch Kampagnen erfolgreich beworben und nun erarbeiten die Partner eine Strategie mit Netzwerkentwicklung, Qualitätsstandards sowie Kommunikationsstrategie und Organisationskonzeption – [0%]; 4. Die Vorlage eines Entwurfs zur Gründung einer Agentur für Verkehrssicherheit sowie die Verbesserung des Leistungsmanagements und die organisatorische Umstrukturierung der Verwaltung des Straßenfonds – [0%]; 5. Bachelor – und Masterstudiengänge für Bauingenieurwesen entwickelt und akkreditiert – Ein Viertel der eingeschriebenen Studenten im Bachelor Studiengang sind Frauen – [17.50%] (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2016b).

³⁸Biodiversität und Klimawandel.

³⁹Vorgehensweise: 1. Integration der umweltrelevanten Ziele für nachhaltige Entwicklung in die nationale Entwicklungsplanung – [0%]; 2. Stärkung der Umweltfolgenabschätzung [Strategische Umweltprüfung und Umweltverträglichkeitsprüfung] – [0%]; 3. Schaffung eines regulativen Rahmens für den Zugang zu genetischen Ressourcen und ihre gerechte Nutzung [Access and Benefit Sharing – auch benachteiligter Bevölkerungsgruppen] – [17.50%]; 4. Gemeinsame Umsetzung der drei Rio-Konventionen – [0%] (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2017a).

Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
Support of the land reform ⁴⁰	Method	1·17.50%	17.50
	1. The project supports the Namibian Ministry of Land Reform, local communities, and other relevant actors in securing access to land for landless households in urban and rural areas. Women and adolescents are given special consideration. This was done through the regulation of land tenure through a flexible land law approach, the so-called Flexible Land Tenure System ⁴¹ . This approach encompasses all three fields of action.	[17.50%]	
Sustainable use of the mineral raw material potential of Namibia ⁴²	Project	$1 \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%$	5.83
	1. Construction raw materials play a role in the project since they can be used by the Namibian population as well as local companies to develop infrastructure [e.g., development of the deep-sea port of Walvis Bay]. As a result of these investigations, three value creation studies on the raw materials feldspar, lithium and the end product glass are prepared, which are presented to potential investors and thus serve as a basis for decision-making for investments in local value creation	[0%]	
	2. Besides, the project will develop thematic maps in which deposits of selected non-metallic raw materials are qualitatively and qualitatively represented	[0%]	

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⁴⁰Unterstützung der Landreform.

⁴¹Vorgehensweise: Das Projekt unterstützt das namibische Ministerium für Landreform, lokale Gemeinden und weitere relevante Akteure darin den Zugang zu Land für landlose Haushalte in städtischen und ländlichen Räumen zu sichern. Frauen und Jugendliche werden besonders berücksichtigt. Dies geschieht durch die Regelung der Grundbesitzverhältnisse durch einen flexiblen Landrechteansatz, dem sogenannten Flexible Land Tenure System – [17.50%]. Dieser Ansatz umfasst alle drei Handlungsfelder (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2017c).

⁴²Nachhaltige Nutzung des mineralischen Rohstoffpotentials Namibias.

Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
	3. Also, training on economic feasibility assessments of raw materials is carried out. They empower the GSN staff to assess the use and marketing of non-metallic raw materials ⁴³	$[\frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Promotion	vocational training including the NTA and the Namibian Chamber of Commerce [NCCI] ⁴⁴	$1 \cdot \frac{1}{6} \cdot 17.50\%$	2.92
	Project activities		
	1. Training for company executives	[0%]	
	2. Support in product development and the introduction of new technologies	[0%]	
	3. The NIC is assisted in the development of foreign direct investment promotion [FDI strategies to support start-ups and the growth of existing companies]	[0%]	
	4. The project, therefore, supports the Chamber of Commerce and Industry [NCCI in communication and lobbying for the private sector]	[0%]	
	5. Limited access to financing solutions is a major hurdle for the economy, especially for SMEs. The Financial Sector Strategy [NFSS, therefore, foresees a series of reforms and measures to improve access to financing solutions for Namibian companies	[0%]	

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⁴³Projekt: 1. Baurohstoffe spielen im Projekt eine Rolle, da sie von der namibischen Bevölkerung sowie lokalen Firmen zum Ausbau von Infrastruktur, z. B. Ausbau des Tiefseehafens von Walvis Bay, genutzt werden können. Als Ergebnis dieser Untersuchungen werden drei Wertschöpfungsstudien zu den Rohstoffen Feldspat, Lithium sowie dem Endprodukt Glas erstellt, die potenziellen Investoren vorgelegt werden und somit als Entscheidungsgrundlage für Investitionen in die lokale Wertschöpfung dienen – [0%]; 2. Darüber hinaus wird das Projekt thematische Karten erarbeiten, auf denen Lagerstätten ausgewählter nichtmetallischer Rohstoffe wirtschaftsgeologisch qualitativ und quantitativ dargestellt werden – [0%]; 3. Ergänzend werden Trainings zu Wirtschaftlichkeitsabschätzungen von Rohstoffen durchgeführt. Sie befähigen die Mitarbeiter zur Bewertung der Nutzung und Vermarktung nichtmetallischer Rohstoffe – [17.50%] (BGR, The Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources [2019b]).

⁴⁴Förderung der NTA und der Chamber of Commerce [NCCI].

Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
	6. In support of these efforts, the project is working with the Namibian Central Bank, Financial Regulator, Development Bank, and other actors to adapt the legal framework, as the Law on Credit Agreements and the Law on Credit Institutions. It examines the extent to which new financing instruments, as venture capital, loan guarantees, and a fund with a risk component, can be realised. Meanwhile, with the support of the project, the Ministry of Finance initiative to promote financial literacy has begun to provide the necessary knowledge to improve access to financing solutions. The initiative includes training to provide business and financial expertise and raise awareness of financial services in general	$[\frac{1}{6} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
SDG initiative		$1 \cdot 17.50\%$	17.50
	Objective		
	1. Requirements for the national implementation of the 2030 Agenda in Namibia have been created. Agenda 2030 is committed to strengthening the role of women ⁴⁵	$[17.50\%]$	
Agricultural advice to beneficiaries of the land reform ⁴⁶		$2 \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%$	11.67
	Approach – of all three fields of action		
	1. The provision of services to farms, and in particular to beneficiaries of land reform, has improved	$[\frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	2. The services of the advisers of the MAWF are professionalised	$[0\%]$	
	3. Beneficiaries of land reform are increasingly using advisory services ⁴⁷	$[\frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Use of the bush biomass ⁴⁸		$1 \cdot \frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%$	3.50
	Effect		

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⁴⁵Ziel: Voraussetzungen für die nationale Implementierung der Agenda 2030 in Namibia sind geschaffen. Agenda 2030 setzt sich für die Stärkung der Rolle der Frau ein. (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2020) Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ), Status: laufendes Projekt 2017)

⁴⁶Landwirtschaftliche Beratung für Begünstigte der Landreform.

⁴⁷Vorgehensweise – aller drei Handlungsfelder: 1. Die Rahmenbedingungen für die Bereitstellung von Dienstleistungen an landwirtschaftliche Betriebe und insbesondere an Begünstigte von Landreform werden verbessert – $[17.50\%]$; 2. Die Dienstleistungen der Beratungen werden professionalisiert – $[17.50\%]$; 3. Die von der Landreform Begünstigten wenden Beratungsangebote verstärkt an – $[17.50\%]$ (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2017b).

⁴⁸Nutzung von Buschbiomasse.

Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
	1. The measure has raised awareness at the political and societal level that biomass used in decommissioning can be used, and that is an essential prerequisite for economically sound shredding	[0%]	
	2. Selected value chains were piloted, including the production of animal feed, the modernised production of charcoal and the supply of wood chips for energy use	[0%]	
	3. Evidence of the economic and environmental sustainability of resource utilisation has been provided	[0%]	
	4. Furthermore, a central advisory service for farmers were set up, and business organisations strengthened so that private-sector activities can be meaningfully coordinated	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	5. With the support of the project, a national pastureland improvement and deforestation strategy was established as the basis for a future national decommissioning program ⁴⁹	[0%]	
Social Security Commission (Social Security Commission 2013 p. 47 ⁵⁰)			
Sick leave benefits		17.50%·74.10%	12.97 ⁵¹
	Total sick leave benefits		
Death benefits		17.50%·0.29%·74.10% ⁵²	0.04
	Total death benefits		

Continue on next page

⁴⁹Wirkung: 1. Durch die Maßnahme wurde auf politischer und gesellschaftlicher Ebene ein Bewusstsein dafür geschaffen, dass die bei der Entbuschung anfallende Biomasse genutzt werden kann und dies eine wichtig Voraussetzung für eine wirtschaftlich tragfähige Entbuschung ist – [0%], 2. Ausgewählte Wertschöpfungsketten wurden pilotiert, darunter die Herstellung von Tierfutter, die modernisierte Produktion von Holzkohle und die Lieferung von Holzschnitzeln zur energetischen Nutzung – [0%], 3. Nachweise über die wirtschaftliche und ökologische Tragfähigkeit der Ressourcenverwertung wurden erbracht – [0%], 4. Des Weiteren wurde ein zentraler Beratungsdienst für Farmer eingerichtet und Unternehmensverbände gestärkt, so dass privatwirtschaftliche Aktivitäten sinnvoll koordiniert werden können – [17.50%], 5. Mit Unterstützung des Vorhabens wurde eine nationale Strategie zur Weidelandverbesserung und Entbuschung als Grundlage eines zukünftigen nationalen Entbuschungsprogramms – [0%] (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) 2018a).

⁵⁰For details, see Social Security Commission 2013 p. 47. The 2012/2013 Social Security report was chosen because data was evaluated in 2012, and the report was published in 2013. This time frame of data evaluation and publication equals the time frame of the chosen multiplier within the national NDHS (MoHSS and ICF International 2014).

⁵¹See explanations in Section 19.2 under bullet point 10, “Sick leave calculation.”

⁵²Overall, yearly, 245 homicide cases have occurred as a result of GBV. Divided by the overall number of GBV cases of 85,191 [according to the NDHS data: 245; 33,099; 25,501; 26,346, displayed in Table 8.5] this is a factor of 0.29 per cent. See Chapter 8 for more detailed information. For the 74.10 per cent, please see explanations in Section 19.2 under bullet point 10, “Sick leave calculation.”

Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
Ministry of Education (Ministry of Finance 2018)			
Programmes and quality assurance		$1 \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%$	5.83
	1. To coordinate the management of the implementation of projects and programmes in the formal sector	[0%]	
	2. To coordinate assessment and counselling of children with special needs	$[\frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	3. To provide professional leadership and guidance	[0%]	
Adult education		$2 \cdot \frac{1}{4} \cdot 17.50\%$	8.75
	1. Development, printing, and production of teaching/learning materials	[0%]	
	2. Setting and maintaining standards in the provision of adult learning	$[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	3. Training of facilitators to effectively implement primary and post-literacy	[0%]	
	4. Family literacy	$[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
HIV and Aids monitoring unit		$3 \cdot \frac{1}{4} \cdot 4.52\%$	3.39
	1. Prevention Programmes of HIV and AIDS activities in the education sector consists of national and international events	$[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
	2. Training and development of materials for conducting awareness	[0%]	
	3. Knowledge of Lifeskills	$[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
	4. To strengthen the HIV and AIDS response	$[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 4.52\%]$	
Health and Social Services (Ministry of Finance 2018)			
Referral hospital services		$2 \cdot \frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%$	7.00
	1. The provision of skilled specialist services in all major clinical disciplines	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	2. Nuclear medicine diagnostic facilities	[0%]	
	3. Oncology treatment services	[0%]	
	4. Provision of full-scale intensive care services	[0%]	
	5. Emergency casualty evacuation from any centre in Namibia	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Regional health and social welfare services		$2 \cdot \frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%$	7.00
	1. Policy design	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	2. Standard setting and quality assurance	[0%]	
	3. Provision of technical support to the regional and district levels	[0%]	
	4. Resource and information management	[0%]	
	5. Networking and linkages with other sectors	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Development of Social Welfare services		$4 \cdot \frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%$	14.00
	1. Provision of emergency relief to the aged, disabled and other groups or groups or individuals in need	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	2. General social casework	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	3. Support for welfare organisations	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	4. Old age homes	[0%]	

Continue on next page

Continue Table 19.1

Category	Main operations	Formula	Multiplier [%]
	5. Children's homes	$[\frac{1}{5} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Special disease programmes		1.4.52%	4.52
	1. To formulate policies, guidelines, mobilise resources, provide training and technical support, and monitor and evaluate the national programmes which are geared towards preventing deaths, reduce illnesses, improve health and socioeconomic losses due to HIV	$[1 \cdot 4.52\%]$	
Poverty Eradication and Social Welfare [additional programmes (Ministry of Finance 2018)]			
Poverty Eradication and Social Welfare programmes		$3 \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%$	17.50
	1. Poverty Reduction Program	$[\frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	2. The Ministry plays a major role to encourage women and men from disadvantaged communities to embark on income-generating activities to promote self-employment among the urban and rural poor communities	$[\frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	3. Increase the capacity of individuals, communities, and all stakeholders involved in the delivery of such services. Mothers who have been caring for infants and young children for generations in communities	$[\frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
Social assistance		$[1 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot 17.50\%]$	11.29
	1. Timely payment and facilitating of Social Assistance	$[\frac{1}{2} \cdot 17.50\%]$	$[1 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot 0.29\% \cdot 17.50\%]$
	2. Funeral Benefits	$[17.50\% \cdot 0.29\%]$	⁵³
Food provision programmes		$2 \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%$	11.67
	1. On the functioning and operations of the Food Bank	$[\frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	2. To implement other poverty eradication programmes	$[\frac{1}{3} \cdot 17.50\%]$	
	3. To ensure that appropriate systems on the implementation of such programmes are put in place	$[0\%]$	
Food Bank		1.17.50%	17.50 ⁵⁴
	Overall Food Bank aid	$[1 \cdot 17.50\%]$	

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

⁵³Overall, yearly, 245 homicide cases have occurred as a result of GBV. Divided by the overall number of GBV cases of 85,191 [according to the NDHS data: 245; 33,099; 25,501; 26,346, displayed in Table 8.5] this is 0.29 per cent (Hartman 2016). See Chapter 8 for more detailed information.

⁵⁴The GBV prevalence ratio is applied to take in the cohort that is affected by GBV, and as a consequence, has to rely on Food Banks.

Summary

Chapter 19 has explicitly dealt with the multiplier data used to calculate the total expenses of the social welfare and special service costs. The derivation and the individual steps, based on which the specific multiplier factors are determined, were explained. Table 19.1 has holistically summarised the various sub-steps that were conducted. These sub-calculations were very important to compute the exact results shown in Chapter 10. In summary, it can be said that the category of the social welfare and special service costs is calculated very comprehensively and covers a wide variety of cost classes and relevant stakeholders.

20. Personal costs

20.1. Introduction

Chapter 20 provides detailed information on the personal costs and describes the application and adjustment of the unit-cost approach. Section 20.2 presents the calculation of the case numbers and multiplier data. The applied census data is explained in detail as well. Section 20.3 depicts the estimates of the unit costs in more detail. A distinction is made between unit costs for divorce, relocations, or damage to property. Finally, a summary and overview are provided.

20.2. Calculation of case numbers

All multiplier calculations are explained in Table 20.1

Table 20.1.: Results of the total personal costs.

Category	Cases [numbers]	Factor [%]	Relevant survivors [numbers]
Legal costs for a divorce, average case	women: 120,614; men: 10,324	women: 3.08; men: 1.82	3,903
Legal costs for a divorce, average opposed case		women: 1.32; men: 0.78	1,673
Protection Order	–	–	–
Relocation expenses	women: 120,614; men: 10,324	women: 4.4; men: 2.6	5,575
Property damage	women: 120,614	women only: 19.85	23,942
Phone security	–	–	–
Repossession	households: 13,295	women only: 17.50	2,327

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

1. Calculation of the relevant number of survivors for the category “Legal costs of a divorce”:
 - a) Case numbers: 120,614 women and 10,324 men got subjected to GBV. For detailed information, see Table 7.1 in Section 7.3 for women and Table 7.2 in Table 16.7. Please note, the case number of 10,324 men was used, as it represents the number of men in (previous) union /marriage. [In contrast, in the lost economic output category, the entire cohort of men suffering from GBV was chosen. See Section 7.3 for men].
 - b) The multiplier for an average divorce case: A] 4.40 per cent of women are divorced or separated (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 30). Seventy per cent of those have

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- had an opposed divorce case (The Namibian High Court [2018](#)). B] 2.60 per cent of men are divorced or separated (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#), p. 30), of which again 70 per cent have an opposed divorce case, according to records of The Namibian High Court [2018](#). As a result, the formula applied was A] 4.40 per cent [of the respective number of affected] ·70 per cent and B] 2.60 per cent [of the respective number of affected] ·70 per cent. Hence, the used multipliers are 3.08 per cent [70 per cent of 4.40 per cent] and 1.82 per cent [70 per cent of 2.60 per cent], respectively.
- c) The multiplier for an average opposed divorce case: 4.40 per cent of women are divorced or separated (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#), p. 30). Thirty per cent of which have an opposed divorce case (The Namibian High Court [2018](#)). 2.60 per cent of men are divorced or separated (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#), p. 30), of which again 30 per cent have an opposed divorce case, according to data of The Namibian High Court [2018](#). Thus, the applied formula was A] 4.40 per cent [of the respective number of affected] ·30 per cent and B] 2.60 per cent [of the respective number of affected] ·30 per cent. The used multipliers are 1.32 per cent [30 per cent of 4.40 per cent] and 0.78 per cent [30 per cent of 2.60 per cent], respectively.
2. The number of individuals that apply for a protection order: it was not calculated as there are no fees associated with receiving a protection order in Namibia (Namibia Paralegal Association (NPA) [2012](#), p. 56). The respective government expenditures have already been calculated in Chapter [9](#).
3. Relevant number of survivors for relocation expenses:
- a) Case numbers: see information under the relevant number of survivors for legal costs of a divorce.
- b) Multipliers: 4.40 per cent of women and 2.60 per cent of men are divorced or separated (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#), p. 30). It is assumed that both women and men subjected to GBV relocate due to divorce and separation. There is no official data on how many people relocate because of GBV. In a conservative approach, the multipliers for the average opposed divorce case were therefore taken as a proxy, and are 1.32 per cent and 0.78 per cent, respectively.
4. Relevant number of property damages:
- a) Case numbers: only the overall amount of women [120,614] who got subjected to GBV is used, as Access Economics [2004a](#), p. 45 provides data for women only. For further information, see Table [7.1](#) in Section [7.3](#).
- b) Multiplier: according to Australian research, 39.70 per cent of women who experienced violence by a previous partner had their property damaged or destroyed. In a conservative estimate, the paper discounts this percentage by a further 50 per cent. See Henderson [2000](#), p. 45 and Access Economics [2004a](#), p. 45. Hence, the factor of 19.85 is used [1](#).
5. Relevant number of repossession cases:
- a) Case numbers:

¹As a substitute because the Namibian data was not available. U.K. data indicates that women, despite their ethnic background, are equally affected by GBV, suggesting that the British and other global results on GBV are applicable across ethnic groups. See Chapter [6](#)

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- i. Twenty-three per cent of households [125,425] owed outstanding balances in one form of debt or another in 2015 (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) [2016](#) p. 14, 80). Household-level includes both genders, men and women. The data was chosen as information on debt that does not stringently separate between both genders. Further, debts and loans are, in most cases, taken on a household level since most marriages are in a community of property, according to The Namibian High Court [2018](#).
 - ii. However, the Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) [2016](#) p. 14, 80 data was surveyed in 2015. The 2015 data is used because they were the most holistic findings available at the point of research. However, the output is indicated as a proportion of the 2018 GDP. Hence, the numbers were adjusted to 2018 figures. The Namibian 2018 population was 2,448,255. There were 2,314,904 citizens in 2015 (World Bank [2020c](#)). The adjustment factor is around 1.06, and all findings were inflated by factor 1.06 to estimate the households [132,951] that owned outstanding balances.
 - iii. Further, overall, ten per cent of indebted households went through the process of repossession, according to the African Auction Authority. Precisely ten per cent of all bank-funded cars were repossessed, according to the reference (Ngatjiheue [2015](#)). Due to the lack of other valid data, this ratio serves as a proxy and is applied to the overall household consumption level. Possible distortions are acknowledged. Thus, the calculation used is 132,951 households [households with outstanding balances in 2018] · ten per cent [repossession ratio] is 13,295 households.
- b) Multiplier: 17.50 per cent of women have experienced physical and sexual violence enacted by all intimate partners, family members, or third parties over the past 12 months. In detail, 3.70 per cent of women have experienced sexual violence (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) p. 300), and 13.80 per cent have suffered from physical violence (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) p. 298). This 17.50 per cent ratio is applied to all Namibian households that got repossessed (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) [2016](#)).²

20.3. Calculation of unit costs

Unit costs were calculated for the following categories:

1. Unit cost of divorce: costs are based on a survey from the Legal Assistance Center. Rudd, Hubbard, and Engelbrecht [2013](#) have carried out research with legal agencies to evaluate data on the average cost of an uncontested divorce, which is between N\$ 5,000 and N\$ 10,000. For opposed cases, it is, on average N\$ 30,000 and goes until N\$ 100,000 occasionally. Based on the number of cases, the median value of N\$ 7,500 was formed for the first value. Based on the assumptions in this research paper, the conservative

²The 17.5 per cent factor was also surveyed at the household level (MoHSS and ICF International [2014](#) p. 4).

lower value of N\$ 30,000 was used for the second cost section. Both values were linked to the CPI in order to level figures from 2013 to 2018.

2. Unit cost of a protection order: currently, it is not necessary to be represented by a lawyer to apply and qualify for a protection order (Dianne and Rimmer [2007](#), p. 25). Further, there are no fees associated with receiving such support (Namibia Paralegal Association (NPA) [2012](#), p. 56). In summary, the introduction has made it inexpensive to assist citizens in receiving such protection (Immigration and Refugee Board of Canada [2012](#)). The costs that occurred to the government were calculated already in Chapter [9](#).
3. Unit cost of relocation expenses: unit cost derives from the quotations of moving companies, conducted in March 2018. The baseline is the average price [N\$ 4,500] for a two-bedroom apartment (Breuer [2018](#)). Although family members and friends in most cases support individuals to relocate, the factor of N\$ 4,500 is applied nevertheless. Since the costs for women who cannot afford a relocation or depend on the free-of-charge help of family and friends should not be left out in this estimation. Cost for the community as a whole is created. If the before-mentioned survivors had income, they could have afforded a translocation without relying on in-kind/free of charge support. In this way, the costs incurred for family members are also recognised and taken into account in the calculation.
4. Unit cost of property damage: no data for Namibia or Southern Africa was available; thus, the unit cost from the Access Economics [2004a](#) and Henderson [2000](#), p. 45 paper is used³ and were converted into 2018 Namibia dollars. According to Access Economics [2004a](#), p. 7, the overall cost of destroyed and damaged property was A\$ 243.7 million for 88,586 affected female survivors, which translates into a unit cost of A\$ 2,751 per woman. However, Henderson [2000](#), p. 45 calculated the cost of property damage to be A\$ 1,092.05 per survivor in his paper. This figure is used as baseline data. The difference in the data record and Henderson's calculation should only be briefly addressed here. The Figures are available for female survivors only. A possible distortion is acknowledged.

Table 20.2.: Overview of unit cost calculations: property damages.

Unit cost	Unit cost, per person [A\$] in 2000	Unit cost, per person [N\$] in 2002	Unit cost, per person [N\$] in 2018
Result	1,092.05	4,917 ⁴	13,866 ⁵

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

According to a qualitative survey in South Africa, damage to property as a result of GBV was the third most frequently registered violation. Property damage most often occurs in conjunction with other types of offences, such as substance abuse. Still, according to

³The overall cost of the damaged or destroyed property was US\$ 243.7 million from 2002 to 2003, according to Access Economics [2004a](#), p. 45.

⁴The PPP conversion factor from A\$ to US\$ in 2002 was 1.34 (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) [2019](#)). The PPP conversion factor from US\$ to N\$ in 2002 was 3.36 (World Bank [2019a](#)). Hence, the applied formula was A\$ 1,092.05 · 1.34 factor [A\$–US\$] · 3.36 factor [US\$–N\$], which is rounded N\$ 4,917.

⁵The 2002 figure was levelled by the Namibian CPI for the period of 2002 to 2018 [CPI Namibia 2018/CPI Namibia 2002; $152.3/54.02 = 2.82$] (World Bank [2020d](#)).

Makofane [2015](#), cases are not treated with the required importance by police officers, which leads again to an underreporting of cases.

5. Unit cost of Phone Security: Such security measures are not comprehensively accessible in Namibia (Solidaritätsdienst International e. V. (SODI) [2018](#)) and hence, were not estimated.
6. Unit cost of repossession: The data was extracted from the 2015 Namibia Household Income and Expenditure Survey and was adjusted to 2018 figures.

Table 20.3.: Overview of the average consumption calculation: Personal costs.

	Average per capita consumption [N\$], in 2015	Relevant average per capita consumption [N\$], in 2015	Relevant average per capita consumption [N\$], in 2018
Result	28,434 (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) 2016 p. 96)	12,682 ⁶	14,965 ⁷

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.
Source: Own representation.

20.4. Summary

Chapter [20](#) described the calculation of the unit costs in further detail. The various cost classes in this category and, if required, their conversions were presented. Then the calculation of the case numbers and multiplier data for the individual subcategories was explained in more detail. These sub-calculations were very important to compute the exact results displayed in Chapter [11](#)

In the following, Chapter [21](#) will provide more detailed information on how the Physical and Emotional Impact was calculated.

⁶According to the 2015 Namibia Household Income and Expenditure Survey, the annual average consumption is 31.80 per cent on housing; 5.30 per cent on furniture and equipment; and 7.50 per cent on transport and communication, which is 44.60 per cent in total (Namibia Statistics Agency (NSA) [2016](#) p. 100). According to the African Auction Authority records, it is the computed household consumption ratio, which is relevant for external borrowing and eventual repossession. Hence, the used formula was 44.60 per cent [share of the relevant consumption] of N\$ 28,434 [in 2015 figures], which is around N\$ 12,682 [in 2015 figures].

⁷The factor of the Namibian 2018 CPI [152.3] and the Namibian 2015 CPI [128.9] is rounded 1.18 (World Bank [2016](#)). Hence, the employed formula was N\$ 12,682 [in 2015 figures] · 1.18, which is rounded N\$ 14,965 [in 2018 figures].

21. Intangibles, physical, and emotional impact

21.1. Introduction

Chapter 21 describes the more detailed information necessary to calculate the intangible, physical, and emotional impact cost category. Section 21.2 presents the calculation of the case numbers in more detail. They involve the following criminological classes: homicide, wounding, sexual offences, and common assault. Section 21.3 describes the application and adaptation of the QALY-loss-based WTP approach. It explains the QALY data, which have a closer link to GBV, and describes their transferability to the context of this study. Data that had to be adjusted to the Namibian context are also presented. This is primarily data related to HIV/AIDS. This adjustment is mainly reflected in the QALY values of rape and sexual assault. Section 21.4 presents the calculation of the unit costs in more detail, and the conversion of individual datasets is explained.

21.2. Calculation of case numbers

Similar case numbers and multipliers were already used in the calculations for health service costs in Chapter 8¹. See Table 21.1 for an overview assessment.

Table 21.1.: Overview of case numbers: intangibles.

Category	Cases [numbers] ²
Homicide	245
Wounding	33,099 ³
Sexual offences	25,501 ⁴
Common assault	26,346 ⁵

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.

Source: Own representation.

¹For more details, see Section 8.3 on the case numbers and the respective multiplier calculations.

21.3. QALY data on GBV

Section 21.3 presents the transferability of GBV-QALY data in greater detail.

Transferability of GBV-QALY data

It is assumed that British research can be transferred to other international settings, as specific GBV patterns are observed worldwide to be alike (Heise, Pitanguy, and Germain 1994). For detailed information, read Chapter 6. Globally, GBV has similar consequences on an individual's physical and mental health state. As a result, a transferability of QALY data is presumed. The following section lists the available primary QALY data on GBV.

Primary QALY data on GBV

As described in Sections 5.5 and 6.2 the primary data derived from research of Bolling, Mattinson, and Myhill 2002; Budd *et al.* 2000; Dolan *et al.* 2005; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005. In particular, the QALY categories of wounding, common assault, rape, and sexual assault have been employed. See Table 21.2 for a detailed overview.

Table 21.2.: Overview of utilised QALY data.

Category	Original QALY loss, in years of full health (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005)	Adjusted QALY loss, in years of full health ⁶
Homicide	–	–
Wounding	0.033	0.033
Sexual offences ⁷	–	0.686
Common assault	0.007	0.007

Source: Own representation based on Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005

Data had to be adjusted in order to be applicable. The details of this alignment will be explained in the next paragraph.

QALY data on rape and sexual assault

It is not clear what precisely the Namibian NDHS under its term “sexual offences” includes, as the data do not distinguish between rape and sexual assault incidents (MoHSS and ICF International 2014, p. 300) as Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005, p. 7, 19, 43 do. Therefore, a QALY called “sexual offences,” which symbolises the mean value of the rape and sexual assault

²See Table 8.4. The calculation of case numbers is based on NDHS data.

³The figure comprehends women aged 15 to 49 years (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b).

⁴The number reflects survivors that are 20 to 49 years (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018a).

⁵The figure comprehends women aged 15 to 49 years (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2018b).

⁶Own calculation.

⁷For more detailed information, see Table 21.3.

value has been computed, based on the findings of Dolan *et al.* [2005] Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005], of which Table [21.3] provides a summary.

Table 21.3.: Utilised QALY data: sexual offences.

Category	Original QALY loss, in years of full health (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005])	Adjusted QALY loss, in years of full health ⁸
Sexual offences	- ⁹	0.686 ¹⁰

Source: Own representation.

Nevertheless, if the NDHS term and data include rape cases only, then this approach leads to an underestimation of cost, as the QALY loss for rape is with 1.211¹¹ lost years, much higher than the one for sexual assault with 0.164 years lost. However, the NDHS data do not specify whether they cover both rape and sexual assault incidents. Hence, the mean value is used. In addition, within this mean-value approach, the HIV factor has been adjusted again to reflect the Namibian reality better.

Altered HIV factor within the QALY data on rape

The rape and sexual assault QALY has been changed to the Namibian situation, as the HIV ratio was adjusted to the local prevalence¹² Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] p. 34 have evaluated an HIV prevalence of 0.000001 for the crime types of rape and sexual assault¹³ However, HIV/AIDS infections have a tremendous negative impact on the Namibian population, and prevalence is higher compared to the E.U. Hence, a higher HIV ratio of 0.258, based on Jewkes *et al.* [2010] p. 6 research in South Africa, is applied. This adjustment was only made for the rape, not for the sexual assault QALY [0.160], as the latter one does not contain an HIV determinant, according to Dolan *et al.* [2005] Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005], Table [21.4] presents the calculation of the lost QALYs caused by rape.

⁸Own calculation.

⁹The authors Dolan *et al.* [2005] Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] state the QALYs of rape with 0.561 and sexual assault with 0.160. However, the Namibian NDHS sexual crime primary ratios do not distinguish between the two, and there are not detailed Namibian ratios.

¹⁰It is the mean value of the QALY for rape with 1.211 [See own calculations in Table [21.4], and of sexual assault with 0.160 [See Dolan *et al.* [2005] p. 965; and Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] p. 34].

¹¹For more information, see Table [21.4].

¹²See Section [6.4] for more details.

¹³Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] base their assumptions on reviews from the Department of Health, HIV Surveys Steering Group and others [1999] and Fong [2001] in Dolan *et al.* [2005] p. 974. Both the Department of Health, HIV Surveys Steering Group and others [1999] and Fong [2001] have surveyed their data in the U.K.

¹⁴The data is derived from the findings of Dolan *et al.* [2005] p. 973 f. and Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] p. 34.

¹⁵The figure is computed based on the multiplication of the QALY loss in years and the rape prevalence. The numbers are rounded to three decimal places to achieve more accuracy.

¹⁶For further details, see the information under Section [12.5.3]

¹⁷Dolan *et al.* [2005] p. 975; and Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005] p. 34 each list the factor of 0.561. Nevertheless, the summary of the presented numbers indicates a factor of 0.559 only. However, since the

Table 21.4.: Calculation of the Namibian QALY-data: rape.

Health states ¹⁴	QALY loss, in years	Rape prevalence, original	Prevalence- based QALY loss ¹⁵	Rape prevalence, adapted	Prevalence- based QALY loss
Physical health status					
Broken bones	0.0228	0.037	[0.001]	0.037	[0.001]
Broken nose	0.0066	–	–	–	–
Minor bruise/black eye	0.0014	0.192	[0.000]	0.192	[0.000]
Severe bruising	0.0057	0.111	[0.001]	0.111	[0.001]
Scratches	0.0002	–	–	–	–
Cuts	0.0026	–	–	–	–
Broken or lost teeth	0.0021	–	–	–	–
Chipped teeth	0.0011	–	–	–	–
Concussion	0.0060	–	–	–	–
Other injury	0.0019	0.033	[0.000]	0.033	[0.000]
HIV diagnosis	2.5260	0.000	[0.000]	0.2580	[0.652]
Gonorrhea	0.0002	0.040	[0.000]	0.040	[0.000]
Chlamydial infection	0.0002	0.020	[0.000]	0.020	[0.000]
Trichomoniasis	0.0002	0.120	[0.000]	0.120	[0.000]
Bacterial vaginosis	0.0002	0.190	[0.000]	0.190	[0.000]
Abortion	0.0122	0.025	[0.000]	0.025	[0.000]
Miscarriage	0.0122	0.006	[0.000]	0.006	[0.000]
Psychological health state					
Acute stress disorder	0.0100	1.000	[0.010]	1.000	[0.010]
Mild/moderate PTSD	0.3670	0.343	[0.126]	0.343	[0.126]
Severe PTSD	1.4398	0.147	[0.212]	0.147	[0.212]
Drug abuse	1.1559	0.023	[0.027]	0.023	[0.027]
Alcohol abuse ¹⁶	0.8256	0.018	[0.015]	0.018	[0.015]
Depression	0.3439	0.200	[0.069]	0.200	[0.069]
Suicide	17.6411	0.001	[0.018]	0.001	[0.018]
Obesity/eating disorder	0.6422	0.050	[0.032]	0.050	[0.032]
Anxiety	0.4841	0.050	[0.024]	0.050	[0.024]
Sexual dysfunction	0.0324	0.780	[0.025]	0.780	[0.025]
Sum		0.561	[0.559] ¹⁷		1.211

Source: Own representation based on Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns²⁰⁰⁵, p. 34.

Discrepancies arose as well as for the sexual assault figure of 0.160. Dolan *et al.*²⁰⁰⁵; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns²⁰⁰⁵ list that number; however, a summary of the sub-factors has resulted in an outcome of 0.164. However, since the 0.160 factor is utilised in the primary research of Dolan *et al.*²⁰⁰⁵; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns²⁰⁰⁵, it is applied in this study as well. A possible distortion is acknowledged.

factor 0.561 is used in the primary literature of Dolan *et al.*²⁰⁰⁵; Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns²⁰⁰⁵ it is also utilised in this calculation. The same concern occurred for the sexual assault figure of 0.160 as well. See Table^{21.5}.

Table 21.5.: Calculation of the Namibian QALY-data: sexual assault.

Health states	QALY loss, in years	Sexual assault prevalence, original	Prevalence- based QALY loss
Physical health status			
Broken bones	0.0228	0.007	[0.000]
Broken nose	0.0066	–	–
Minor bruise/black eye	0.0014	0.036	[0.000]
Severe bruising	0.0057	0.021	[0.000]
Scratches	0.0002	–	–
Cuts	0.0026	–	–
Broken or lost teeth	0.0021	–	–
Chipped teeth	0.0011	–	–
Concussion	0.0060	–	–
Other injury	0.0019	0.006	[0.000]
HIV diagnosis	2.5260	¹⁸	–
Gonorrhea	0.0002	–	–
Chlamydial infection	0.0002	–	–
Trichomoniasis	0.0002	–	–
Bacterial vaginosis	0.0002	–	–
Abortion	0.0122	–	–
Miscarriage	0.0122	–	–
Psychological health state			
Acute stress disorder	0.0100	1.000	[0.010]
Mild/moderate PTSD	0.3670	0.157	[0.058]
Severe PTSD	1.4398	0.067	[0.096]
Drug abuse	1.1559	–	–
Alcohol abuse	0.8256	–	–
Depression	0.3439	–	–
Suicide	17.6411	–	–
Obesity/eating disorder	0.6422	–	–
Anxiety	0.4841	–	–
Sexual dysfunction	0.0324	–	–
Sum			[0.164] ¹⁹

Source: Own representation based on Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#) p. 34.

Again, no variance was detected for the factors of wounding 0.033, common assault 0.007, and robbery 0.028 (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#) p. 34). Section [21.4](#) explains the calculation of the unit cost in greater detail.

¹⁸There was no need to alter the sexual assault figure, as this calculation does not include HIV data (Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#) p. 34).

¹⁹Dolan *et al.* [2005](#) p. 965; and Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns [2005](#) p. 34 list a factor of 0.160. Nevertheless, the summary of the presented numbers provides a factor of 0.164. However, since the value of 0.160 is used in other research, it is also utilised in this paper. It is assumed that the deviation occurred due to potential rounding errors in the papers' QALY data.

21.4. Calculation of costs

The unit costs are derived from international research on GBV. All details on how data was transferred to Namibia are summarised in Table 21.6.

Table 21.6.: Adjustments of the British QALY data: PPP.

Unit cost	Unit cost, per person [£], in 1997	Unit cost, per person [N\$], in 1997	Unit cost, per person [N\$], in 2018
Result	80,620 ²⁰	276,527 ²¹	671,961 ²²

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.
Source: Own representation.

However, using a unit value of N\$671,961 translates into a GDP share of 4.38 per cent. Therefore, only using the PPP for the intangibles leads to distortion, and an alternative is applied. The details are presented in Table 21.7.

Table 21.7.: Adjustments of the British QALY data: GDP share.

Unit cost	Unit cost, per person [£], in 1997	GDP share [Namibia – U.K.] per capita [£], in 1997	Unit cost, per person [N\$], in 1997	Unit cost, per person [N\$], in 2018
Result	80,620 ²³	7,062 ²⁴	24,223 ²⁵	58,862 ²⁶

Note: Figures may contain rounding errors.
Source: Own representation.

²⁰The unit cost per QALY was £80,620 based on Carthy *et al.* 1998, in Dubourg, Hamed, and Thorns 2005 p. 34. Carthy *et al.* 1998 p. 195 use a representative sample of 167 respondents chosen by professional market research organisations. It is acknowledged that the period of data collection is out-of-date. Nevertheless, prices are updated and transferred to 2018 Namibia dollars. Further, does the GBV literature, as in Walby and Olive 2014 still applies the results.

²¹The PPP for Namibia was set in relation to the PPP of Great Britain for the year 1997 to transfer the research to Namibia. The PPP conversion factor from £ to N\$ in 1997 was £1–N\$3.43. [Based on – US\$1.0 = £0.7; US\$1.0 = N\$2.4] (World Bank 2018h). Hence, the applied formula was £80,620 · 3.43 factor [£ N\$], which is rounded N\$276,527.

²²The Namibian 1997 CPI was 62.6 [based on the World Bank's 2010 CPI = 100]. CPI's were only measured since 2002 for Namibia. Hence, the CPI figure of 62.6, which corresponds to 2002, serves as a substitute. The Namibian 2018 CPI was 152.3 [based on the World Bank's 2010 CPI = 100]. The fraction number of the Namibian 2018 and 2002 CPI [152.3/62.6] is 2.43 [rounded] (World Bank 2016). Hence, N\$276,527 [in 1997] · 2.43 is around N\$671,961 [in 2018 prices].

21.5. Summary

Chapter 21 provided more information regarding the category of intangibles, physical, and emotional impact. The calculation of the case numbers is based on census and police data. Both records are included in the estimation of the case numbers to compute costs that are as realistic as possible. The transferability of data to the Namibian context was discussed in more detail. The HIV/AIDS data adaptation has been described, which is an underlying value in calculating specific QALY data. In the further course, the calculation of the unit costs was explained. The main focus was laid on PPP factors and matters around the gross domestic product share.

Chapter 22 provides more information and data on the calculation of the second-generation costs.

²³See Table 21.6

²⁴The GDP share per capita approach was chosen as the conversion of PPPs alone would not have adequately reflected the purchase price differences between the two countries for the category of intangibles, as such values are not part of the PPP's basket. For more information on PPPs, see Section 6.3. The British GDP per capita [in current US\$] in 1997 was rounded US\$ 26,622 (World Bank 2018c). The Namibian GDP per capita [in current US\$] in 1997 was around US\$ 2,332 (World Bank 2018c). The economic ratio, namely the GDP share [2,332/26,622], is 8.76 per cent, and 8.76 per cent of £ 80,620 is £ 7,062. This share-approach was only conducted for this cost class, as PPPs turned out not to be suitable for the category of intangibles.

²⁵Based on that share, the PPPs for Namibia was set in relation to the PPPs of Great Britain for the year 1997 in order to transfer the research to Namibia. The PPP conversion factor from £ to N\$ in 1997 was £ 1–N\$ 3.43 [N\$ 2.4/0.7]. [Based on – US\$ 1.0 = £ 0.7; US\$ 1.0 = N\$ 2.4] (World Bank 2018h). Hence, the applied formula was £ 7,062 · 3.43 factor [£–N\$], which is rounded N\$ 24,223.

²⁶The Namibian 1997 CPI was 62.6 [based on the World Bank's 2010 CPI = 100]. Again, CPI's were only measured since 2002 for Namibia. Hence, the CPI figure of 62.6, which corresponds to 2002, serves as a substitute. The Namibian 2018 CPI was 152.3 [based on the World Bank's 2010 CPI = 100]. The fraction number of the Namibian 2018 and 2002 CPI [152.3/62.6] is 2.43 [rounded] (World Bank 2016). Hence, N\$ 24,223 [in 1997] · 2.43 is around N\$ 58,862 [in 2018 prices].

22. Second-generation costs

22.1. Introduction

Chapter [22](#) presents all other important information and data for estimating the costs for the second generation, and Section [22.2](#) provides more information on the Population Attributable Fractions [PAF] data.

22.2. Calculation of case numbers

Calculation of Population Attributable Fractions [PAFs] data

PAFs were applied to determine the dimension of morbidity and mortality. All PAF equations contain (1) Relative risk [RR] of an adverse health state [e.g., depression] based on exposure to a risk factor [violence against minors], or an odds ratio [OR] which was converted into an estimate of the relative risk [RR]; and (2) a measure of prevalence. The prevalence was linked to the DALY losses surveyed in the Global Burden of Disease report. The data is restricted to depressive disorders, anxiety disorders, alcohol use disorders, drug use disorders, STDs [excluding HIV], HIV, interpersonal violence and self-harm. Further, Fang *et al.* [2017](#) use the Cape Area Panel Study [CAPS] as an additional data analyses on violence against children. The CAPS derives from a representative sample of teenagers in the Cape Town area, as they developed from adolescence to adulthood. The survey was conducted in five successive waves from 2002 to 2009. Deriving from the CAPS data, Fang *et al.* [2017](#) conducted linear models [for binary outcome variables] or linear regression [for continuous outcome variables] to calculate the linkage between the different types of violence against children and the related adverse consequences. Later, the Heckman two-stage approach was applied to correct for selection bias. Regressions were controlled for determinants, as socio-demographic or biological confounding factors.

The PAF proportions were applied to the census data and are depicted in Table [22.1](#)

Table 22.1.: World Bank census data for Namibia in 2018.

Country Name	Series Name	Year of 2018
Namibia	Population ages 15–19, female	122,797
	Population ages 15–19, male	121,136
	Population ages 20–24, female	123,446
	Population ages 20–24, male	119,975
	Population ages 25–29, female	112,697
	Population ages 25–29, male	108,174
Overall		708,225

Note: Data from the database – Population estimates and projections (World Bank 2018g).

Source: Own representation.

Summary

Chapter 22 showcased the census data briefly and the available data basis for transferring the PAF data to the Namibian context.

In order to continue, the final Chapter 23 deals with certain general data calculations. It presents the databases that were of importance for conducting sub-calculations to compare the studies included in the literature overview, which are presented in Chapters 3 to 15.

23. Other data

Introduction

Chapter 23 presents the sub-calculations that were made to determine specific census data. These census data were of importance to calculate several prevalence rates in Chapters 3 and 15, as not all studies included in this literature review showed an overall prevalence rate needed for systematic comparison. The used databases and computed figures are depicted in Tables 23.1 to 23.7

Census data on the United States

Table 23.1.: World Bank census data for the United States in 2003.

Country Name	Country Code	Series Name	2003
United States	U.S.	Age population, age 18, female, interpolated	2,024,891
		Age population, age 19, female, interpolated	2,007,342
		Female population 20–24	9,751,441
		Female population 25–29	9,547,594
		Female population 30–34	9,859,293
		Female population 35–39	10,633,424
		Female population 40–44	11,337,479
		Female population 45–49	10,893,618
		Female population 50–54	9,757,071
		Female population 55–59	8,127,951
		Female population 60–64	6,219,799
		Female population 65–69	5,174,968
		Female population 70–74	4,721,410
		Female population 75–79	4,275,441
Female population 80+	6,424,531		
Overall			110,756,253

Note: Last Updated – 09/20/2018.

Source: Own representation based on data from World Bank's database – Population estimates and projections (World Bank 2018g).

Table 23.2.: World Bank census data for the United States in 1993 and 1996.

Country Name	Country Code	Series Name	1993
United States	U.S.	Population ages 15–64, female	84,926,398
		Population ages 65 and above, female	19,531,693
			104,458,091
Country Name	Country Code	Series Name	1996
United States	U.S.	Population ages 15–64 females	84,926,398
		Age population, age 19, female, interpolated	1,788,743
		Female population 20–24	9,027,753
		Female population 25–29	9,576,302
		Female population 30–34	10,778,488
		Female population 35–39	11,233,625
		Female population 40–44	10,435,603
		Female population 45–49	9,218,850
		Female population 50–54	7,393,820
		Female population 55–59	5,931,213
		Female population 60–64	5,290,473
		Female population 65–69	5,311,984
		Female population 70–74	4,984,860
		Female population 75–79	4,050,586
Female population 80+	5,664,367		
	Overall	102,480,546	

Note: Last Updated – 09/20/2018.

Source: Own representation based on data from World Bank's database – Population estimates and projections (World Bank 2018g).

Census data on Australia

Table 23.3.: World Bank census data for Australia in 2012.

Country Name	Country Code	Series Name	2012
Australia	AUS	Female population 15–19	723,201
		Female population 20–24	794,483
		Female population 25–29	837,533
		Female population 30–34	778,528
		Female population 35–39	797,169
		Female population 40–44	792,545
		Female population 45–49	783,026
		Female population 50–54	763,721
		Female population 55–59	684,148
		Female population 60–64	625,441
		Female population 65–69	503,374
		Female population 70–74	376,030
		Female population 75–79	302,782
		Female population 80+	524,432
Overall			9,286,413

Note: Last Updated – 09/20/2018.

Source: Own representation based on data from World Bank's database – Population estimates and projections (World Bank 2018g).

Table 23.4.: World Bank census data for Australia in 2021.

Country Name	Country Code	Series Name	2021
Australia	AUS	Female population 15–19	760,000
		Female population 20–24	784,000
		Female population 25–29	863,000
		Female population 30–34	930,000
		Female population 35–39	932,000
		Female population 40–44	829,000
		Female population 45–49	845,000
		Female population 50–54	799,000
		Female population 55–59	788,000
		Female population 60–64	734,000
		Female population 65–69	649,000
		Female population 70–74	575,000
		Female population 75–79	419,000
		Female population 80+	618,000
Overall			10,525,000

Note: Last Updated – 09/20/2018.

Source: Own representation based on data from World Bank's database – Population estimates and projections (World Bank 2018g).

Census data on Denmark

Table 23.5.: Total number of survivors for Denmark in 2010.

Cost component	Survivors [numbers]
Health care contacts due to injury by violence	5,690
Attributable health care costs	5,210
Labour market	
Income impact	3,600
Production loss	2,225
Judicial system	
Police reported physical violence	3,500
Police reported threats	3,900
Domestic disputes	8,775
Restrictions imposed by police	400
Police reported rape	400
Shelters	1,800
	35,500

Source: Own representation based on category data of Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010 p. 11.

Table 23.6.: Prevalence ratio for Denmark in 2010.

Country Name	Country Code	Series Name	2010
Denmark	DNK	Age population, age 16, female, interpolated	34,683
		Age population, age 17, female, interpolated	34,753
		Age population, age 18, female, interpolated	34,455
		Age population, age 19, female, interpolated	33,917
		Female population 20–24	162,066
		Female population 25–29	154,838
		Female population 30–34	172,856
		Female population 35–39	193,064
		Female population 40–44	197,943
		Female population 45–49	202,840
		Female population 50–54	181,169
		Female population 55–59	174,279
		Female population 60–64	185,492
		Overall	1,762,355
Survivors	35,500		
Prevalence [%]	2.01		

Note: Last Updated – 09/20/2018.

Source: Own representation based on data from World Bank's database – Population estimates and projections. In detail, the calculation is based on the World Bank's 2010 census data (World Bank 2018g) and category data of Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010 p. 11.

Census data on Sweden

Table 23.7.: Prevalence ratio for Sweden in 2004.

Country Name	Country Code	Series Name	2004
Sweden	SWE	Female population 15–19	277,805
		Female population 20–24	252,938
		Female population 25–29	270,767
		Female population 30–34	304,074
		Female population 35–39	314,478
		Female population 40–44	302,218
		Female population 45–49	286,029
		Female population 50–54	293,694
		Female population 55–59	315,482
		Female population 60–64	264,769
		Overall	2,882,254
	Survivors per annum ¹	75,000	
	Prevalence [%]	2.60	

Note: Last Updated – 09/20/2018.

Source: Own representation based on World Bank's database – Population estimates and projections. In detail, the ratio was calculated based on the World Bank's 2004 census data (World Bank 2018g).

Summary

Chapter 23 presented the more detailed survey that was conducted for, e.g. the United States of America to compute the 2003 data for the Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (NCIPC) 2003 study, or to calculate the 1996 census data for the works of Miller, Cohen, and Wiersema 1996; Miller, Fisher, and Cohen 2001 [see Tables 23.1 and 23.2]. Tables 23.3 and 23.4 showed the underlying calculations required for the Australian publications of KPMG Australia 2016 National Council to Reduce Violence against Women and their Children (NCRVAW&C) 2009. Tables 23.5 and 23.6 presented the data needed for a more in-depth analysis of the Danish Helweg-Larsen *et al.* 2010 study. Table 23.7 displays the census data for Sweden that was necessary to analyse the publication of Envall and Eriksson 2006.

In summary, it can be said that this Appendix, from Chapters 15 to 23 provided more detailed information on the calculations performed in the main sections, which were not included in Chapters 3 to 13 due to their level of detail.

¹According to Envall and Eriksson (Envall and Eriksson 2006, p. 7).

24. Summary

24.1. Summary in English

Worldwide, an estimated one in three women will be physically or sexually abused in their lifetime, most often by family members or intimate partners (García-Moreno *et al.* 2013). Hence, such violence is a problem of significant magnitude.

GBV is not only a violation of human rights, but it also poses costs to society as a whole. In summary, this paper attempts to estimate the full range of its expenses at the individual, community, and macro-level by bringing together findings from different sectors, including public health, sociology, psychology, and economics, to holistically identify the negative impacts of GBV.

GBV has tremendous consequences on the survivors¹ physical and mental health (Heise, Pitanguy, and Germain 1994 World Health Organization (WHO) 2009). Such violence does not only causes expenses to complainants in terms of lost economic output or personal losses, but the violence creates a cost to society as a whole too. GBV goes beyond today's time frame and triggers costs across generations (Dunkle *et al.* 2004). In brief, it restrains a whole society from unfolding its true potential because it hampers the economic growth and development of a nation across generations. GBV disproportionately affects low- and middle-income countries and is likely to be more severe in developing and emerging nations. For instance, calculations of the cost of violence are 1.35 per cent of the Gross Domestic Product [GDP] in Australia (KPMG Australia 2016), 3.19 per cent in Vietnam (Duvvury and Carney 2012), 3.93 per cent in Colombia (Ribero and Sánchez Torres 2004), and up to 1.30 per cent in South Africa (KPMG South Africa 2014). For Namibia, no such data exist yet, although the problem is a pressing one, as GBV prevalence ratios are high. Overall, 20 per cent of ever-married Namibian women have experienced physical or sexual violence enacted by their current or most recent husband during the past 12 months (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 310).

However, this study's definition goes beyond the mere spousal violence and includes abuse enacted by third persons. Third parties can, for instance, include the stepfather, police, or soldiers (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 299)² In sum, this study's prevalence ratio comprises:

¹See the definition of the survivor term in Chapter 2

²See Chapter 2 on the GBV definition.

17.50 per cent of women who experienced physical and sexual violence, which was enacted by all intimate partners, family members, or third parties within the past 12 months.³

Computing the cost of GBV provides a better basis for policy action and implementation. It provides information for policymakers to carry out informed decision-making, including the formulation of targeted spending priorities. The data further assists in conducting a comparative evaluation of the impacts of preventive measures. In sum, international costing studies indicate the implications for non-intervention for today and future generations (García-Moreno *et al.* 2005; World Health Organization (WHO) 2013a; World Health Organization (WHO) 2016b).

This paper's GBV definition originates from the findings advanced by the Declaration on the Elimination of Violence Against Women by the United Nations (UN) General Assembly 1993 and Council of Europe 2011, respectively. In detail, it includes violence between close family members, other relatives and intimates, such as father, stepfather, brother, or uncle, as well as violence between acquaintances and strangers, such as friends, work colleagues, teachers, police officers, or soldiers. The employed GBV definition also covers sexual abuse by strangers, cultural practices, or structural violence in institutions like schools.

A common way to organise the economic cost of GBV is to place them in categories based on their consequences and the services utilised as a result. In summary, this study computes the following cost classes:

1. lost economic output,
2. health service costs,
3. legal costs,
4. social welfare costs and specialised service costs,
5. personal costs,
6. intangibles, physical, and emotional impact,
7. second-generation costs.

These categories are derived from a holistic and extensive literature review. This includes research in both developing and developed nations from 2000 onwards, which was narrowed down to a set of around 20 studies for further in-depth review. The division into developing, emerging, and industrialised countries is based on the classifications of the World Bank. Based on this careful examination, the following became evident:

1. A lack of appropriate literature for developing and emerging countries: studies conducted for developing and emerging countries were often found to have different incompleteness. For instance, either not all categories were calculated, or costs were not projected to a national level.
2. Lack of available data: various data gaps within the current costing studies resulted in non-comprehensive calculations.

³In detail, 3.70 per cent of women have experienced sexual violence (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 300), and 13.80 per cent have suffered from physical violence (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 298).

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3. Methodological differences: minor methodological variations have led to significant differences in cost outcomes. The higher GBV prevalence ratios found in developing nations did not automatically translate into increased GDP cost-shares, as the calculations in developed countries often apply a more holistic approach, among others.

There is a wide range of methodical differences in the current GBV costing literature. Based on the analysis of the feasibility and availability of data in Southern Africa, the following approaches were identified to compute best the Namibian case⁴

1. Lost economic output: the health state model reflects all major and minor health consequences resulting from GBV.
2. Health service costs: the unit-cost approach derives from internationally accepted unit cost data for health services.
3. Legal costs and social welfare costs: the budget-share approach offers the most holistic way to apply the Namibian datasets found in this category.
4. Personal costs: the unit-cost method delivers the best result to handle the primarily qualitative datasets available for this cost class.
5. Intangibles, physical, and emotional impact: the quality-adjusted life years [QALYs] approach based on the willingness to pay [WTP] model provides the most comprehensive results currently available to calculate the intangibles.
6. Second-generation costs: the DALY approach and data best reflect the environmental situation and the living conditions of Namibian children.

Table 24.1 displays the results that were calculated based on the presented methods.

Table 24.1.: Results.

Cost category	GDP share [%]
Lost economic output	1.64
Health service costs	0.26
Legal costs	0.50
Social welfare costs and special service costs	1.09
Personal costs	0.28
Intangibles, physical, and emotional impact	0.62
Second-generation costs	1.62
Total [without second-generation costs]	4.39
Total	6.01

Source: Own representation.

⁴The detailed derivations and reasonings for the Namibian context are presented in Chapters 3 and 5

24.2. Summary in German

Weltweit wird schätzungsweise jede dritte Frau in ihrem Leben körperlich oder sexuell missbraucht, am häufigsten von einem Familienmitglied oder einem Partner. Gender-Based Violence ist daher ein Problem von erheblichem Ausmaß.

GBV stellt nicht nur eine Verletzung der Menschenrechte dar, sondern verursacht auch Kosten für die gesamte Gesellschaft per se. Zusammenfassend will diese Studie, die volle Bandbreite der Ausgaben auf der Einzel-, Gemeinde- und Makroebene abschätzen, indem Forschungsergebnisse aus verschiedenen Sektoren, einschließlich der öffentlichen Gesundheit, Soziologie, Psychologie und Wirtschaft, zusammengeführt werden. Ziel dieser Arbeit ist es, die negativen Auswirkungen von GBV ganzheitlich zu quantifizieren.

GBV hat enorme Konsequenzen auf die körperliche und geistige Gesundheit von Betroffenen und ihren Angehörigen (World Health Organization (WHO) 2009). Die Gewalt verursacht nicht nur Kosten für die Betroffenen in Bezug auf verlorene Wirtschaftsleistung oder persönliche Verluste, sondern es entstehen auch Verluste für die gesamte Nation. Diese Verluste gehen über den heutigen Zeitrahmen hinaus und verursachen Kosten die über Altersgruppen hinweg reichen (Dunkle u. a. 2004). Kurz gesagt, GBV hält eine ganze Gesellschaft davon ab, ihr wahres [wirtschaftliches] Potenzial auszuschöpfen, da es das Wirtschaftswachstum und die Entwicklung einer Nation über Generationen hinweg einschränkt. GBV betrifft überproportional Länder mit niedrigem und mittlerem Einkommen, und für Entwicklungs- und Schwellenländer sind diese negativen Auswirkungen daher besonders gravierend. Beispielsweise betragen die Berechnungen der Kosten von Gewalt 1,35 Prozent des Bruttoinlandsprodukts [BIP] in Australien (KPMG Australia 2016), 3,19 Prozent in Vietnam (Duvvury und Carney 2012), 3,93 Prozent in Kolumbien (Ribero und Sánchez Torres 2004), oder 1,30 Prozent in Südafrika (KPMG South Africa 2014). Für Namibia existieren solche Kostenschätzungen bisher noch nicht, obwohl die GBV-Prävalenzraten überproportional hoch sind. Insgesamt haben 20 Prozent der jemals verheirateten namibischen Frauen in den letzten 12 Monaten körperliche oder sexuelle Gewalt erfahren, die durch ihren derzeitigen oder letzten Ehemann verübt wurde (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 310). Die GBV-Definition dieser Studie geht jedoch über die bloße Gewalt in der Ehe hinaus und schließt auch Gewalt ein, die von Dritten verübt wird. Zu diesen dritten Personen können beispielsweise der Stiefvater, die Polizei, Soldaten oder Lehrkräfte gehören (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 299)⁹. Insgesamt umfasst die Prävalenzrate dieser Studie: 17,50 Prozent der Frauen, die körperliche und sexuelle Gewalt in den letzten 12 Monaten erlebt haben, welche von intimen Partnern, Familienmitgliedern und Dritten verübt wurde. Im Detail haben 3,70 Prozent der Frauen sexuelle Gewalt erlebt, (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 300) und 13,80 Prozent litten unter körperlicher Gewalt (MoHSS and ICF International 2014 p. 298).

Die Berechnung der Kosten von GBV bietet eine bessere Entscheidungsgrundlage für politische Entscheidungsträger und deren Maßnahmen, einschließlich der Formulierung gezielter politischer Ausgabenprioritäten. Zusammenfassend zeigen internationale Kostenstudien deutlich die

⁹Siehe Kapitel 2 zur GBV-Definition.

Auswirkungen eines Nicht-aktiv-werdens für heutige und zukünftige Generationen (Council of Europe 2011).

Diese Studie basiert auf einer breiteren Definition von GBV. Sie stützt sich auf den Begriff von der Erklärung der Vereinten Nationen zur Beseitigung von Gewalt gegen Frauen (United Nations (UN) General Assembly 1993), und des Europarates (Council of Europe 2011). Im Detail umfasst der Begriff, verübte Gewalt durch Familienmitglieder, wie Vater, Stiefmutter oder Bruder, einschließlich weiteren Verwandten oder Bekannten. Die verwendete GBV-Definition schließt auch Missbrauch durch Fremde, oder strukturelle Gewalt durch Personen im Öffentlichen Sektor und durch staatliche Institutionen mit ein.

Eine übliche Methode zur Organisation der wirtschaftlichen Kosten von GBV besteht darin, diese anhand ihren Folgen oder den daraus resultierenden Dienstleistungen einzuteilen. Zusammenfassend berechnet diese Studie die folgenden Kostenklassen:

1. Verlorene Wirtschaftsleistung,
2. Kosten des Gesundheitswesens,
3. Rechtskosten,
4. Sozialkosten und Kosten für spezialisierte Dienstleistungen,
5. Persönliche Kosten,
6. Immaterielle Werte – Physische und emotionale Auswirkungen,
7. Kosten der zweiten Generation.

Diese Kategorien leiten sich aus einer ganzheitlichen und umfassenden Literaturrecherche ab. Diese beinhaltet die Forschung sowohl in Entwicklungs- als auch in Industrieländern ab dem Jahr 2000, die zu einer weiteren eingehenderen Überprüfung auf rund 20 Studien eingegrenzt wurde. Dabei basiert die Aufteilung in Entwicklungs-, Schwellen- und Industrieländer auf den Klassifikationen der Weltbank. Aus dieser sorgfältigen Überprüfung ergab sich Folgendes:

1. Mangel an geeigneter Literatur für Entwicklungs- und Schwellenländer: Studien, die für Entwicklungs- und Schwellenländer durchgeführt wurden, wiesen häufig verschiedene Unvollständigkeiten auf. Beispielsweise wurden entweder nicht alle Kategorien berechnet oder die Kosten nicht auf eine gesamte, nationale Ebene projiziert.
2. Mangel an verfügbaren Daten: In den aktuellen Kostenstudien gibt es eine Vielzahl von Datenlücken, wodurch die Berechnungen fehlerhaft werden.
3. Methodische Abweichungen: Geringfügige methodische Abweichungen haben zu erheblichen Unterschieden in den Kostenergebnissen geführt. Zudem haben die höheren GBV-Prävalenzquoten in den Entwicklungsländern nicht automatisch zu höheren BIP-Kostenanteilen geführt, da die Berechnungen in Industrieländern häufig einen ganzheitlicheren Ansatz verfolgen.

In der aktuellen GBV-Kostenliteratur gibt es eine Vielzahl von methodischen Unterschieden. Basierend auf der Analyse der Machbarkeit und der Verfügbarkeit von Daten im südlichen Afrika wurden die folgenden Methoden für die einzelnen Kostenkategorien identifiziert ⁶

1. Verlorene Wirtschaftsleistung: Das Gesundheitszustandsmodell, da es alle wesentlichen und geringfügigen gesundheitlichen Folgen aufnimmt, die sich aus GBV ergeben.
2. Kosten des Gesundheitswesens: Der Einheitskostenansatz, der sich aus international anerkannten Stückkostendaten für das Gesundheitswesen ableitet.
3. Rechtskosten und Sozialkosten: Der Budget-Share-Ansatz bietet die ganzheitlichste Möglichkeit, die in dieser Kategorie enthaltenen namibischen Datensätze anzuwenden.
4. Persönliche Kosten: Die Stückkostenmethode liefert das beste Ergebnis für die Verarbeitung der meist qualitativen Datensätze, die für diese Kostenklasse verfügbar sind.
5. Immaterielle Vermögenswerte – physische und emotionale Auswirkungen: Der Ansatz der qualitätsangepassten Lebensjahre [QALYs], der auf dem Zahlungsbereitschaftsmodell [WTP] basiert, liefert umfassende Ergebnisse für die Berechnung von immateriellen Vermögenswerten.
6. Kosten der zweiten Generation: Der DALY-Ansatz und Daten spiegeln die Umweltsituation und die Lebensspezifikationen namibischer Kinder am besten wider.

Die folgenden Ergebnisse wurden basierend auf den oben dargestellten Methoden berechnet [siehe Tabelle ^{24.2}].

Tabelle 24.2.: Ergebnisse.

Kostenkategorie	BIP-Anteil [%]
Verlorene Wirtschaftsleistung	1.64
Kosten für das Gesundheitswesen	0.26
Rechtskosten	0.50
Sozialkosten und spezielle Servicekosten	1.09
Persönliche Kosten	0.28
Immaterielle Verluste – physische und emotionale Auswirkungen	0.62
Kosten der zweiten Generation	1.62
Gesamt [ohne Kosten der zweiten Generation]	4.39
Gesamt	6.01

Quelle: Eigene Darstellung.

⁶Die detaillierten Ableitungen und Argumente für den namibischen Kontext werden in den Kapiteln ³ und ⁵ vorgestellt.

Eidesstattliche Versicherung

Ich, Saskia Breuer, versichere an Eides statt, dass ich die Dissertation mit dem Titel:

„Economic analyses on the cost of Gender-Based Violence in Namibia“

selbst und bei einer Zusammenarbeit mit anderen Wissenschaftlerinnen oder Wissenschaftlern gemäß den beigefügten Darlegungen nach §6 Abs.3 der Promotionsordnung der Fakultät für Wirtschafts- und Sozialwissenschaften vom 24. August 2010 verfasst habe. Andere als die angegebenen Hilfsmittel habe ich nicht benutzt.

Lungern, den 6. April 2022

Ort/Datum

Unterschrift Doktorand/in

Unterschrift Verwaltung

Erklärung

Hiermit erkläre ich, Saskia Breuer, dass ich keine kommerzielle Promotionsberatung in Anspruch genommen habe. Die Arbeit wurde nicht schon einmal in einem früheren Promotionsverfahren angenommen oder als ungenügend beurteilt.

Lungern, den 6. April 2022

Ort/Datum

Unterschrift Doktorand/in

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